

**Mathematics, Natural Philosophy, and Providential Theology:
An inquiry into the ontological problem of the causation of gravity force in Newton's physics**

A Thesis Submitted to the Institute of Philosophy
of the
UNIVERSIDAD DE ANTIOQUIA

By
Felipe Ochoa

In Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements for the Degree of
DOCTOR OF PHILOSOPHY

Advisor
John Henry
Science Studies Unit, University of Edinburgh

Institute of Philosophy, Universidad de Antioquia

August
2012

Contents

Acknowledgements	3
1. Introduction: Newton's bifurcated historiography.....	4
2. Newton's natural philosophy.....	16
2.1. Analysis and Synthesis	19
2.2. Experimental philosophy.....	38
2.3. Hypotheses in Newton's Natural Philosophy.....	47
2.4. The true Natural Philosophy before its corruption	53
3. The mechanical philosophy: From inert matter to active principles.....	69
3.1. Substantial forms and Occult qualities.....	72
4. Newton's ontology of mathematical entities and the causation of gravity force.....	94
4.1. Mechanism and Geometry in the <i>Principia</i>	95
5. Newton's ontology of gravity force in the <i>Principia</i>	123
5.1. Geometry and Nature in the Preface to the <i>Principia</i>	129
5.2. The ontological basis of mechanics in the <i>Principia</i>	138
5.3. Gravity as a superadded quality and action at a distance	147
6. Closing Remarks.....	167
References	171

Acknowledgements

During this research I have received valuable assistance, support, encouragement, and helpful criticism from teachers and colleagues, and I am grateful to all of them.

First and foremost, John Henry, my advisor, has been the most important person for the realisation of this dissertation. He has been an inestimable mentor, advisor and support during these years. I owe him a great debt for his acute insight in Newton's natural philosophy, his massive erudition as historian of science, and for his Herculean patience with me during the writing of the ideas contained in this study.

Secondly, I am very thankful to the Institute of Philosophy in the University of Antioquia, not only for having accepted me as Ph.D student but for having welcomed me as part of the academic staff where I have conducted my career as a teacher for just over a decade.

This investigation has been possible thanks to a grant received from the Administrative Department of Science, Technology and Innovation COLCIENCIAS.

1. Introduction: Newton's bifurcated historiography

It is well known that the last half century has witnessed a massive increase of our understanding of Newton's image both as an icon and as a historical person. By icon I mean the way Newton has been reconstructed by scholars from his times up to now, and by historical person the circumstances under which his intellectual life and works took shape. Now, as a consequence of this state of affairs it is to be expected that these two approaches would render a harmonious picture of Newton regarding the motivations, influences, orientations and impact of his inquiries, or at least some sort of convergence on the fundamentals of his researches. Notwithstanding this laudable expectation, when reading the numerous studies, companion books and specialised articles on Newton's natural philosophy during these last decades, one finds a very different situation. The Newtonian scholarship –and in consequence the Newtonian industry– seems to be divided with respect to the proper perspective to be adopted in order to understand and evaluate Newton both as icon and as a historical person.

According to the more traditional approach, Newton's significance should be evaluated in the light of his achievements in mathematics, calculus, astronomy, optics and mechanics. These form the basis, we are told, for describing him as the epitome of modern scientific reasoning whose mathematical and experimental method as shown in his *Principia* and *Opticks* is taken to be the highest expression of his inquiries. From this perspective it is important to focus on offering models of coherence between the fundamental components of his 'scientific' thought i.e., between his mathematical way applied to the study of nature and his experimental philosophy; as well as between the physical and mathematical usage of terms and their philosophical understanding in his thought. On the other side, along with a newer approach, it is stated that Newton's studies on ancient thought in theology, philosophy, and mythology, in conjunction with his undertakings in biblical exegesis and alchemy form an integral part of his endeavours and, consequently, they should be integrated into the overall system of his natural philosophy in order to appreciate in its full scale the significance of his achievements.¹

¹ Additionally, the roots of these sophisticated divergent approaches to Newton's natural philosophy are also well known to all those acquaintances with the sale at Sotheby's public auction in 1932 of the Portsmouth papers which contained the material from which the Newtonian industry has developed. As an outcome, there appeared editions of Newton's mathematics, optics, dynamics, mechanics and correspondence. To name just a few, A. Rupert Hall and Marie Boas Hall, *Unpublished Scientific Papers of Isaac Newton* (Cambridge University Press, 1962); John W. Herivel, *The Background to Newton's Principia: A Study of Newton's Dynamical Researches in the years 1664–1684* (Oxford, Clarendon Press, 1965); I.B. Cohen, *Introduction to Newton's Principia* (Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 1971); *Isaac Newton's Philosophiae Naturalis Principia Mathematica* (1726 edition, with variant readings (eds.) I.B. Cohen and

The crux of this divergence seems to lie in what amounts to the ‘fundamentals’ of his researches and by implication of all his system of natural philosophy. Thus, on the one side, we are told that Newton’s mathematics and his experimental philosophy established the patterns of enquiry of any research aimed at being science.² This stance on his significance focuses on a Newton ‘for us’ inasmuch as his accomplishments forged ‘our’ way of doing science, a science deprived of any ‘irrational’ taint like theology or alchemy. It was deprived of theology in so far as it is due to Newton that men of science learned how to separate in their thought and work science from religion. In this line of reasoning the influential scholar I. Bernard Cohen underscored this fundamental characteristic of Newton’s science:

A feature of Newton’s science, as set forth in the *Principia*, was that the development of the subject matter should proceed without any appeal to religious principles or arguments in favour of one or another school of philosophy. That is, Newton consciously and purposely excluded from the scientific text any overt considerations of theology or fundamental philosophy. In later editions of the *Principia* (1713, 1726) he added a supplementary General Scholium, in which he introduced topics of theology and scientific method and the foundations of scientific knowledge. But the system of rational mechanics and the Newtonian gravitational system of the world were free of any overt reference to questions of theology and philosophy. In this sense, the *Principia* established a mode of scientific presentation that was free of what we today would call extra-scientific considerations (2002, pp. 8-9).

And it was deprived of alchemy inasmuch as it became despicable occultist nonsense. In this line of reasoning the declarations of another leading scholar, A. Rupert Hall, are worthy to be quoted.

I unashamedly follow a positivist or even whiggish line, for it is impossible to write in the same sentence of the victors’ and the losers’ view of a battle. I do not believe (...) that Newton’s name is immortal because he read alchemical authors (...). I have tried to analyse, to set in context, to understand the creative work of men and women; if one is interested in creativity, one must, to a large extent, follow the victorious and not the defeated.

A. Koyré) two volumes (Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 1972); *The Optical Papers of Isaac Newton*, Vol. 1 (The Optical Lectures, 1670-1672), edited by Alan E. Shapiro (Cambridge University Press, 1984); Vol. 2, in preparation; *Isaac Newton. The Principia. Mathematical Principles of Natural Philosophy*, translated from Latin into English by I. Bernard Cohen and Anne Whitman with the assistance of Julia Budenz, with a Guide to the Principia by I. Bernard Cohen (Berkeley, Los Angeles, London, University of California Press, 1999). In 1950 Herbert McLachlan edited a small volume of the *Theological manuscripts*, which according to the specialists is not of much help for the understanding of Newton’s complex theology. In stark contrast, the papers related to theology and alchemy hardly were printed and at the worse largely refused to be published. For a brief sketch of the upsetting experiences for the publication of theological and alchemical papers, see Popkin, 2004.

² Thus, I. Bernard Cohen, speaking of Newton’s *Principia* asserted the impact of this epoch-making work highlighting that “this great treatise epitomized the application of mathematics to natural philosophy and set a standard which scientists in such diverse areas as palaeontology and physical chemistry saw as the goal for all developing sciences” (Cohen, 1982, p. 21). See also Westfall, 1983.

Atavism must be accepted, but not supposed to be more interesting and significant than creativity leading to the abandonment of traditional ideas (1983, p. 2).

These feelings of rejection towards Newton's alchemy can be traced back as far as 1855 in David Brewster's biography of Newton. In fact, Brewster declared that he "cannot understand how a mind of such power, and so nobly occupied with the abstractions of geometry, and the study of the material world, could stoop to be even the copyist of the most contemptible alchemical poetry, and the annotator of a work, the obvious production of a fool and a knave" (1855, pp. 374-375).

As a result of this traditional approach, Newton's 'hard science' is of enduring importance and is what really matters for posterity (Cohen, 2002, p. 23). This is a reductionist approach indeed since it gives us a narrowed and distorted picture of Newton's historicity. Narrowed because it fails to account for the 'atavistic' and 'contemptible' studies he undertook, and distorted because it offers an image in accordance with the lines of thought akin to the present way of doing science, alien to Newton's undertakings. By following this line of interpretation, one is prone to produce an idealised comprehension of his thought, and to fail to notice the nuanced transformation of his ideas into what we now know as Newtonianism.³

As to the second approach to the fundamentals of Newton's system of natural philosophy, recent historians of science who analyse the wide spectrum of his researches in ancient thought, alchemy and theology have found important clues –precisely in those fields neglected by the traditional approach– to understand the agendas that Newton laid down in his entire project for natural philosophy, aimed at understanding Newton in conformity with his own preoccupations. From this perspective, Newton's research in ancient thought, his endeavour to restore the lost ancient wisdom, his traditionalism with regard to mathematics and his reverence for earliest authorities seem to set him in the opposite way with respect to the modernism attributed to his works in particular and to the scientific revolution in general. In short, this approach considers him more like a reactionary than a revolutionary. On this respect, John Maynard Keynes's pronouncements are telling. In his "Newton, the Man" he asserted that Newton

was not the first of the age of reason. He was the last of the magicians, the last of the Babylonians and Sumerians, the last great mind which looked out on the visible and intellectual world with the same eyes as those who began to build our intellectual inheritance rather less than 10,000 years ago (Keynes, 1946, p. 27).

³ As it may be seen, this is a problem related to the philosophy of the history of science which does not discredit the importance of outstanding scholars like Cohen and Hall, not to mention all those like Derek T. Whiteside, Alan E. Shapiro, John Herivel, and others who have contributed to the understanding of the complexity of Newton's mathematics, the intellectual background to his natural philosophy and its technical aspects to a great extent. In addition to the aforementioned authors, these and related aspects of Newton's natural philosophy have been analysed also by scholars like Michael Blay, J. Bruce Brackenridge, Mordechai Feingold, Niccolò Guicciardini, William Harper, Helena Pycior, George Smith, and Curtis Wilson.

Both these approaches establish their positions based upon the evidence of Newton's own statements, so the task of offering a structural account for these seemingly unrelated researches – scientific and non-scientific – arguably has been the main problem for the historians of the second half of the twentieth century onwards, as it was expressed thirty years ago by Richard Westfall, the first scholar in proposing the thesis of Newton's unity of thought. Indeed, in his essay review to *A Portrait of Isaac Newton* by Frank Manuel, Westfall dwelt for a moment upon the mass of new products of the Newtonian industry and recorded that, in general terms, those manuscripts in alchemy and theology should not be analysed in isolation from his mathematical and associated researches: "As new facets of the historical Newton appear, the problem, as it appears to me, is not merely to describe them but to join them into a coherent view of the man and his career" (Westfall, 1976, p. 179). From the historical point of view, Newton's religious views were largely neglected because of the deleterious effects upon his image, and the same could be said as for his alchemy.

Far from the sober Westfall who called for an integrated analysis of Newton's alchemy and theology with his science, the picture of Newton as the father of modern science was to be demythologised by Keynes in his 1946 paper "Newton, the Man". In this paper he voiced the feared face of the Newton of Brewster and his fellow travellers. Newton, wrote Keynes,

looked on the whole universe and all that is in it *as a riddle*, as a secret which could be read by applying pure thought to certain evidence, certain mystic clues which God had laid about the world to allow a sort of philosopher's treasure hunt to the esoteric brotherhood. He believed that these clues were to be found partly in the evidence of the heavens and in the constitution of elements (and that is what gives the false suggestion of his being an experimental natural philosopher), but also partly in certain papers and traditions handed down by the brethren in an unbroken chain back to the original cryptic revelation in Babylonia. He regarded the universe as a cryptogram set by the Almighty (Keynes, 1946, p. 29).

At this point two caveats are in order. First, according to our present hindsight, we tend to separate the 'scientific' from the 'extra-scientific' elements in Newton's thought to obtain a rational picture of him, 'rational' understood as coherence between his mathematics, physics, astronomy, mechanics and optics, and their affinity with the current approach to science. In this sense, 'extra-scientific' elements such as theology and alchemy do not contribute to the understanding of his system of natural philosophy, and they are separated from it and, on the contrary, they are seen to be at odds with it. Notwithstanding this, if one accepts Westfall's thesis – as I do – one does not have to believe that extra-scientific elements should be kept separate. In point of fact, they help us to understand what made his science different from that of his contemporaries; e.g., Newton's alchemy enabled him to accept active principles, while Descartes did not. Secondly, one should bear in mind that the word 'scientist' as we understand it nowadays was coined in the nineteenth century and that its earlier meaning encompassed precisely 'considerations' judged 'extra-scientific' today (Ross, 1962). Consequently, while it must be recognised that Newton's mathematics, physics, astronomy,

mechanics, and optics constitute his most perdurable contributions to the making of modern science, it would be erroneous to reduce his natural philosophy to such areas.

On the other hand, if one is to understand Newton in his own terms, aims and ends, we must include his endeavours in ancient thought, in theology, philosophy, mythology, biblical exegesis and alchemy. These two routes of interpretation on Newton seem to be irreconcilable in view of the results obtained from each one of them. From one perspective, we have a modern Newton who marked a new era of the scientific enterprise; from the other, we have a traditionalist Newton whose main business was the restoration of a long tradition of thought. This dichotomy of appreciation was highlighted twenty years after Keynes's assertions by J. E. McGuire and P. Rattansi in commenting:

It is certainly difficult for us in the twentieth century to conceive one whose scientific achievements were so great, pursuing with equal interest and energy such other studies, especially when his efforts in those fields produced so little of enduring value. It is even more difficult for us to imagine the mechanics and cosmology of the *Principia* being influenced by Newton's theological views and his belief in a pristine knowledge. Sir Isaac Newton, however, was not a 'scientist' but a Philosopher of Nature. In the intellectual environment of his century, it was a legitimate task to use a wide variety of materials to reconstruct the unified wisdom of Creation (McGuire & Rattansi, 1966, p. 138).

Perhaps no one statement like the following of Cohen could provide better evidence of the irreconcilable character of Newtonian scholarship regarding this bifurcated Newton. In the recent book *The foundations of Newtonian scholarship*, beating down the extra-scientific approach to Newton, Cohen asserted: "In today's scholarly world of irrationalism and lack of respect for any realism in scientific truth, Keynes' statements about Newton as a non-rational magician find an ever-growing sympathetic audience" (2000, p. 15).

This pronouncement expresses the very dichotomy that one finds in the recent literature on Newton, and captures the tension between Newton as an icon and Newton as a historical person.

Notwithstanding the acknowledgement of Newton's adherence to the ancient wisdom, some scholars remain unconvinced of the importance of these researches and, on the contrary, have reinforced the exclusively present-day approach to his work. This was the stance adopted by Cohen in the "Introduction" to *The Cambridge Companion to Newton*.

Newton seems to have believed that there was a unity in all the areas that he explored: the interpretation of the Bible, the tradition of ancient wisdom, Church history, alchemy, prophecy, optics and color theory, theory of matter, rational mechanics, and celestial dynamics. But it is a fact of record that in his writings on mathematics, in the *Principia*, and in his writing about optics proper, there was no trace of his concern for these esoteric subjects. Only in the later Queries to the *Opticks* do we find a hint of his concern for alchemy, in that part of the queries where he speculates about the structure of matter. *In*

short, these esoteric subjects were not features of the known thought of the public Newton or the Newton of history, the Newton who has been so important a figure in modern thought. For the philosopher, therefore, it is important to be aware of the range of Newton's thought and concerns; yet the Newton who has had so important an influence in the historical development of thought is rather the Newton of experiments and scientific theory, the mathematician who was a creator of the calculus, and the Newton who established the science of rational mechanics and set forth the Newtonian system of the world (Cohen, 2002, pp. 28-29, emphasis added).

These approaches to Newton need to be qualified both historically and philosophically if one aims at a unified understanding of Newton both as icon and as a historical person.⁴ First, Cohen's and Hall's strategy of separating theology and alchemy from Newton's natural philosophy, and their effort to present him as the rational figure par excellence, hardly have a historical correspondence in the light of Newton's own statements. Secondly, when Hall asserts his endeavour to put in context the creative work of Newton (in the present case), once again historical evidence amply contradicts him when he refuses to take into account his alchemy, theology and chronological researches. Thirdly, Cohen's concession about the unity of thought or at least his acknowledgement of such idea in Newton himself, and at the same time the dismissal of it in his attempt to preserve his hero untainted by the darkness of irrationalism is revealing on the limits of his stance. Indeed, Cohen's assertions, as well as his acknowledgement of Newton's interests and pursuits in extra-scientific considerations like alchemy and theology, seem to fit with Hall's motto to follow the victorious and not the defeated. Their approaches exhibit a rational essentialism which creates an astigmatic view of history, at the best. These are in the line of a long-standing understanding of rationalism in terms of consistency between mathematics and experimentalism, typical of nineteenth and twentieth century views.

In this long tradition of antagonism on the part of Newton scholars to attempt to situate Newton's philosophy in relation to his non-scientific studies, recently we have the approach of Andrew Janiak. Not wishing to deal with these concerns of Newton, and rejecting a view of the philosophical heritage of Newtonian doctrines, Janiak tries to fit Newton into the revolutionary 'Newtonian style' (Cohen, 1980) of doing proper science, in which quantitative reasoning and a meticulous subjection of nature to experimental examination surpasses the outdated speculative approach of the Schools and the unworkable hypothetical philosophy of Cartesians as the appropriate methodology for inquiring into nature. On this ground, for Janiak, Newton was a natural philosopher, but one who redefined the epistemological canon for knowledge-claims, circumventing unproductive controversies over metaphysics and theology (Janiak, 2008).

But Newton, the natural philosopher, did not consider theology, metaphysics and alchemy as alien to his other natural philosophical researches. On the contrary, they formed an integral part of his endeavours and are constituents of his project for natural philosophy. From this perspective,

⁴ For an analysis of Newton's unity of thought, see Dobbs, 1991, 1993; Force, 1990; Henry, 2007; and McGuire, 1995.

Keynes's view of Newton as the last of the magicians is also a misconception of the very nature of natural philosophy in general and Newton's own project in particular. The customary practice of dividing the activities of a natural philosopher between rational and irrational is anachronistic and misses the point at understanding the nature of Newton's inquiries into natural philosophy. Thus, for example B. J. T. Dobbs in her book *The Janus faces of genius. The role of alchemy in Newton's thought* of 1991 emphasises Newton's unity of thought by means of what she calls a "religious interpretation" (p. 251) of Newton's alchemy. Consistent with this plan Dobbs aims is to reinforce the "ultimate unity of Newton's thought" (p. 253) having as basis the "doctrine of the unity of Truth" that is "guaranteed by the unity of God" (p. 255). Notwithstanding this, her choice of title shows that she thinks of Newton as two-faced —partly looking back to the past and partly looking to the future. So, Newton is a divided thinker, and not a unified thinker.

In this way McGuire and Rattansi are right in pointing out that Newton was not a scientist but a philosopher of nature.

In this sense the meaning of 'natural philosophy' could shed light on the understanding of how problematic it is to label Newton as scientist. Indeed, for centuries *scientia* has been a totemic word which expresses the production and demonstration of knowledge based upon causes and demonstrable principles; in this way theology and mathematics (arithmetic and geometry) have both been considered as sciences (*scientiae*); natural philosophy, in the Aristotelian sense, and also theology (from 13th century in the Middle Ages) were considered *scientiae*. Now, natural philosophy during seventeenth-and eighteenth-centuries included mathematics and experimentalism within a theological framework, but not only these: it also included a systematic reflection on the basic constituents of nature, its Creator and his relationship to the world. So, within the domain of natural philosophy, therefore, one finds *scientiae* but these are not reducible to *scientia* in its earlier meaning nor to 'science' in the later one (nineteenth century onwards).

Given the complexity of disciplines and the diverse objects of their research, it might be difficult to understand how one and the same person, like Newton, could undertake such dissimilar fields of research. One should bear in mind, notwithstanding this, that the putative disciplinary incongruence is not Newton's but ours, and what for us is irrational and inconsistent, for him was entirely rational and coherent. In this state of affairs, how is it possible to contextualise and to follow the victorious Newton, disregarding the defeated one? How are we to understand the public Newton, setting aside the private one? How can the stunning success of the *Principia* and the *Opticks* be explained without the powerful theological core underlying them? How it is possible to discern the last of the magicians downplaying his achievements in mathematics and rational mechanics?

In a few words, Newton's natural philosophy is much more complex than a simplistic division of its constituent elements between rational and irrational, scientific and extra-scientific. Such labels are inapplicable and untenable to his natural philosophy, for theology, metaphysics, alchemy, and magic go hand in hand with mathematics and experimentalism in the study of Nature. This essential character of natural philosophy of the scientific revolution was underlined some years ago by John A. Schuster who defined its domain and the areas embraced by it in the following terms:

In the period of the Scientific Revolution, every system of natural philosophy, whether of a generally Aristotelian, mechanistic or Neo-Platonic magical / alchemical type, purported to describe and explain the entire universe and the relation of that universe to God, however conceived. The enterprise also involved, explicitly, a concern with the place of human beings and society in that universe (Schuster, 1990, p. 224).

From this definition of natural philosophy emerges an important clue to discern the split between Newton the scientist and Newton the natural philosopher, namely, “Nature” and “Providence” and *how* they are related within the work of the natural philosopher. Thus, for example, when Cohen states that Newton separated theology from mathematics, rational mechanics, optics, and colour theory, he is asserting obliquely that Newton’s natural philosophy is not concerned about God anymore, and in consequence God does not buttress his inquiries into –and knowledge of– Nature. In such a case, Nature alone becomes *la raison d’être* of Newton’s researches and ‘in this sense, the *Principia* established a mode of scientific presentation that was free of what we today would call extra-scientific considerations.’ This interpretation implies that in Newton’s natural philosophy the notion of God and *how* he is related to the world becomes ineffectual.

A similar line has been followed by the medievalist Edward Grant in affirming that in the *Principia*: “God may lie in the background as Creator, or perhaps simply as inspiration, but He does not enter into the content of their works, or affect it, because that would have proved futile” (Grant, 2000, p. 291).⁵ Well and good, in so far as no natural philosopher ever simply attributes a physical phenomenon to God’s intervention. In fact, they always explain phenomena in terms of secondary causes, but God is always the primary cause.

Both Cohen and Grant invoke the disciplinary distinctions and subject matter of natural philosophy to defend their positions. Thus, for example, commenting on the cause of gravity force in the *Principia*, and Newton’s attitude towards offering its causal explanation, Grant pointed to the inoperative character of God as causal explanation in Newton’s masterpiece:

Newton did not do so. Why not? Probably because he was well aware that such an explanation would have been to no avail. It would have explained nothing. If you believe, as Newton did, that God has created our world and all of its operations, then you cannot invoke God to function as an explanation for the cause of any particular effect. You must assume that God provided a natural cause for that effect, and it is the task of the natural philosopher to discover it (p. 291).

Such is, indeed, the task of the natural philosopher as Grant maintains. But the answer to the question about *how God is related to the world* is not a single and simple one. When Grant talks about the close and obvious relationship between God and natural philosophy, he is not just simplifying the complex theology behind Newton’s *Principia*; he is also ignoring or minimising the role of the theological debates e.g., voluntarism and intellectualism, around the different natural

⁵ Gale Christianson has taken a similar approach in his biography of Newton; see Christianson, 1984, p. 312.

philosophical traditions in the understanding of God's relationship to Nature during the scientific revolution. So, the issue is not just about an overt assertion of God and his relationship to the world –which is a truism during the scientific revolution– but about *how God is related to the world* through secondary causation.

The specific nature of God and how Newton's conception of God shaped his natural philosophical inquiries help us understand the stance adopted in the *Principia*. In consequence, when Grant emphasises that “theology and faith could not enter it in any significant manner because to do so would transform natural philosophy into supernatural philosophy, natural theology, or theology” (*Ibid.*) he simply misses the point or makes a category because he assumes that natural philosophy and God are unrelated, thus relegating God as a mere background and inspiration for natural philosophers and even scientists (pp. 290-291).

But the apparent separation and non-relationship of God and theological commitments in Newton's *Principia* –and *Opticks*– is not at all an unmistakable sign of his stolidity or indifference towards theological matters. Quite the contrary, a close reading of the General Scholium of the *Principia* and the Queries appended to the *Opticks* reveal a very different picture of him. So, in order to understand the motivations and reasons for keeping silence regarding the cause of gravity and the putative absence of God in the *Principia* and *Opticks*, it is necessary to focus on the underlying strata of his public pronouncements.

As a matter of fact, although Cohen may be right in pointing out that the ‘esoteric’ subjects that Newton undertook were not features of his public image, it does not necessarily imply that they should be ruled out of the historical analysis of his thought. And more to the point, when he says that in Newton's main works ‘there was no trace of his concern for these esoteric subjects’ it does not mean that such undertakings do not appear veiled in the text itself –*Principia*, *Opticks* (Snobelen, 1999, 2001, 2004, 2005). In fact, a careful reading of the *Principia* reveals a deep religious commitment and a strong, albeit heterodox, theology; and in the case of the *Opticks*, besides the just mentioned features. It is also possible to grasp a theory of matter subsidiary to his previous alchemical researches.

Finally, it could be argued, from a debatable philosophy of science, as Cohen and Hall do, that the analysis of the development and content of Newton's theories could proceed without any appeal to the intellectual and cultural settings from which they emerged, and working through to present-day scientific categories it is possible to grasp the development of Newtonian science. But in this particular conception underlies the debatable character of such an approach, for when we leave aside the wider context within which Newton's natural philosophy took shape and was embraced, prominent aspects for assents and dissents regarding his work are also missed, thus rendering a simplistic view of history of science.⁶

Contrary to this approach, it is perfectly possible to characterise natural philosophy (and science) as a cultural product embedded in the internal dynamic of each culture and tradition of thought. The advantage of this approach over the traditional one lies in its capability to integrate

⁶ See Schofield, 1970 for a traditional approach to Newtonian natural philosophy from 1687 to 1815, and Heimann 1973 for a criticism of it.

and articulate the apparently irreconcilable and contradictory areas in Newton's natural philosophy. Such an integration and articulation are possible by virtue of Newton's unity of thought, an idea proposed and developed by Westfall, and followed by David Castillejo, Betty Jo Dobbs, James E. McGuire, Stephen Snobelen, James Force and John Henry, among others.⁷

Central to this idea is the acknowledgement of the paramount role that providence played during the scientific revolution in figures as diverse as Cassendi, Boyle, Locke and Newton himself. Indeed, the government and guidance of creation and God's relationship to the world form an essential part of seventeenth century thought. These topics emerge as a consequence of the reassessment of Aristotelian natural philosophy which, under the notions of nature and its substantial forms, aimed at explaining all natural phenomena. As is well known, the metaphor of nature as machine composed of atoms in motion originating the variety in the world was the alternative most adopted and adapted by natural philosophers. Adopted in view of its explanatory capability, and adapted to render it harmonious within the various theological contexts within which it was developed (Boas, 1952; Dijksterhuis, 1961; Dear, 1995, 2001).

With respect to Newton, it is primordial to discern this very theological component of his natural philosophy to understand the coherence and unity of his thought. In effect, the interconnection among pristine theology (*prisca theologia*), primordial wisdom (*prisca sapientia*), experience (experimentalism, which includes alchemy), mathematical certainty, and moral rightness, are unified in his project for natural philosophy; and the interplay of natural, moral and divine knowledge comprehends Newton's unified thought. This unity is best understood as the interaction of the by then current natural philosophical practices in Newton's time, and not as an epistemological unity (Markley, 1993).

Notwithstanding the general acceptance of the unity of Newton's thought among historians and philosophers of Newtonian scholarship, this thesis has been recently challenged by Rob Iliffe, who defends that "disciplinary divisions (...) both conditioned and facilitated [Newton's] early investigations in science and mathematics" and that "the concepts used by Newton throughout his career were intimately bound up with these appropriate generic or quasi-disciplinary 'structures'" (Iliffe, 2004, p. 227).

In effect, a good example of Newton's distinction of forms of argument and objects of investigation can be distinguished in his works. Thus, for example in the *Principia* he declares in the introduction to Book III, "The System of the World", that he has been treating his principles of philosophy from the 'mathematical' view point, while some passages are illuminated by 'philosophical scholiums'. Another example comes from *De gravitatione* where he affirms his goal in treating the topic of gravitation and equilibrium of fluids from both mathematics and philosophy, just as in the *Principia's* statements.⁸ These instances show that he explicitly distinguishes between

⁷ See, Castillejo, 1981; Dobbs, 1975, 1990, 1991; McGuire, 1995; Force, 1999a; Henry, 2007.

⁸ Thus, for example in the *Principia*: "In the preceding books I have presented principles of philosophy that are not, however, philosophical but strictly mathematical—that is, those on which the study of philosophy can be based. These principles are the laws and conditions of motions and of forces, which especially relates to philosophy. But in order to prevent these principles from seeming sterile, I have illustrated them with some philosophical scholiums [i.e., scholiums dealing with natural philosophy], treating topics that are general and that seem to be the most fundamental

these things. Now, from the point of view of objects of investigation, the “Seven statements on religion” gives us a clear indication of Newton’s thought: “Religion & Philosophy are to be preserved distinct. We are not to introduce divine revelations into Philosophy, nor philosophical opinions into religion” (Newton, 1710c: 1’). The separation here is both discursive and thematic.

This, in passing, does not invalidate the underlying unity of thought in Newton’s natural philosophy, but makes clear the disciplinary structure of Newton’s discourses. So, although Newton’s “later efforts to bring together active principles, aethers and voids in various works (...) were bold attempts to meld together concepts or ontologies that belonged to distinct enquiries”, this conforms more to epistemological than philosophical restrictions.

Nevertheless, it has been shown that Newton “experimented with a ‘mathematical’ style” (Delgado-Moreira, 2006, p. 224) in his biblical researches, and from the methodological viewpoint a unity in Newton’s natural philosophy has also been asserted (Mammiani, 2001). In mathematics Newton also separated what was worthy to be published from what he considered debatable from the philosophical view point (Guicciardini, 2003, 2004 a, 2004 b) considering “the audiences, projects, genres, disciplinary formations and linguistic styles in and for whom they were first written”. Newton’s unity of thought does not mean, as I can see, that his multifarious “research[es] [were] essentially the same thing” (Iliffe, 2004, p. 250), but *aimed* at a single end: the restoration of the pristine natural knowledge and the recovery of the original religion.

Under the notion of unity of thought it is possible to achieve an articulated view of Newton both as an icon and as a historical person. As an icon, inasmuch as the process whereby his name came to be associated to a successful way of doing science –in our present day understanding of this term– is closely linked to the emerging ways of negotiating key procedures in natural philosophy as those related to experience, experimentation, production of matters of fact, mathematical approaches to nature, levels of enquiry, and connections and relations among these levels.

By examining these procedures of negotiation, it is possible to grasp a more nuanced and historically contextualised understanding of the change and transformation of Newton’s own conceptions of natural enquiry through the diverse cultural settings in which his ideas were adopted and adapted under the rubric “Newtonianism” (Schaffer, 1990; Stewart, 2004; Higgitt, 2007). And as a historical person in so far as Newton’s natural philosophy forms part of a specific socio-cultural setting in which beliefs, assumptions, modes of argumentation, validations, rejection and sanctions in natural philosophical procedures and researches are active modes of interactions and practices

for philosophy” (Newton, 1999, p. 793). And in *De gravitatione*: “It is proper to treat the science of gravity and of the equilibrium of fluid and solid bodies in fluids by two methods. To the extent that it appertains to the mathematical sciences, it is reasonable that I largely abstract it from physical considerations. And for this reason I have undertaken to demonstrate its individual propositions from abstract principles, sufficiently well known to the student, strictly and geometrically. Since this doctrine may be judged to be somewhat akin to natural philosophy, in so far as it may be applied to making clear many of the phenomena of natural philosophy, and in order, moreover, that its usefulness may be particularly apparent and the certainty of its principles perhaps confirmed, I shall not be reluctant to illustrate the propositions abundantly from experiments as well, in such a way, however, that this freer method of discussion, disposed in scholia, may not be confused with the former which is treated in Lemmas, propositions and corollaries” (Newton, 1668, p. 121).

which made use of multifarious intellectual tools and discourses regarding the aims and objectives to which natural philosophy was directed.

Both the adaptations and adoptions of Newton's natural philosophy, on the one hand, and the diverse ways of thought within his concrete sociocultural milieu, on the other, demand a closer analysis of his natural philosophy in all its parts. In doing so, the philosophical motivations he embraced, the traditions of thought he adhered to, the values he promoted, the styles of thought he criticised, and the agendas he established in his work, will be distinguished. By taking a close look at these features of Newton's natural philosophy, it is possible to discern its scopes and limits much better than the Newtonian historiography which analyses Newton in a context-neutral or idealistic standpoint ever could.

From this perspective, it will be argued that the diverse studies and practices that Newton undertook in natural philosophy aimed at the discernment of providence by means of the investigation of nature. This being so, we need to elucidate how Newton's natural philosophy is related to the voluntaristic theological framework which directed his thought, in order to account for the ontological causation of what is taken to be the central achievement of his undertakings, namely, the gravity force.

2. Newton's natural philosophy

Among Newton's scholars, there is a consensus that his most celebrated public statements on the metaphysical and methodological issues in his natural philosophy are the (1) Scholium to the Definitions, (2) the Rules for the Study of Natural Philosophy, (3) the General Scholium to the *Principia*; and (4) the Queries added to the *Opticks*. Thus, for example, in the scholium to the definitions we find the definition of Newton's absolute space and time and a reference to the Holy Scriptures;⁹ in the Rules for the study of natural philosophy, his methodological procedures in natural philosophy;¹⁰ in the General Scholium (a) a criticism to Descartes' vortex theory, (b) a characterization of Newton's God and his relationship to the world, (c) the phenomenalistic and agnostic stance regarding the cause of gravity force, and related to this (d) his refusal to feign hypotheses in natural philosophy, and finally (e) the allusion to a certain electric and elastic spirit (See, Hall, 1959; Howe, 1982; Koyré & Cohen, 1960).

In the *Opticks*, Newton's design was "not to explain the Properties of Light by Hypothesis, but to propose and prove them by Reason and Experiments" (Newton, 1704, Book 1, p. 1), nevertheless at the end of Book III he announced:

When I made the foregoing Observations,¹¹ I design'd to repeat most of them with more care and exactness, and to make some new ones for determining the manner how the Rays of Light are bent in their passage by Bodies for making the Fringes of Colours with the dark lines between them. But I was then interrupted, and cannot now think of taking these things into farther Consideration. And since I have not finish'd this part of my Design, I shall conclude, with proposing only some Queries in order to a farther search to be made by others (Newton, 1717, p. 313).

⁹ Cohen wrote a paper on this topic but he opted for highlighting this aspect as a prelude to the separation of "science" and theology. See Cohen, 1969.

¹⁰ During the several editions of the *Principia* Newton made substantial changes to this part of his *Principia*: Thus, for example, in the first edition (1687) there were 10 hypotheses and no rule at all; the second edition (1713) changes hypotheses 1 and 2 into rules, hypothesis 3 is replaced by a new rule, number 3, hypothesis 4 becomes 1, and the remaining 6 change into Phenomena; and for the third edition (1726) Newton added a new rule, number 4.

¹¹ He refers to the experimental "Observations concerning the Inflexions of the rays of Light and the Colours made thereby", the name of the third book, which are 11 in total.

This statement suggests a research programme in natural philosophy, and as such it was interpreted ever since. But through the three different editions of this work Newton progressively stretched it so as to include further queries aimed at a more ambitious plan. Thus, in the first edition (1704) there were originally sixteen (1-16) Queries dealing with Newton's acceptance of action at a distance¹² and the interaction between light and matter;¹³ to the second edition (1706) a new set of Queries (25-31, as arranged in the third edition) was included in the Latin translation, by Samuel Clarke, touching topics of nature of light, body, the forces which endow activity to nature and the relationship of God to the world; in the third edition (1717) Newton, again, incorporated eight new Queries (17-24 as organised in the third edition) related to an ether, or subtle fluid, proposed as an alternative means to explain the workings of nature.

The queries added to the Latin edition of the *Opticks* (1706) represent an exceptional source of information regarding the metaphysical and theological conceptions underlying Newton's natural philosophy. Indeed, for the first time, they display to the public gaze Newton's ontology of nature, the role of God in his creation, and Newton's goals in philosophy of nature (Westfall, 1980: 640-649). The topics and the deepness of the consequences arising out of a careful reading of the last Query 31 (which constitutes about fifty per cent of the queries), as numbered in the third edition (1717), deserves a separate treatment. Nonetheless, for the present purposes I will focus the attention on the last paragraph which synthesises and shows the interplay of each and every part of Newton's natural philosophy. At the end of his *Opticks*, Newton writes:

In the two first Books of these Opticks, I proceeded by this Analysis. (...) And these Discoveries being proved, may be assumed in the Method of Composition for explaining the Phaenomena arising from them. (...) In this third Book I have only begun the Analysis of what remains to be discover'd about Light and its Effects upon the Frame of Nature. (...) And if natural Philosophy in all its Parts, by pursuing this Method, shall at length be perfected, the Bounds of Moral Philosophy will be also enlarged. For so far as we can know by natural Philosophy what is the first Cause, what Power he has over us, and what Benefits we receive from him, so far, our Duty towards him, as well as that towards one another, will appear to

¹² Thus for example, *Query* 1. Do not Bodies act upon Light at a distance, and by their action bend its Rays, and is not this action (*cæteris paribus*) strongest at the least distance? *Query*. 4. Do not the Rays of Light which fall upon Bodies, and are reflected or refracted, begin to bend before they arrive at the Bodies; and are they not reflected, refracted, and inflected by one and the same Principle, acting variously in various Circumstances? (Newton, 1717, p. 313-314).

¹³ *Qu.* 5. Do not Bodies and Light act mutually upon one another, that is to say, Bodies upon Light in emitting, reflecting, refracting and inflecting it, and Light upon Bodies for heating them, and putting their parts into a vibrating motion wherein heat consists? *Qu.* 6. Do not black Bodies conceive heat more easily from Light than those of other Colours do, by reason that the Light falling on them is not reflected outwards, but enters the Bodies, and is often reflected and refracted within them, until it be stifled and lost? *Qu.* 7. Is not the strength and vigor of the action between Light and sulphureous Bodies observed above, one reason why sulphureous Bodies take fire more readily, and burn more vehemently, than other Bodies do? *Qu.* 8. Do not all fix'd Bodies when heated beyond a certain degree, emit Light and shine, and is not this Emission perform'd by the vibrating Motions of their parts? And do not all Bodies which abound with terrestrial parts, and especially with sulphureous ones, emit Light as often as those parts are sufficiently agitated; whether that agitation be made by Heat, or by Friction, or Percussion, or Putrefaction, or by any vital Motion, or any other Cause? *Qu.* 9. Is not Fire a Body heated so hot as to emit Light copiously? For what else is a red hot Iron than Fire? And what else is a burning Coal than red hot Wood? (Newton, 1717, p. 315-316).

us by the Light of Nature. And no doubt, if the Worship of false Gods had not blinded the Heathen, their moral Philosophy would have gone farther than to the four Cardinal Virtues; and instead of teaching the Transmigration of Souls, and to worship the Sun and Moon, and dead Heroes, they would have taught us to worship our true Author and Benefactor, as their Ancestors did under the Government of *Noah* and his Sons before they corrupted themselves (Newton, 1717: 381-382).

Among Newton's public pronouncements, these statements exhibit straightforwardly his research programme for natural philosophy. Besides telling us that his method is that of analysis and synthesis and that it is applied to the experimental researches, Newton grippingly emphasises that the true knowledge of natural order led us to the acknowledgement and worship of the Creator, and this influences directly the moral philosophy, this is, 'our duty towards one another'. Here we find the basic tenets of religion according to Newton.

In fact, a manuscript dated from the same period of the publication of the *Queries*, entitled *Three paragraphs on religion*, captures more directly the idea expressed in this Query about the absolute dominion of God: "God made & governs the world invisibly & hath commanded us to love & worship him & no other God & to honour our parents & masters & love our neighbours as our selves" (Newton, 1710c b, p. 4^r). And in a related manuscript he declared once again: "In matters of religion the first & great Commandment hath always been: Thou shalt love the Lord thy God with all thy heart & with all thy soul & with all thy mind. And the second is like unto it: Thou shalt love thy neighbour as thy self. On these two hang all the Law & the Prophets" (Newton, 1710c c. p. 1). These tenets are not new, they are the purest expression of the primordial religion,¹⁴ before it was corrupted. Newton's classicism, understood as his belief that in the past lay the pure and true knowledge, is integrated to his philosophy of mathematics, and therefore both religion and natural philosophy are connected and are mutually dependent in Newton's endeavours. This interdependent feature has been called the unity of Truth, a truth which can be restored following the proper way to enquiry of nature.¹⁵

In order to grasp better this articulation, it is suitable to aim at a précis of (1) the method of analysis and synthesis in Newton, (2) his experimental approach to the frame of nature, and how these two aspects play the role in the knowledge of (3) the first cause, all this in the framework of his classicism which helps us to understand the task of the restoration of *prisca sapientia* which encompassed the knowledge of God through the frame of nature.

¹⁴ Compare for example this assertion with a previous one in a manuscript from the decade of 1690: "[T]he religion which Moses taught the Jews was no other than the religion purged from the corruptions of the nations. For [...] Moses retained all the religion of the Egyptians concerning the worship of the true God; & rejected only what belonged to the worship of their false Gods the Sun Planets & Elements, Jupiter Hammon, Osiris, Isis, Orus [...] And that this is so appears further by the consent of the religions of Noah and Moses." (Newton, 1690c, p. 5^r)

¹⁵ See Dobbs, 1991; McGuire, 1995; McGuire & Rattansi, 1966.

2.1. Analysis and Synthesis

As is well known, the search for a reliable method to achieve the best possible knowledge is one of the main characteristics throughout the origins of modern science, and on account of the acceptance of Newton's natural philosophy, as devised especially in the *Principia* and in the *Opticks*, it became current to think his method as the best. In fact, this view was common in the many popularisations of his philosophy;¹⁶ in addition, the analysis of Newton's method is one of the major concerns of Newtonian scholarship.¹⁷ As for Newton himself, his public statements on the method, as for its nature and relation to natural philosophy, come from the *Optice*, the Latin translation (1706) by Samuel Clarke, where he introduced a set of seven new queries (17-23) which covers his views regarding the nature of light, matter, the forces which furnish nature with activity, the relation of God to the universe, and his methodology as well. As for this last topic, in the *Questio 23* one reads:

Quemadmodum in Mathematica, ita etiam in Physica, investigatio rerum difficilium ea Methodo, quae vocatur Analytica, semper antecedere debet eam quae appellatur Synthetica. Methodus Analytica est, experimenta capere, phaenomena observare; indeque; ex rebus compositis, ratiocinatione colligere simplices; ex Motibus, vires moventes; & in universum, ex effectis, causas; ex causisque particularibus, generales; donec ad generalissimas tandem sit deventum. Methodus Synthetica est, causas investigatas & comprobatas assumere pro Principiis, eorumq; ope explicare Phaenomena ex iisdem orta, istaque explicaciones comprobare.¹⁸

Moreover, in a draft intended for the Preface for the *Opticks* of 1704 found by J. E. McGuire and entitled by him as "Newton's 'Principles of Philosophy'", Newton was more explicit with respect to his methodology based on the methods of analysis and synthesis, as well as to the close relationship entailed in his inquiries both into mathematics and natural philosophy:

As Mathematicians have two Methods of doing things w^{ch} they call Composition & Resolution & in all difficulties have recourse to their method of resolution (before they compound) so in explaining the Phaenomena of nature the like methods are to be used & he that expects success must resolve before he compounds. ffor the explications of Phaenomena are Problems much harder than those in (Abstracted) Mathematicks. The method of Resolution consists in trying experiments & considering all the Phaenomena (of nature from whence anything can be) relating to the subject in hand (& drawing conclusions from them) & examining the truth of those conclusions by new experiments & drawing new conclusions (if it may be) from those experiments & so proceeding alternately from

¹⁶ See Maclaurin 1748; Pemberton, 1728; Brewster, 1855; Clarke, 1730; Whiston, 1716, 1728; Voltaire, 1740; du Châtelet, 1738; 'sGravesande, 1738.

¹⁷ See Bechler, 1991; Cohen, 1980; Shapiro, 2002, 2004; Smith, 2002.

¹⁸ Newton, 1706, p. 347.

experiments to conclusions & from conclusions to experiments untill you come to the general properties of things (and when you), [& by experiments & phaenomena have established the truth of those properties] Then assuming those properties as Principles of Philosophy you may (proceed from) by them explain the causes of such Phaenomena as (depend upon them &) follow from them: w^{ch} is the method of Composition.¹⁹

Finally, the statements of Query 31 of the second English edition of the *Opticks* (1717), regarding his method in natural philosophy, included some lines about the argument of induction and his rejection of hypotheses, in close resemblance to the fourth *Regula philosophandi* of the third edition of his *Principia* (1726). Thus, in this Query one reads:

As in Mathematicks, so in Natural Philosophy, the Investigation of difficult Things by the Method of Analysis, ought ever to precede the Method of Composition. This Analysis consists in making Experiments and Observations, and in drawing general Conclusions from them by Induction, and admitting of no Objections against the Conclusions, but such as are taken from Experiments, or other certain Truths. For Hypotheses are not to be regarded in experimental Philosophy. And although the arguing from Experiments and Observations by Induction be no Demonstration of general Conclusions; yet it is the best way of arguing which the Nature of Things admits of, and may be looked upon as so much the stronger, by how much the Induction is more general. And if no Exception occur from Phaenomena, the Conclusion may be pronounced generally. But if at any time afterwards any Exception shall occur from Experiments, it may then begin to be pronounced with such Exceptions as occur.²⁰ By this way of Analysis we may proceed from Compounds to Ingredients, and from Motions to the Forces producing them; and in general, from Effects to their Causes, and from particular Causes to more general ones, till the Argument end in the most general. This is the Method of Analysis: And the Synthesis consists in assuming the Causes discover'd, and establish'd as Principles, and by them explaining the Phaenomena proceeding from them, and proving the Explanations (Newton, 1717, p. 380-381).

The first thing to be noted here is the relationship that Newton declares to be between mathematics and physics, as for the dual method in the investigation which is that of analysis and synthesis. In this section I will focus on the examination of Newton's methodology with regard to its mathematical character, and in the next section its experimental side will be considered.

Drawn from ancient geometrical thought, during the origins of modern science analysis and synthesis were considered the most powerful and suitable tools in order to reach secure truths as for their discovery and indisputable demonstration. The interest for this procedure of discovery (analysis) and proof (synthesis) was closely linked to the revival of Greek mathematical thought

¹⁹ Newton, 1970, p. 184-185. Square brackets are Newton's, parentheses indicate cancellations and interpolations.

²⁰ The following is also found in Query 23, above quoted.

represented by figures such as Apollonius, Diophantus, Hero, Pappus, Ptolemy and Proclus, besides Archimedes and Euclid, during the sixteenth-century which was marked by the direct return to the Greek texts. As a result of this Renaissance in mathematics, as shown in the endeavours of Regiomontanus, Maurolico, and notably Commandino towards the restoration of ancient mathematical thought, various translations into Latin of Greek works were published. Thus, for example, Federico Commandino translated Apollonius's *Conics* (1566), Euclid's *Elements* (1572), Diophantus's *Arithmetica* (1575), and notably Pappus's *Mathematical collection* (1588) (Rose, 1973; Cochrane, 1976).

This groundwork facilitated the assembling of the majority of the corpus of ancient mathematical writings, and opened the way to mathematical improvements in the seventeenth-century. The names of François Viète in symbolic algebra, Descartes in algebraic geometry and Newton and Leibniz in calculus instantiate these improvements.

Analysis and synthesis constitute a dual procedure for discovery and proof. With regard to analysis, it is applied to prove the propositions found (theorems), and to the resolution (constructions) of propounded problems; and that of synthesis is the reverse process of the former. In this manner, analysis departs from what is sought, taken for granted to be true, and through successive moves backwards it arrives at the solution of that which is required. Next, in order to demonstrate the findings arrived at by analysis, synthesis is used for rigor's sake, and it consists in the orderly arrangement of each of the elements which comprise the discovery or solution, in order to be certain about all the consequences grasped by means of analysis. In the *Elements* of Euclid analysis and synthesis are defined in the following terms:

Analysis is an assumption of that which is sought as if it were admitted (and the passage) through its consequences to something admitted (to be) true. Synthesis is an assumption of that which is admitted (and the passage) through its consequences to the finishing or attainment of what is sought (Euclid, 1956: Vol. IV, p. 442).

Analysis is divided into two classes. If it is aiming at the search for the truth, it is called theoretical; and if it is aimed at a specific solution, it is called problematical. In the first case, if analysis departs from an assumed truth, it will arrive also at truth, and conversely, if it departs from a falsehood, that which is sought will be also false. In the second case, if that which is sought is possible and reachable (in mathematical jargon, what is *given*), it will be possible to reach what is asked to find, and the reverse process of proof will be in accord with what is given, and conversely, if it departs from an impossibility, the problem will be unreachable too (Duhamel, 1865, pp. 39-50, 51-54).

The method of analysis and synthesis became known in Europe owing to the translation of Pappus's *Mathematicae collectiones* by Federico Commandino. In this synopsis of the ancient geometrical thought the process whereby the Ancients accomplished their findings is defined in the following terms:

Analysis is the passage from the thing sought, as if it were admitted, through the things which follow in order [from it], to something admitted as the result of synthesis.

There are two types of analysis: that which seeks the truth, which is called theoretical; and that which obtains [the solution of the problem] set forth, which is called problematical. Now, in the *theoretical* type we posit the thing sought as existing and as true and then, according to the hypothesis, we pass through the things which follow in order [from it], [positing them] as true and as existing, to something admitted: if that thing admitted is true, the thing sought also will be true, and the proof will be the reverse of the analysis; but if we happen upon something admitted to be false, the thing sought will also be false. In the problematical type, we posit the [problem] set forth as known and then pass through the things which follow in order [from it], [positing them] as true, to something admitted: if the thing admitted is possible and obtainable, what they call in mathematics given, the [problem] set forth also will be possible, and again the proof will be the reverse of the analysis; but if we should happen upon something admitted to be impossible, the problem also will be impossible.²¹

This twofold process furnished the early enquirers into mathematics and geometry with an important set of tools, as testified in several works such as Apollonius's *Conics*, Aristaeus *Solid loci*, and Eratosthenes's *On means*. As a matter of fact, as said earlier, much of the effort in the sixteenth and seventeenth centuries was focused upon the restoration of these works. The fruits of those efforts in early modern science led to the eventual development of the new symbolic algebra and the birth of calculus.

The characteristic sentiment of the Renaissance towards the Ancients as an exemplary set of thinkers was of superiority with respect to the moderns. This point could be illustrated by the high regard for the achievements of the Ancients which promoted the search for the lost works that contained the means they employed for such wealthy fruits, not only in architecture, music, and philosophy but in mathematics and geometry as well, in order to determine the nature of Greek methods. Moreover, it also was thought that the very method of discovery was kept hidden in order to keep it out of the public domain, and the reasons for keeping it shrouded in secrecy were, it could be said, esoteric ones, that is to say, reserved only to adepts or to those who mastered the method of analysis. The belief in the possession of such valuable tools for discovery was expressed not only by Renaissance thinkers but also by leading philosophers of Modernity, for example by René Descartes.

In spite of distancing himself from the Ancients, Descartes recognises their possession of a method which enabled those who made use of it to make great discoveries. Thus, for example, in the fourth 'Regula ad directionem ingenii' significantly entitled "Necessaria est methodus ad veritatem investigandam", one reads:

²¹ *Pappi Alexandrini Collectionis quae Supersunt*, Fredericus Hultsch (ed.), Berlin, 1877, Vol. II, pp. 634, 1-636, 14. As quoted in Mahoney, 1968, p. 322.

Indeed I seem to recognize certain traces of this true [*mathesis*] in Pappus and Diophantus, who though not belonging to the earliest age, yet lived many centuries before our own times. But my opinion is that these writers then with a sort of low cunning, deplorable indeed, suppressed this knowledge. Possibly they acted just as many inventors are known to have done in the case of their discoveries, i.e. they feared that their method being so easy and simple would become cheapened on being divulged, and they preferred to exhibit in its place certain barren truths, deductively demonstrated with show enough of ingenuity, as the results of their art, in order to win from us our admiration for these achievements, rather than to disclose to us that method itself which would have wholly annulled the admiration accorded. Finally, there have been certain men of talent who in the present age have tried to revive this same art. For it seems to be precisely that science known by the barbarous name Algebra (Descartes, 1952, pp. 7-8).

Descartes read Commandino's translation of Pappus's *Mathematicae collectiones*, and was encouraged by it to find the way of using the ancient analysis to solve philosophical problems regarding the method, as well as geometrical problems, as in the case of the *Géométrie* (1637). In Descartes's hands this method was baptised as "mathesis universalis" so indicating that it could be applied not only to the *mathematicae scientiae* but to all human inquiries in general. With Descartes, therefore, we have an instance of how analysis was thought and practiced both at its suggestive (as in the case of the *Discourse on the method* and in the *Meditations*) and prescriptive (as in his *Géométrie*) levels.²² Furthermore, as Descartes observes, a by-product of this effort for restoring the ancient method was symbolic algebra.

The analytic reasoning of algebra has been deemed sometimes to be in accord with the ancient tradition of analysis but, as Niccolò Guicciardini remarks, "as the seventeenth-century progressed, the rapid advance in mathematical techniques made this form of reference to the ancients less and less plausible, since the results that mathematicians were obtaining obviously were beyond the grasp of the ancient geometers" (Guicciardini, 2002, p. 310).²³ This double movement of tradition and innovation, and the tension implied between the methods of ancient and modern mathematical thinking, can be seen in François Viète's *In artem analyticem isagoge* which is the earliest work on symbolic algebra (Mahoney, 2005; Hill, 1997a, 1997b, 1998). In this work Viète set down the foundations of modern analysis, which combines the rigor of the ancient geometrical reasoning with the operating capacity of algebra, using a symbolical notation both for known and unknown quantities. In such a way, then, he introduced into mathematics the language of formulas. This fact represents an innovation with respect to the ancient *ars analytica* in introducing symbols instead of verbal descriptions, and its heuristic features rest upon the mechanical character of computations.

Descartes's *Geometry* also represents an innovation with respect to Ancient geometrical thought. In this work Descartes justifies and puts in practice the application of algebra to geometry.

²² See, Descartes 1973-1978, Vol. X, pp. 377-379; Van de Pitte, 1991.

²³ See also Westfall, 1980, p. 24.

In the first chapter he constructs an algebra of line segments and shows that the basic operations of mathematics (addition, subtraction, multiplication and extraction of roots) can be applied to, and have a representation in, geometry. This programme is stated in the very title which opens this work: “Any problem in geometry can easily be reduced to such terms that a knowledge of the lengths of certain straight lines is sufficient for its construction.” Then, in sharp contrast with Euclid’s *Elements*, which begins with definitions and postulates, Descartes straightforwardly commences his *Geometry* with the assimilation of numbers to lines. This is done for the sake of simplicity, and Descartes does not trouble himself with the issue of the differences and similarities that lines and numbers entail. This happens, it could be thought, because of his methodological principle according to which in the study of difficult things it must be started with the simplest things (or notions) and those most easy to apprehend; or owing to his diminishing of the intuitive and foundational concerns of mathematics, and his inclination towards the acceptance of imaginary and irrational numbers. This created problems of justification about these mathematical entities not only for Descartes but for all the supporters of the symbolical character of the new algebra and its connection to geometry.

In England, William Oughtred’s *Clavis mathematicae* (1631) marked another step towards the advancement of arithmetic and algebra by emphasising the use of symbols. He is recognised for the introduction of the cross sign for multiplication (X), for the dot sign of proportion (::), and for the sign of difference (–). Oughtred’s works also contributed to the symbolising for sine, cosine, tangent and cotangent, as well as the radix method of calculating logarithms, and the first table of logarithms.

In the development of modern analysis, the name of John Wallis should also be mentioned. He contributed to this field by introducing Cartesian analytical methods, as well as enlarging its scope. Thus, for example, in his *De sectionibus conicis* (1655) he pioneered the analytic treatment of conics in England. In his *Arithmetica infinitorum* (1656) he used infinite series in order to calculate areas under curves. In this work Wallis made use of negative numbers and fractions, for the first time the sign ∞ was used to symbolise infinity, he also represented imaginary numbers geometrically, as well as he produced an infinite product for π . It could be said, moreover, that this work was an important factor for the move from geometrical thinking to algebraic reasoning in England. In his *A treatise of algebra both historical and practical* (1685), he included a treatment of infinite series (Pycior 1997, p. 40-69).

Newton’s acquaintance with analysis dates from 1664 when he departed from the standard curriculum of his studies in the Trinity College in Cambridge, and undertook the study of the new trends of mathematical research in higher mathematics through the works of the leading mathematicians of his time. During the course of his readings, he grasped the topics of modern analysis such as number theory, traditional and modern geometry, algebra and theory of equations, infinitesimals, and the method of tangents. Thus, for example, he learnt from Oughtred’s *Clavis mathematicae*, the symbolic notation; from Descartes’s *Geometry*, the algebraic symbolism; from Barrow’s *Euclidis Elementorum*, the forms of proof; from Viète’s *In artem analyticam isagoge* and Oughtred’s *Clavis*, the use of algebraic variables; and from Wallis’s *Arithmetica infinitorum*, the

method of infinite series. What is not so clear, as has been observed by some Newton scholars, is the order in which he followed these readings' (Newton 1968-1980, vol. I, pp. 7-9; Westfall, 1980, p. 106).

The main problems with which early modern analysis was concerned were the finding or construction of areas under curves (integration), the finding or construction of tangents to curves (differentiation), and the finding of maxima and minima. Through the reading of works on modern analysis, Newton not only acquired the knowledge of the present state of mathematics but he also enlarged it and improved it. At the beginning he tackled these problems algebraically. From Wallis's techniques of interpolation, he realised that polynomials could be expressed in finite series, and next, by expanding polynomials including fractions and negative numbers, these become infinite series with an infinite number of terms of some sequence. This realisation led Newton to his first mathematical discovery, the binomial theorem.

The second advance he introduced in modern analysis was the unification of the procedures both for drawing tangents and for calculating the area under curves, which he found to be inversely related to each other. In this second step, Newton handled quadratures kinematically, conceiving the areas swept by curves as the product of a line in movement. Next, from the static summation of infinitesimals, and from the consideration of points in motion, he proceeded to tackle the problems mechanically in speaking of bodies in motion instead of moving points or lines. This third phase was undertaken in the *October tract* of 1666 which summarises his previous researches on calculus.

This line of development of Newton's acquaintance with, and improvement of, mathematics which goes from 1664 to 1666, gives us an idea that at this stage Newton's calculus was shaped at its embryo stage, or in Westfall's words, if it "was not born, certainly it had been conceived" (Westfall, 1980: 109-121; Guicciardini, 1999: 31, 17-38; Kitcher, 1973; Pepper, 1988).

The years 1665 and 1666 of Newton's intellectual development have been regarded by some scholars as the *anni mirabiles*, a period during which he developed his seminal contributions in optics, mechanics and mathematics. This estimation, in addition, is supported by Newton's own words (Westfall, 1980, p. 143). However, it is more akin to a myth than to the real progress of his ideas concerning optics, and mechanics, viewed in the light of his manuscripts and recent publications of his papers now at the disposal of investigators. This theme has been discussed by, for example, R. S. Westfall (Westfall, 1980a, 1980, pp. 140-175), but what in fact is clear from this period (including 1664) is that Newton the mathematician was born, and that his calculus started to take shape (Whiteside, 1964, 1982). Certainly, Newton's contact with modern analysis led him to devise his calculus which involves three phases of development. First, in *De analysi per aequationes numero terminorum infinitas* (1669, but published in 1711) his approach to analytical geometry was mainly by means of infinitesimals; second, in *De Methodis serierum et fluxionum* (1670-1, but published in 1736 translated into English) he made use of fluxions; and third, in *De quadratura curvarum* (1693, published in 1704 as appendix to the first edition of the *Opticks*) he tackled the problems using the method of first and ultimate ratios (Boyer, 1959, pp. 187-202; Guicciardini, 2002, 2003, 2004b).

In the approach to geometrical problems by means of analytical geometry, the use of finite series (Descartes, Oughtred) was labelled by Newton "common" or "modern analysis", and the

recourse to infinite series (Wallis, Barrow), which were thought to be infinite equations he named “new analysis”. In the line of work of modern analysis, by 1664-5, Newton advanced by introducing his first mathematical discovery, the binomial theorem. With the aid of which he tackled the problem of squaring a large class of curvilinear figures in an analytical mode, introducing negative and fractional exponents, in addition to infinitesimals (in this case, infinite equations or infinite series). As he wrote in *De analysi*:

Neither do I know any Thing of this kind to which this Method doth not extend, and that in various Ways (...) And whatever common Analysis performs by Means of Equations of a finite number of terms (provided they can be done) this can always perform the same by Means of infinite Equations: So I have not made any Question of giving this the name of *Analysis* likewise. For the Reasonings in this are no less certain than in the other; nor the Equations less exact (Newton, 1745, p. 340).

The use of this theorem, which helped to abbreviate the division and root extraction by the incorporation of infinite series into the common analysis, was mentioned in two letters written to Leibniz via Oldenburg in 1676 (*epistola prior* June 13, and *epistola posterior* October 24²⁴), concerning Newton’s analytical method to resolve geometrical problems. With the aid of this tool, he asserted once again that the very limits of analysis are enlarged and, what is more important, its improvement offers a new approach to the determination of several problems regarding geometry (areas, volumes, and so forth). Thus, in the first of these letters he asserted that “From all this it is to be seen how much the limits of analysis are enlarged by such infinite equations; in fact by their help analysis reaches, I might almost say, to all problems, the numerical problems of Diophantus and the like excepted” (Newton, 1959-1977: Vol., 2, p. 39; Biot & Lefort, 1856, p. 109).

De Analysisi, a work drawn from the early drafted October Tract of 1666, is an investigation into the properties of curvilinear figures and their measure as well as their squaring (quadrature) the subject matter was the development of an algorithm by which the resolution of problems regarding the quadrature could be simplified. It begins by expounding in three *regulae* the method whereby to determine the area of curves by means of infinite series. Firstly, it deals with simple curves, next with the quadrature of curves compounded of simple ones, and lastly with the quadrature of all other curves (Newton, 1711, pp. 1, 2, 5).

Another work on Newton’s use of analysis for in the dominion of geometry is his *De methodis serierum et fluxionum* written in 1670-1, a work in which he started to size his attention on the foundations of his calculus in terms of fluxions. Additionally, *De methodis* enhances and develops his previous *De analysi*, and also focuses on the preliminary problems (1-13) of the fluxional October Tract of 1666. Thus, in the line of the new analysis, Newton remarks in the introductory paragraph his intention to enlarge it by means of the analytical treatment of problems regarding maxima and minima, quadrature of curves, arc lengths, etc.:

²⁴ Biot and Lefort, 1856, pp. 102-112, 122-145; Newton, 1968-1980, Vol. III, Appendix A, pp. 24-26.

Observing that the majority of geometers, with an almost complete neglect of the ancients' synthetical method, now for the most part apply themselves to the cultivation of analysis and with its aid have overcome so many formidable difficulties that they seem to have exhausted virtually everything apart from the squaring of curves and certain topics of like nature not yet fully elucidated: I found it not amiss, for the satisfaction of learners, to draw up the following short tract in which I might at once widen the boundaries of the field of analysis and advance the doctrine of curves (Newton, 1670-1, p. 33).²⁵

The introduction of infinitesimal quantities plays a central role in this work, being the main and foremost characteristic of *De methodis* the way Newton formulates his calculus in terms of continuous increase. At this stage time plays the principal function:

The advantage of decimals consists in this, that when all fractions and roots have been reduced to them they take on in a certain measure the nature of integers; so it is the advantage of infinite variable-sequences that classes of more complicated terms (such as fractions whose denominators are complex quantities, the roots of complex quantities and the roots of affected equations) may be reduced to the class of simple ones: that is, to infinite series of fractions having simple numerators and denominators and without the all but insuperable encumbrances which beset the others. I will first, consequently, show how to reduce other quantities to terms of this sort, revealing less familiar methods of doing so, and then I will apply this Analysis to the resolution of problems (p. 35).²⁶

Having shown the computational 'less familiar' methods of reduction by division and of affected equations—a passage which constitutes an adjustment and an augmentation (Newton, 1668-1680, Vol. III: notes 7 and 8, pp. 36, 42) of *De analysi*—he proceeded to reduce the difficulties concerning curves and surfaces to two fundamental problems:

1. Given the length of the space continuously (that is, at every [instant of] time), to find the speed of motion at any time proposed.
2. Given the speed of motion continuously, to find the length of the space described at any time proposed (Newton, 1670-1, p. 71).

This reduction, in the words of Guicciardini, is "one of the greatest generalizations in the history of mathematics" since (1) tangents, extreme points, curvatures, and (2) the finding of areas (Guicciardini, 1999, pp. 23-24), can be rendered into mathematical language—as in fact Newton does—in the following terms: "Given the relation of the flowing quantities to one another, to determinate the relation of the fluxions" and "When an equation involving the fluxions of quantities

²⁵ Newton, 1670-1, p. 33.

²⁶ See De Gandt, 1995, pp. 209-213; Guicciardini, 1999, pp. 17-27.

is exhibited, to determinate the relation of the quantities one to another” (Newton, 1670-1, pp. 74, 83).

Moreover, aiming to geometrize the motion, Newton additionally developed this phase of his calculus by postulating a group of concepts (independent variables) which enabled him to solve them by means of a more naturalistic approach derived from nature herself (Newton, 1670-1, pp. 282-283, 327-328; 1704, p. 165). In this phase, Newton dealt with geometrical problems mechanically by considering figures in motion generated by fluxions. Thus, for example, in a cancelled passage of an addendum to his *De methodis* he wrote in terms such as:

If a straight line should move in any manner whatever over some surface, the fluxion of the surface generated by that motion will be as the fluxion of some other straight line let fall from a given point to the mid-point of the first line, multiplied into that first line (Newton, 1670-1, p. 339).

As a result, he regarded the quantities which flow in time, defining *flow* as each of the indefinite increments of quantity of motion in time; *fluent*, each of the increments generated by the flow; *fluxion*, the speeds of flow and their increments by motion; and *momentum*, as “the infinitely small additions by which those quantities increase during each infinitely small interval of time” (p. 81).

The last stage of Newton’s development of calculus is the method of first and last ratios which he stated for the first time in the *Geometria curvilinea*, an unfinished work dated by Whiteside in or about 1680 (Newton, 1680c, pp. 420-505, esp. 411, 420), in Axiom 6, saying that “fluxions of quantities are, in the first ratio of their nascent parts or, what is exactly the same, in the last ratio of those parts as they vanish by defluxion” (p. 427). This method was also used later on in Book I, Section I of the *Principia*. Thus, in Lemma I, he writes: “Quantities, and also ratios of quantities, which in any finite time constantly tend to equality, and which before the end of that time approach so close to one another that their difference is less than any given quantity, become ultimately equal” (Newton, 1999, p. 423). This lemma, and the ten subsequent ones, conform to the basic understanding of Newton’s theory of limits for the analysis of orbital motion with which Book I is concerned. Finally, in the Introduction to *De quadratura curvarum*, Newton expounded the mechanical genesis of geometry under a continual motion, making use of fluxions, and relating them to the ratios (Pourciau, 1998; De Gandt, 1995, pp. 225-234; Guicciardini, 1999, pp. 22-37, 43-47).

In sketching out the development of Newton’s calculus through the phases of infinitesimals, fluxions, and first and ultimate ratios, the improvements he imparted to modern analysis can be discerned. Such improvements were aimed at providing general solutions to the current problems in the field of mathematics, in contrast with the singular treatment and solution to each and every single problem, by means of a general algorithm arising out of the practice of new analysis.

Thus far, it can be said that the pre-eminent role of mathematical research was restricted to the context of discovery, the very ambit which provided to mathematics its strength. Nevertheless, seen in the light of the twofold procedure of discovery *and* proof (or analysis *and* synthesis, in other

words) which both together constituted for Ancients the vigour of mathematical inquiries, some problems emerge.

Basically, the problems that modern analysis was faced with, despite its powerful heuristic character, were those of the lack of intuitive validity, and the lack of a rigorous foundation. Furthermore, there were problems concerning the poverty of algebraic manipulations when viewed as derivations aiming at proofs. These problems arose when this new mathematical thought was compared to, and contrasted with, the imperatives of ancient mathematical thought. To begin with, the new analysis allowed what for the Ancients would have been unthinkable or forbidden operations such as dividing by zero; secondly, it accepted negative and imaginary numbers; and lastly, it handled infinitely small quantities (Pycior, 1997).

In a wider context, the new developments of mathematics thanks to the use of modern analysis created a philosophical debate regarding the legitimacy of that new way of doing mathematics, and the place of analysis itself in the sphere of mathematical practise; the legitimacy of abstract manipulations, and its epistemological validity; the hierarchic arrangement in mathematics of geometry regarded as a branch of mathematics with a concrete ontological content, arithmetic and algebra considered as a mode of reasoning on abstract signs, and modern analysis (or algebra) deemed as a heuristic tool.

Since a new style of doing mathematics was emerging and it implied, in consequence, a new conception of mathematics itself, this debate was indeed a philosophical one. At the centre of this debate there was a tension between the fidelity to the traditional conception of mathematical research, and the adoption of new mathematical procedures which welcomed conceptions that had been avoided in ancient mathematical thought, becoming thus an innovative mathematics. In short, this debate was another battle in the war between Ancients and Moderns. Some of its components have to do with the procedures, for instance, concerning the central role attributed to analysis (and synthesis); the way of disposing hierarchically geometry, arithmetic, and algebra; and the empiricist or rationalist stance adopted towards the foundations of mathematics. Labels such as realism, constructivism, formalism, and nominalism are conceptual contrivances designed to analyse these issues, which encompass number theory, equations, geometry of infinitesimals, fluxions, and first and ultimate ratios. It is a complex debate indeed, and owing to this very complexity it is difficult to attribute, or to discern, a homogeneous philosophy of mathematics in each of its actors, for the most of times, viewed from the standpoint of Ancients against Moderns, some of them adopted in certain themes pro-ancient views, whereas with respect to other topics they seem to be in agreement with Moderns or innovationists.

In general terms the philosophical debate within mathematical thinking between the supporters of ancient and modern ways of doing mathematics can be characterised by the viewpoints adopted regarding the nature of mathematics and the progress or regress involved in the acceptance (pro-Moderns), or the refusal (pro-Ancients) of the values and techniques shared by both sides of the controversy. On the side of supporters and promoters of modern mathematics the prominence given to algebra over geometry, the approval of new symbolism, the embracing of algebra because of its heuristic power, the valuation of analysis for propaedeutic purposes, the

innovative character of new and modern analysis in doing mathematics, the predilection for discovery over proof, the belief in the notion of progress, and the anchoring of the method of analysis over that of synthesis, constituted their promoted values. On the opposite side, defenders of traditional mathematical thought endorsed values such as the high regard for geometry over algebra, the refusal of symbolism, the estimation of analysis as sheer heuristic tool, the traditional techniques of presentation of synthetic proofs, the belief in the decay of nature, and the promotion of synthetic methods.

In the case of Newton, he was not absent from this debate. As a matter of fact, it should be observed that his sentiments towards modern analysis regarded as a technique of doing mathematics which mingled arithmetical computations with geometrical representations such as lines, points, surfaces, etc., underwent a deep change in his thought. At the beginning, they were of sympathy and approval, but as the time passed, he increasingly departed from it as his mathematical treatment of problems became increasingly sophisticated; moreover, he increased his taste for the ancient method of synthesis, which led to the eventual rejection of analysis for epistemological, philosophical, and metaphysical reasons.

By the middle of the decade of 1670s, after the redaction of *De methodis*, Newton's philosophy of mathematics underwent a sensible shift towards ancient thought, a shift which would pervade entirely his natural philosophy, not only in mathematics and physics but in metaphysics and theology as well. In the domain of mathematics, he started to distance himself from modern analysis and leaned towards the ancient geometrical thinking which favoured the synthetic proof and kept hidden the process of discovery by analysis. Ancient mathematics, and particularly ancient geometry, were regarded by him as more simple and elegant, and with a definite ontological content; in the ambit of physics, he considered the results of his researches as a rediscovery of ancient truths, and consequently he saw his philosophical endeavours as a continuation of the tradition rather than a revolutionary set of progressions; in metaphysics he embraced the idea according to which through the time mankind has been subjected to a process of degeneration and regress from the pristine truth contained in the *prisca sapientia*; and in theology, he developed a heretical theology which rejected and disbelieved the dogma of trinity, and sought through the study of natural phenomena the discernment of God's providential plan.

Newton's reorientation of mathematical research, that is to say, his shift from modern analysis to geometry; his dissatisfaction with the status of infinitesimals which he considered as controversial, and his leaning to limits; and his rejection of modern analysis in favour of the geometry of Ancients took place mainly in the sphere of calculus (Guicciardini, 1999). In point of fact, he departed from the common analysis governed by algebra; then, by means of the use of infinite series (or infinite equations) and the introduction of fluxions, fluents and moments he expanded modern analysis, and described his calculus as an analytical method of fluxions; next, by 1670s Newton leaned towards the ancient geometrical thought which favoured the synthetic presentation of proofs, this phase was considered by him as the synthetic method of fluxions (Newton, 1968-1980, Vol. VIII, pp. 455-457); finally, his physics was expounded in terms of pure geometry, such as the case of his *Principia* (Guicciardini, 2004b, De Gandt, 1995).

Notwithstanding the advance Newton bestowed to calculus, he did not publish the results he arrived to, and the circumstances under which he made them public were, as it is well known, the controversy with Leibniz on the invention of calculus. Besides, the motivations surrounding his choice are complex and relate to restrictions concerning some specificities of mathematical qualities as well as to the contemporary social and cultural state of affairs.

As a matter of fact, despite the foundation of journals intended to make public the results of investigations in natural philosophy, there existed other means than publication in journals, namely, letters and manuscript copies of mathematical treatises and essays which circulated in restricted circles. This form of publication made possible the control of the audience these materials were intended for, in contradistinction to the open accessibility of the printed form. Thus, for instance, *De analysi* was communicated to John Collins via Isaac Barrow in the wake of Nicolas Mercator's *Logarithmotechnia* (1668), but Newton refused to publish it because he wanted to make some improvements to it. In a letter to Collins on the publication of this tract he wrote:

As for my paper I sent about infinite series, I know not whether it will be proper to print it. I leave it to your discretion. In my apprehension it may do as well to suppress it, but if you think otherwise I desire you would give me notice it go to y^e Press, because of altering an expression or two (Newton, 1959-1977, p. 95).

The two *epistolae* written to Leibniz via Henry Oldenburg are another example in which Newton communicated to the German philosopher cryptically his discoveries in infinite series, and the binomial theorem *inter alia*. Besides this form of publication, Newton also made use of the printed form to divulge his discoveries, the most notable illustration being perhaps his *New theory about light and colors* (1672). In addition, it should be noticed that in the sphere of his mathematical researches other circumstances were unfavourable for publication. For instance, *De methodis* was intended to be published several times, mainly through the exhortation of Collins and Barrow but there were some reasons which led Newton to leave it unpublished: such as his fear of being engaged in disputes like those which emerged when he published his paper on optics in 1672, his occupations with the optical lectures, and the unfavourable expectations for its sale figures (Guicciardini, 2004c).

The reorientation of Newton's philosophy of mathematics centres on his critical attitude towards some basic characteristics of Modernity in general, and on the way of doing mathematics in particular. Along these lines it is possible to distinguish epistemological, philosophical, and metaphysical levels of his system of natural philosophy, all of which motivated his shift towards traditionalism in mathematics. Epistemological, in so far as his calling for a mathematics empirically well founded on a clear ontological content, and the demand for certitude in the methods utilised in mathematics in particular, and in philosophy of nature in general; philosophical with respect to his refusal of symbolism; and metaphysical due to his preference for the ancient approach to the synthetic presentation of the results achieved, which is linked to the tradition of ancient ways of tackling geometrical problems. So, in order to examine this shift, I will discuss each of them, focusing the analysis principally on what concerns his philosophy of mathematics.

As mentioned above, in the wake of the developments of mathematics in analytic geometry, infinitesimals, and symbolic reasoning of algebra, and due to the stances adopted towards that new way of doing mathematics, sometimes supporting it, and sometimes criticising it, and in assuming a traditionalist and conservative attitude towards the ancient geometry, it is difficult to determine a homogeneous philosophy of mathematics in a number of seventeenth-century natural philosophers. In Newton's case we find the same situation. As David Sepkoski has observed, "Newton stands as a problematic and fascinating character, torn between (...) constructivism and ontological realism, and between traditional geometry and analysis". From the perspective of analysis of realism and constructivism, Newton transcended such categories by virtue of the entities he conceived in his natural philosophy such as forces operating in the framework of the absolutes of time and space (Sepkoski, 2002, p. 202). And as Sepkoski convincingly argues, Newton's philosophy of mathematics resists an outright classification in either or both categories whether realist or constructivist. For example, in defining absolute time and space in the scholium to the Definitions of the *Principia*, Newton speaks of them having an independent existence which "flows uniformly" with regard to the first one, and "always remain[ing] homogeneous and immovable" with regard to the second. In this scholium, Newton takes for granted their existence, and so therefore it would be possible to enlist him on the side of realists since he seems to indicate the possibility of apprehending their essences or natures, all the more so since in both definitions he speaks of their "own nature[s]" (Newton, 1668, pp. 90-121, 121-56).

Notwithstanding this, the knowledge of the absolutes, time and space, is obtained inferentially by means of the study of their sensible measures, and the ontological correspondence between absolute and relative time and space is attainable by the analysis of their properties, causes and effects as illustrated in the experiments expounded in this scholium.²⁷ It should be observed, that in this instance, as the scholium shows, experience is the most reliable, if not the only way in Newton's natural philosophy, to (inferential) knowledge of the natural world.

Albeit the distinction of time and space between absolute and relative, true and apparent, and mathematical and common, by means of the inferential knowledge, Newton at the same time seems to be aiming at the reduction of the gap between mathematics and physics. Such an attitude in Newton's natural philosophy also can be found earlier in his *Quaestiones quaedam philosophicae* (1664) in the essay entitled "On Quantity". In this respect, McGuire and Rattansi have remarked that Newton "attempts to minimize the divide between mathematical representations of imagination and the sensible world itself" although they see in it a move from realism towards conceptualism in Newton's thought (Newton, 1985, pp. 91-113).²⁸

Taking into consideration Newton's philosophy of mathematics, it is possible to say that this is not a homogeneous philosophy. By examining the development of his mathematical inquiries it is easy to discern two stages: one characterised by his adoption of the new tools and techniques of mathematical research which is governed by modern analysis which proved to be powerful enough in his shaping of calculus; the second stage is marked by his critical attitude towards the new way of

²⁷ See Disalle, 2002; Rynasiewicz, 1995a, 1995b.

²⁸ See esp. 112.

doing mathematics, and his preference for the traditional methods of ancient geometrical thought which privileged synthesis over analysis. As earlier stated, Newton was by no means the only figure of his time with an indefinite philosophy of mathematics; quite contrary, outstanding names such as John Wallis and Isaac Barrow, when analysed in the battleground of Ancients vs. Moderns with respect to mathematical thought, also exhibit a heterogeneous conception of mathematics (Hill, 1997a, 1997b, 1998).

As for labels such as realist and constructivist, they break down, to use Sepkoski's expression (2005, p. 52), in view of the entities postulated by Newton in his ontology of the natural world. It should be clarified, however, that in mathematics Newton's philosophy is more akin to constructivism, and this observation can be reinforced by his experimentalism. On the other hand, Newton's realism becomes even more problematic if this characteristic of his thought is examined only through his most representative works i.e., the *Principia* and the *Opticks*. It is necessary to peruse this problem in the light of important manuscripts which clarify and expand the meaning of his public works.

Sepkoski's assertion regarding Newton's mathematics is in concurrence with that of Guicciardini. According to this latter, "it would be excessive to attribute to Newton a definite philosophy of mathematics" (Guicciardini, 2003, p. 418). Newton's move from analysis to synthesis and his rejection of symbolism which dates from the decade of 1670 is a significant one, but it was not definitive, for he published for example in 1707 the *Arithmetica Universalis*, and Guicciardini is right in noting that he was a good enough algebraist as to let aside completely modern analysis (p. 416). In sum, if it is sufficiently clear that from the epistemological viewpoint Newton's mathematics is not homogeneous, it is indeed quite evident that he was led to a mathematical empiricism which led to a "philosophy of mathematics—and particularly geometry—that was 'physicalist'; that is to say, a belief that mathematical representations should be closely aligned with the properties of physical bodies and their motions" as Sepkoski has pointed out (2002, p. 251).

The study of Greek mathematics was the starting point of Newton's revision of the scopes and limits of modern analysis and the re-evaluation of this method, as well as the place he attributed to it with respect to mathematical methodology. Through the reading of Pappus's *Mathematicae Collectiones*—especially the seventh book—he discovered an elegance and simplicity in Greek mathematical researches. Such features he found worthy to be emulated, and this methodology in geometry also was a tradition which deserved to be continued.

Generally speaking, the ancient mathematical methodology represented for him a higher style of thought compared to modern analysis. The elegance and simplicity of ancient geometrical thought lay, according to Newton, in the fact that this kind of reasoning is established upon discernible objects by the senses—a conception which fits well with his empiricism—in contradistinction to the intelligibility of reasoning on symbols devoid of a concrete referential content. Secondly, through his examination of the merits of algebraic calculus by means of abbreviating mathematical process, he estimated it to be very complicated, and in consequence they seemed not to shorten mathematics. Instead of it, verbal descriptions were considered more

suitable than the abbreviated ones. And thirdly, in the process of inquiries into geometry their results should be offered in synthetic style, omitting the analytic phase, in accordance to the ancient practice. One of the most representative figures who anchored modern analysis was Descartes, a fountain of inspiration for Newton in his youth, and more often than not one of the main targets of his criticisms as he shaped and matured his natural philosophy. By *circa* 1680, commenting on the solution of Descartes to the *solid locus* problem, Newton expressed his sentiments on both modern analysis, and the ancient practice of tackling geometrical problems.

To be sure, their [the Ancients's] method is more elegant by far than the Cartesian one. For he [Descartes] achieved the result by an algebraic calculus which, when transposed into words (following the practice of the Ancients in their writings), would prove to be so tedious and entangled as to provoke nausea, nor might it be understood. But they accomplished it by certain simple propositions, judging that nothing written in a different style was worthy to be read, and in consequence concealing the analysis by which they found their constructions (Newton, 1680c. b, p. 277).

In this passage Newton's criticisms are directed to algebraic manipulations in the view of their derivations aiming at a proof. According to his approach, such a procedure becomes completely knotty as to be worthy of publication, provided that the process of discovery is omitted and the results are expressed clearly in a few words in the form of propositions; that is to say, here Newton is calling for the second step of the twin procedure of analysis *and* synthesis. In effect, some lines below this passage, he adopts this standpoint which is in accordance with the ancient values he was then promoting:

Hence it is not to be wondered if complicated results should arise which it would be loathsome to construct in their entirety by a geometrical procedure. (...) This arithmetical approach is indeed fine—and a geometrical one inelegant—where the synthetic method has the whiphand, but is at fault, conversely, should ever an over-elaborate analysis deserve to be called no less of a defect than the over-complicated construction of a problem. Observing therefore that numerous kinds of problem which are usually resolved by [an algebraic] analysis may (at least for the most part) be more simply effected by synthesis, I have written the following treatise on the topic (Newton, 1680 c. a, p. 423).

These quotations clearly show how Newton sided with the traditional methodology of ancient geometers, and in turn we can perceive the place he conferred upon analysis in mathematical researches. Newton's emphasis was markedly on synthesis, and regarded analysis as a route, the first part of a process, towards synthesis (or composition, as it was also named), or in other words as a heuristic tool. Already in 1683, his thoughts on analysis were directed to regarding it in that manner. Thus, in one of his lectures on algebra, he stated:

Present-day geometers indulge too much in speculation from equations. The simplicity of these is a consideration belonging to analysis: we are here occupied with composition, and laws are not to be laid down for composition from an analytical standpoint. Analysis guides us to the composition, but true composition is not achieved before it is freed from all its analysis. Let even the slightest trace of the analysis be present in the composition and you will not yet have attained the true composition. Composition is perfect in itself and shrinks from any admixture with analytical speculations. Simplicity in figures is dependent on the simplicity of their genesis and conception, and it is not its equation but its description (whether geometrical or mechanical) by which a figure is generated and rendered easy to conceive (Newton, 1683-1684: Vol. V, p. 477).

The examination of ancient methods of mathematics led Newton to shape his *Principia* in the direction appointed in this passage, i.e., he composed his *magnum opus* in the style of ancient geometers, that is, in the synthetic mode which concealed analysis. This assertion, it ought to be advised, is a problematic one, and we have notice of this procedure not from a direct statement of Newton himself in this work, but in the wake of the quarrel with Leibniz on the priority of the invention of calculus. We learn from the masterful exposition of Guicciardini on Newton's mathematical methods (!) in his *Principia* that this is a complex work in which a plurality of geometrical techniques and analytical methods of fluxions is used, and with good reason he observes: "complex, varied and stratified are Newton's mathematical methods for natural philosophy. Newton did not possess a universal mathematical tool which he applied to natural philosophy. He was rather in possession of a whole variety of mathematical instruments" (Guicciardini, 1999: 1, *passim*). And as for the controversy with Leibniz, it is well known that this episode gave rise to vehement pronouncements by the author of the gravity law concerning the method he employed to achieve his findings, and more exactly, how he was in possession of calculus as early as he developed his first mathematical discoveries. By the decade of 1710 Newton wrote a number of papers related to his use of analysis and synthesis in mathematical researches. Among them we find draft prefaces to the second edition of the *Principia*, as well as related documents with the controversy itself. Perhaps one of the most celebrated comes from his (anonymous) review of the *Commercium Epistolicum*.

By the help of this new Analysis Mr Newton found out most of the Propositions in his *Principia Philosophiae*. But because the Ancients for making things certain admitted nothing into Geometry before it was demonstrated synthetically, he demonstrated the Propositions synthetically that the systeme of the heavens might be founded upon good Geometry. And this makes it now difficult for unskillful men to see the Analysis by w^{ch} those Propositions were found out.²⁹

²⁹ Newton, 1715, pp. 598-599. With respect to this report of Newton, scholars of the *Principia* such as Bernard Cohen, Rupert Hall, Niccolò Guicciardini, and Derek T. Whiteside have asserted its rhetorical weight, and have emphasised how internal evidence contradicts to Newton. Thus for instance the outstanding authority of Newton's

Newton's adherence to the ancient tradition of tackling geometrical problems is shown by his way of presenting the results, i.e., synthetically. In the various papers he wrote concerning his use of analysis and synthesis in the *Principia*, in particular, and in geometrical inquiries in general, he repeatedly emphasised that only by means of synthesis demonstrations achieve the indisputable character of a true proof, at the same time he underlined the heuristic character of analysis. Thus, for instance, in one of his draft prefaces intended for the second edition to the *Principia*, he asserted the magnificence of geometry by virtue of its certainty which is attained synthetically. As regards analysis, he declared that it "is useful for finding out truths, but the certainty of a finding ought to be attested through the composition of a demonstration".³⁰

During the controversy with Leibniz, both a concrete referential content of geometry founded upon nature, and the exigency of the demonstrations synthetically constructed, were recurrent claims in Newton's pronouncements. The stance adopted in the course of this controversy is both founded upon his interest to continue the ancient Greek geometrical tradition, and upon his empiricist epistemology. In *De quadratura curvarum* Newton describes the mathematical quantities as generated by motion in contrast with Leibniz's notion of indivisibles; instead of indivisibles, Newton's fluxions "take place in the physical world and are daily enacted in the motion of bodies visible before our eyes" and consequently since they are real "ought to have their own symbols".³¹ The contrast between the methods of Newton becomes even more evident in Newton's review of the *Commercium Epistolicum*. In commenting on their difference, Newton appealed to the tradition of the Ancients as he depicted Leibniz's method devoid of referential content, and as a simple heuristic tool lacking demonstrative character.

We have no ideas of infinitely little quantities & therefore M^r Newton introduced fluxions into his method that it might proceed by finite quantities as much as possible. It is more natural & geometrical because founded upon the *primae quantitatum nascentium rationes* w^{ch} have a being in Geometry, whilst *indivisibles* upon which the Differential Method is founded, have no being either in Geometry or in Nature. There are *rationes primae quantitatum nascentium*, but not *quantitates primae nascentes*. Nature generates quantities by continual flux or increase, & the ancient Geometers admitted such a Generation of areas & solids when they drew one line into another by local motion to generate an area & the area into a line by local motion to generate a solid. But the summing up of indivisibles to compose an area or solid was never yet admitted into Geometry. M^r Newton's method is also of greater use & certainty being adapted either to the ready finding out of a Proposition by such approximations as will create no error in the conclusion, or to the demonstrating

mathematical papers, Derek T. Whiteside, has remarked that "based on the examination of the surviving corpus of his [Newton's] working papers and calculations sheets [...] 'the published state of the *Principia* ... is the exact same as that in which was written'". *Ibid.*, p. 443, fn. 1, italics in original.

³⁰ Isaac Newton, ULC. Add. 3968.9, p. 107', in Newton, 1968-1980, VIII, p. 449. See also ULC. Add. 3968.9, p. 105'. *Ibid.*, pp. 647-648.

³¹ Isaac Newton, Add. 3960.13 in Newton 1968-1980, Vol. VIII, pp. 107, 115 respectively.

it exactly: M^r Leibnitz's is only for finding it out.³²

This statement exhibits the crux of Newton's orientation of his mathematical inquiries. Firstly, he asserted the foundation of geometrical researches upon nature; secondly, he presents his researches as a continuation of the ancient tradition of geometrical thought; and lastly, he highlights the demonstrative character of his calculus. At the same time Leibniz's method of indivisibles is downgraded to a heuristic tool. On the other hand, Newton's distrust of symbolism, specifically when devoid of referential content, sharply contrasts with Leibniz's attitude towards the symbolic aspect of analysis. In truth, Leibniz was an enthusiastic and active promoter of mathematical notation, whereas Newton's interest in notation was a minor topic in his mathematical researches.

In addition to his interest in presenting the results of his inquiries in the line of the tradition of ancient geometry, there is another important reason for adopting the language of geometry in his mathematical researches, and even more important in the *Principia*: the mathematisation of force, and in accord with his conception of the foundations of mathematics, its geometrization; displacements and the action of forces in accelerations are adequately represented in the form of geometrical language.³³

In the context of Newton's research programme for the philosophy of nature, mathematics plays a central role—along with his experimentalism—in his endeavours to investigate the natural world. As is well known, throughout the scientific revolution one of the main aims was to reveal the structure of nature, and such a structure was thought, by some, to be a mathematical one. The metaphor of the book of nature written in mathematical language voiced by Galileo³⁴, for Newton was a conviction, and in fact without mathematics it was quite implausible to gain a firm comprehension of nature.

Newton's conception of mathematics becomes understandable in its complexity viewed in the light of this approach to nature. Precisely in the close relationship entailed between mathematics and nature, Newton's mathematics is focused on the perspective of the physicist who aimed at—and achieved—the mathematisation of force and the geometrization of motion. From this perspective also his demand for a mathematics founded upon a concrete ontological content, and his distrust to any symbolism devoid of it, becomes comprehensible. Indeed, for Newton there was no such thing as an ideal mathematics on the one side, and the material and empirical world of physics on the other side. For this reason, we find notions such as fluxions and fluents representing velocities and increments of motions in his mathematical inquiries, thus making mechanics the

³² Newton, 1715, pp. 597-598.

³³ See Guicciardini, 1999, p. 50-51, 104-106.

³⁴ "Philosophy is written in this all-encompassing book that is constantly open before our eyes, that is the universe; but it cannot be understood unless one first learns to understand the language and knows the characters in which it is written. It is written in mathematical language, and its characters are triangles, circles, and other geometrical figures; without these it is humanly impossible to understand a word of it, and one wanders around pointlessly in a dark labyrinth." Galilei, *The Assayer*, as quoted in Finocchiaro, 2008, p. 183.

basis of geometry. The conception of geometry founded upon mechanics is in effect in the line of the classical tradition, but the geometrization of motion in Newton's hands signified the departure from the ancient tradition to a more innovatory approach, as Guicciardini rightly has reminded us.³⁵ The core of Newton's conviction regarding the mathematical structure of the book of nature lay in the fact that for him motion—and even more important force, its causal agent—was not a concept deprived of physical reality, it was not a form of mathematical speech but—in addition to the absolute time and space—the basic constituents of the framework of nature.

Newton's physicalist philosophy of mathematics helps us to clarify the differences between him and those whom he criticised. Thus, for example, whereas the champions of modern analysis were in a great deal concerned with the logic of discovery and its heuristic strength, Newton was mainly concerned with the proof of truth founded upon *rerum natura* and its facts as well as with its ontological foundation which provides the legitimacy and usefulness of natural philosophy, above its logical structure.

The reorientation of Newton's mathematical researches took its inspiration from the classical tradition of Greek geometers, and his classicism determined to a great extent his entire natural philosophy, but to centre the attention only around the facet of his mathematics is simplistic and misleading to the understanding of his success in disclosing the mathematical structure of the book of nature, which lay precisely in the mathematisation of the force of gravity. The demand for the ontological content of mathematics is to a large extent in agreement with his experimental philosophy based on matters of fact; this is the very dimension on which truth must be based, and any arguments for natural philosophy—as he repeatedly affirmed—have to come from phenomena, from the effects to the causes. Both in the fourth *regula philosophandi* of the *Principia* and in the Query 31st of the *Opticks* he pointed out this way of philosophising as the “best way of arguing that the Nature of things admits of”.³⁶ This approach to the study of nature consequently leads us to the experimental side of his natural philosophy in all its parts.

2.2. Experimental philosophy

The experimental side of Newton's natural philosophy is another main focus of analysis both for historians and philosophers of science. We all know, for example, the much-mentioned motto *hypotheses non fingo* (I do not feign hypotheses) of the General Scholium appended to the second edition of the *Principia* (1713). Such a motto, as we also know, was addressed by Newton to his Continental critics—and mainly to Leibniz—who demanded a causal (i.e., mechanistic in the Cartesian sense) explanation of the most weighty and momentous concept of that work, namely, the gravity force, in order to express the disdain, he felt towards any unsubstantiated explanation of natural phenomena. However, the General Scholium was not the first public defence made by Newton regarding his approach to natural philosophy. In effect, his very first contribution to the

³⁵ Guicciardini, 2003, pp. 407-31, p. 425.

³⁶ Newton, 1730, p. 380.

learned world in the *Philosophical Transactions* of the Royal Society,³⁷ his *New Theory about Light and Colors*, was followed by a series of criticisms³⁸ which pressed Newton to clarify and justify his method and his mathematical approach to the study of nature.³⁹ In the case of the *Principia*, or more precisely, in the wake of the criticisms aroused from its publication, Newton once again was compelled to elucidate and to define precisely his natural philosophy both in his mathematical and experimental aspects. From the point of view of mathematics, the controversy on the invention of calculus was the crux of the debate between Leibniz and Newton. Given the fact that Newton's *Principia* was written following the ancient tradition of mathematics which presented the discoveries synthetically, his critics (notably Leibniz) naturally assumed that he lacked knowledge of the new analytic method of calculus.⁴⁰

As for the experimental philosophy, the repercussions of the dissatisfaction of Newton's critics with respect to the nature of gravity force were of far-reaching consequences. As a matter of fact, from the publication of his *Principia* Newton was focused on strengthening and on clearly defining the fundamentals of his natural philosophy, and effectively he produced a number of papers related to his methodology, as well as to his ontology of nature and theological views; some of them were published in the Queries of the *Opticks* as well as in the General Scholium in the *Principia* (1713), one was published anonymously by him⁴¹, and some others remained unpublished until the second half of the past century.⁴²

Despite the fact that Newton publicly declared his natural philosophy as "experimental" for the first time in 1713⁴³ in the General Scholium to the *Principia*, in order to legitimise his notion of universal gravitation, we can find this experimental stance from the very beginning of his career. Thus, in his *Quaestiones quaedam Philosophiae* (1664) we find under the headline 'Philosophy' that "The nature of things is more securely & naturally deduced from their operations one upon another than upon our senses. And when by the former Experiments we have found the nature of bodys, by the latter we may more clearly find the nature of our senses."⁴⁴ And in his *New Theory about Light and Colors*

³⁷ Isaac Newton. "New Theory about Light and Colors", *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society*, 80, 1671/2, pp. 3075-3087. In this paper Newton announced his conception of light as "a *Heterogeneous mixture of differently refrangible Rays*" and colours "not *Qualifications of Light*, derived from Refractions, or Reflections of natural Bodies (as 'tis generally believed,) but *Original and connate properties*, which in divers Rays are divers." Newton, 1672, pp. 3079, 3081, respectively. Italics in original.

³⁸ See Newton, 1958, pp. 47-238.

³⁹ In his paper of 1672, Newton declared openly his mathematical approach to the study of optical phenomena: "A naturalist would scarce expect to see ye science of those [i.e., colours] become mathematicall, & yet I dare affirm that there is as much certainty in it as in any other part of Opticks. For what I shall tell concerning them is not an Hypothesis but most rigid consequence, not conjectured by barely inferring 'tis thus because not otherwise or because it satisfies all phaenomena (the Philosophers universall Topick,) but evinced by ye mediation of experiments concluding directly & without any suspicion of doubt." Newton, 1959-1977, vol. I, pp. 398-399.

⁴⁰ See Hall, 1980; Meli, 1993; Guicciardini, 1999.

⁴¹ See Newton, 1714/5.

⁴² See McGuire, 1966, 1968, 1970; McGuire and Rattansi, 1966; Casini, 1984; Schüller, 2001.

⁴³ See Shapiro, 2004.

⁴⁴ Newton, 1664: 28. Newton's first choice for this headline was "Occult Qualities", but then he cancelled it and wrote "Philosophy". As is well known, the abolishment of occult qualities (in the Aristotelian sense) was one of the main reforms introduced during early modern science. This passage, as far as I can see, clearly shows Newton taking part on,

that it “was founded on the Hypothesis of the proportionality of the *sines* of Incidence, and Refraction, which though by my own Experience I could not imagine to be so erroneous, as to make that Angle...”⁴⁵

These statements, if truth be told, look meagre when compared to the materials he produced as a result of the criticisms directed against his *Principia*. Let us take, for instance, the General Scholium.

In a few words, the contents of this celebrated and important piece of the *Principia* could be summarised as an apology and declaration of Newton’s entire natural philosophy. The first topic is an attack on the Cartesian theory of vortices which is incompatible with Kepler’s laws; the second is the introduction and a defence of the void from the experimental viewpoint according to Boyle’s vacuum; following the postulation of the void, the third topic is the argument from the design which settles the context for including the discourse about God from the standpoint of a voluntaristic theology and the reasons why such discourse certainly belongs to natural philosophy.⁴⁶ The next topic, the most important with respect to his experimental philosophy, asserts the perspective adopted in the study of heavenly and earthy bodies by means of the gravity force: the “explanation” given in the *Principia* is a mathematical one, and as for its nature he declares that he has “not yet assigned a cause to gravity” and instead of offering a cause he describes how this force operates.⁴⁷ The justification for this approach comes directly from his methodological strictures. Indeed, he says:

I have not as yet been able to deduce from phenomena the reason for these properties of gravity, and I do not feign hypotheses. For whatever is not deduced from the phenomena must be called a hypothesis; and hypotheses, whether metaphysical or physical, or based on occult qualities, or mechanical, have no place in experimental philosophy. In this [experimental]⁴⁸ philosophy, propositions are deduced from the phenomena and are made general by induction. The impenetrability, mobility, and impetus of bodies, and the laws of

so to speak, ‘empiricism’ after considering also ‘rationalism’, the mentioned passage continues: “But so long as we are ignorant of the nature of both soule & body we cannot clearly distinguish how far an act of sensation proceeds from the soule & how far from the body &c.” (*Ibid.*). For the theme of occult qualities see Boas, 1952. But a much more nuanced view of this issue is found in Hutchison, 1982; and Henry, 1986.

⁴⁵ Newton, 1672, p. 3077.

⁴⁶ As a matter of fact, in the first published version of the General Scholium (1713), Newton wrote “Philosophiam experimentalem” instead of “philosophiam naturalem” (1726): “Et haec de Deo; de quo utique ex Phaenomenis dissirere, ad Philosophiam experimentalem pertinet. Newton, 1713, p. 483.

⁴⁷ According to Newton, “this force arises from some cause that penetrates as far as the centers of the sun and planets without any diminution of its power to act, and that acts not in proportion to the quantity of the surfaces of the particles on which it acts (as mechanical causes are wont to do) but in proportion to the quantity of solid matter, and whose action is extended everywhere to immense distances, always decreasing as the squares of the distances. Gravity toward the sun is compounded of the gravities toward the individual particles of the sun, and at increasing distances from the sun decreases exactly as the squares of the distances as far out as the orbit of Saturn, as is manifest from the fact that the aphelia of the planets are at rest, and even as far as the farthest aphelia of the comets, provided that those aphelia are at rest.” Newton, 1999, p. 943.

⁴⁸ Cohen and Whitman rendered the original “In hac philosophia propositiones deducuntur...” (Newton, 1972: 764) as “In this *experimental* philosophy, propositions are deduced...” (Emphasis added); Andrew Motte translated it as “In this philosophy particular propositions are infer’d...” Newton, 1729, p. 392.

motion and the law of gravity have been found by this method. And it is enough that gravity really exists and acts according to the laws that we have set forth and is sufficient to explain all the motions of the heavenly bodies and of our sea.⁴⁹

This is perhaps the most succinct description that Newton ever published regarding his experimental methodology, and due to its very succinctness, it has given rise to the interpretation of him as an outright positivist ‘scientist’ and philosopher.⁵⁰ Nevertheless, Newton’s meaning is much more extensive when these declarations are analysed in the light of his letters and unpublished papers. For this reason, the discernment of the precise meaning of these statements, besides placing these words in the context of Newton’s own natural philosophy, and correcting the positivistic interpretation originating out of them, help us to clarify the problem regarding the nature of force and Newton’s commitments in its elucidation.

There is much to say about these statements, but notwithstanding this I will focus the attention in this section on what I consider key concepts such as ‘phenomena’ and ‘hypothesis’. These notions form the basis of Newton’s defence and legitimisation of his use of gravity force in the *Principia*. This being so, a close reading of these concepts will render explicit the implicit signification of his meaning in the passage just quoted.

In the first sentence Newton clarifies that up till then (“yet”) he has not been able to deduce from phenomena the reason (i.e., its nature) for gravity properties, thus indicating that its discovery remains open to investigation in the domain of experimental philosophy, and eventually that reason (nature) would fit into his programmatic research project to square the study of natural events within the framework of forces as he stated in the Preface to the *Principia*.⁵¹ It is clear, therefore, that there is no indication about his renunciation of the causal investigation regarding the properties of gravity, and, on the contrary, what restricts an outright declaration about its nature is the lack of a sound analysis of phenomena which explain its cause. The last topic of the General Scholium precisely adopts this approach when Newton makes a reference to a certain electrical spirit:

A few things could now be added concerning a certain very subtle spirit pervading gross bodies and lying hidden in them; by its force and actions, the particles of bodies attract one another at very small distances and cohere when they become contiguous; and electrical [i.e., electrified] bodies act at greater distances, repelling as well as attracting neighboring corpuscles; and light

⁴⁹ Newton, 1999, p. 943.

⁵⁰ For instance, in his *The Science of Mechanics* (1893), Ernst Mach put Newton on the pedestal of positivistic philosophy on account of these statements in the General Scholium. As a matter of fact, he wrote: “Newton’s reiterated and emphatic protestations that he is not concerned with hypotheses as to the causes of phenomena, but has simply to do with the investigation and transformed statement of *actual facts*,—a direction of thought that is distinctly and tersely uttered in his words ‘hypotheses non fingo,’ ‘I do not frame hypotheses,’—stamps him as a philosopher of the *highest* rank.” Mach, 1919: 193. Emphasis in original. Around three decades later, Keynes starting point in his “Newton, the Man” was precisely this approach to the figure of Newton: “In the eighteenth century and since, Newton came to be thought of as the first and greatest of the modern age of scientists, a rationalist, one who taught us to think on the lines of cold and untinctured reason.” Keynes, 1947, p. 27.

⁵¹ See Newton, 1999, p. 382.

is emitted, reflected, refracted, inflected, and heats bodies; and all sensation is excited, and the limbs of animals move at command of the will, namely, by the vibrations of this spirit being propagated through the solid fibers of the nerves from the external organs of the senses to the brain and from the brain into the muscles. But these things cannot be explained in a few words; furthermore, there is not a sufficient number of experiments to determine and demonstrate accurately the laws governing the actions of this spirit.⁵²

As it will be seen, Newton not only tried to find and understand the cause of gravity, and forces in general, right through the study of electrical phenomena, but also in alchemy and in the etherial speculations of the current mechanical philosophy. Indeed, in the suppressed Conclusion to the first edition for the *Principia* (1687) he expressed his ideas on the possible cause of gravity based upon the attractive and repulsive forces occurring in minute or subsensible bodies, drawn from his alchemical researches:

I have briefly set these matters out, not in order to make a rash assertion that there are attractive and repulsive forces in bodies, but so that I can give an opportunity to imagine further experiments by which it can be ascertained more certainly whether they exist or not.⁵³ For if it shall be settled that they are true [forces] it will remain for us to investigate their causes and properties diligently, as being the true principles from which, according to geometrical reasoning, all the more secret motions of the least particles are no less brought into being than are the motions of greater bodies which as we saw in the foregoing [books] derived from the laws of gravity.⁵⁴

Further experimental research, then, leaves open the investigation about the causality of force; but in order to legitimate its results it is required to subject the investigation itself to mathematical treatment ('geometrical reasoning') of phenomena. The *Principia* shows the mathematical treatment of gravity force, considered as a phenomenon. As for the definite implication of this word, Newton was not very explicit in this work about the meaning of the term 'phenomenon', but from the context it is reasonable to understand it as a fact, event or occurrence, the elucidation of which remains to be discovered by means of further experiments.⁵⁵

⁵² Newton, 1999: 943-944. In one of the many drafts related to his anonymous "Recensio Libri" of the *Commercium Epistolicum*, the report of the Royal Society on the dispute over the invention of calculus (CUL Add. Ms 3968 f. 586), Newton declared the same idea of the General Scholium, namely, the lack of "sufficient number of experiments to determine and demonstrate accurately the laws governing the actions of this spirit", in the following terms: "He has told his friends that there are sufficient Phaenomena to ground an inquiry upon but not yet sufficient to determin [sic] the laws of attraction." CUL Add. Ms 3968 f. 586, as quoted in Cohen, 1999: 282) On Newton's treatment of electrical phenomena see Hall and Hall, 1959; Howe, 1982; Koyré and Cohen, 1960; Cohen, 1999: 280-282.

⁵³ This same restriction was pointed out in the Advertisement II to his *Opticks* (1717) in saying that he was "not yet satisfied about [the cause of gravity] for want of experiments."

⁵⁴ Newton, 1962: 340-341.

⁵⁵ Our present day understanding of this word strongly preserves this sense. Thus, for instance, the *Oxford English Dictionary* defines 'phenomenon' as "A thing which appears, or which is perceived or observed; a particular (kind of)

In the second edition of the *Principia* (1713) the beginning of Book 3 was reconfigured and what formerly was a set of ‘Hypotheses’ became several sets of (1) Rules for Natural Philosophy, (2) Phenomena,⁵⁶ and (3) Hypothesis.⁵⁷ This new structure is closely related to Newton’s programme for clarifying and strengthening the central concepts of his natural philosophy, as well as for dissipating the Continental criticisms to his work which considered the gravity force an unsound natural-philosophical hypothesis viewed from their mechanism. After the second edition Newton still kept working on the way that his notions and concepts should be understood, and as Koyré and Cohen convincingly have shown, Newton was actively, though indirectly, engaged during the interchange of letters between his spokesman Clarke and his sharp-witted critic Leibniz.⁵⁸ Additionally, McGuire has also shown how Newton was reshaping the structure of Book 3⁵⁹ in order to convert the unconvinced Continental readers.

In Books 1 and 2 of the first edition (1687) Newton illustrated some of the “topics that are general and that seem to be the most fundamental for [natural] philosophy” in various scholia, topics such as “the density and resistance of bodies, spaces void of bodies, and the motion of light and sounds”,⁶⁰ and around 1716 his intention was to be even more specific about them and also about those which aroused some misunderstandings regarding his work. Consequently, he composed a draft series of ‘definitions’⁶¹ to be implemented in a future edition of the *Principia* with the purpose of making precise the meaning of central concepts for Book 3 such as ‘body’, ‘vacuum’, ‘hypothesis’, ‘rule’ and ‘phenomenon’. Albeit the intrinsic importance to the exactness of the conceptual structure of the *Principia*, these specifications never reached the press.

The first Definition is about the understanding of “phenomena”. As it is evident from the common usage, these are grasped by human faculties as senses, but in Newton’s mind the gist of this word is much wider. Thus, he clarifies firstly that:

Definition I

Phenomena I call whatever things can be perceived, either things external which become known by the five senses, or things internal which we contemplate in our minds by thinking. As fire is hot and water is wet, and gold is heavy, and sun is light, I am and I think.⁶² All these

fact, occurrence, or change as perceived through the senses or known intellectually; esp. a fact or occurrence, the cause or explanation of which is in question.”

⁵⁶ See also Newton, 1962: 378-385.

⁵⁷ For a synoptic account of Newton’s revisions of his *Principia* see Guicciardini, 2005: 78-82, especially pp. 80-82. The reader interested in a complete ‘history’ about the origins and development of the *Principia* through its three editions (1687, 1713, and 1726) should consult Cohen, 1971. See also Westfall, 1980: 402-468.

⁵⁸ See, Koyré and Cohen, 1962; Shapin, 1981; Vailati, 1997; Bertoloni Meli, 2002.

⁵⁹ See, McGuire, 1966.

⁶⁰ Newton, 1999: 793.

⁶¹ See McGuire 1966, 1995.

⁶² Note how Newton’s empiricism extends even to the Cartesian *cogito* argument. In another Draft related to the *Opticks* Newton made explicit this argument: “Even that celebrated Proposition *Ego cogito ergo sum* is known to us by experience. We know that we think by an inward sensation of our thoughts. And therefrom from that Proposition we cannot conclude that anything more is true than what we deduce from experience.” (Newton, ULC MS. Add. 3970 f. 621^v. As quoted in Rogers, 1979: 204. For an analysis of Newton’s empiricism and its relationship to Locke’s epistemology see Rogers, 1979 and 1982.

are sensible things and can be called phenomena in a wide sense; but those things are *properly called* phenomena which can be seen, but I understand the word in a wider sense.⁶³

From the perspective of ‘a wider sense’ of phenomena, Definition II develops the understanding of the word ‘body’ against the background of Definition I, and to this end the role of sensory experience informs us about the existence of bodies as well as it categorises them according to their sensible nature and manifest effects. This empirical approach articulates Newton’s phenomenalist analysis of nature. From this definition we understand that (1):

Definition II

Body I call everything which can be moved and touched, in which there is resistance⁶⁴ to tangible things, and its resistance, if it is great enough, can be perceived.

It is indeed in this sense that the common people always accept the word body. And of this sort are metals, stones, sand, clay, mud, earth, salts, wood, bones, flesh, water, oil, milk, blood, air, wind, smoke, exhalations, flames, and whatever can be included under the four elements or flow from them by exhalation and return to them by means of condensation. I add the heavenly bodies.⁶⁵

But more importantly, (2) this definition also applies to celestial bodies in as much as:

These emit and reflect light and are numbered among phenomena, and are weighed down by their parts pressing heavily upon them, and assume a round shape, and in their motions observe the laws of bodies.⁶⁶

Following the enumeration of terrestrial and celestial bodies, the next focus of attention is directed on (3) the characterisation of the word ‘spirit’ as a phenomenon. This is important because by this way of classifying natural events at microscopic scale, Newton promotes and legitimates the study of alchemy and electricity, for example, in the ambit of natural philosophy; additionally, it spells an occultist interpretation of spirits out by making manifest (by phenomena⁶⁷) their actions:

⁶³ Newton, 1716c[b]: 422^v.

⁶⁴ That is to say ‘vacuum’. Definition III reads: “Vacuum I call every place in which bodies are able to move without resistance. It is in this sense that the common people understand the significance of the word. But it follows from the first Definition *that vacuum is that which is not a tangible thing and does not impede the motion of bodies*. For just as geometers define a line that has length without breadth, so that their propositions concerning lines of this sort are only understood, and in mechanics, however, and other sciences the line having breadth has a place; thus body and vacuum are here defined so that these words may be understood in the sense defined in what follows. About other sorts of bodies and other sorts of void let authors in other sciences dispute.” Newton, 1716c [b]: 422^v.

⁶⁵ Newton, 1716c[a]: 422^r.

⁶⁶ *Ibid.*

⁶⁷ In the Query 31 of the *Opticks*, active principles such as gravity, and those responsible for the fermentation, and the cohesion of bodies are stated as manifest qualities, in opposition to the occult ones, but in addition to this active principles there could be enlisted those of the generation, vegetation, nutrition, and corruption of living bodies, attractive and repulsive forces. In this Query he asserts: “These principles I consider, not as occult qualities, supposed to

Vapours and exhalations on account of their rarity lose almost all perceptible resistance and in the common acceptance often lose even the name of bodies and are called spirits. And yet they can be called bodies in so far as they are effluvia of bodies and *have a force of resistance proportional to their density*.⁶⁸

The remaining part of Definition II is illustrative in so far as in it (4) Newton contrasts the phenomenal sensible world of those entities with those which are not phenomena as such, these entities do not form part of enquiries in experimental philosophy and their analysis is left to further levels of natural philosophy:

Mathematical solids are not *perceived* do not move by touching *nor cause a resistance*, nor are they usually called bodies. The quintessence is different from the four elements, and is subject to none of the senses nor is it numbered among phenomena. The prime matter⁶⁹ which is neither a thing, nor possessed of quality, nor a thing which can be measured, is not a phenomenon. The solid orbs in which the planets inhere are not phenomena. The subtle matter in which the *planets* float, and *in which* bodies move without resistance is not a phenomenon. And what are not phenomena, and subject to none of the senses, have no place in experimental philosophy.⁷⁰

Subsequently, (5) Newton proceeds to indicate under which conditions it is suitable to deal with those so to speak non-phenomenal entities, namely, within the domain of hypothetical philosophy or metaphysics, thus making a clear stratification of levels of enquiry—and eventually causality—in natural philosophy where the beginning are unifications or generalisations by virtue of induction:⁷¹

result from the specific forms of things, but as general laws of nature, by which the things themselves are formed; their truth appearing to us by phenomena, though their causes be not yet discovered. For these are manifest qualities, and their causes only are occult.” Newton 1717: 376-377.

⁶⁸ Newton, 1716c[a]: 422’.

⁶⁹ In his the *Questiones quaedam Philosophiae*, the juvenile notebook of Newton’s natural philosophy, we find his rejection of considering the prime matter in metaphysical terms (mathematical points, or a simple entity before division indistinct) and his option for the atomism: “‘*Off the first mater*’ Whither it be mathematicall points: or Mathematicall points & parts: or a simple entity before division indistinct: or individualls i.e. Attomes. 1 Not of mathematicall points since wt wants dimentions cannot constitute a body in their conjunction because they will sinke into the same point. An infinite number of mathematicall points sink into one being added together & that being still a mathematicall point is indivisible but a body is divisible. Not of parts & Math: points; for such a point is either something or nothing. if something tis a part & so added betweene 2 parts will make a line of 3 parts. if nothing, then added betwixt two parts there is still nothing betwixt the 2 parts & consequently the line consists of nothing still but 2 parts. & Not of simple entity before division indistinct. for this must be an union of the parts into which a body is divisible since those parts may againe bee united & become one body as they were before at the creation. Now the nature of union (being but a modall ens) is to depend on its pts (which are absolute entities) therefore it cannot be the terme of creation, or first matter for tis a contradiction to say the first matter depends on some other subject since that implys some former matter on which it must depende (...) ‘*Of Attomes*’. It remains therefore that the first matter must be attoms.” Newton, 1664: 1-3.

⁷⁰ Newton, 1716c[a]: 422’.

⁷¹ See Chapter 2.

Inductive argument taken from experiments and the observations of sensible things on which experimental philosophy is based cannot be applied except by means of hypotheses to hypothetical or metaphysical entities. Therefore, the things which are said in this book about bodies through the power of induction bear no reference to entities of this sort. Here we are concerned only with sensible things and their parts, for it is in these things alone that the inductive argument has its place.⁷²

In the last part of this Definition II, (6) a distinction between the research areas regarding those 'things' that do not belong to the experimental philosophy is made: they could be investigated along the lines of metaphysics—the alternative adopted by Newton—and hypothetical philosophy, which is the one he rejects. This passage, furthermore, besides making explicit that the starting point of natural philosophy is the experimental stage with its sensible objects, do not stop there and rounds off with the generalizations through induction. These inductions, as we are told in the Rule 4 of the *Principia*, are to be considered “either exactly or very nearly true”⁷³, something that (a) leave the phenomenistic research open to new observations and experimentations; (b) put on firm grounds the empirical research, and (c) avoid the interference of hypothetical claims:

The other things which cannot be perceived, but yet are hypothetically termed bodies by some people, these things are more properly treated of in metaphysics and hypothetical philosophy. *We must begin from phenomena* (The following phrase is written above the last.) *Philosophy begins with phenomena*. Experimental philosophy consists in treating of such things.

But more importantly, Newton's statements in this draft point towards the succeeding steps taken in natural philosophy:

One must pass from *experimental* philosophy to the efficient and final causes of *things* and *from all these to the nature of imperceptible things and finally* to hypothetical philosophy.⁷⁴

This admission of the hypothetical philosophy as a phase, or as a final stage in natural philosophy looks indeed awkward coming from Newton's pen, but if we take into consideration that here we are dealing with a draft, we will find corrected this avowal in his printed assertions. In fact, the Query 28 in the *Opticks* provide us with a more corrected version of his meaning, there Newton says that “the main business of natural philosophy is to argue from phenomena without feigning hypotheses,

⁷² Newton, 1716c[a]: 422'.

⁷³ See Newton, 1999: 796.

⁷⁴ Newton, 1716c[a]: 422'. This Definition II ends with the differentiation between the comprehensions of matter in the former two Books and this new one: “At the beginning of the first book I have defined the quantity of matter so that it may be treated in mathematical terms; here I have defined body composed of such matter in order that it may be treated in physical terms. *Ibid.*”

and to deduce causes from effects, till we come to the very first cause, which certainly is not mechanical.”⁷⁵ Against this background we are now in a better position to understand Newton’s attitude towards hypothesis.

2.3. Hypotheses in Newton’s Natural Philosophy

It is no exaggeration to describe Newton’s attitude towards hypotheses as an outright aversion which emerged from the very beginning of his career, an aversion that became even more acute and sophisticated through the years.

There are three main perspectives from which hypotheses in Newton’s thought can be analysed. The first one could be called epistemological in so far as it is related to Newton’s search for the highest degree of certainty in natural philosophy;⁷⁶ the second one could be labelled methodological in so far as it restricts the place for applying them in experimental philosophy; the third one, which could be called philosophical, is closely related to the second inasmuch as hypotheses are rejected when, on the one hand, they are said to provide causal explanations (or they are aimed at that end) without any empirical basis, and on the other hand, when they are deleterious to the proper natural philosophy.

As for the epistemological perspective, from the very beginning of his career Newton was keenly interested in the firmness of knowledge. For this reason, he was much more concerned with the security found in the solid mathematical reasoning than with the provisional and conjectural character of hypotheses at the moment of constructing or developing an argumentation aimed at a theory, or doctrine as he also called it. And so in opposition to the habitual practice of the Royal Society which encouraged and promoted the investigations and which encouraged the virtuosi to present the experimental results of their investigations as hypotheses to be overtly discussed in their meetings,⁷⁷ the standpoint adopted by Newton was at odds with these values and on the contrary he was more interested in the truth itself than in disputes and debates, for this reason the chief and foundational element is the certainty achieved by means of mathematical reasoning which expresses the sound analysis of phenomena. As a matter of fact, in a passage omitted in the published version of his *New Theory about Light and Colors* he affirmed that what he “shall tell concerning [colours] is not an Hypothesis but most rigid consequence, not conjectured by barely inferring ‘tis thus because not otherwise or because it satisfies all phaenomena (the Philosophers universall Topick,) but evinced by ye mediation of experiments concluding directly & wthout any suspicion of doubt”⁷⁸ thus affirming his distance from conjectures, i.e., hypotheses, and declaring the superiority of a reliable corpus of notions articulated “after the mode of the Mathematicians.”⁷⁹

⁷⁵ Newton, 1717: 344.

⁷⁶ On this topic see Shapiro, 1993: 12-40.

⁷⁷ On the different approaches to the study of nature between mathematicians and naturalists in the Royal Society, see Feingold, 2001.

⁷⁸ Newton, 1959-1977, vol. I: 96-97.

⁷⁹ *Ibid.* 188.

This is precisely the reason why he considered without ‘any suspicion of doubt’ that his theory about the composition of white light, in keeping with the mathematical reasoning, was a theory in itself.

In a letter related to his *New Theory* he emphasised again the validity and superiority of his theory by virtue of the fact that “the *Science of Colours was Mathematical and as certain as any other part of Optiques*.” Now, owing to the close relationship between physical principles and mathematical demonstrations, “the absolute certainty of a Science cannot exceed the certainty of its Principles”, and so, “the evidence by which [Newton] asserted the Propositions of colours [has been derived] from *Experiments*, and so but *Physical*” it should be acknowledged that “the propositions themselves can be esteemed no more than *Physical Principles* of a Science.”⁸⁰ In sum, this perspective highlights the articulation of phenomena experimentally with their mathematical treatment. This attitude in Newton’s thought perhaps forms part of the influence that Isaac Barrow exerted over him.⁸¹ In the case of the optics, it was considered in the Aristotelian tradition as part of mixed mathematics and in consequence susceptible of being as rigorous as mathematics itself when treated *more geometrico*.

In contradistinction to the copious ways of plausible and provisional explanations offered by hypotheses, the ideal of highest certainty in a mathematised natural philosophy is straightforwardly stated by Newton in one of his *Optical Lectures*, in saying: “with the help of philosophical geometers and geometrical philosophers, instead of the conjectures and probabilities that are being blazoned about everywhere, we shall finally achieve a science of nature supported by the highest evidence.”⁸²

On the other side, as is well known, the subsequent correspondence after the publication of the *New Theory* was focused on the explanatory device underlying the mathematical presentation of results, and more often than not it was called a hypothesis’ by his critics, notwithstanding Newton’s refusal to consider it as such. This brings us to the methodological perspective from which the word hypothesis could be interpreted.

The major reason that created perplexity among the readers of the *New Theory* in 1672, as well as those of the *Principia* in 1687, was Newton’s elusiveness to make public his own considerations with respect to the mechanism responsible for the workings of nature.

As for the *New Theory*, Newton’s defence of his theory was based upon his methodology which is nothing other than the mathematical description of natural phenomena without supposing or guessing possible and plausible explanatory mechanisms underlying this analysis; in this case hypotheses are excluded from the analysis of natural phenomena in so far as they do not furnish explanatory power to the theory. Newton adopted this perspective in one of his responses to the objections to his theory by Robert Hooke in saying: “But whatever be the advantages or

⁸⁰ *Ibid.* 187. Emphasis in original.

⁸¹ See, for example, Malet, 1997.

⁸² Newton *Optical Lectures* as quoted in Shapiro, 1993: 25.

disadvantages of [Hooke's] *Hypothesis*, I hope I may be excused from taking it up, since I do not think it needful to explicate my Doctrine by any *Hypothesis* at all."⁸³

In another case hypotheses are viewed as subsidiary and subordinated to the theory and not fundamental to it, and since a phenomenon (e.g., colours) could be explained through a multiplicity of hypotheses without affecting the theory itself, these become dispensable and the theory could proceed without the need of them. In the same mentioned letter, Newton asserted that "the *Properties*, which I declar'd of *Light*, were in some measure capable of being explicated not only by that [Hooke's], but by many other *Mechanical Hypotheses*. And therefore I chose to decline them all, and to speak of *Light* in *general* terms, considering it abstractly."⁸⁴

In a third sense, if a hypothesis is "a very plausible *consequence* of the Doctrine, and not a fundamental *Supposition*",⁸⁵ it must be consistent with the known data, albeit being neither verified nor shown to be false. The process of verification or falsification is worked out through the experimental phase, in that case "'tis better to put the Event on further Circumstances of the *Experiment*, than to acquiesce in the possibility of any *Hypothetical* Explication."⁸⁶ Here hypotheses are not called properly in that mode but they are named 'conjectures' or much better, as we know, 'queries' that provide new experimental paths in order to test, improve or modify the theory in question.⁸⁷ This is precisely the line adopted by Newton near the end of the *New Theory* in writing: "I see the discourse it self will lead to divers Experiments sufficient for its examination."⁸⁸ And in a further paper he sent to the Royal Society, and published in *The Philosophical Transactions* under the title "A serie's of Queries..." concerning the evaluation of his *New Theory*:

To determine by Experiments these and such like *Quaere's* which involve the propounded Theory, seems the most proper and direct way to a conclusion. And therefore, I could wish all objections were suspended, taken from *Hypotheses* or any other heads than these two; Of shewing the insufficiency of Experiments to determine these *Quaere's* or prove any other parts of my Theory, by assigning the flaws and defects in my conclusions drawn from them; Or of producing other Experiments which directly contradict me, if any such may seem to occur. For if the Experiments, which I urge, be defective, it cannot be difficult to show the defects; but if valid, then by proving the Theory they must render all Objections invalid.⁸⁹

⁸³ Newton, 1958: 123. Emphasis in original.

⁸⁴ *Ibid.*, 118-119.

⁸⁵ *Ibid.*

⁸⁶ *Ibid.* 129.

⁸⁷ In the Query 31 of the *Opticks* this argument becomes more sophisticated. The Newton writes: "it is the best way of arguing which the nature of things admits of, and may be looked on as so much the stronger, by how much the induction is more general. And if no exception occur from phenomena, the conclusion may be pronounced generally. But if at any time afterwards any exception shall occur from experiments, it may then begin to be pronounced with such exceptions as occur." Newton, 1717: 404.

⁸⁸ Newton, 1958: 57.

⁸⁹ *Ibid.*, 94.

Finally, in another letter, this time addressed to Father Ignace-Gaston Pardies, Newton expressed in general terms the above senses of hypotheses,⁹⁰ but more importantly in the last paragraph he observed that, although by the word hypothesis customarily people understand “whatever is explained in philosophy”, Newton avoided the use of such a word “to prevent the prevalence of the term, which might be *prejudicial to true philosophy*.”⁹¹

If we consider Newton’s pronouncements it is clear the change he has imposed upon the common usage of the word “hypothesis” understood as a supposition taken for granted to account for the nature of phenomena; in the *Lexicon Technicum* John Harris characterised the meaning of the word hypothesis along these lines. In this sense, hypotheses were posited with the purpose of (1) drawing “conclusions from [them], in order to the proof of a point in question”, a sense which is akin to the mathematical jargon, and in natural philosophy they played the role of (2) “a supposition supposed as granted, that from thence an intelligible and plausible account of the causes may be given.”⁹² Now because of this semantic transformation we can understand the reason why Newton’s readers found themselves perplexed by the lack of a positive and direct statement about the nature of light when he wrote in his *New Theory* of his intention *not* “to determine more absolutely, what Light is, after what manner refracted, and by what modes or actions it produceth in our minds the Phantasms of colours” because that “is not so easy” and to do so would be to “mingle conjectures with certainties”⁹³ which would ‘be prejudicial to *true philosophy*.’

The question that now arises is how we should understand the claim that hypotheses, understood as ‘conjectures’, could be harmful to philosophy, and even more to *true philosophy*. This could be seen as a vexed question since we know that throughout his career Newton promulgated a multitude of hypotheses aimed at explicating the workings of nature, and that could impinge directly upon the true philosophy he was trying to propound without introducing any deleterious element of speculation. In order to deal with this supposed ambivalence towards hypothesis we need to make clear, first, in what sense hypotheses are allowed and in what sense they are banned, and secondly what Newton meant by ‘true philosophy.’ Having analysed both the methodological and epistemological perspectives, the philosophical approach to Newton’s understanding of hypothesis permits us to grasp coherently his meaning.

Central to this discernment of Newton’s admission and rejection of hypothesis is the statement in the General Scholium where he says “whatever is not deduced from the phenomena must be called a hypothesis,”⁹⁴ which highlights the central role of experience in the investigation

⁹⁰ “In answer to this, it is to be observed that the doctrine which I explained concerning refraction and colours, consists only in certain properties of light, without regarding any hypotheses, by which those properties might be explained. For the best and safest method of philosophizing seems to be, first to inquire diligently into the properties of things, and establishing those properties by experiments and then to proceed more slowly to hypotheses for the explanation of them. For hypotheses should be subservient only in explaining the properties of things, but not assumed in determining them; unless so far as they may furnish experiments. For if the possibility of hypotheses is to be the test of the truth of things, I see not how certainty can be obtained in any science; since numerous hypotheses may always be devised, which shall seem to overcome new difficulties.” *Ibid.* 106.

⁹¹ *Ibid.*, 109. Emphasis added.

⁹² Harris, 1704, see entry “Hypothesis”.

⁹³ *Ibid.*, 57.

⁹⁴ Newton, 1999: 943.

of the workings of nature *and* their mathematical treatment. From this regulative principle phenomena come first and then their mathematisation. Once a phenomenon has been subjected to such a procedure it can be sanctioned as a proposition; now, those propositions which have not been taken from phenomena are called hypotheses. From this point of view, it can be distinguished when hypotheses are both admitted and rejected.

On the one side, if hypotheses have not been yet deduced from phenomena that does not mean they are to be rejected, that only means, as in the case of the electric and elastic spirit mentioned in the last paragraph of the General Scholium, for example, where Newton asserts that “there is not a sufficient number of experiments to determine and demonstrate accurately the laws governing the actions of this spirit”⁹⁵ in this case phenomena under enquiry require further experimental research in order to be sanctioned, once their mathematical laws have been found. So therefore, hypotheses from this perspective are admissible steps towards the explanation of phenomena, and eventually they could have a place within the domain of propositions.

On the other side, when hypotheses are not deducible from phenomena that means that those hypotheses have no reference to phenomena or they are incompatible with them; in this case they are rejected and fall outside the domain of experimental philosophy. The Scholium to Proposition 53 in the Book 2 of the *Principia* adopts this stance when we are told that “the hypothesis of vortices can in no way be reconciled with astronomical phenomena and serves less to clarify the celestial motions than to obscure them.”⁹⁶ In a letter to the editor of the *Principia* (1713), Roger Cotes, Newton pointed out his meaning of hypotheses in distinguishing (1) the epistemological status they have in natural philosophy in comparison to mathematics; (2) how propositions in natural philosophy are deduced, and (3) what he meant by his rejection of hypotheses:

In Geometry the word Hypothesis is not taken in so large a sense as to include the Axiomes & Postulates, so in Experimental Philosophy it is not to be taken in so large a sense as to include the first Principles or Axiomes w^{ch} I call the laws of motion. These Principles are deduced from Phenomena and made general by Induction: w^{ch} is the highest evidence that a Proposition can have in this philosophy. And the word Hypothesis is here used by me to signify only such a Proposition as is not a Phenomenon nor deduced from any Phenomena but assumed or supposed wth out any experimental proof.

And as for banned hypotheses, as those of his Continental critics, he contrasted his experimental philosophy to the hypothetical one:

Experimental Philosophy reduces Phaenomena to general Rules & looks upon the Rules to be general when they hold generally in Phaenomena.... Hypothetical Philosophy consists in imaginary explications of things & imaginary arguments for or against such explications, or

⁹⁵ *Ibid.*, 944.

⁹⁶ *Ibid.*, 790.

against the arguments of Experimental Philosophers founded upon Induction. The first sort of Philosophy is followed by me, the latter too much by Cartes, Leibnitz & some others.⁹⁷

It is feasible now to understand Newton's rejection of hypotheses in so far as they are asserted to be explanatory devices or explicatory entities of natural phenomena without any empirical basis and/or without any reference to phenomena in the investigation of their properties. In a few words, therefore, Newton is attacking the so-called method of hypothesis in which it is made use of the abovementioned contrivances in order to determinate the phenomena themselves. This was one of the main arguments he put forward against this method in the wake of his *New Theory*:

And if anyone offers conjectures about the truth of things from the mere possibility of hypothesis, I do not see by what stipulation anything certain can be determined in any science; since one or another set of hypotheses may always be devised which will to supply new difficulties. Hence, I judged that one should abstain from contemplating hypotheses, as from improper argumentation.⁹⁸

Newton's new approach to the term hypothesis and its place within the framework of his experimental philosophy, as well as his rejection of the method of hypothesis, shows a new way to approach the study of nature. First, phenomena are the starting point to the study of nature and the facts obtained from their study. Secondly, the main expository tool is that of mathematics in so far as it provides the argumentative rigour to the study of phenomena by subjecting them to the desideratum of the establishment of laws. Thirdly, by this way of philosophising, speculative devices aimed at the explanation of phenomena are rejected when they are (1) plausible explanatory mechanisms of phenomena, (2) subordinate to the mathematical theory of analysed phenomena, and (3) when hypotheses are inconsistent with data from phenomena.

As for the series of hypotheses he developed in order to explain certain phenomena such as the nature of light and the diverse versions of ether in order to understand the nature of repulsive and attractive force, as well as to explain the planetary motions and the cause of gravity itself, along the lines of mechanical philosophy *à la* Descartes, such as "An Hypothesis explaining the Properties of Light", Newton's letter to Boyle, February 28, 1679, "Some Thoughts about the Nature of Acids", "Of Natures obvious laws & processes in vegetation", the "Conclusion" to the *Principia* and the Queries in the *Opticks*,⁹⁹ Newton did not developed them as 'imaginary explications of things &

⁹⁷ Newton, 1959-1977, vol. V: 396-397, 399. And in his "An Account of the Book entitled *Commercium Epistolicum*" the anonymous review Newton wrote on the trial of the Royal Society on the invention of calculus he expressed the same ideas in the following terms: "The Philosophy which Mr. *Newton* in his *Principles* and *Optiques* has pursued is Experimental; and it is not the Business of Experimental Philosophy to teach the Causes of things any further than they can be proved by Experiments. We are not to fill this Philosophy with Opinions which cannot be proved by Phaenomena. In this Philosophy Hypotheses have no place, unless as Conjectures or Questions proposed to be examined by Experiments." Newton, 1714/5: 223.

⁹⁸ Newton, 1959-1977, vol. I: 169.

⁹⁹ See Newton, 1672c, 1675, 1679, 1692, 1704, 1959-1977, Vol. 2: 288-295; 1962: 320-347.

imaginary arguments', but along the lines of experimental philosophy, thus furnishing new paths of further experimental and mathematical calculations.¹⁰⁰

On these grounds it is also possible to get a glimpse of the prejudicial implications of hypotheses, not only to 'experimental' philosophy, but to the 'true natural philosophy' as he affirmed to Pardies.

2.4. The true Natural Philosophy before its corruption

From the experimental viewpoint Newton considered the Cartesian hypothesis of planetary vortices not only bogus empirically but also mathematically inconsistent; two weighty reasons to reject it. But more importantly, from the natural philosophical viewpoint, the consequences of hypotheses are even more dangerous since they lead to a wrong conception of God and religion, and therefore to a wrong natural philosophy.

In Newton's view, Descartes and the Cartesians represented a wrong natural philosophy which led to atheism; and in the case of Descartes, for example, Newton subjected his conception of body, motion and space to a penetrating criticism in his *De gravitatione*. In this unfinished treatise he pointed out the deleterious consequences for natural theology involved in Descartes' notion of extension, in asserting: "do we not manifestly offer a path to Atheism, both because extension is not created but has existed eternally, and because we have an absolute idea of it without any relationship to God [?]"¹⁰¹ Two decades after Newton's death Colin Maclaurin, in his *An Account of Isaac Newton's Philosophical Discoveries* (1748), expressed the same point regarding the menaces implied in an incorrect approach to nature, denouncing the implications of untrue philosophies. According to Maclaurin, "False schemes of natural philosophy may lead to atheism, or suggest opinions, concerning the Deity and the Universe, of most dangerous consequence to mankind."¹⁰²

False philosophies based upon hypothetical reasonings on the book of nature divert mankind towards misconceptions both of God's works and his Word, and the way to correct such a state of affairs was to work out a purification both of natural philosophy and religion, since natural philosophy "is subservient to purposes of a higher kind, and is chiefly valued as it lays a sure foundation for natural religion and moral philosophy; by leading us, in a satisfactory manner to the knowledge of the Author and Governor of the universe."¹⁰³ So when Newton wrote that hypotheses 'might be prejudicial to true philosophy' he was not only defending a sound natural philosophy from the experimental standpoint, but also he was expressing the danger of hypotheses to natural theology as well.

As in the case of Newton's experimental philosophy, the study of nature must be based on phenomena in order to construct a sound interpretation of it, and in the same way, the proper

¹⁰⁰ See Raftopoulos, 1999; Achinstein, 1990; McMullin, 1978, 2001; Hall, 1999.

¹⁰¹ Newton, 1668: 142-3.

¹⁰² Maclaurin, 1748: 4.

¹⁰³ *Ibid.*, 3. The tenor this statement is closely related to the final words of Newton's *Opticks* and very probably is inspired by them. Notwithstanding Maclaurin had in mind the atheistic interpretation of Lucretius's doctrine of atomism, his argument also had in mind Berkeley's criticisms in *The Analyst* (1734).

understanding of the ancient records contained in the Bible should proceed in a correct way in order to accomplish the true interpretation. Writing about the importance of understanding the Bible correctly in the “Untitled treatise on Revelation”, we find a symmetrical assertion about how an inappropriate elucidation of the book of the Scriptures turns away humankind from the benefits of the Creator, and eventually from the duties towards Him: “For to frame fals interpretations is to prejudice men & divert them from the right understanding of this book And this is a corruption equipollent to the adding or taking from it, since it equally deprives men of the use & benefit thereof.”¹⁰⁴

Such deprivations were a clear symptom of corruption in the proper understanding of Nature and her Author. Robert Markley has observed, “the political, moral, ecological, and economic corruption of their own times encourages writers in the 1600s to read history as an ongoing fall from a golden age of prosperity and virtue and, consequently, to see their own task as the recovery of universal patterns of meaning in an otherwise meaningless world.”¹⁰⁵ Given that corruption was manifest in such multifarious aspects—but most importantly for our analysis in those of natural philosophy and religion—one outcome of that condition was the need to discern the origins and precise nature of that progression of decay in the historical records themselves. To this end, the study of the Bible was one of the central concerns since it was considered the most reliable source of historical records. As analysed by Peter Harrison in *The Bible, Protestantism, and the rise of natural science*, the Bible played a central role in several perspectives of analysis in order to understand the historical process of humankind in moral, political and natural philosophical matters.¹⁰⁶ In this last aspect—additionally to the conviction of the historicity contained in the Bible—natural philosophy, through a process of exegetical accommodation, was intended to harmonise with the Bible, since in the Bible “the scientific information is clothed in metaphors so as to remain understandable to the masses.”¹⁰⁷ This idea was shared by Henry More, Robert Boyle, Richard Bentley and Newton himself, as we shall see.

The importance of studying the Bible in the seventeenth-and eighteenth-centuries consists in the fact that it was taken for granted that it contained truths that transcend the boundaries of space and time in moral teachings, it also provided information about the constitution of the original religions, and through its metaphoric language it expressed how the total frame of nature was related to the ancient rites of worship. It was natural, in consequence, that the interest in arts and sciences, as well as in ancient philosophy, chronology, geography and history was focused on this book.

The works of Hugo Grotius, Gerard Vossius, Joseph Mede, Edward Stillingfleet and John Spencer, among others, were aimed at demonstrating how the ancient myths are related to Christian religion, thus discerning its original condition. Newton, needless to say, formed part of this cultural setting that paid tribute to the ancient knowledge and was actively involved in it. In fact,

¹⁰⁴ Newton, 1670-1680c: 8’.

¹⁰⁵ Markley, 1999: 123.

¹⁰⁶ Harrison, 1998: 121-160.

¹⁰⁷ Funkenstein, 1986: 215. On the exegetical principle of accommodation, see *ibid.*: 213-271, and Harrison, 1998: 129-138.

he not only read Vossius, Spencer, and Mede, but also ancient scholars such as Josephus, Philo and Maimonides.¹⁰⁸ These readings constitute a theoretical unity in which the harmony between natural theology and natural philosophy which reveals the Divine Providence could be perceived.

The ancient possessors of this twofold knowledge, both Divine and natural, safeguarded that *prisca sapientia* concealing it and transmitted their learning by means of figures and symbolical language. From this perspective the paramount importance conferred upon the proper understanding of that symbolic system becomes explainable. In effect, the lack of an adequate hermeneutics was a source for drifting apart from the proper understanding of this pure wisdom, towards idolatry and false philosophies. The notion of purification and the belief in corruption implied, consequently, the pivotal idea about the true wisdom lying in the past.

Edward Stillingfleet, a critic of the idolatry in the Catholic Church, as was Newton, and fountain of inspiration for Newton in composing his own *Irenicum*,¹⁰⁹ expressed the common idea of corruption and purification in his *Origines sacrae: Or, a rational account of the grounds of natural and reveal'd religion* through the study of history and Biblical hermeneutics. He emphasised that

we must of necessity, for the clearing the truth from its corruption, have recourse to ancient History, to see if thereby we can find out where the Original tradition was best preserved, by what means it came to be corrupted, and whereby we may distinguish those corruptions from the Truths to which they are annexed.

Stillingfleet's approach to the history is articulated with the Bible as the main source of information regarding the original condition of knowledge, and based upon his careful reading it would be possible

To demonstrate that there was a certain original and general tradition preserved in the World concerning the eldest Ages of the World; that this tradition was gradually corrupted among Heathens; that notwithstanding this corruption there were sufficient remainders of it to evidence its true original; that the full account of this tradition is alone preserved in those Books we call *Scriptures*: That where any other History seems to cross the report contained in them, we have sufficient ground to question their credibility; and that there is sufficient evidence to clear the undoubted certainty in that History which is contained in the sacred Records of the Scripture.¹¹⁰

Of the same kind of the *Origines sacrae* we also find leading figures in Newton's time showing an outright interest in the past such as Francis Bacon, Isaac Barrow, Samuel Clarke, Thomas Burnet and Robert Boyle. Thus, for example Bacon wrote:

¹⁰⁸ See Force, 1999b; Goldish, 1998; Haycock, 2004; Westfall, 1980: 344-356.

¹⁰⁹ Goldish, 1998: 114.

¹¹⁰ Stillingfleet, 1709: 9.

The Antiquities of the first Age (except those we find in Sacred Writ) were buried in Oblivion and Silence: Silence was succeeded by Poetical Fables; and fables again were followed by the Records we now enjoy. So that the Mysteries and Secrets of Antiquity were distinguished and separated from the Records and Evidences of succeeding Times by the Veil of Fiction, which interposed it self, and came between those things which perished, and those which are extant.(...) in the first Ages (when many humane Inventions and Con[c]lusions which are now common, and vulgar, were new, and not generally known), all things were Full of Fables, Enigma's, Parables, and Similies of all sorts: By which they sought to teach, and lay open, not to hide and conceal Knowledge; especially seeing the Understandings of Men were in those times rude and impatient, and almost incapable of any Subtilties (...) for as Hieroglyphicks preceded Letters, so Parables were more ancient than Arguments.¹¹¹

The relation of Genesis to Moses's understanding of the natural world and its laws was another main motif in biblical hermeneutics for them. Thus, for example, Samuel Clarke contended that "among the writings of all, even the most ancient and learned Nations, there are *None but* the books of the *Jews*, which [have] given any tolerable account in particular, of the *Formation of this earth* into its present *habitable State*." Moreover, characteristically, these accounts were written in a simple way in order to be understood by the majority of people. Thus Isaac Barrow stated that the Bible "being not penned by Masters of humane art or science; nor directed to persons of more than ordinary capacities or improvements, doth not intend to use words otherwise than in the most plain and ordinary manner", and as indicated by Thomas Burnet in a similar vein, "the account given by Moses (...) is not true in it self, but only spoken popularly to comply with the (...) Israelites."¹¹² Through the simplicity of those words, natural philosophical findings could be discerned as well.

Robert Boyle emphasised the unity of truth in God's works, that is to say, nature and Scriptures, and mankind's duty towards the Creator. In this sense, Boyle also represents the general and common assumption according to which a sound natural philosophy does not oppose the Scriptures and, on the contrary, it confirms the Biblical pronouncements.¹¹³

And indeed so far is God from being unwilling, that we should pry into his works, that by divers dispensations he imposes on us, little less than a necessity of studying them. For first he begins the book of scripture with the description of the book of nature, of which he not only gives us a general account, to inform us, that he made the world (since for that end, the very first verse in the bible might have sufficed) but he vouchsafes us by retail the narrative of each day's proceedings; and in the two first chapters of *Genesis*, is pleased to give nobler

¹¹¹ Francis Bacon, "The wisdom of the Ancients", in *The essays, or councils, civil and moral, of Sir. Francis Bacon*, London, 1701. As quoted in Haycock, 2004: 609.

¹¹² Samuel Clarke, *Evidences of Natural and Revealed Religion*, in *The Works of Samuel Clarke DD*, 2 vols, London, 1738, vol II: 745; Isaac Barrow, "Of Justifying Faith", in *The Theological Works of Isaac Barrow*, 9 vols., Alexander Napier (ed.) Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 1839, vol. II: 55; Thomas Burnet, *Archaeologiae philosophicae*, London, 1692, I.2 c. 7, 8, 9; As quoted in Harrison, 1998: 126, 134, and 135, respectively.

¹¹³ See Henry, 2007: 5.

hints of natural philosophy than men are yet perhaps aware of. Though, that in most other places of the scripture, where the works of nature are mentioned but incidently, or in order to other purposes, they are spoken of rather in a popular than accurate manner, I dare not peremptorily deny, being unwilling to interest the reputation of Holy Writ (designed to teach us rather divinity than philosophy) in the doubtful contentions of naturalists, about such matters, as may (though the history of the creation cannot) be known by the meer light of natural reason (...) We may next observe, that God has made some knowledge of his created book, both conducive to the belief, and necessary to the understanding of his written one.¹¹⁴

Finally, Thomas Sprat, based upon the study of history, was also convinced of the pristine character of ancient knowledge which encompassed astronomy, mathematics, religion, morals, and also shared the belief that it was transmitted by way of a figurative language in order to be kept secret from those not able to deal with it. Thus, in *The History of the Royal Society* he observed:

It is evident from, the Universal testimony of *History*, that all learning and civility were deriv'd down to us, from the *Eastern* parts of the world. There it was, that Mankind arose. (...) it is but just, that we should attribute the original of *Astronomy, Geometry, (...)* to the *Assyrians, the Chaldeans, and Egyptians*. And as to them we owe the *Invention*; so from them proceeded the first *Corruption* of knowledge. It was the custom of their Wise men, to wrap up their Observations on Nature, and the Manners of Men, in the Dark Shadows of Hieroglyphicks; and to conceal them, as sacred *Mysteries*, from the apprehensions of the vulgar.¹¹⁵

The picture gathered from this background is a flawless structure which combines the historicity of the Bible with the ancient mythology, natural philosophy, chronology and religion. This is the background against which Newton's shared attitude towards the ancient wisdom, as expressed in pronouncements related to his natural philosophy and religion will be analysed.

To begin with, let us take as starting point the *Principia*. The opening words make reference to the study of the workings of nature, pointing out how mechanics is related to mathematics as for its aim at reducing natural phenomena to mathematical laws. In view of that, "it has seemed best in this treatise to concentrate on *mathematics* as it relates to natural philosophy." As a result, in the introduction to the Book 3 Newton advanced his approach so as to apply those mathematical principles to the system of the world, in order to prove the applicability of mathematics to natural phenomena in the vein of the ancients, as mentioned in the Preface. Nevertheless, Newton's ambition was so extensive as to include a popularised version of Book 3, "The System of the World",

¹¹⁴ Robert Boyle, "Some Considerations Touching the Usefulness of Experimental Natural Philosophy", in *The Works of Robert Boyle in Six Volumes to which prefixed the Life of the Author*, Thomas Birch (ed), London, 1772: 19.

¹¹⁵ Sprat, 1702: 5.

but he restricted himself to present those “principles of philosophy that are not, however, philosophical but strictly mathematical.”¹¹⁶

The word ‘philosophical’ was not restricted *only* to the study of nature and the interactions of bodies, notwithstanding the common usage,¹¹⁷ and this becomes manifest from the context of this passage. In fact, having cleared the mathematical approach adopted in the *Principia* (Books 1 and 2), there is a telling assertion regarding another way to expose the arguments developed throughout Books 3: “On this subject I composed an earlier version of book 3 in popular form, so that it might be more widely read,” but once again Newton limited his approach to the mathematical domain and “translated the substance of the earlier version into propositions in a mathematical style, so that they may be read only by those who have first mastered the principles.” This limitation could be understood given Newton’s separation of levels of speech, but this interpretation looks weak since he “illustrated [those mathematical principles] with some philosophical scholiums, treating topics that are general and that seem to be the most fundamental for philosophy, such as the density and resistance of bodies, spaces void of bodies, and the motion of light and sounds,”¹¹⁸ not to mention the General Scholium itself in the second and third editions of the *Principia* (1713, 1726). Another interpretation could be his reluctant character to get involved in disputes as those of 1670s about his *New Theory*.¹¹⁹ Lastly, one could deduce Newton as being

¹¹⁶ Newton, 1999: 381.

¹¹⁷ In the footnote to the introduction to Book 3, Bernard Cohen makes the following comment: “In this introduction to book 3, Newton uses ‘philosophy’ and its adjective ‘philosophical’ to refer to ‘natural philosophy,’ According to John Harris’s *Lexicon Technicum* (London, 1704), natural philosophy is that ‘Science which contemplates the Powers of Nature, the Properties of Natural Bodies, and their mutual Action one upon another.’ The half title of the third edition of the *Principia* reads ‘Newtoni Principia Philosophiae’ (‘Newton’s Principles of Philosophy’). The dedication page of the *Principia*, in all editions, refers to the Royal Society as founded ‘ad philosophiam promovendam’ (‘for the promotion of philosophy’).” Newton, 1999: 793. Though this clarification in general terms is correct, it would be erroneous, as I shall illustrate, to make such a reduction to Newton. By the word “philosophy”, and its cognates, Newton *also* understood theological, religious, alchemical, and exegetical implications of his natural philosophy. As I take Cohen’s assertion, it forms part of his understanding of Newton’s natural philosophy aimed at presenting it in manner akin to ‘science’ as we recognise the word nowadays. Needless to say, Cohen’s directions need to be contrasted to the cultural setting of Newton’s own words.

¹¹⁸ Newton, 1999: 793. With hindsight, it is almost ironic to read Newton’s hope “to avoid lengthy disputations” (Newton, 1999: 793) in view of (1) the criticisms regarding, precisely, his mathematical style in the *Principia*. As Whewell commented, “The ponderous instrument of synthesis, so effective in [Newton’s] hands, has never since been grasped by one who could use it for such purposes; and we gaze at it with admiring curiosity, as on some gigantic implement of war, which stands idle among the memorials of ancient days, and makes us wonder what manner of man he was who could wield as a weapon what we can hardly lift as a burden.” (Whewell, 1837: 167). (2) His mathematical approach to the concept of force, notwithstanding his several disclaimers about it, as it was reported in one of the first reviews of the *Principia*: “In order to make an *opus* as perfect as possible, M. Newton has only to give us a Physics as exact as his Mechanics. He will give it when he substitutes true motions for those that he has supposed.” (*Journal des Sçavans* (2 August 1688), pp. 153 ff). And (3) the theological interpretation of his natural philosophy in hands of Leibniz who claimed that “Natural Religion it self, seems to decay [in England] very much. Many will have Human Souls to be material: Others make God himself a corporeal Being.” (Clarke, 1717: 3).

¹¹⁹ If the psychological impact caused by the disputes around his optical researches cannot be denied, it is also true that his reluctance to discuss his researches in mathematics, alchemy, ancient wisdom, and religion cannot be reduced only to that event neither. As a matter of fact, thanks to the works of Derek T. Whiteside and Niccolò Guicciardini, for example, we know the Newton made use of a series of strategies intended to spread his findings in mathematics [See the instructive introductions by Whiteside to *The Mathematical Papers of Isaac Newton*, (Derek T. Whiteside (ed. and trans.), 8 vols. Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 1968-1980) and Guicciardini, 2004]. To Betty Jo Dobbs and

consistent with his goal of dealing with the ‘mathematical’ principles governing the workings of nature, and so he expected from his readers to be familiarised firstly with the principles, since “those who have not sufficiently grasped the principles set down here will certainly not perceive the force of the conclusions” but more significantly, “nor will they lay aside the preconceptions to which they have become accustomed over many years.”¹²⁰

As is known, the popularised version to which Newton was alluding was published posthumously in 1728 under the same title of the *Principia* Book 3, namely *De mundi systemate*,¹²¹ composed probably in 1685. In this work Newton revealed that philosophy, untold in the *Principia*, which straightforwardly linked him with the acknowledgement of the authority of the ancient sages in natural philosophy, who taught the motion of planets in spaces free of resistance in a heliocentric system under the action of gravity force:

It was the ancient opinion of not a few, in the earliest ages of philosophy, that the fixed stars stood immovable in the highest parts of the world; that under the fixed stars the planets were carried about the sun; that the earth, as one of the planets, described an annual course about the sun, while by a diurnal motion it was in the meantime revolved about its own axis; and that the sun, as the common fire which served to warm the whole, was fixed in the centre of the universe.

After listing chronologically those who transmitted this teaching like Philolaus, Aristarchus of Samos, the Pythagoreans, and Anaximander, Newton immediately connects this astronomical knowledge to theology, pointing out to Pompilius as one of the first of the wise kings in constructing a Vestal temple, or Prytanaea, who “as a symbol of the figure of the world with the sun in the centre, erected a round temple in honor of *Vesta*, and ordained perpetual fire to be kept in the middle of it.” This second topic of the temple is also traced backwards from the Romans through Greeks up to the Egyptians, who communicated “their mysteries, that is, their philosophy of things above the common way of thinking, under the veil of religious rites and hieroglyphic symbols.” Finally, through the research of the lineage of the heliocentric philosophy, Newton asserts how occurred the first corruption to the harmony of natural philosophy and natural theology, which was by positing the solid orbs “introduced by Eudoxus, Calippus, and Aristotle; when the ancient philosophy began to decline, and to give place to the new prevailing fictions of the Greeks.”¹²² With respect to the central

Richard Westfall, among others, we also know that in the field of alchemy Newton practiced the reserved technique to transmit his ideas, discoveries and procedures [See Dobbs, 1975, 1991; Westfall, 1975, 1980]. And lastly, due to Frank Manuel, James Force, Stephen Snobelen, Rob Iliffe, and many other recent scholars in Newton’s theology and religion, we have a better understanding of his means to express his theology, in such a way that exhibits clearly his willingness to make his case. See Force, James E. and Popkin, Richard H., 1994, 1999; Snobelen, 1999; Goldish, 1998.

¹²⁰ Newton, 1999: 793. Whatever be the case, the first edition of Newton’s *Principia* (1687) appeared as a quite secular work which—with the exception of a couple of allusions to the ancients (more precisely, to Pappus) in the Preface and to the Scriptures in the scholium to the Definitions—deliberately omitted any outright reference regarding the awareness by the ancient sages of the theory developed in it.

¹²¹ Newton, 1934: Vol. 2: 549-626.

¹²² Newton, 1934: 549.

concept of his *magnum opus*, the force of gravity, in the last paragraph related to the ancient wisdom about the force which retains bodies 'within certain bounds', Newton declares that its cause was untold:

After this time, we do not know in what manner the ancients explained the question, how the planets came to be retained within certain bounds in these free spaces, and to be drawn off from the rectilinear courses, which, left to themselves, they should have pursued, into regular revolutions in curvilinear orbits. Probably it was to give some sort of satisfaction to this difficulty that solid orbs had been introduced.¹²³

By charting the origin of the heliocentric system as well as the notion of motion in spaces free of resistance by virtue of gravity force, Newton was not only making an act of deference towards the ancients, but he was, more importantly, asserting when and where the decline of philosophy, which encompassed both natural philosophy and religion, began to take place.

The ideas expressed in the first lines of *De mundi systemate* evidence, obliquely, a deeper research programme that Newton undertook from the decade of 1670s, which became one of his central concerns during the rest of his life. This is not a detached agenda from his natural philosophical inquiries but a unified network around the original knowledge of the ancients. Thus, it is possible to discern the close relationship among natural philosophy, natural theology and religion. In this way, we can recognise why the unity of natural philosophy and natural theology expressed in the final Query in the *Opticks* and the General Scholium in the *Principia*, constitutes the main subject of enquiry in Newton's historical endeavours aimed at deciphering, through exegetical and hermeneutical analysis, the pristine knowledge of natural philosophy.

Along the same lines of his theological researches from 1675, the decade of 1690s represents another important period in Newton's intellectual life inasmuch as during this time he was actively involved in the study of the *prisca sapientia*. From that time onwards, he spent a great deal of his efforts in analysing the earliest records and the opinions about the unanswered question, both in the *Principia* and in *De mundi systemate*, about the cause of gravity.

The history of the main manuscripts related to these researches dates from July 9, 1684 when the Scottish mathematician and astronomer David Gregory, nephew of James Gregory, sent to the professor of mathematics in Cambridge, Isaac Newton, his *Exercitatio geometrica de dimensione figurarum* (Edinburgh, 1684) "expressing his hopes and expectations, that Mr. Newton's methods [of infinite series] (long since contrived, but not yet published in print) will now shortly be made publick."¹²⁴ The tenor of the final words of the review in the *Philosophical Transactions* of Gregory's *Exercitatio* are revealing in so far as they provide some insight into the numerous attempts made by Newton's acquaintances and friends to publish his mathematical discoveries,¹²⁵ and also shows

¹²³ *Ibid.*, 550.

¹²⁴ *Philosophical Transactions* (1683-1775), Volume 14, pp. 730-732, on p. 732. De analysi per aequationes numero terminorum infinitas

¹²⁵ Newton's main works on infinite series are *De analysi per aequationes numero terminorum infinitas* (Newton, 1967–1981, Vol. 2: 206-247), and *De methodis serierum et fluxionum*, (Newton, 1967–1981, Vol. 3: 32-353). The episode with

Gregory's eagerness to establish a fluent communication with the author of the *Principia*.¹²⁶ Gregory, as the story goes, never received any answer from the professor of Cambridge, notwithstanding having read his *Exercitatio*. As a matter of fact, it could be said that the relation between these mathematicians was difficult at the beginning, given Newton's reserved personality and the irascible character at the moment of defending his expertise in natural philosophy. As it has been documented by Guicciardini and Whiteside, Newton made public some of his discoveries pressed by the progress achieved by some of his contemporaries,¹²⁷ among them the Scottish mathematician, who "made a clumsy attempt to claim for himself the 'prime theorem' on quadratures that Newton had communicated to Craig in 1685."¹²⁸

Notwithstanding the potential tension between these leading British mathematicians, they would strike up a good relationship eventually. As a matter of fact, soon after the publication of the *Principia*, Gregory undertook the project of writing a running commentary on this work which he considered would arouse the admiration of the best "geometers and naturalists",¹²⁹ under the title *Notae in Newtoni Principia mathematica philosophiae naturalis*. In spite of his admiration for the masterpiece, the approach adopted by Gregory was not in the line of an unbiased mathematician who highly praised the due merits of the work without dealing with its internal difficulties. In point of fact, Gregory was one of the many readers who found himself perplexed by the brevity and obscurity of the underlying methods of discovery, and also showed a preference for tackling symbolically the demonstrations.¹³⁰

Gregory and Newton met personally in 1691,¹³¹ and eventually, by Newton's recommendation, the professorship in astronomy at Oxford was occupied by the Scottish mathematician. In a letter to Arthur Charlett, eulogising Gregory's abilities as the 'greatest mathematician in Scotland,' Newton also made a reference to his proficiency "in Analysis & Geometry both new & Old."¹³² Additionally, Gregory's reputation made of him one of the prospective editors (the other being Nicholas Fatio de Dullier) of a second edition of the *Principia*, an edition that never reached the press as planned in 1690s. In effect, during his stay in Cambridge from May 5th to 7th, Gregory was allowed to peruse and take notes from some of Newton's

Leibniz about the calculus, as is known, persuaded Newton to publish, partially, his achievements in mathematics. Guicciardini has analysed Newton's strategies to spread his ideas on mathematics, as well as the fruitless attempts by his friends, in Guicciardini 2004.

¹²⁶ See Newton, 1959-1977, vol. 2: 396. "S^r. Altho I have not y^e honour of your acquaintance, yet y^e character and place yee bear in the learned world I presume gives me a title to adress you especially in a matter of this sort, which is humbly to present you with a treatise latly published by me heir, which I am sure contains things new to the greatest parte of the geometers."

¹²⁷ See Newton 1967-1981, Vol. 7: 3 ss; Guicciardini, 1999, 2004.

¹²⁸ Guicciardini, 2004: 465.

¹²⁹ Newton, 1959-1977, vol. 2: 311.

¹³⁰ Gregory's *Notae* were at odds with Newton's philosophy of mathematics, as for instance, in the effort for working out symbolic demonstrations, and critical for considering obscure the underlying methods of demonstration, not to mention the attribution of the methods in the *Principia* to others. See Guicciardini, 1999: 179-184.

¹³¹ Westfall, 1980: 496, 499-500, 510-517.

¹³² See Newton, 1959-1977, vol. 3: 154.

unpublished mathematical papers related to infinite series and the method of proof based upon the quadrature of curves.

In talking about the planned second edition of the *Principia*, Gregory also learnt Newton's preference for the ancient methods of geometry, and could discern why the *Principia* was a means of promoting Newton's philosophy of mathematics with his characteristic reverence for the ancients.¹³³ In addition to the ancient way of doing mathematics, Gregory's visit to Newton also gave him the opportunity to hear from Newton how he considered his natural philosophy to be a recovery of the *prisca* in natural philosophical matters. This aspect of his private thoughts was recorded in one of Gregory's memoranda from 1694, and so, writing on the philosophy of the *Principia*, he commented: "He will spread himself in exhibiting the agreement of the philosophy with that of the Ancients and principally with that of Thales. The philosophy of Epicurus and Lucretius is true and old, but was wrongly interpreted by the ancients as atheism."¹³⁴ It was said that the evidence of this was projected to be included in the Book 3. There

He will make a big change in Hypothesis III. page 402. He will show that the most ancient philosophy is in agreement with his as much because the Egyptians and others taught the Copernican system, as he shows from their religion and hieroglyphics and images of the Gods, as because Plato and others—Plutarch and Galileo refer to it—observed the gravitation of all bodies towards all.¹³⁵

The alluded hypothesis which asserts the ability of bodies to transform into others¹³⁶ was, in fact, discarded in the successive editions of the *Principia*, but the material that Gregory mentioned was intended to be included in a future—but never printed—edition of the *Principia* as scholiums to the propositions 4 through 9 of Book 3, and projected to illustrate the idea according to which Newton's philosophy of nature was not new but an ancient one discernible through the works of the earliest philosophers. As a matter of fact, in these Classical Scholia,¹³⁷ as these papers are known today,

¹³³ See Guicciardini, 2004: 465-466; Westfall, 1980: 506-507.

¹³⁴ Newton, 1959-1977, Vol. 3: 336.

¹³⁵ *Ibid.*, 384.

¹³⁶ I.e. "Corpus omne in alterius cujuscunque generis corpus transformari posse, & qualitatum gradus omnes intermedios successive induere." On Newton's doctrine of essential qualities, see McGuire, 1968b.

¹³⁷ The first scholar who called the attention of these manuscripts was I Bernard Cohen who planned to "publish an edited version of them, together with other similar material from Newton's annotations in his own copies of the *Principia* and from his MS. Papers" (Cohen, 1964: 148) but that material was never printed. Two years later, Jams E. McGuire and Piyo Rattansi published the Classical Scholia partially in their groundbreaking study "Newton and the 'Pipes of Pan'", but regretfully, there was "not space to present the material of these 'classical' Scholia *in extenso*." (McGuire and Rattansi, 1966: 111). In 1981 Paolo Casini published the classical scholia entirely in his "Newton: gli scolii classici", *Giornale critico della filosofia italiana Quinta serie* vol. I anno LX (LXII), pp. 7-53, translated into English by Rupert Hall in 1984 as "Newton: The Classical Scholia", *History of Science* 22, pp. 1-58. Unfortunately, Hall did not translate the scholia themselves, but only the introduction by Casini. So far, the definitive edition of Newton's classical scholia, and translation into English, is Volkmar Schüller's "Newton's scholia from David Gregory's estate on the propositions IV through IX book III of his *Principia*." According to Schüller, "Casini contains quite a few misread errors and does not stand up to strict philological standards." (Schüller, 2001: 213). Schüller's edition will be used here.

Newton developed a careful doxography in order to put into agreement his natural philosophy and the ancient knowledge about the system of the world.

Propositions 1 to 3 deal with the force which is inversely as the square of the distance from the centre in the satellites of Jupiter (Proposition 1), primary planets of the solar system (Proposition 2), and in the moon with respect to the Earth.

Propositions 4 through 9, those related to the Classical Scholia, form the core of Newton's theory of universal gravitation in the *Principia* and the task of the scholia is precisely to relate this doctrine to the ancient thought in natural philosophy. Thus, in Scholium IV to Proposition 4, which asserts the preservation of the orbital motion of the moon by virtue of gravity force,¹³⁸ Newton writes:

That the earth's moon is a body made of earth, and that it is heavy and would fall toward our earth due to the force of gravity if it were not prevented from doing so due to the force of its circular motion, is an old view.¹³⁹

Here Newton traces the ancient conceptions about the physical nature of the moon which was considered as a part of the earth, and as mixture of air and fire—although being, at the same time, a dense body. Next, he passes to discern through the different schools of philosophy, beginning with the Ionic philosophy of Thales, the transmission of this idea in the statements of Anaximander and Anaximenes to Anaxagoras and his followers Archelaus, Euripides, Metrodorus, Democritus, and Diogenes. The constitution of heavenly bodies, according to this tradition, was heavy. As for the gravity force, the name of Anaxagoras is important in so far as he introduced the figure of the lion to represent the power which maintains heavenly bodies in their harmony.

Through the fiction of the lion falling from the earth's moon and the stone falling from the sun he [Anaxagoras] taught the gravity of the bodies of the sun and the earth's moon; through the figment of ascending stones he taught the force opposite to gravity, that of rotation. This is not to be understood literally. The mystic philosophers usually hid their tenets behind such figments and mystical language.¹⁴⁰

The final part is concerned with the way that ancients thought how planets acquired their circular motion right after having reached their solid nature, a viewpoint contended by the Pythagorean school, Plato and even Galileo in his *Dialogue Concerning the Two Chief World Systems*. In Newton's view, this circular motion implied the tacit acceptance of gravity force.

¹³⁸ Proposition 4: "The moon gravitates toward the earth and by the force of gravity is always drawn back from rectilinear motion and kept in its orbit." Newton, 1999: 803.

¹³⁹ Schüller, 2001: 219.

¹⁴⁰ *Ibid.*, 221.

The subsequent focus of attention¹⁴¹ in Scholium V is directed on the solar system in general, and the role of the force which hinders the eventual congregation of the system at its centre in absence of gravity. The argument is supported in Democritus and Lucretius who taught, in Newton's interpretation, that the systems of Jupiter, Saturn and the Sun are retained in their orbits because of the gravity force.

Democritus, however, when he said that there was an infinite number of worlds, and understood these individual worlds to be not individual planets, but individual systems of planets, thought that not only the planets which belong to <one and> the same system mutually are heavy toward each other, but that their gravity also extended all over toward the other systems.¹⁴²

The proportionality of gravity to the masses¹⁴³ constitutes the next stage in the shrewd doxography trailed by Newton in order to corroborate the linkage between his natural philosophy and those of the ancients in Scholium VI. Starting with Lucretius's assertions, two basic statements are worthy to be highlighted, the first one is related to the natural gravity of bodies referred by the figure of 'the office of the body', and the second one has to do with the non-existence of heaviness in void spaces. Then, he attributes to Lucretius the notion of gravity residing in the atoms which bodies are made of: "He teaches that fire and the other bodies which are called Light bodies do not ascend of their own accord, but as a result of a force driving upwards, just as wood, which is a heavy body, rises in water: but all bodies are carried downward through empty space."¹⁴⁴ Lastly, Lucretius's assertions and ideas are traced back to older philosophers like Epicurus and Democritus who pondered in two ways the heaviness of bodies according to (1) the number of atoms, those who thought atoms to be equal in size, or to (2) the quantity of solid matter of bodies, for those who thought atoms to be unequal.

In keeping with the line of enquiry into the primeval teachings about the characterisation of gravity force, Scholium VII deals with the perception of its proportionality.¹⁴⁵ In the records of the earliest philosophers there is the conception of gravity as the product of the sum of individual particles, or atoms, of bodies. The illustration of this idea is given by the analogy with the magnet. A derivative idea of this notion is the portrayal of the universe as infinite. The nub of this argument lies in the fact that if the universe were limited in extension there would not be equilibrium in the

¹⁴¹ Proposition 5: "The circumjovial planets [or satellites of Jupiter] gravitate toward Jupiter, the circumsaturnian planets [or satellites of Saturn] gravitate toward Saturn, and the circumsolar [or primary] planets gravitate toward the sun, and by the force of their gravity they are always drawn back from rectilinear motions and kept in curvilinear orbits." Newton, 1999: 805.

¹⁴² Schüller, 2001: 223.

¹⁴³ Proposition 6: "All bodies gravitate toward each of the planets, and at any given distance from the center of any one planet the weight of any body whatever toward that planet is proportional to the quantity of matter which the body contains." Newton, 1999: 806.

¹⁴⁴ Schüller, 2001:225.

¹⁴⁵ Proposition 7: "Gravity exists in all bodies universally and is proportional to the quantity of matter in each." Newton, 1999: 810.

outermost bodies, and as a consequence they would have a propensity to gather at the centre of the whole.¹⁴⁶ In view of that: “All worlds gravitate toward each other and, are prevented by their gravity toward the worlds located on one side from falling toward the worlds located on the other.” Notwithstanding this synchronization in the system, it is fated to its eventual decay. This same idea, maintained in the *Opticks* (1717),¹⁴⁷ is attributed in the Classical Scholia to Democritus who declared that “at some point in time [planets] will fall due to the force of the superior gravity.”¹⁴⁸

Scholium VIII deals with the mathematical aspect of gravity law which acts in inverse proportion as the square of the distance between bodies.¹⁴⁹ According to Newton, the Pythagoreans foreshadowed the decreasing of gravity as a function of the increment of distance through the well-known figure of the music of spheres. Thus, the ancients

appear to have concealed this ratio using the harmony of the celestial spheres, whereby they portrayed the sun and the remaining six planets Mercury, Venus, Earth, Mars, Jupiter, Saturn as Apollo with the seven-stringed lyre and measured the intervals between the spheres through the tone intervals.¹⁵⁰

The musical model developed from this figure relates the inverse proportion of the tone of the sound and the length of the strings. In this manner, the remote Saturn would produce the lower tone and the remaining planets higher ones as they are closer to the Sun, who performs the role of playing the strings. “Through this symbol” the Pythagoreans, asserts Newton, “indicated that the sun acts on the planets with its force in the same harmonic ratio to the different distances as that of the tensile force to strings of different length, i.e., in a duplicate inverse ratio to the distances.” Additionally, it is reported by Macrobius that such anticipation is based upon the experience realised by Pythagoras, and so “stretching sheep intestines or ox tendons with different weights attached, he also learned that the tones correspond to the attached weights in a similar manner.” Just as in the first scholium on the constitution of the moon, an interpolation is added in the argumentative sequence in order to point out that “the philosophers loved to arrange their mystical language such that they offered the masses quite inappropriate general posts for the sake of derision and hid the truth behind such language.”¹⁵¹

¹⁴⁶ See Newton’s letter to Richard Bentley Cambridge, 25 February 1692/3.

¹⁴⁷ “Comets move in very excentrick Orbs in all manner of Positions, blind Fate could never make all the Planets move one and the same way in Orbs concentrick, some inconsiderable Irregularities excepted which may have risen from the mutual Actions of Comets and Planets upon one another, and which will be apt to increase, till this System wants a Reformation.” Newton, 1717: 378.

¹⁴⁸ *Ibid.*, 233, 235.

¹⁴⁹ Proposition 8: “If two globes gravitate toward each other, and their matter is homogeneous on all sides in regions that are equally distant from their centers, then the weight of either globe toward the other will be inversely as the square of the distance between the centers.” Newton, 1999: 811.

¹⁵⁰ Schüller, 2001: 235.

¹⁵¹ *Ibid.*

The final Scholium IX—to Proposition 9 in the *Principia*¹⁵²—deals with the reconstruction of the ancient conception of the causality of universal attraction. Through the previous five scholiums Newton has been explaining, within the framework of the primordial philosophy of nature throughout the teachings of the first sages, the properties of gravity force, and now his account will be focused on their beliefs about its causation. Here the notion of soul in a theosophical context articulates the ancient perception about what endows matter with motion. In this way Thales first, and then Pythagoras, assimilated animated bodies to Gods:

Therefore he [Thales] taught that everything is full of Gods, whereby with “Gods” he meant animate bodies. In the same sense Pythagoras believed the sun and the planets to be Gods and said that the sun, because of its powerful force of attraction, is Jupiter’s jail, that is, a body endowed with the greatest possible divine force, with which the planets are locked inside their shells.¹⁵³

This divinisation of force was taught by means of the character of Pan, the godly nature who, manipulating “this world and melodically play[ing] it like a musical instrument with the harmonic ratio,”¹⁵⁴ gave rise to the notion of the theatre of nature synchronised with the chorale of numbers.

A variant folio to the Scholium corresponding to Proposition 9 is more detailed with respect to the conceptualisation of the notion of soul and its relationship to matter and space. In this refinement, which consists mainly of two introductory paragraphs to the previous draft and a concluding one, we are told the ancients thought of space void of bodies as filled everywhere with certain *spiritus* which was identified with God, but some others differentiated “the highest God” from the divinised space (*spiritus*) by naming it “the world soul”¹⁵⁵ which furnishes planets, for some philosophers, and all bodies for others, with their particular souls. The import of this clarification lay in the ontological hierarchy that emerges from this picture of the world where God represents the highest dignity, the infinite space, assimilated to the universal *spiritus* or *anima mundi* provides animation to matter, and bodies endowed with their particular soul.¹⁵⁶

This last Scholium concludes with a religious representation of the world by means of the structure of the ancient temples which, as a microcosm constituted by the central fire, the hall, and people, symbolise the macrocosm characterized by God, space and matter:

¹⁵² Proposition 9: “In going inward from the surfaces of the planets, gravity decreases very nearly in the ratio of the distances from the center.” Newton, 1999: 815.

¹⁵³ Schüller, 2001: 239.

¹⁵⁴ *Ibid.*

¹⁵⁵ *Ibid.*, 241.

¹⁵⁶ A caveat is in order here. One could be tempted to interpret this hierarchy against the religious background of Trinitarism by attributing to the *anima mundi* the role of the Holy Ghost, or as the intermediary means whereby God deliver activity to matter, but that is not the case. From the religious standpoint, such an elucidation is untenable in the light of Newton’s theological convictions. And as for the role of furnishing activity to matter, that regard contradicts Newton’s denial of intermediaries in his treatise *De gravitatione*, written long before the Classical Scholia. The inclusion of this *spiritus*, more than aimed at establishing the chain of being concerning the force, could be seen as to absolute space within a divinised nature in her entirety.

They believed that this one God lives in all bodies as its temple, and thus they fashioned the old temples following the example of the heavens by portraying the sun as a fire in the center of the hall and the planets as the people walking around it, which they called the microcosm. Because this custom was referred to by Cicero, Macrobius, when he remarked upon Cicero's words, wrote the following: "His designation of the universe as the temple of God was appropriate, too."¹⁵⁷

The character of the doxography undertaken by Newton in these Classical Scholia hardly could be underestimated, viewed in the light of his entire philosophical programme. In a broad sense, present day scholars –whether for recognising or discarding– are quite aware of the existence of the mass of manuscripts, and printed works (mainly in theology and chronology), where Newton assumes the endeavour of mapping out the theological, mathematical, alchemical and natural philosophical issues of the ancient thought aligned with his own philosophy. And in a narrow sense, as in the case of the *Principia* with the Classical Scholia, where he develops a specific syncretism between the mathematical physics of his *Principia* and the natural philosophy of the earliest philosophers in key issues as those related to the atomic structure of matter, its motion in spaces void of resistance, the universal reach of influence of gravity force, its decrease by the inverse square ratio of the distance between bodies, all of this within the framework of God's Providence.

This supposedly preposterous approach, as it may seem to those who place Newton at the pinnacle of scientific rationality, loses its putative extravagant character when Newton's research programme for the philosophy of nature is contrasted against the cultural background and the historical setting of his career.

The positive attitude towards ancient thought was by no means uncommon during the sixteenth-and seventeenth-centuries, and as a matter of fact a number of well-known natural philosophers saw their endeavours as a continuation, restoration or reinstatement of a long-lost truth eroded through the distortions and misinterpretations of the archaic teachings. As a matter of fact, the proper understanding of theology as well as an appropriate knowledge of ancient history, chronology and prophesy were essential requirements in order to develop a correct and true natural philosophy. So therefore, it is not surprising to find Newton's philosophy of nature deeply embedded in the pristine knowledge of ancient natural philosophers (Haycock, 2004; Force, 1999b). From the perspective of aiming at the restoration of the true philosophy, the *Principia* was contemplated by Newton as a way to turn the human comprehension of Creation back to its integrity. The mathematical analysis deployed along the three books of his masterpiece is just a new way of demonstrating the primeval truth about the universe. This conviction was expressed in a draft preface to the *Principia* in the following terms:

The Chaldeans long ago believed that the planets revolve in nearly concentric orbits around the sun and that the comets do so in extremely eccentric orbits, and the Pythagoreans introduced this philosophy into Greece. But it was also known to the ancients that the moon

¹⁵⁷ Schüller, 2001: 243.

is heavy toward the earth, and that the stars are heavy toward one another, and that all bodies in a vacuum fall to the earth with equal velocity and thus are heavy in proportion to the quantity of matter in each of them. Because of lack of demonstrations, this philosophy fell into disuse, and I did not invent it but have only tried to use the force of demonstrations to revive it (Newton, 1999, p. 53).

Newton's purpose, notwithstanding the mathematical force of his arguments, did not persuade entirely his Continental readers; and the demand for intelligibility showed the divergences of Newton and his critics regarding the nature of the central concept of his work, namely the ontology of force.

3. The mechanical philosophy: From inert matter to active principles

When Newton published his *Principia* in 1687, it seemed that the so-called scientific revolution had reached its apex inasmuch as the major natural phenomena could be explained, mathematically, through the central concepts of his work, namely the three laws of motion and the universal principle of gravitation. In this vein, as it is stated in Book 3, Proposition 6, Theorem 6, “all bodies gravitate toward each of the planets, and at any given distance from the center of any one planet the weight of any body whatever toward the planet is proportional to the quantity of matter which the body contains”, and in Proposition 7, Theorem 7, we are told that “gravity exists universally and is proportional to the quantity of matter in the earth.”¹⁵⁸

In the wake of the astonishing explanatory achievement of Newtonian mathematical principles of natural philosophy, R. S. Westfall, the outstanding scholar and biographer of Newton, remarked that the discovery of the gravity law “was the culmination of a radical restructuring of Western mankind’s understanding of nature”.¹⁵⁹ This characterisation of Newton’s realisation is not uncommon at all since the very appearance of the *Principia*, but notwithstanding this commendation, and setting the panegyric tone of this remark aside, there is much to say about this approach to Newton’s accomplishment. In point of fact, divergent assessments on the merits of this work arose right after its publication.¹⁶⁰

On the one hand, the book was highly praised by virtue of the mathematical deployment for the treatment of natural phenomena; and on the other hand, it provoked severe criticisms given the fact that it seemed to contravene the mainstream form of explanation of the current natural philosophy. In order to illustrate this tension, compare, for example, the reviews written by Edmond Halley, the first editor of the *Principia*, with the Continental one attributed to Pierre-Sylvain Régis, an enthusiastic promoter and champion of the Cartesian philosophy. Thus, Halley wrote:

This incomparable author [Newton], (...) has in this treatise given a most notable instance of the extent of the powers of his mind; and has at once shewn what are the Principles of Natural Philosophy, and so far derived from them their consequences, that he seems to have

¹⁵⁸ Newton, 1999: 806, 810.

¹⁵⁹ Westfall, 1993: 33.

¹⁶⁰ The *Principia* was the object of four reviews. One by Edmond Halley in the *Philosophical Transactions* of the Royal Society, and three written anonymously in the *Bibliothèque Universelle* (attributed to Locke), the *Acta Eruditorum* (possibly by Christoph Pfautz), and in the *Journal des Sçavans* whose author is considered to be Pierre-Sylvain Régis. For details of each of these reviews see Cohen 1992.

exhausted his argument, and left little to be done by those that shall succeed him. His great skill in the old and new geometry, helped by his own improvements of the latter, (...) has enabled him to master those problems, which for their difficulty would have still lain unresolved, had one less qualified than himself attempted them. (...) Here the verity of the hypothesis of Kepler is demonstrated, and a full resolution given to all the difficulties that occur in the astronomical science; they being nothing else but the necessary consequences of the Sun, Earth, Moon, and Planets, having all of them a gravitation or tendency towards their centres, proportional to the quantity of matter in each of them, and whose force abates in duplicate proportion of the distance reciprocally.¹⁶¹

From another perspective, a very different tone is adopted by the French reviewer who, despite the fact of giving a positive verdict on the mathematical value of the *Principia*, he downgraded it to a simple tract on mechanics since the main concept of the work, the gravity force, remained unexplained as for its cause. Thus, Régis wrote:

The work of M. Newton is a mechanics, the most perfect that one could imagine, as it is not possible to make demonstrations more precise or more exact than those he gives in the first two books (...). But one has to confess that one cannot regard these demonstrations otherwise than as only mechanical; indeed the author recognizes himself at the end of page four and the beginning of page five that he has not considered their Principles as a Physicist, but as a mere Geometer.

He confesses the same thing at the beginning of the third book, where he endeavors nevertheless to explain the System of the World. But it is [done] only by hypotheses that are, most of them, arbitrary, and that, consequently, can serve as foundation only to a treatise of pure mechanics. He bases the explanation (...) on the principle that all planets gravitate reciprocally toward each other (...). But this supposition is arbitrary as it has not been proven; the demonstration that depends on it can therefore only be mechanics.

In order to make an *opus* as perfect as possible, M. Newton has only to give us a Physics as exact as his Mechanics. He will give it when he substitutes true motions for those that he has supposed.¹⁶²

By aligning the *Principia* with the science of mechanics, Régis was not only relegating its import to an inferior science in the Aristotelian tradition, that is to say, to a subordinate science consisting in the application of mathematical results to natural phenomena without enquiring into the nature or cause of those phenomena. But more importantly, he was obliquely regretting a latent return to

¹⁶¹ Halley, Edmond. (1687) "Review of the *Principia*", *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London*, Vol. 16, (1686-1687), pp. 291-297. As quoted in Rigaud, 1838, Apendix XXI: 71, 76.

¹⁶² Régis, Pierre-Sylvain, "Review of the *Principia*" *Journal des Sçavans*, August 02, 1688, p. 153 ff. As quoted in Koyré, 1965: 115.

the Scholastic and Aristotelian natural philosophy, supposedly superseded by the nascent modern science, as other critics, like Leibniz, would explicitly declare.

For instance, it was felt that in asking why ‘all bodies gravitate toward each of the planets’ the answer would be, because of the gravity force. But this answer would be inadmissible for a thorough Cartesian like Régis, and by extension for any strict Cartesian mechanical philosopher. This is the reason why the reviewer branded this notion as an arbitrary, unproven and supposed hypothesis. In order to be sanctioned as ‘a physics’, and in consequence to raise it to the rank of natural philosophy, Newton was expected, by his detractors, to declare the very nature or cause of the central concept of his masterpiece.

The unexplained gravitational attraction among bodies was seen by its opponents, in due course, as a backwards step towards occult qualities and substantial forms, both of which were seen as characteristic of the Aristotelian tradition of scholasticism and of Renaissance natural philosophers, which the emerging worldview, broadly known as mechanical philosophy,¹⁶³ was concerned to abolish.

Indeed, the mechanical philosophy as developed mainly by Descartes and his followers, tackled the analysis of the workings of nature by means of the principles of shape, size and motion, thus intending the banishment of any trait of occult qualities in natural philosophy. The rationale behind the disapproval of this way of philosophising emphasised three aspects regarded as problematic. Firstly, forms and occult qualities were unnecessary in so far as they were thought to offer only verbal accounts with no real physical underpinning; secondly, they were considered to lack clarity and, indeed, for some critics to be completely unintelligible. Newton’s gravity was judged precisely, along this line of criticism, notwithstanding the undeniably powerful mathematical treatment throughout the *Principia*.¹⁶⁴

Despite the fact that by postulating an unknown (and perhaps an unknowable) force operating at a distance among bodies Newton seemed to have been contravening the principles of scientific explanation established by Continental mechanical philosophers, he was by no means a marginal figure of the scientific revolution. Quite the opposite, and to tell the truth, Newton’s fellow countrymen—as can be inferred from Halley’s review—did not have any problem at all in accepting what for the strict mechanical philosophers, the Cartesians, was plainly unacceptable’. So therefore, the crux of the divergence in a broad sense between Continental and British parties of the dispute on the nature of gravity force lay in their epistemological and ontological attitudes towards what constitutes science and upon what grounds it is based. If this précis is clear, then its examination is called for.

Most of the narratives about the emergence of modern science tend to emphasise the change of attitudes towards what amounts to scientific explanation, and in this vein, it is affirmed that the

¹⁶³ On the multifarious ways to understand ‘mechanism’, see Garber, 2008; Maglo, 2007; McGuire, 1972.

¹⁶⁴ In respect of this, Julian Barbur has observed: “It is ironic that the establishment in the *Principia* of the correct principles of dynamics passed almost without comment –an earth-shaking event if ever there was one, yet it aroused remarkably little interest compared with what was seen as the pernicious reintroduction of Aristotelian occult qualities” (Barbur, 2001, p. 677).

prevailing Aristotelian natural philosophy became precarious because of its defective way of explaining the workings of nature, when subjected to the new demands of intelligibility. Thus, substantial forms and real qualities, the backbones of Aristotelian and scholastic natural philosophy, were discarded.

As alternatives, the mechanical philosophy developed the principles of size, shape and motion, and the various arrangements of matter, in order to replace the discredited way of explanations by means of forms and qualities –thus purportedly surpassing the deficiencies of scholasticism– and to institute a new standard of intelligibility in natural philosophy. Notwithstanding such a *desideratum* for clearness and comprehensibility, the mechanical philosophy with its stress in explaining everything only in terms of matter and contact action, and disallowing inexplicable qualities, was found beset with serious problems regarding the demand for the causal explanation of natural phenomena, especially with regard to the phenomenon of transferring motion from one moving body to another. Eventually, explanations *à la* Descartes came to be regarded as imaginative hypotheses as unexplainable as the rejected qualities of the Aristotelians.

Newton's philosophy of nature, which in addition to matter and motion introduced the concept of force as the causal principle of motion and rest,¹⁶⁵ successfully could give a sound theory about natural phenomena, by relying on the evidence offered by observation, and by expressing the results in the mathematical language of natural laws.

In these terms the issue of intelligibility could be situated as the central notion around which the debate over gravity force was focused, and by way of a clarification of its different meanings, one can discern more appropriately the problem of the ontological causation of gravity force.

3.1. Substantial forms and Occult qualities

At the basis of the Aristotelian theory of scientific knowledge (*episteme*, or *scientia*) lay the notion of causal explanation. Thus, as stated in the authoritative passage from *Posterior Analytics*, perfect science is acquired when “we know that the cause from which the fact results is the cause of that fact, and that the fact cannot be otherwise.”¹⁶⁶ Along these lines, any enquiry eventually would lead to science provided the causes involved in the subject matter under investigation are firmly grasped. The opening words of Aristotle's *Physics* develop this idea more fully by affirming from the outset that natural philosophy is required to follow this kind of analysis.

Knowledge and scientific knowledge, in every inquiry where there are principles or causes or elements, comes from the grasp of these things. For we think we know a thing when we grasp its primary causes and its first principles and we are down to its elements. It is evident,

¹⁶⁵ Newton, 1668; Westfall, 1971.

¹⁶⁶ Aristotle, 1960: 29. See also Aristotle *Posterior Analytics* I. 13, 78a 22; I.2, 71b 9-11; *Physics* II.3, 194b 17-19.

then, that in the science of nature too the primary task must be to settle the things which concern the principles.¹⁶⁷

In order to explain nature as a whole, Aristotle developed an ontology of nature based upon the principles of *prime matter*, *form* and *deprivation*. Prime matter being regarded as the undifferentiated substance which in lacking of any feature cannot be perceived as different or distinct, in the Peripatetic jargon it is pure potentiality. In the act of being actualised, this prime matter, becoming thus an entity with general distinctive features, is operated on by the *form* which furnishes matter with the discernible features that make it what it is within the category of species. Viewed in this light, forms are active principles which, by informing the deprived prime matter, endow the entities with their particular features, confer the nature or essence to it, and are causally responsible for the change effected in the substance. A second type of form, the so called accidental, typifies the entities as particularly distinguishable among others.

This metaphysics of substance in Aristotle is complemented by the allied theory of elements (fire, air, water, and earth) and their respective primary qualities (heat, cold, moisture, and dryness), for purposes of explanation of physical phenomena. Based on this schema, Aristotelian natural philosophy was able to account for the workings of nature by means of the combination, loss, increase and communication of forms and qualities among substances.

Later scholastics introduced three new qualities to this framework, namely, motivity, lightness and heaviness, all of them encompassed by the rubric “real qualities”. This was intended to reinforce the explanatory strength of the Aristotelian schema. In this fashion, a typical Aristotelian explanation of an entity was to be articulated by the conceptual arrangement between its substantial form or essence and the inherent real qualities in it. The phenomena of gravity, for instance, was explained by stating that matter tends downward to the Earth and thus to the centre of the world since it is heavy and it is heavy because of its quality of heaviness.¹⁶⁸

The Aristotelian and scholastic scheme of causal explanation, though reshaped and adapted to fit with the new philosophical perspectives of schools and universities during the Middle Ages, basically remained the same in its structure, and it reflected how nature should be understood properly from the metaphysical standpoint, as well as it determined the authoritative method of elucidation in scientific knowledge.

Now, with the advent of the seventeenth century, natural philosophers embarked on a searching scrutiny of the Aristotelian worldview of physical reality, placing special emphasis on aspects like what amounts to a sufficient and satisfactory explanation, the ontological basis which supports the tenets of matter and form, as well as qualities, and the role of experience. Examinations of this type and their ensuing criticisms were a commonplace during Aristotle’s time and throughout the Middle Ages, but they became even more prolific during the Renaissance and the

¹⁶⁷ Aristotle, *Physics*, Book I, (184a 10-b14). The passage is taken from Robert Bollon as translated in his “Aristotle’s Method in Natural Science: *Physics I*”, included in *Aristotle’s Physics. A Collection of Essays*, Judson, Lindsay (ed.), Oxford, Clarendon Press, 2003, pp. 1 – 29, on p. 2.

¹⁶⁸ See Bodnár and Pellegrin, 2006; Ariew & Gabbey, 1988; Wallace, 1988; Nadler, 1988; Boas, 1952; Henry, 2000.

beginnings of modern science, when rivals of the Aristotelian tradition emerged with fresh approaches to nature, mostly taken from ancient philosophers but with new lines of reasoning. The result of these appraisals rendered as a final judgement that such an approach to nature was in need of replacement by a more sound natural philosophy.¹⁶⁹

With respect to what constitutes a satisfactory explanation, following a principle like Okcham's razor according to which entities should not be multiplied beyond necessity, explanations couched in terms of substantial forms were regarded as too specific and particular, thus multiplying the explanatory entities which form the basis for the account of phenomena.¹⁷⁰ Moreover, accounting for phenomena like, for instance, the colour red because of its red-ness, or for a heavy body in terms of its heavy-ness is, according to Boyle, to give an instance, "so groundless and so unintelligible, or so nugatory, or so impertinent to the subject, or at least so insufficient for the purpose it is alleged for." In other words, the *modus operandi* remained unexplained by appealing to substantial forms and occult qualities. In a similar vein Leibniz wrote:

The consideration of these forms serves no purpose in the details of physics and must not be used to explain particular phenomena. That is where the Scholastics failed, as did the physicians of the past who followed their example, believing that they could account for the properties of bodies by talking about forms and qualities without taking the trouble to examine their manner of operation. It is as if they were content to say that a clock has a quality of clockness derived from its form without considering in what all of this consists.

A second aspect criticised was the implicit anthropomorphism in the usage of substantial forms to give an explanation for the essence of the entity purported to explain. Thus, for instance, Hobbes not only considered the use of forms and real qualities "none at all but empty words," but additionally pointed out at the mentioned underlying characteristic. Taking as an example the fall of a body to the earth, he poked some fun at the notion of natural place, and so if it was desired "to know why some kind of bodies sink naturally downwards toward the earth (...) the Schools will tell you, out of Aristotle (...) that the bodies that sink" do so because they seek their natural place and "the center of the earth is the place of rest and conservation for heavy things, and therefore they endeavour to be there", in which case this is "as if stones and metals had a desire, or could discern the place they would be at, as man does; or loved rest, as man does not; or that a piece of glass were less safe in the window than falling into the street." Pascal also called attention to this propensity of projecting Man's nature onto the natural world; according to him, in so doing, "we taint [nature's entities] with our own qualities, and stamp our composite being on all the simple things we contemplate."

¹⁶⁹ Criticisms to Aristotelian philosophy are wide and complex. In pint of fact, they are traceable back to Aristotle's own time, not to mention Humanist and Renaissance philosophies which had as a common target Aristotle and his teachings. Here I focus on the problem of explanation and the development of a new ontology of nature. For a survey of such criticisms see Menn, 1988. See also Grant, 1987

¹⁷⁰ See Nadler, 1988: 519 where he enlists about one hundred (!) qualities taking Clemens Timpler's *Physica, seu philosophia naturalis* as illustration.

It should be also noted here that while natural philosophers generally agreed in accepting God as the background against which supernatural phenomena are effected causally, invoking spiritual and preternatural entities to account for the workings of the physical world was sharply slated. A case in point is Francis Bacon who harshly criticised the Pythagoreans for planting “a monstrous imagination” in declaring that “the world was one entire perfect living creature.” In this fashion, Apollonius of Tyana, following Pythagoras –Bacon continues– was able to elucidate the phenomenon of the ebbing and flowing of the sea by virtue of this form of vitalism, asserting that it was due to the “respiration of the world, drawing in water breath, and putting it forth again.” By offering such accounts and similar ones like the *spiritus mundi*, Bacon contended, this sort of scholastic philosophers “might build upon it what they would.” He even took further his criticisms as to include philosophers of the Hermetic tradition. In this way, later naturalists like Paracelsus, he writes, “stayed not here; but went further” and maintained an ontological analogy between the macrocosm (the universe) and microcosm (the man). Upon this premise nature could be commanded. For Bacon, “with these vast and bottomless follies men have been (in part) entertained.”¹⁷¹

Besides focusing on the redundant character of forms and real qualities, their almost limitless complexity and their anthropomorphism, the criticisms to Aristotelian schemata of explanation also highlighted a particular feature of that way of explicating natural phenomena, namely, the recourse to forms and qualities, which was considered as a refuge of ignorance, by which it was meant the lack of intelligibility. In this vein, Boyle asserted that “substantial forms are some of them such as I confess I cannot reconcile my reason to”, and when applied to the analysis of nature their use is almost ineffectual. In a similar manner, Locke stated that in the search for the precise meaning of substantial forms philosophers “were led yet farther out of the way, by having their minds set upon fruitless inquiries after substantial forms, wholly unintelligible, and whereof we have scarce so much as any obscure or confused conception in general.” Finally, consider Bacon’s condemnation of the use of notions like hidden properties, specific virtues and so forth, typical of “the slothful manner of men” which are no more than “shifts of ignorance.”¹⁷²

Statements like these abound throughout the Renaissance and early seventeenth century. In point of fact, a devalued appreciation for Aristotelianism from the pen of its detractors was brought into play to prefigure a new conceptual framework for a proper explanation in natural philosophy, and such a proper explanation was developed along lines of the so-called mechanical philosophy.

Though it is not possible to portray the mechanical philosophy as an unvarying doctrine given the multifarious sources from which it took shape –like the mathematical and theoretical tradition of Archimedes’s mechanics, the practical and technical of Heron of Alexandria, the atomism of

¹⁷¹ Boyle, 1991; Leibniz, 1970; Hobbes, 1651 *Leviathan, or the Matter, Forme, & Power of a Common-wealth Ecclesiasticall and Civill*, London, printed for Andrew Crooke, at the Green Dragon in St. Pauls Church-yard. P. 424. Blaise Pascal. (2004) *Pensées*, Ariew, Roger (ed. and trans.), Cambridge, Hackett Publishing Company. p. 63. Bacon, 1857: 640, 641.

¹⁷² Boyle, 1991; Locke, *An Essay concerning Human Understanding* 3.6.10; Bacon, Works, 1886, vol. II, p. 355)

Democritus, Epicurus and Leucippus, and the voluntarism and nominalism of the Middle Ages—some elements that stand as characteristic to its approach to nature can be discerned, however.

Firstly, its aim was directed at the minimising and clarifying of the ontological constituents of physical reality in order to outperform the scholastic and Renaissance forms and qualities, and to make this emergent natural philosophy an intelligible one. In this sense, the mainstream theories of matter conceived nature as composed of atoms or corpuscles whose differences in size, shape, motion and their diverse arrangements and rearrangements could account for all natural phenomena. Here it is worth mentioning in passing, that by regarding the world as a machine the fundamental dichotomy in Aristotelian natural philosophy between natural and unnatural, or artificial, is dissipated.

Secondly, its principles were established in accordance with the functioning of mechanical artefacts in order to be more easily discernible;¹⁷³ in this way the metaphor of nature as a huge machine was more often than not invoked as a means to denote a system amenable to mathematical treatment, and this picture of the world was utilised to explain the workings of nature at the microscopic level by analogy to the macroscopic one.¹⁷⁴ As Steven Shapin observed, “just as the spectacular late sixteenth-century clock in the cathedral at Strasbourg used mechanical parts and movements to mimic the complex motions of the (geocentric) cosmos, so Boyle, Descartes, and other mechanical philosophers recommended the clock metaphor as a philosophically legitimate way of understanding how the natural world was put together and how it functioned.”¹⁷⁵

And thirdly, the properties and behaviour of things were causally explained as a result of the array of matter and motion taking place in void spaces (Gassendi, Newton) or in a plenum (Descartes, Leibniz, Huygens).

Upon the principles of matter and motion, the mechanical philosophy established a new standard of intelligibility and developed a new framework for allowable scientific explanations. Robert Boyle, who baptised this philosophy as mechanical, summarised in his *About the excellency and grounds of the mechanical hypothesis* (1674) the requirements of this new approach to nature that should satisfy the conditions that (1) “there cannot be *fewer* principles than the two grand ones of Mechanical philosophy” namely matter and motion, nor cannot be (2) “any principles more

¹⁷³ This relationship between mechanics and the mechanical philosophy has been highlighted by Bertoloni Meli in a recent book asserting that “a key feature of the mechanical philosophy was the miniaturization of machines. Descartes claimed that the only difference between artificial and natural bodies was one of size. In artifacts made by craftsmen the machines are large and visible, whereas in nature they are small and often invisible, but the motion of a clock is in principle no different from the growth of a tree from a seed to the production of fruits and more seeds. [...] In this sense the mechanical philosophy resembled not only atomism but also the approach originating in antiquity and so thoroughly pursued by dal Monte, Galileo, and other contemporary mathematicians of trying to uncover macroscopic masked levers operating in other machines [...]. In a similar but far more radical fashion, the mechanical philosophy aimed at uncovering different types of machines, often microscopic ones, in the folds of and behind natural phenomena, enabling the investigator to explain how and at the same time why they occurred.” (Bertoloni Meli, 2006: 138) Bertoloni Meli, Domenico. (2006) *Thinking with Objects. The Transformation of Mechanics in the Seventeenth Century*, Baltimore, The Johns Hopkins University Press. On the relationship between mechanics and mechanical philosophy, see Garber, Daniel. (2002) “Descartes, Mechanics, and the Mechanical Philosophy”, *Midwest Studies in Philosophy*, 26, pp. 185-204; and Bennett, J. A. (1986) “The Mechanics’ Philosophy and the Mechanical Philosophy,” *History of Science* 24, pp. 1-28.

¹⁷⁴ See Dear, 1995: 151-153.

¹⁷⁵ Shapin, 1996: 134.

primary” than these, (3) “neither can there be any physical principles more *simple* than matter and motion, neither of them being resolvable into any things whereof it may be truly, or so much as tolerably, said to be compounded.” In this fashion, he continued, “men do so easily understand one another’s meaning”, inasmuch as “when they talk of *local motion, rest, bigness, shape, order, situation, and contexture* of material substances, (...) these principles do afford such clear accounts of those things that are rightly deduced from them only.” For Boyle, notions like “soul of the world”, “universal spirit” or “plastic power” of Hermetic and Neoplatonic roots, as well as substantial forms and real qualities of Aristotelians, failed in offering the means and the manner whereby natural phenomena are produced.

By contrast, the mechanical philosophy, according to Boyle’s approach, could comply with the requisites of ‘intelligibleness or clearness’ and to account for nature in such a manner that other philosophies could be embraced into this scheme. In fact, “the mechanical principles are so universal and therefore applicable to so many things,” observes Boyle, that “they are rather fitted to *include*, than necessitated to *exclude*, any other hypothesis that is founded in nature.” Because of its simplicity and comprehensiveness Boyle adhered to the mechanical philosophy which he considered as a unifying and the best hypothesis to analyse the workings of nature; indeed, “such hypotheses, if prudently considered by a skilful and moderate person who is rather disposed to unite sects than multiply them, will be found, as far as they have truth in them, to be either legitimately (though perhaps not immediately) deducible from the mechanical principles, or fairly reconcilable to them”.

Boyle’s conception of mechanical philosophy amply represents some of the major tasks and features of the new worldview of mechanism with respect to what amounts to a proper scientific explanation: perspicuity, verisimilitude, factualness, consistence, economy and simplicity are distinguished epistemological values shared by the majority of adherents to this approach to nature.¹⁷⁶ Additionally, such a mechanist stance was minimalist in so far as it aimed to explain the largest part of phenomena through a few principles and, as it was in Boyle’s case, it was more reductionist than essentialist. Pierre Gassendi, a champion of this new philosophy of nature and as wholehearted as Descartes, expressed the fundamentals of the mechanism in such a manner that it fairly and squarely could be considered the credo of mechanical philosophy. Thus, in his *Syntagma*

¹⁷⁶ Boyle, 1991: 141, 140, 145. Boyle’s demands for the best way of explaining nature are found in a MS entitled “Notes on a good and an excellent Hypothesis”. There he characterized the new approach to causal explanation along the lines of the mechanical philosophy. As for what constitutes a good hypothesis, he established the following six features: “(1) That it be Intelligible. (2) That it Contain nothing Impossible or manifestly False. (3) That it Suppose not any thing that is either Unintelligible, Impossible or Absurd. (4) That it be Consistent with it self. (5) That it be fit & Sufficient to Explicate the *Phaenomena*, especially the Chief. (6) That it be at least Consistent with the rest of the *Phaenomena* it particularly relates to, & do not Contradict any other known *Phaenomena* of Nature, or manifest Physical Truth.” With regard to what makes a hypothesis excellent, he determined theses conditions: “(1) That it be not Precarious, but have sufficient Grounds in the nature of the Thing it self, or at lest be well recommended by some Auxiliary Proofs. (2) That it be the Simplest of all the Good ones we are able to frame, at lest Containing nothing that is Superfluous or Impertinent. (3) That it be the only Hypothesis that Can explicate the *Phaenomena*, or at lest that does explicate them so well. (4) That it enable a skilfull Naturalist to Foretell Future *Phaenomena*, by their Congruity or Incongruity to it: and especially the Events of such Expts as are aptly devisd to Examine it; as Things tht ought or ought not to be Consequent to it.” Boyle, 1991, p. 119.

philosophicum he wrote: “there is no effect without a cause; no cause acts without motion; nothing acts on distant things except through itself or an organ or connection or transmission; nothing moves unless it is touched, whether directly or through an organ or through another body.”¹⁷⁷

The nature of the mechanical philosophy gave rise to the ensuing endeavours to carry out experimental analyses of nature and its subsequent mathematisation. Experimental inasmuch as nature could be couched in terms of atoms of diverse shapes, arrangements and motions, and mathematical to the extent that it could be measured and quantified with accuracy. Along the lines of such a mathematisation, the physical world lends itself to a precise, unbiased and universal determination. Understood in terms of numbers and figures, on one side, and forces on the other, the divide between nature as it was perceived subjectively and as it was conceived as a mathematical assembly, that is to say objectively, was blurred. In this sense the grounds for physico-mathematics were disposed. This picture of mechanism, in its full scale, can be appreciated in Descartes’s programme for natural philosophy. So, in order to round off the background against which the criticisms to Newton’s gravity were articulated, it is suitable to dwell for a while upon Descartes’s natural philosophy.

As is well known, Descartes’s project was to build, upon an entirely new ground, a philosophical system to replace the prevailing Aristotelian-Scholastic one.¹⁷⁸ The development of this project can be traced back to 1628 when in the *Rules for the Direction of the Mind* he sought to establish a new methodological way of enquiry, in all fields of knowledge, on the bases of clear and distinct ideas, taking as a model the geometrical method of analysis and synthesis.¹⁷⁹ This work was left unfinished when he undertook the task of developing his physics in *The World, or Treatise on Light* (1633) in which, as he wrote to Mersenne on November 13 of 1629, he had “decided to explain all the phenomena of nature, that is to say, the whole of physics.”¹⁸⁰

¹⁷⁷ Cassendi, *Syntagma philosophicum*, vol. I, p. 450, as quoted in Osler, 2001, p. 430.

¹⁷⁸ The introductory remarks in the *Meditations on First Philosophy* are revealing on this point. There, he wrote: “It is some years now since I realized how many false opinions I had accepted as true from childhood onwards, and that, whatever I had since built on such shaky foundations, could only be highly doubtful. Hence I saw that at some stage in my life the whole structure would have to be utterly demolished, and that I should have to begin again from the bottom up if I wished to construct something lasting and unshakeable in the sciences.” (Descartes, 2008: 13) See Des Chene, 2008.

¹⁷⁹ See Descartes’s *Rules for the Direction of the Mind*, Rules I, II, III, IV and XII. In the first Rule, it is established that the objective of any enquiry is to be directed towards the pronouncement of solid and truthful judgements; the second one asserts the characteristics of validity for knowledge claims, namely they must be certain and unquestionable (or, as in the *Meditations*, clear and distinct); the third one defines the procedure whereby such claims are obtained, that is, induction (analysis) and deduction (synthesis); in the fourth rule Descartes develops the genealogy of this method of analysis and synthesis which articulates the investigations in the mathematical field and which he extrapolates to all possible objects of knowledge under the name of *mathesis universalis*; rule twelfth deals with Cartesian psychology of knowledge.

¹⁸⁰ Descartes, 1991, vol 3: 7. Due to the commendation of Galileo, in the wake of the *Dialogue Concerning Two Chief World Systems* (1632), Descartes decided not to publish any word about this ambitious project, since those ‘thoughts which some will find satisfying and with which others will have no cause to disagree’ were based upon the Copernican thesis of heliocentrism, the very reason for Galileo’s troubles with the Church. Thus, by the end of November of 1633, he notified his decision to Mersenne: “I took the trouble to inquire in Leiden and Amsterdam whether Galileo’s *World System* was available, for I thought I had heard that it was published in Italy last year. I was told that it had indeed been

Next, he composed the *Discourse on the Method of Correctly Conducting One's Reason and Seeking Truth in the Sciences* (1637) which he presented as an introductory essay to some examples of his achievements in optics, meteorology and geometry which he saw as fruits of the method that he had been perfecting since the time of the *Rules*.

A further progress in his project was the treatment of God's existence and the distinction of body and soul in the *Meditations on First Philosophy* (1641) where he begins with the task of the possibility of knowledge upon a secure and immovable basis. This metaphysical treatise, as he informed his friend Mersenne, "contain[s] all the foundations of [his] physics." But immediately he asked for secrecy, "for that might make it harder for supporters of Aristotle to approve them", and it was Descartes's desire "that readers will gradually get used to [his] principles, and recognize their truth, before they notice that they destroy the principles of Aristotle."¹⁸¹

The physics that Descartes was mentioning to his French correspondent saw light in 1644 under the title *Principia Philosophiae (Principles of Philosophy)*. Already in 1641, he had announced that he had "resolved to spend [as much time as possible] in writing [his] philosophy in an order which will make it easy to teach"¹⁸² The *Principles* are divided in four parts. Part one is concerning the metaphysical bases of his physics, entitled "The Principles of Human Knowledge", and the remaining three parts are devoted to "The Principles of Material Things", "The Visible World", and "The Earth" (Parts II, III, and IV, respectively). The last step towards the completion of his project was a treatise which had as subject matter the interaction of body and soul (the passions) in the ambit morality, ethics and political philosophy, known as the *Passions of the Soul* (published in 1648). Most of the material contained in this work was stimulated by the correspondence between Descartes and the Princess Elisabeth of Bohemia.

Descartes's dissatisfaction with the prevailing natural philosophy is in the line of the current criticisms to scholastic natural philosophy. Already in the *Rules for the Direction of the Mind* (1628) one finds a first attack on Aristotelian notions like that of motion which he judged as obscure, when compared to his epistemological imperatives. Regarding motion he expressed ironically that those who used to define it along the lines of Aristotle, "would seem to be using magic words, which have an occult power that exceeds the grasp of the human mind", and continued asserting that "thus they declare motion, a thing completely familiar to everyone, to be *actum entis in potentia, prout est in potentia*." Astounded by this enigmatic definition he asked "is there anyone who understands

published but that all the copies had immediately been burnt at Rome, and that Galileo had been convicted and fined. I was so astonished at this that I almost decided to burn all my papers or at least to let no one see them. For I could not imagine that he—an Italian and, as I understand, in the good graces of the Pope—could have been made a criminal for any other reason than that he tried, as he no doubt did, to establish that the earth moves. I know that some Cardinals had already censured this view, but I thought I had heard it said that all the same it was being taught publicly even in Rome. I must admit that if the view is false, so too are the entire foundations of my philosophy, for it can be demonstrated from them quite clearly. And it is so closely interwoven in every part of my treatise that I could not remove it without rendering the whole work defective. But for all the world I did not want to publish a discourse in which a single word could be found that the Church would have disapproved of." (Descartes, 1991, vol 3: 40-41.)

¹⁸¹ Descartes, 1991, vol 3: 173.

¹⁸² Descartes, 1991, vol 3: 172.

these words”,¹⁸³ and in *The World, or Treatise on Light* (1633) the incomprehensibility of this notion is the object of his criticisms as well.¹⁸⁴

The crux of Descartes’s strictures against explanatory schemata, like the Aristotelian and those of the same kind, have as nucleus the difficulty of understanding –when not entirely unintelligible– their key concepts. Furthermore, viewed from the standpoint of their usefulness, such concepts are, as far as Descartes is concerned, to a large degree dispensable.¹⁸⁵ In his opinion, Aristotelian learning consists in obscure verbal descriptions of no use when aimed at clarification and discovery; additionally, in practical matters, such terminology is vacuous. For instance, defending his new philosophy against a scholastic champion of Aristotelian teachings, the Dutch Calvinist theologian and professor of theology at Utrecht, Gisbertus Voetius,¹⁸⁶ Descartes expressed his reservations about this way of philosophising in a letter dated from 1643:

The ordinary philosophy which is taught in the schools and universities is (...) merely a collection of opinions that are for the most part doubtful, as is shown by the continual debates in which they are thrown back and forth. They are quite useless, moreover, as long experience has shown to us; for no one has ever succeeded in deriving any practical benefit from ‘prime matter’, ‘substantial forms’, ‘occult qualities’, and the like. So, it is quite irrational for those who have learnt such opinions, which they themselves confess to be uncertain, to condemn others who are trying to discover more certain ones.¹⁸⁷

A further reason to reject substantial forms is that by their use no explanation at all about the nature of things is obtained. In a letter addressed to Régis, Descartes focuses his critical comments about the Aristotelian natural philosophy on the thorny issue of causation. Substantial

¹⁸³ Descartes, 1958: 66. In this context Descartes criticises this definition on the basis of its redundant character. In fact, lines above this quotation it is stated that “often the learned have a way of being so clever that they have contrived to blind themselves even to those things which are in themselves evident and of which the rustic is never ignorant. This is what happens when they set themselves to explain things which are in themselves evident by something yet more evident.” *Ibid.*

¹⁸⁴ In this vein, writing against Aristotelians, he declared that “they themselves admit that the nature of their motion is very little understood. And trying to make it more intelligible, they have still not been able to explain it more clearly than in these terms: *Motus est actus entis in potentia, prout in potentia est*. These terms are so obscure to me that I am compelled to leave them in Latin because I cannot interpret them. (And in fact the words ‘motion is the act of a being which is in potency, in so far as it is in potency’ are no clearer for being in the vernacular.) (Descartes, 2004: 26)

¹⁸⁵ In a letter to Régis (January, 1642) Descartes adopted this stance, but in addition to epistemological reasons, he offered to his follower a practical reason: to avoid disputes with theologians. In “my *Meteorology*, I said quite expressly that I did not at all reject or deny them, but simply found them unnecessary in setting out my explanations.” (Descartes, 1991: 205)

¹⁸⁶ The controversy with Voetius is interesting inasmuch as it represents the tension between theology and philosophy about the proper domain to deal with the relationship God and nature. As a matter of fact, Voetius considered the mechanical philosophy of Descartes as a menace to theology, mainly in matters of God and his dominion over the universe. On this controversy, see Gaukroger, 1995: 352-361; Clarke [Desmond], 2006: 218-245.

¹⁸⁷ Descartes, 1991: 221. In an earlier letter to Morin he had asserted the unknown nature of forms: “I know that you will say that the form of the clock is only an artificial form, while the form of the sun is natural and substantial; but I reply that this distinction concerns only the cause of these forms, and not at all their nature; or that the substantial form of the sun, in so far as it differs from the qualities to be found in its matter, is an altogether philosophical entity which is unknown to me.” (*Ibid.*: 122)

forms and qualities should be understood and are to be understandable in order to make manifest the phenomena they purport to explain, but on account of their intrinsic unintelligibility they fail to do that. By contradistinction, the privileged viewpoint of geometrical reasoning offered to Descartes not only the clarity he demanded in knowledge claims, but also the possibility to mathematise those phenomena under investigation. In Descartes's view, substantial forms

were introduced by philosophers solely to account for the proper actions of natural things, of which they were supposed to be the principles and bases (...). But no natural action at all can be explained by these substantial forms, since their defenders admit that they are occult and that they do not understand them themselves. If they say that some action proceeds from a substantial form, it is as if they said that it proceeds from something they do not understand; which explains nothing. So, these forms are not to be introduced to explain the causes of natural actions. Essential forms explained in our fashion, on the other hand, give manifest and mathematical reasons for natural actions.¹⁸⁸

In opposition to Aristotelian natural philosophy, Descartes's programme for natural philosophy had as main objective to deal with natural phenomena mathematically. It is contrasting indeed given the fact that for Aristotle mathematics dealt with abstractions and had no place regarding the analysis of nature (specifically in physics), which had to be treated causally, that is to say, to account for the nature of things in terms of their causes, if it aimed at being a proper science, as has been mentioned above. Additionally, his agenda can be best valued in the line of the emerging 'physico-mathematics' understood as the task of analysing the phenomena of nature by means of mathematical methods including the discernment of natures and causes of phenomena.¹⁸⁹

As a matter of fact, he declared in the *Principles of Philosophy* (Part II, art. 64) that he does "not accept or desire any other principle in Physics than in Geometry or abstract Mathematics, because all the phenomena of nature may be explained by their means, and sure demonstration can be given of them."¹⁹⁰ In spite of this attempt at the reduction of physics to mathematical treatment, as he also expressed it to Mersenne,¹⁹¹ Descartes's main works in proper physics like *The World* and the *Principles of Philosophy* (1644) lack any quantitative/numerical exposition of physical phenomena and problems.

If, on the one hand, from this standpoint Descartes's physics can be judged as a mathematical physics without mathematics, it is indeed, on the other hand, a physics with

¹⁸⁸ Descartes, 1991: 208-209.

¹⁸⁹ See Dear, 1995: 151-179.

¹⁹⁰ Descartes, 1967: 269.

¹⁹¹ "I would think I knew nothing in physics if I could say only how things could be, without demonstrating that they could not be otherwise. This is perfectly possible once one has reduced physics to the laws of mathematics. I think I can do it for the small area to which my knowledge extends. But I did not do it in my Essays, because I did not want to present my principles there, and I do not yet see anything to persuade me to present them in future." (Descartes, 1991: 145)

mathesis,¹⁹² that is to say, an inferential system of nature from its geometrical conception. *Mathesis*, according to Descartes's standpoint—and as Van de Pitte has remarked—should be understood “as a science of necessary relations: a purified (nonmathematical) ‘algebra,’ offering a general procedure by which simple elements can be ordered and brought to necessary connections by means of deduction. This usage is exactly appropriate to the term *mathesis*, since a grasp of order and necessary relations is precisely what makes the process of learning possible.”¹⁹³

In the mentioned works Descartes developed his physics consistent with his epistemological rules of clarity and distinction and with the methodological guidance of geometrical thinking. But these articulatory principles of research eventually would render his very physics problematic.

In *The World* Descartes characterised the universe as a “perfectly solid body, which uniformly fills the entire length, breadth, and depth”¹⁹⁴ of space. Here it is important to consider that, by conceiving the essence of matter in a geometrical way, he banished Aristotelian forms and qualities from natural philosophy; and in making extension the foremost attribute of matter, he sought to reveal its legitimate and real substrate. Thus, instead of supposing the scholastic substance of prime matter—unintelligible for Descartes—he emphasises the knowledge of substances by their attributes or properties. Indeed, “there is always one principal property of substance”, we are told in the *Principles of Philosophy* (Part I, art. 53), “which constitutes its nature and essence, and to which all other properties are referred.” In the case of matter, accordingly, “extension in length, breadth, and depth constitutes the nature of corporeal substance.”¹⁹⁵

Some important outcomes of Descartes's identification of matter with extension, which could be considered as a reification of geometry, emerge for his natural philosophy. Firstly, there is the denial of vacuum. In the *Principles* he rejects it in so far as he conceives that a nothingness, or what is the same, a void, could not have a substance at all—otherwise, according to Descartes, that would be a *contradictio in adjecto*—, and space itself in being three-dimensional constitutes a substance, matter. Another reason to not admit the void comes from its ordinary or common usage. Given the inextricableness of matter and extension, it is not to be understood that “a place or space in which there is absolutely nothing” constitutes a void, “but only a place in which there are none of those things we expected to find there” for it “contains created matter and self-existent substance.” In order to rectify this prejudice, it should be realised that “two bodies must touch when there is nothing between them, because it is manifestly contradictory for these two bodies to be apart from one another, or that there should be a distance between them, and yet that this distance

¹⁹² See, Descartes's *Rules for the Direction of the Mind*, Rule IV. On *mathesis universalis* in Descartes see Van de Pitte, 1991.

¹⁹³ Van de Pitte, 1991: 394 (Check!). For Descartes and the programme of a mathematical physics through his correspondence see Garber, 2000.

¹⁹⁴ Descartes, 2004: 22.

¹⁹⁵ Descartes, 2000: 244-245. In Part II, art. 4, the identification of matter with extension is stated straightforwardly in the following terms: “the nature of matter, or body in its universal aspect, does not consist in its being hard, or heavy, or colored, or affecting our senses in some other way, but solely in its being something extended in length, breadth, and depth.” (Descartes, 2000: 254)

should be nothing; for distance is a mode of extension, and without extended substance it cannot therefore exist.”¹⁹⁶

Secondly, from his conceptualisation of matter in terms of extension, the elimination of atoms derives as well. At this point Descartes target is not Aristotelian philosophy in itself but atomism, that of Epicurus, Democritus and Lucretius, and its revival of the seventeenth century.¹⁹⁷ The indefinite or infinite, to be precise, divisibility of the parts of matter is a logical consequence of its extended nature. Due to the rationalist and geometrical conception of material substance, it is possible “in thought to divide [any portion of matter] into two or more parts.” As for its divisibility *in actu* it is attributed to God. In fact, “though God had rendered the particle so small that it was beyond the power of any creature to divide it, he could not deprive himself of his power of division, because it is absolutely impossible that he should lessen his own omnipotence.”¹⁹⁸ Finally, as a corollary of the elimination of vacuum it becomes pretty clear the rejection of action at a distance as well.

With reference to the ‘other properties’ of matter stated in the *Principles* (Part II, art. 53), those which will form his explanatory basis to account for natural phenomena, they are clarified by means of their shape, size, motion, and the “arrangement of its parts” which take the place of the four Aristotelian elements of heat, cold, moistness, and dryness, all of which are “in need of explanation”¹⁹⁹ according to Descartes.

Descartes does not posit four elements like Aristotle, but only three. As for the first one, fire, he imagines “its parts to be much smaller and to move much more quickly than any of the parts of other bodies. Or rather, so that I will not have to allow any void in nature, I do not attribute [to this element] parts having any determinate shape or size”, this element is capable of acquiring all sorts of contours and dimensions in order “to accommodate themselves to the shape of the places they enter”, to legitimise the rejection of vacuum. The second element, called air, is thought as “very subtle fluid in comparison with the third, but compared with the first we need to attribute some size and shape to each of its parts and to imagine them as more or less round and joined together like grains of sand or dust.” Regarding the last and third element, earth, its parts are characterised “to be proportionately larger than and more slowly moving than those of the second, as those of the second are in comparison to those of the first.”²⁰⁰

The speculative geometrical characterisation of the constituents of nature in *The World* is uncomplicatedly stated as real in the *Principles* where he openly declares that the ruling principles of his physics are those of geometry and mathematics, which explain all natural phenomena.

As for the laws of physics (or laws of nature) themselves, in *The World* Descartes posits three. The first law states the conservation of motion, unless it is diverted by impact or collision; the second declares that the total amount of motion in the universe is conserved and it is diversely redistributed

¹⁹⁶ Descartes, 2000: 259-260. See Descartes’s *Principles of Philosophy*, arts. 16, 17, 18.

¹⁹⁷ On the revival of corpuscularism in the seventeenth century, see Wilson, 2008.

¹⁹⁸ Descartes, 2000: 260. Descartes’s *Principles of Philosophy*, art. 20.

¹⁹⁹ Descartes, 2004: 18.

²⁰⁰ Descartes, 2004: 17-18.

by virtue of the collisions among diverse constituent parts of the universe; the last law, the third, affirms the rectilinear character of motion which is the only one that can be determined in an instant, in fact, motion in straight line is the more simple and easy to grasp because of its simple nature.²⁰¹

With regard to the explanation of planetary motion, Descartes based this aspect of his cosmology on the model of an interconnected vortex system. In general terms a vortex is constituted by a number of particles (first or second elements) which entirely fill the space and in which each planet is immersed in that fluid circling matter which carry the planet along with it at variable swiftness depending on the distance from the centre. The balance of planets in their orbits is given by virtue of the interplay of the outward tendency of the planets and the equal inward action exerted by the vortices.²⁰² By means of this construal the phenomenon of terrestrial gravity or heaviness is also explained.²⁰³

The austere ontology developed by Descartes in *The World* starkly contrasts with the Aristotelian and the Renaissance ones. On his account, all activity in the universe can be reduced to the schema of matter in accordance with the epistemological canons taken from the mathematical discourse. In fact, as he maintained in the *Principles*, his physics is based upon the principles of geometry and pure mathematics which are enough to account for all natural phenomena, and provide the means to obtain guaranteed demonstrations. This stance is consistent with his goal to purge nature of Aristotelian substantial forms and Renaissance occult qualities. In so doing the result is an inert world full of passive matter, where the workings of nature are explicated in terms of immediate impact, and the transfer of motion from one bit of moving matter to another bit.²⁰⁴

As regards the reasons to discard both substantial forms and real/occult qualities, they are the same voiced by Descartes's contemporary mechanical philosophers, namely their unintelligibility, redundancy, and lack of explanatory power. Thus, writing to Mersenne in 1643, special emphasis was put on these characteristics by saying "I do not suppose there are in nature

²⁰¹ Descartes postulates these laws as follows: (1) "The first is that each particular part of matter always continues in the same state unless collision with others forces it to change its state." (2) "When one of these bodies pushes another it cannot give the other any motion except by losing as much of its own motion at the same time; nor can it take away any of the other's motion unless its own is increased by the same amount." (3) "When a body is moving, even if its motion most often takes place along a curved line and, as we said above, it can never make any movement that is not in some way circular, nevertheless each of its parts individually tends always to continue moving along a straight line." (Descartes, 2004: 25, 27, 29) See also Descartes, 1967: 267.

²⁰² See Descartes's *Principles of Philosophy*, Part IV, art. 140.

²⁰³ See *Ibid.*, arts. 21-27.

²⁰⁴ In a letter to Morin, boasting about the explanatory advantage of his mechanist system over the Aristotelian one, Descartes highlighted this feature of his natural philosophy: "Compare all their *real qualities*, their *substantial forms*, their *elements* and countless other such things with my single assumption that all bodies are composed of parts. This is something which is visible to the naked eye in many cases and can be proved by countless reasons in others. All that I add to this is that the parts of certain kinds of bodies are of one shape rather than another. This in turn is easy to demonstrate to those who agree that bodies are composed of parts. Compare the deductions I have made from my assumption [...] with what the others have derived from their assumptions on the same topics. I hope this will be enough to convince anyone unbiassed that the effects which I explain have no other causes than the ones from which I have deduced them. (Descartes, 1991: 107)

any *real qualities*, which are attached to substances, like so many little souls to their bodies, and which are separable from them by divine power.” And according to Descartes,

Motion, and all the other modifications of substance which are called *qualities*, have no greater reality, in my view, than is commonly attributed by philosophers to shape, which they call only a *mode* and not a *real quality*. My principal reason for rejecting these real qualities is that I do not see that the human mind has any notion, or particular idea, to conceive them by; so that when we talk about them and assert their existence, we are asserting something we do not conceive and do not ourselves understand. The second reason is that the philosophers posited these real qualities only because they did not think they could otherwise explain all the phenomena of nature; but I find on the contrary that these phenomena are much better explained without them.²⁰⁵

On the basis of clear and distinct ideas Descartes developed his natural philosophy in which geometry plays a central role in the ontological conception of the extended substance, or matter; and kinematics is used to explain all physical change. In harmony with this approach motion is defined as “the transference of one part of matter or one body from the vicinity of those bodies that are in immediate contact with it, and which are regarded as at rest, into the vicinity of others.”²⁰⁶ As is evident from his epistemological principles this definition of motion conforms to Descartes’s task of excluding obscure and unintelligible notions from physics. And so, in explaining his understanding of motion properly speaking he declares it as a mode.²⁰⁷

Descartes’s talk of motion in terms of ‘mode’ instead of ‘substance’ aimed at the demand for clarity and intelligibility.²⁰⁸ Furthermore, in treating motion in this way he avoids conferring upon it a greater reality than those characteristics of bodies which are observable, like size, shape and disposition of parts in matter. As he further observes in the *Principles*:

We can very well conceive how the motion of one body can be caused by that of another, and diversified by the size, shape, and motion of its parts, but we can in no way understand how these same things (namely, size, shape, and motion) can produce something entirely different in nature from themselves, like those substantial forms and real qualities many suppose to exist in bodies.²⁰⁹

²⁰⁵ *Ibid.*: 216.

²⁰⁶ Descartes, 2000: 262.

²⁰⁷ “I say that it is the transference and not either the force or the action that transfers, in order to show that the motion is always in the mobile thing, not in the mover; for these two do not seem to me to be accurately enough distinguished. Further, I understand that it is a mode of the mobile thing and not a substance, just as shape is a mode of the shaped thing, and rest of that which is at rest.” *Ibid.*

²⁰⁸ And yet this was a complicating aspect of his physics which few contemporaries understood. It seems that Descartes wanted to avoid the idea that motion should be regarded as a thing in itself, and so insisted it was only a mode of body, in the same way that shape was. But shapes are not transferred during collisions, and yet motion is. So therefore, what Descartes’s contemporaries wanted to know was how this could happen if motion was only a mode of matter.

²⁰⁹ Descartes, 1991: 268.

Through the laws of motion Descartes aimed to explain the whole natural phenomena including qualities such as colours, odours, sounds and flavours in strict mechanical terms. Besides, he explained the phenomenon of gravity by means of a series of causes related to those laws of motion, which is transferred by contact action from one body to another, thus maintaining his rejection of distant action and preserving his identification of matter with extension. Along these lines in his *The World*, for instance, gravity is accounted for as the effect of the subtle matter surrounding the earth. This force, we are told in this work, “is nothing but, and consists in nothing but, the parts of the small heaven which surround it turning much faster than its own parts about its centre, and tending to move away with greater force from its centre, and as a result pushing the parts of the Earth back toward its centre.”²¹⁰ Notice that the centrifugal tendency of terrestrial bodies, to give an instance, is counteracted by the inward push of the surrounding subtle matter.

Descartes’s mechanical framework for the explanation of gravity (heaviness or weight) involves three basic aspects: the centrifugal impulse of bodies in circular motion, the consideration of such an impulse by means of the quantity of surrounding subtle matter, and the impossibility of vacuum. This being so, it is clear that the successive impacts of minute bodies (subtle matter or ether) upon a heavy body explain the phenomenon of gravity. But this model leaves some questions unanswered when it is confronted with the issue of heaviness, like those related to the size and velocity of the particles which form the first element; the effects derived from the successive impacts of subtle matter on a piece of matter, even more when each impact modifies the state of bodies according to the first law in *The World*; and thirdly, the effects of subtle matter upon large bodies according to their surrounding ether.²¹¹

In keeping with this problem, a scholar has recently asserted that Descartes’s search for causes, and precisely for that of heaviness for the present case, was a substitution of “some causes to other ones” and that in his physics the nature of gravity is reduced to its effects. In this case gravity is accounted for in function of the variation of the place of a body in the revolving subtle matter.²¹²

Such a gambit in Descartes’s approach to the nature of gravity was, one could think, designed in order to avoid many complications that eventually could not be successfully tackled, and foremost of these was that of motion. In effect, how could the phenomenon of a portion of matter imparting motion in a different portion of matter after contact be explained, especially when matter itself was thought inert?

According to Descartes’s own imperatives of clear and distinct ideas, the problem of transference of motion from one body to another was something he could not solve in a satisfactory manner along the lines of his mechanical philosophy, and this was perceived by his contemporaries as a philosophical burden, even more when according to his approach Descartes’s himself did not seem to admit the existence of real force in matter, and I say he did not ‘seem’ to admit such a thing

²¹⁰ Descartes, 2004: 47.

²¹¹ See Descartes 2004, chap 11; 2000, Part IV arts. 23-25.

²¹² See Sophie Roux “Cartesian Mechanics”, in *The Reception of the Galilean Science of Motion in Europe*, C.R. Palmerino and H. Thijssen eds., Dordrecht, Kluwer Academic Publishers, 2004, pp. 25-66, esp. § 3.3.

because the sense in which God is the cause of motion in Descartes natural philosophy is nowadays a matter of ongoing debate among scholars.

The point at issue is how to properly interpret Descartes' ascription of force, if any, to bodies and whether these possesses a real causal agency all the more since the very notion of matter in a Cartesian fashion excludes all sort of activity. This problem of the secondary causation in Descartes's natural philosophy could be analysed in the light of the laws of nature (imposed by God as the primordial underpinning of the workings of nature upon His creation) in addition to the metaphysical standpoints of conservationism, occasionalism, and concurrentism.

According to conservationism, by means of the laws of nature God preserves bodies with their motions whose total amount remains the same in the world, even though that motion might transfer from one body to another, or from one body to several bodies, and so forth. This stance emphasises how 'matter might seem to have its own intrinsic activity, while in fact it is simply passively reacting in accordance with the laws of nature. In this way we are told in *The World* firstly that God "continues to preserve it [matter] thus that there may be many changes in its parts that cannot, it seems to me, properly be attributed to the action of God, because this action never changes, and which I therefore attribute to Nature" and secondly, a few lines later that "while God subsequently preserves [the motions] in the same way He created them, He does not preserve them in the same state."²¹³

At the opposite side we find the stance which maintains that the activity of matter does not exist at all because there is no genuine cause other than God. This occasionalism asserts that the whole workings of nature are brought about by God himself. In *The Meditations* and *The Principles* Descartes adopts this point of view. In effect we find a statement on human existence which is applicable to matter as well: "we can easily recognize that there is no strength in us whereby we may conserve ourselves, but that he who has so much power that he can conserve us out of himself must by so much the greater reason conserve himself, or rather not require to be conserved by any other, for, in short, he is God."²¹⁴ Finally, in a middle position we find the view known as concurrentism according to which both causes (God) and effects (creatures) concur simultaneously in the workings of nature.

Descartes's commitment to conservationism in *The world* and his subsequent change of mind in *The Meditations* and *The Principles* towards a certain kind of occasionalism reveals how problematic it is to discern in his natural philosophy a sound conception of secondary causation in the case of motion, precisely on account of his outright rejection of active principles in matter, and as Voltaire observed, "at this point his philosophy became no more than an ingenious tale",²¹⁵ overwhelmed with problems akin of those of the Aristotelian philosophy he undertook to overtake.²¹⁶

²¹³ Descartes, 2004: 25.

²¹⁴ Descartes, 2000: 236.

²¹⁵ Voltaire, 2007: 50.

²¹⁶ The problem of causality in Descartes's natural philosophy is currently a topic amply analysed. The following works do not pretend to exhaust the present state of scholarship but only to point out some of the main perspectives and scholars. Among many others see, Alan Gabbey. (1980) "Force and Inertia in the Seventeenth Century: Descartes and

Despite the promising outcomes of the mechanical philosophy *à la* Descartes and its far-reaching explanatory potential, it eventually proved to have insurmountable problems on epistemological, philosophical and theological grounds, owing to the rejection of activity in matter. On epistemological grounds because in absence of a conceptualisation of force, the treatment of natural phenomena was restricted to the domain of kinematics where motions are studied without any consideration of the forces causing them.

On philosophical grounds because the rationale for equating intelligibility with truth, based on the principle that by means of pure thought the ultimate reality of nature could be grasped, soon turned out to be impracticable. The scepticism regarding the possibility of finding the true causes behind the phenomena eventually gave rise to the demand for intelligibility, which was the main requirement for a natural philosophical explanation, and not a seemingly rational coherence.²¹⁷

And as for the theological objections, Cartesian mechanical philosophy was deemed a danger to natural religion by its critics, since a picture of the universe as composed of inert matter, diversely reconfigured on account of motion, seemed to place in jeopardy the guiding Providence, thus leading to some form of materialism or deism, or in a more extreme case it could be judged as a promoter of atheism.²¹⁸

One of the early critical responses in England to Cartesian mechanism came from Ralph Cudworth and especially from Henry More, two of the chief representatives of the Cambridge Platonists, who although they approved in general terms the philosophy of Descartes, they thought that such an approach to nature with its denial of void, and especially its rejection of activity in matter, left out God from the world and for that reason they thought Cartesian mechanism was required to be

Newton,” in *Descartes: Philosophy, Mathematics and Physics*, Gaukroger, Stephen (ed.), Sussex, The Harvester Press, pp. 230-320; Andrew Pessin. (2003) “Descartes’s Nomic Concurrentism: Finite Causation and Divine Concurrence”, *Journal of the History of Philosophy*, 41 pp. 25-49; Daniel Garber. (1992) *Descartes’ Metaphysical Physics*, Chicago, University of Chicago Press, Chapter. 9; *Idem*. (2001) “How God Causes Motion: Descartes, Divine Sustenance and Occasionalism”, in. *Descartes Embodied*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, pp. 189-220; Dennis Des Chene. (1996) *Physiologia: Natural Philosophy in Late Aristotelian and Cartesian Thought*, Ithaca, Cornell University Press. Chapter 8; Freddoso, Alfred J. (1991) “God’s General Concurrence with Secondary Causes: Why Conservation is not Enough”, *Philosophical Perspectives*, 5, pp. 553-585; Gary Hatfield. (1979) “Force (God) in Descartes’ Physics”, *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science*, 10, pp. 113-140; Geoffrey Gorham. (2004) “Cartesian Causation: Continuous, Instantaneous, Overdetermined”, *Journal of the History of Philosophy* 42, pp. 389-423; Helen Hattab. (2001) “The Problem of Secondary Causation in Descartes: A Response to Des Chene”, *Perspectives on Science*, 8, pp. 93-118; *Idem* (2007) “Concurrence or Divergence? Reconciling Descartes’s Physics with his Metaphysics”, *Journal of the History of Philosophy*, 45, 1, pp. 49-78; *Idem* (2009) *Descartes on Forms and Mechanisms*, New York, Cambridge University Press; Michael Della Rocca. (1999) “If a Body Meet a Body’: Descartes on Body-Body Causation,” *New Essays on the Rationalists*, Gennaro, Rocco J. and Huenemann, Charles (eds.), Oxford, Oxford University Press, pp. 48-81; Peter Machamer and James E. McGuire (2009) *Descartes’s Changing Mind* Princeton, Princeton University Press. Chapter 4; Tad M. Schmaltz. (2003) “Cartesian causation: body-body interaction, motion, and eternal truths”, *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science*, 34, pp. 737-762; Westfall, Richard S. (1971) *Force in Newton’s Physics: The Science of Dynamics in the Seventeenth Century*, New York, American Elsevier, 1971, Chapter 2.

²¹⁷ Christiaan Huygens, for example, adopted this stance and in fact he developed an account for the cause of gravity based upon Descartes’s principles of ether model labelling it a supposition. See Christiaan Huygens, *Oeuvres complètes de Christiaan Huygens*, 22 vols., The Hague, Martinus Nijhoff, 1888-1950, vol. 19, pp. 631-640. See also Dear, 2006: 24-28.

²¹⁸ See McGuire, 1977; Osler, 2000; Gabbey, 1990; Principe, 1998: 203-213; Crocker, 143-166; Jenkins, 2000.

supplemented with the authorship and spiritual guidance of God by means of active principles in matter so as to prevent harmful consequences for religiosity.

The type of mechanism criticised by Cudworth was mainly the Epicurean, but the way he characterised it fits quite well with that of the Cartesian school.

Moreover, when [mechanical philosophers] further considered the First of these, the material or corporeal principle, they being not able clearly to conceive any thing else in it, besides magnitude, figure, site, and motion or rest, which are all several modes of extended bulk, concluded therefore according to reason, that there was really nothing else existing in bodies without, besides the various complexions and conjugations of those simple elements, that is, nothing but mechanism.

For Cudworth, the conclusion was evident, given that “if this be not Atheism, to derive the original of all things, even of life and mind itself, from dead and stupid matter fortuitously moved, then there can be no such thing at all.”²¹⁹

Now, by means of a combination of Platonism and Neoplatonism the Cambridge Platonists sought to restore the original character of ancient Christianity²²⁰ in which God animates and makes sense of the natural world. Thus, as maintained by Cudworth and More, since matter is a purely passive principle and does not necessarily exist, it must depend on a higher ontological entity that enacts its activity.

If the first principle and original of all things in the universe [writes Cudworth], be thus supposed to be body or matter, devoid of all animality, sense and consciousness, then it must of necessity be either perfectly dead and stupid, and without all manner of life, or else endowed with such a kind of life only, as is by some called plastic spermatical and vegetative, by others the life of nature, or natural perception.

This manner of establishing an ontological and compatible linkage between matter and spirit by means of the coexistence of active principles in matter guarantees not only the divine omniscience but, more importantly, God’s Providence. Indeed, “to assert a God”, Cudworth asserts, “is to derive all things from some one Principle, or to suppose one Perfect Living and Understanding Being, to be the Original of all things, and the Architect of the whole Universe.”²²¹

The ontology of nature developed by Ralph Cudworth and Henry More heavily rest upon a hierarchical system of entities in which God occupies the highest degree of dignity, and through these intermediary entities (diversely named plastic nature, spermatoc logos, hierarchic principles or spirit of nature) subordinated to him, he unfolds his providence. In fact, Cudworth observes, “it is certain, that in the universe things did not thus ascend and mount, or climb up from lower

²¹⁹ Cudworth, 1837: 84, 168.

²²⁰ See, for example, Cudworth, 1837: 63.

²²¹ Cudworth, 1837: 159. See also Cudworth, 1837: 213.

perfection to higher; but, on the contrary, descend and slide down from higher to lower: so that the first original of all things was not the most imperfect, but the most perfect being.”²²²

Inert or stupid matter, as Cudworth and More called it, is by itself utterly incapable to give rise to the variety of phenomena exhibited in nature, and consequently some agent to accomplish such a task is required.²²³ In *The True Intellectual System of the Universe* (1678) Cudworth gives us a complete illustration of this system of God, intermediaries, matter and activity. Due to the completeness of this description, it is worth quoting it at some length.

Wherefore since neither all things are produced fortuitously, or by the unguided mechanism of matter, nor God himself may reasonably be thought to do all things immediately and miraculously; it may well be concluded, that there is a plastic nature under him, which as an inferior and subordinate instrument, doth drudgingly execute that part of his Providence, which consists in the regular and orderly motion of matter; yet so as that there is also besides this, a higher Providence to be acknowledged, which presiding over it, doth often supply the defects of it, and sometimes overrule it; forasmuch as this plastic nature cannot act electively nor with discretion. And by this means the wisdom of God will not be shut up nor concluded wholly within his own breast, but will display it self abroad, and print its stamps and signatures every where throughout the world; so that God, as Plato (after Orpheus) speaks, will be not only the beginning and end, but also the middle of all things, they being as much to be ascribed to his causality, as if himself had done them all immediately, without the concurrent instrumentality of any subordinate natural cause. Notwithstanding which, in this way it will appear also to humane reason, that all things are disposed and ordered by the deity, without any solicitous care or distractious providence.

As for Henry More, in the same vein he also developed a notion like that of Ralph Cudworth, inspired by Plato's *anima mundi* and the Stoic *pneuma* which serves as intermediary agent between matter and God, and which is responsible for the activity in the universe, namely the Spirit of Nature. This spirit, diffused through the space, acts in matter and gives rise to physical phenomena. As defined by More, the spirit of nature is

²²² Cudworth, 1838: 149.

²²³ Thus, Cudworth writes: “Wherefore since neither all things are produced fortuitously, or by the unguided mechanism of matter, nor God himself may reasonably be thought to do all things immediately and miraculously; it may well be concluded, that there is a *plastick nature* under him, which as an inferior and subordinate instrument, doth drudgingly execute that part of his Providence, which consists in the regular and orderly motion of matter; yet so as that there is also besides this, a higher Providence to be acknowledged, which presiding over it, doth often supply the defects of it, and sometimes overrule it; forasmuch as this plastic nature cannot act electively nor with discretion. And by this means the wisdom of God will not be shut up nor concluded wholly within his own breast, but will display it self abroad, and print its stamps and signatures every where throughout the world; so that God, as Plato (after Orpheus) speaks, will be not only the beginning and end, but also the middle of all things, they being as much to be ascribed to his causality, as if himself had done them all immediately, without the concurrent instrumentality of any subordinate natural cause. notwithstanding which, in this way it will appear also to humane reason, that all things are disposed and ordered by the deity, without any solicitous care or distractious providence.” (Cudworth, 1837: 213)

a substance incorporeal, but without sense and animadversion, pervading the whole matter of the Universe, and exercising a plastical power therein according to the sundry predispositions and occasions in the parts it works upon, raising such phaenomena in the World, by directing the parts of the matter and their motion, as cannot be resolved into mere Mechanical powers.²²⁴

Both Cudworth's plastic nature, and More's spirit of nature, safeguard God's sovereignty in the world and put a stop to an eventual materialistic interpretation of mechanism like that of Descartes could lead to, as for instance to consider that God is just required at the moment of putting matter in motion, and from then onwards the transference from one body to another is the way that nature deploys its diverse configurations. Furthermore, by considering these active principles as God's vicarious agents, they secure God's place above the creation and preclude a "monistic materialist system of mechanical philosophy (in which God's role is simply written out)."²²⁵ And finally, his Providence is highlighted in so far as these agents carry out the role of instruments whereby his actions in the world become manifest.

Cudworth's strictures against that type of mechanism that could take away the role of God in the universe, that is to say his Providence, are relevant within the sphere of theology. As a matter of fact, his *True Intellectual System of the Universe* sought to establish a solid foundation for the demonstration of the highest deity, based upon the evidence provided by those ancient philosophers characterised as theists, contrasting them with the atheistic philosophies built upon a materialistic conception of the world attributing an intrinsic life to matter detached from God.

Cudworth and More form part of the complex web of influences upon which Newton developed his intellectual system and especially his outlook on nature. In contrast to the Cartesian mechanical philosophy, Newton conceived of nature both as a passive and an active entity in which distant action takes an outstanding place. As a matter of fact, before the *Principia* (1687), in which the universal gravitation is the main explanatory agent of the workings of the universe, the sources of change in nature were considered from diverse types of active agents both material and quasi material deploying an interaction with matter in a non-mechanical way.²²⁶

The Cambridge Platonists and mainly Cudworth and More have been rightly taken to be important influences upon Newton's view of nature and on his thoughts on the occult and active principles. But notwithstanding this, in point of fact these agents of activity are in no way concepts exclusive or restricted to these men.²²⁷ In fact, besides serving as a way to surmount the problems related to theology and especially about God's providence of the mechanical philosophy that explained natural phenomena merely by means of passive matter moving uniquely in an inertial

²²⁴ More, 1925: 169

²²⁵ Henry, 2008.

²²⁶ As McGuire has observed, "we should not be surprised, therefore, to learn that Newton and many of [Newton's] contemporaries consider gravitational [and distant] action to be a direct manifestation in physical nature of divine power" (1970, pp. 104, 104).

²²⁷ At the best of my knowledge, the main survey of the English natural philosophical tradition accepting and working along the lines of occult qualities and active principles is John Henry's paper of 1986 "Occult qualities and experimental philosophy".

manner, the English mechanical philosophy that accepted unambiguously occult qualities also had a remarkable notable feature: the experimental method. It was a conviction in natural philosophy that this method would provide an unprejudiced and objective explanation of the workings of nature, in contrast to the speculative –and hypothetical– approach of the current Continental one. As underlined by Henry (1986), “the experimentalist could claim that he was revealing only ‘facts’ about the world, which anyone else could confirm by following the same simple procedures. His work was, therefore, largely free from the bias inherent in all efforts to explain the world along preconceived rationalist lines” (p. 338). The experimental method, from the perspective of the English natural philosophers, is closely related and linked to the theological background, the voluntarism, for the acceptance of occult qualities and active principles in matter.

The favourable attitude towards the conception of matter endowed with unexplained –but hopefully explainable– active principles, occult qualities, and forces that operate at a distance is closely related to the empiricist epistemology. This is founded upon the notion that given our limited capacity to acquire a complete knowledge of the innermost constitution of nature. For a number of English natural philosophers, and for Newton in particular, matter is conceived of as endowed with agents which are not capable of being explained by the mainstream of mechanical philosophy, that is to say by particles in motion. Inert matter, along this line of thought, is incapable to give rise to the variety of nature in its workings. So, for example, in the 31st Query of the *Opticks* Newton insisted upon the idea that the conservation and recruitment of motion requires active principles:

The *Vis inertiae* is a passive Principle by which Bodies persist in their Motion or Rest, receive Motion in proportion to the Force impressing it, and resist as much as they are resisted. By this Principle alone there never could have been any Motion in the World. Some other Principle was necessary for putting Bodies into Motion; and now they are in Motion, some other Principle is necessary for conserving the Motion (Newton, 1952, p. 397)

This declared other principle that Newton refers to is the occult cause, that is to say, to the latent reason for the behaviour of nature. The problematic aspect here lies in the precise meaning and understanding of the ideas implied in the term occult. The first meaning of occult, the pejorative one used by critics of Newton’s natural philosophy such as Leibniz, is related to that which is unintelligible. Here occult qualities are understood in this sense as properties, virtues or powers that resisted a rational explanation and which could not be provided. The second meaning is related to those qualities which are out of the reach of perception. Contrary to the former approach to the occult, in which rational is defined in a more or less subjective manner, this second view of occult qualities could be termed manifest inasmuch as experience is the source of information regarding the actions of matter. Qualities of the first class are, for instance colours, odours and tastes, whereas to this second class belong the attractive virtue of magnets and the specific virtues of medicines (Millen, 1985). This distinction between unintelligible and insensible qualities is used by Newton. Indeed, again in the 31st Query of the *Opticks* he states this distinction.

To tell us that every Species of Things is endow'd with an occult specific Quality by which it acts and produces manifest Effects, is to tell us nothing: But to derive two or three general Principles of Motion from Phaenomena, and afterwards to tell us how the Properties and Actions of all corporeal Things follow from those manifest Principles, would be a very great step in Philosophy, though the Causes of those Principles were not yet discover'd (pp. 401-402)

To the evidence obtained from the observation and experimentation Newton's epistemology it is conferred primacy over the speculative Cartesian causal hypothesis. Now, in order to have a more complete picture of Newton's natural philosophy, and more specifically of the causation of gravity force, it is required to look more closely to his clarification of the nature of universal attraction in his magnum opus, the *Principia*.

4. Newton's ontology of mathematical entities and the causation of gravity force

The fact that Newton developed an ontology of force along with a mathematical treatment of physics has always remained a problematic issue for both historians and philosophers of science. This state of affairs has created a divide among Newtonian scholars between those who privilege the accounts for gravity force from the methodological and conceptual standpoint, and those who favour the contextual circumstances –i.e., historical and cultural– within which Newton developed his mathematical physics.

Thus, in general terms, conceptualist analyses tend to confer a paramount importance to the logical and methodological structure of Newton's *Principia* in matters such as the cogency of mathematical statements, the systematization of mathematical results and the strength of the proofs. Concepts such as attraction, gravity and forces, for instance, are analysed as purely mathematical concepts devoid of any causal implications and are regarded, on the contrary, strictly as the core of the broad mathematical construal out of which the *Principia* is made. In this way, Newton is freed from the constraints imposed by the need to discourse about the very nature of gravity force. By talking of bodies under the attractive forces –as we are told from the conceptual viewpoint– Newton is making use of terms for the sake of convenience given his audience, that is to say, mathematical readers.²²⁸ Likewise, when considering the nature of gravity force, in a similar vein, conceptualist scholars are inclined to stress Newton's agnosticism towards the issue of the cause of gravity force, thus implying some underlying positivism in his natural philosophy. This line of analysis tends to downplay Newton's commitments to the ontology of gravity force.

On the other hand, contextualist scholars put special emphasis upon the underlying set of specific views on mathematics that Newton adhered to, and the traditions behind them, as well as the improvements and / or innovations he produced in his *Principia* according to this outlook. Furthermore, they also focus their accounts for the causation of gravity force by highlighting the philosophical foundations upon which the diverse communities of natural philosophers understood the ultimate goals of their researches and how they were to be achieved. As is well known, this is precisely the case with regard to the reception of Newton's theory of universal attraction by his critics, and what amounts to a causal explanation in physics is the very rationale behind the debate on the nature of gravity force. Along the lines of the contextualist inquiries into the provenance and vindication of Newton's inclusion and usage of a notion such as action at a distance, which seemed to be at odds with the current epistemological scheme of continental

²²⁸ Cf. Section XI, Bk. 1, Cohen, 1980, p. 73.

mechanism, the issue at stake has been approached by means of understanding Newton's alchemical studies and their relationship to the development of key concepts in the *Principia* such as attraction, repulsion, force and gravitation. Or, from his metaphysics of nature, key concepts in Newton's physics such as absolute space and absolute time as well as gravitation are explicated by means of his insight into the nature of the divine providence. Such a metaphysics, founded upon a voluntaristic theology, makes sense of Newton's involvement in the clarification of the causation of gravity force. This line of interpretation harmonises Newton's mathematical physics and coheres his natural philosophy with the framework of British natural philosophy.

In spite of this state of affairs, Newton's philosophy of mathematics, and especially his ontology of mathematical entities, has remained largely unexplored in both sides of scholarship when the nature of gravity force is analysed. The purpose in this chapter is precisely to undertake an analysis of Newton's ontology of gravity force by means of the examination of his ontology of mathematical entities, as deployed in the *Principia*, to show that along the lines of Newton's own philosophy of mathematics and his practice it is possible to account for his understanding of the ontological causation of gravity force. To do so, first I will sketch some of the most influential interpretations regarding Newton's attitude and understanding towards the causation of gravity within his natural-philosophical researches and the allied problem of the action at a distance. Secondly, the ontology of mathematical entities in the *Principia* will be expounded in order to discern the way that gravity force could be grasped ontologically in the framework of Newton's masterwork. Finally, against this background, the scopes and limits of both conceptualist and contextualist analyses will be considered. This is aimed at offering a new perspective of analysis to such a protracted problem as the causation of gravity force.

4.1. Mechanism and Geometry in the *Principia*

"Newton's style", I. Bernard Cohen's unit of analysis of Newton's mathematical procedures in the *Principia* and its success, is well known. According to Cohen, it is due to this approach that Newton was able to make his original contributions to mathematics, like his theory of limits and the geometry of conic sections; to dynamics in basic concepts such as mass, momentum and force; and in the systematization of the principles of dynamics by means of the postulation of the three laws of motion.²²⁹

The Newtonian style, in accordance with Cohen, consists of a series of mathematical idealisations of physical reality from which it is possible to draw mathematical conclusions regarding the workings of nature. Moreover, these series of (mathematical) idealisations are to be understood as gradual approximations, through successive stages, to the natural world by means of a continuous increase of new elements added to the initial (mathematical) conditions in order to attain a close resemblance to the (physical) reality.

Analysed from this standpoint, Newton's way of proceeding in the *Principia* departs from the comparative simplicity of mathematical abstraction to the complexity of a physico-

²²⁹ Cohen, 1980 especially, and *idem.*, 1982, 1995, 1999, 2003; Cohen & Smith, 2003, *inter alia*.

mathematical system analogous to that of nature (Cohen, 1980, p. 55, *passim*). In reference to this approach, “even the Newtonian system of the world, when said by Newton (in the final editions of the *Principia*) to be based on ‘phenomena’, is in fact based also to some degree on truths of mathematical systems or idealizations of nature that are seen to be approximate to but not identical equivalents of the conditions of the external world” (p. 65). Furthermore, given this way of dealing with the workings of nature, Cohen asserts, Newton does not have to deal with the conundrum of the very nature of gravity (pp. 26, 64, 75),²³⁰ notwithstanding his assertion in the concluding General scholium added to the second edition of the *Principia* (1713) that gravity “really exists” (*revera existat*) and acts according to the laws established in that work (Newton, 1999, p. 943).

Cohen’s exposition of Newton’s style is best illustrated in his *The Newtonian revolution* (1980), and it is restated time and again along his further studies on Newton’s methodology in the *Principia*. This style is constituted by three phases or stages.

In the first phase Newton starts with “a set of assumed physical entities and physical conditions that are simpler than those of nature, and which can be transferred from the world of physical nature to the domain of mathematics” (p. 62). An example of such a reduction is the system of planetary motion to a one-body system. Cohen justifies the fact of speaking of “one-body system”, *inter alia*, to the degree that it represents a simplified and idealised scheme composed of two entities, namely, a single body *and* a central force field around which that body orbits. Thus, for example, in the *Principia*, Book 1, sect. 2, Prop. 2, Th. 2, we read:

Every body that moves in some curved line described in a plane and, by a radius drawn to a point, either unmoving or moving uniformly forward with a rectilinear motion, describes areas around that point proportional to the times, is urged by a centripetal force tending toward that same point (Newton, 1999, p. 446).

And in Book 1, sect. 2, Prop. 6, Th. 6:

If in a nonresisting space a body revolves in any orbit about an immobile center and describes any just-nascent arc in a minimally small time, and if the sagitta of the arc is understood to be drawn so as to bisect the chord and, when produced, to pass through the

²³⁰ As Cohen remarked in the preceding *Guide* to his (and Whitman’s) translation of Newton’s *Principia*, “There is no way of telling whether the Newtonian style of initially dealing with the subject on a mathematical rather than a physical plane was only a subterfuge to avoid criticism or a sincere expression of methodological principle. But, from Newton’s point of view, this style enabled him to develop the laws of the action of a gravity-like force in a mathematical analogue of the world of nature without having to be concerned with whether or not gravity exists” (1999, p. 278). Elsewhere, Cohen extended this idea of Newton’s methodology in the following terms: “Newton himself was clear about levels of mathematical and physical discourse; the distinction between them and their relations to each other constitute, in fact, the essential ingredient of the Newtonian style. And yet the most acute students of Newton’s thought seem either not to have believed what Newton wrote on these topics or to have believed that Newton did not mean what he said (or did not say what he believed)” (Cohen, 1982, p. 23).

center of forces, the centripetal force in the middle of the arc will be as the sagitta directly and as the time twice [i.e., as the square of the time] inversely (Newton, 1999, p. 453).²³¹

The second stage of Newton's analysis of natural phenomena in the *Principia*, following Cohen's line of analysis, is characterised by the comparison and contrast of the mathematical constructs with physical systems, by means of the data provided by experiments and observations. Thus, the one-body system is shown "to be a necessary and sufficient condition for the law of areas, which had been found to be a phenomenologically verifiable relation in the external astronomical world" (Cohen, 1980, p. 63). Consequently, through the successive complexity added to the initial system, the subsequent comparisons and contrasts with the natural world, and the required modification of the system of the first stage –Newton successively adds further entities, concepts, or conditions to the imaginatively constructed system (*Ibid.*)–, there appears a second phase. In this manner, a complexity added to the original one-body system consists in adding new conditions such as a system of two interacting bodies, and next a system constituted by several bodies. Subsequent to this new level of complexity, and in due course, there will be the examination of the previous systems taking into consideration bodies of finite sizes and diverse shapes. At this level of sophistication, phase two is not dealing anymore with mass points but with bodies quite akin to those exhibited in nature. The final part of this phase is the introduction into the system of resisting mediums taken as environments where bodies carry out their motions.

The last phase of Newton's style has to do with the application of "the aggregate of mathematical principles to natural philosophy" (p. 64). That is to say, the previous mathematical constructions of Books 1 and 2 are compared *vis à vis* to the natural world, and its main characteristic is the close resemblance that the mathematical model reveals when weighed against the realities of the external world. In sum, phase three is the explanation of the system of the world (the very title of Book 3) "by means of propositions demonstrated mathematically in books 1 and 2" (Newton, 1999, p. 382). In this manner, the method and the title itself of Newton's masterwork, namely the *Mathematical principles of natural philosophy*, are justified.

Broadly speaking, phase one could be said to predominate throughout Book 1 of the *Principia* where Newton develops a broad-spectrum theory of motions under centripetal forces. In the second phase, throughout Book 2, he accomplishes a study of motion under resisting media. And the third phase throughout Book 3, the theory of universal gravitation and its effects is undertaken, by which the soundness of the mathematical style of analysis of the workings of nature is corroborated. It is only at this last stage, phase three, that Newton would have to be committed to an inquiry into the cause of the central concept of his tour de force. As Cohen states, "it is only

²³¹ In point of fact, in the *Principia* Newton does not use an expression like this nor a similar one, except when it is applied at least to two-bodies. But as Cohen himself observes, throughout his book he has opted for "the expression 'one-body system, even though strictly speaking a single body cannot of and by itself constitute a 'system'. But I know of no other way to indicate simply the kinship between such a 'one-body system' and a two-body system, three-body system, many-body system. Furthermore, the Newtonian 'one-body system' is a 'system' to the extent that it is composed of two entities, even though these are not homologous, as in the case of a system of two bodies: these are a single body (or mass point) and a center of force (Cohen, 1980, p. 302, n. 3).

after this stage, not earlier, that Newton himself would have to yield to the demand for investigation into the nature, cause, or mode of operation of such forces as he had used in accounting for the motions of terrestrial bodies, the planets, their moons, our moon, the comets, the tides, and various other phenomena” (Cohen, 1980, p. 64, emphasis added).

Along the lines of Cohen’s description of Newton’s style, the crux of the methodology deployed in the *Principia* lies in the uninterrupted interplay between mathematical theory and observation and / or experimentation, from which the original mathematical model progressively becomes more and more complex and simultaneously improved and enhanced, and at the same time it becomes more similar, parallel or analogous to the physical reality. Judith V. Grabiner, commenting on Cohen’s account of Newton’s style, has pointed out that, “what makes this [Cohen’s] approach nontrivial is the sophistication of the mathematics and the repeated improvement of the process. It is sophisticated mathematics, not only a series of experiments or observations, that links a mathematically describable law to a set of causal conditions” (Grabiner, 2004, p. 842).

Now, when Cohen asserts that ‘after this stage’ (phase three) there is the consequential need for the inquiry into the cause or mode of operation of gravity force, it is not clear, but he may be obliquely referring to the last paragraph of the General Scholium added to the second edition of the *Principia* (1713) where Newton alludes to certain electric and elastic spirit as a means to explicate the causal mechanism of gravitation.²³²

This is a pressing question, all the more since, as Cohen himself declares, the investigation for the cause(s) of force(s) “went beyond the requirements of the Newtonian style, however, at least in so far as the *Principia* is concerned” (*Ibid.*). In keeping with this statement, and given the fact that all the “known physical explanations [for the mechanical cause of gravity] failed” (Cohen, 1980, p. 110; 1987, p. 588), with regard to accounting for the philosophical problem of the type of entity which produces the centripetal force, Cohen believes Newton is correct to show himself as an agnostic with regard to the cause of gravity force. According to Cohen, Newton rightly adopts a proto-positivistic stance towards the causation of force (Cohen, 1980, pp. 75, 113, 130).²³³ Thus,

²³² This renowned entity added to the second edition of the *Principia* is powerful in so far as its explanatory scope. In point of fact, the attraction among bodies, the phenomenon of light and the functioning of the nervous system are phenomena attributed to the action of this subtle spirit. On this new entity, Newton wrote: “A few things could now be added concerning a certain very subtle spirit pervading gross bodies and lying hidden in them; by its force and actions, the particles of bodies attract one another at very small distances and cohere when distances, repelling as well as attracting neighboring corpuscles; and light is emitted, reflected, refracted, inflected, and heats bodies; and all sensation is excited, and the limbs of animals move at command of the will, namely, by the vibrations of this spirit being propagated through the solid fibers of the nerves from the external organs of the senses to the brain and from the brain into the muscles” (Newton, 1999, p. 944). Albeit not being mentioned as the agent that could explain the attraction among bodies, by virtue of the explanatory power of this subtle spirit it could be deduced that it also would explain the phenomenon of gravity as well. See, Hawes (1968)

²³³ Take as illustration the following declarations made by Cohen. “The great advantage of the three-phase Newtonian procedure is that it separates the basic questions of science into separate categories. In phase one Newton could explore the consequences of any condition or conditions that he found mathematically interesting or stimulating-and he could do so just as his inspiration drove him, without being blocked or deflected by questions whether certain forces or conditions of resistance do or do not ever occur in nature (or might or might not do so). We have seen, in the case of Huygens, how inhibiting it was not to have this freedom. (...) Having shown in phase three that gravity exists and serves

Cohen writes: “even in the general scholium with which the later editions of the *Principia* conclude, Newton insisted that his gravitational dynamics and his system of the world could be accepted even though he had said nothing about the cause of gravity. But he did then express his personal conviction that gravity ‘really exists’” (p. 64).²³⁴

Consistent with Cohen’s analysis of the Newtonian style in the *Principia* there is a depiction of Newton as logically and methodologically unconcerned with the cause of gravity force. Logically, because of the very nature of the mathematical research undertaken in the *Principia*, which has as a main feature the progressive approximation of an ideal mathematics to a real physics up to the point of becoming a mathematical system analogous and closely related to the real world. And methodologically, by virtue of the independence of experimental and scientific results with regard to the philosophical discernment and explanations on the origin and mode of action of the causes of forces used in the *Principia*. In this very same line of assessment, Cohen contends, the philosophical question about the nature of gravity is put aside (p. 79). In sum, and from the methodological standpoint, by the Newtonian style Cohen is “implying anything more than a description of the way in which Newton combined two levels of ontology, the mathematical and the experiential” (1982, p. 49). In this way, the hierarchy of causes –mathematical and physical– establishes that the transparency of the former is not to be mingled with –or obscured by– the explanations of the latter (1980, pp. 26, 28). In point of fact, “the elucidation of the properties of universal gravity was distinct from –that is, on a different level from– the search for the cause of gravity” (p. 32).

As is well known, properties of gravity force such as its far-reaching range, its decrease proportional to the square of the distance from bodies, its nullity inside of homogenous spherical bodies, its homogenous action upon bodies which penetrates until the very centre of bodies acted upon, and its proportionality to the mass, in contradistinction to the surface action of mechanical forces of impact, are elucidated and explicated within the domain of mathematical discourse in the *Principia*. And it is proposed in contradistinction to the mechanical means of explanation, precisely because these modes of action are mechanistically inexplicable.²³⁵ And as is also well known, Newton’s multifarious attempts to explain gravity along the lines of mechanical philosophy proved

to account for the phenomena, he declares the validity of his system of the world, even though the cause of gravity remains hidden from us. Newton was never, however, a true positivist, because he himself never gave up the search for the cause of gravity and because he actually believed that such a cause exists and may be found; but he acts like a positivist to the extent that his system is said to be acceptable because it works, even though the cause of universal gravity may be unknown and even if gravity itself cannot be explained” (Cohen, 1980, p. 113). There are some nuances in predicating that Newton is agnostic with respect to the causation of force and that he is a proto-positivistic on this issue. The first predicament is understandable given Newton’s empiricism, but to talk of Newton’s positivistic (or proto-positivistic) epistemology is to set aside his natural philosophy.

²³⁴ I consider that it is hard to find a more suited adjective other than positivist to the Newton pictured by Cohen, especially since as he observes, “we shall see him [Newton] successively attempting to account for gravity by a kind of aethereal shower, by electricity, by a new kind of all-pervading aether of varying density. None of these attempted explanations worked fully and in detail. One reason for their failure is that they are all mechanical models of action, and we know today that gravity cannot be explained mechanically” (Cohen, 1980, pp. 111-112).

²³⁵ For Newton’s attempts to solve the problem of causation of gravity force along the lines of the credo of mechanical philosophy, see *inter alia* Cohen, 1980 pp. 113-116.

to be unsatisfactory in view of experiments and observations, and mathematical analysis (e.g., the ability to reduce a massive gravitating body to a geometrical 'centre of gravity'). Furthermore, the various types of aethers, whether pictured as showers of tiny particles or of a varying density or Cartesian vortices, did not fit with one of the chief characteristics of universal gravity which is its variation inversely as the square of the distances. So therefore, in view of the fact that gravity acts mutually and equally on gravitating bodies obeying the inverse square law, explanations by way of aethers must be rejected (1980, pp. 109-120; 1982, pp. 56-58).²³⁶

In this line of reasoning Cohen appropriately observed that "however much Newton may have cherished the illusion that the force of universal gravity could be reduced to the action of an aethereal matter and motion, the actual contribution of this point of view to the formulation of the principle of universal gravitation and the elaboration of the properties and actions of the force of universal gravity must be adjudged to have been nil" (1982, p. 40), given that it was counterfactual in the light of experiments. As for the "very subtle spirit pervading gross bodies and lying hidden in them" the lack of a "sufficient number of experiments to determine and demonstrate accurately the laws governing the actions of this spirit" was the underlying principle reason for rejecting it as a causal explanation of gravity force (Newton, 1999, p. 943-944).

A difficulty derived from Newton's postulation of universal attraction in the *Principia* is the so-called problem of action at a distance, which is a direct consequence from the dispelling of aethereal mediums as explanatory devices for the gravity force, in view of their incompatibility with phenomena. At this point it is fitted to bear in mind that in distinction from Book 1, where Newton undertakes a general analysis of motion caused by forces and their variation according to the distances from a central force in spaces free of any resistance, in Book 2 a general theory of motion is developed under varied resisting mediums or forces of resistance. As a matter of fact, seven out of the nine sections that comprise Book 2 of the *Principia* are devoted to providing a thorough refutation of the fluid vortices as explicatory means for the orbital motion of planets, and by implication as explanation of the cause of attraction among bodies and universal gravitation. The

²³⁶ Cohen's reconstruction of Newton's reasons to reject the explanation of gravity by means of aether(s) is found summarised in the following passage: "The subject of Newton's belief in an aether is of real importance in assessing the stages toward universal gravitation, because the concept of gravity being caused by an aether does not lead to *universal* gravitation, but even turns out to be in one respect inconsistent with universal gravitation. That is, the explanations of gravity by means of an aether could not account for a gravitational force acting mutually and equally on two gravitating bodies according to the inverse-square law. Newton's suggestion of a "shower" of aethereal particles and his hypothesis of the mid-1670's, in which there would be a density gradient in the aether might supply a plausible mechanism for bodies being "heavy" toward the earth or toward the sun or any other planet, but could not explain why the earth would be just as "heavy" toward an apple as an apple is toward the earth. Furthermore, the supposition that the aether whirls in huge vortices, in the Cartesian manner, may serve to explain a gravitational "endeavour" of bodies in the vortex toward the center, but such an "endeavour" would not then depend on the presence of an actual material body physically located at the center, which could be the seat of that gravitational "endeavour". This is the reason –namely, that the vortex theory did not lead to the concept of a *centripetal* force arising only from an "attracting" *body* or central body– that the vortex theory could not have led to mutual forces acting equally between two bodies" (1980, p. 37).

main thrust of Newton's argument for the rejection of fluid vortices in Book 2 is found summarised in the last paragraph of Section 7, here we read:

And even if air, water, quicksilver, and similar fluids, by some infinite division of their parts, could be subtilized and become infinitely fluid mediums, they would not resist projected balls any the less. For the resistance which is the subject of the preceding propositions arises from the inertia of matter; and the inertia of matter is essential to bodies and is always proportional to the quantity of matter. By the division of the parts of a fluid, the resistance that arises from the tenacity and friction of the parts can indeed be diminished, but the quantity of matter is not diminished by the division of its parts; and since the quantity of matter remains the same, its force of inertia – to which the resistance discussed here is always proportional – remains the same. For the resistance to be diminished, the quantity of matter in the spaces through which bodies move must be diminished. And therefore the celestial spaces, through which the globes of the planets and comets move continually in all directions freely and without any sensible diminution of motion, are devoid of any corporeal fluid, except perhaps the very rarest of vapors and rays of light transmitted through those spaces (Newton, 1999, p. 761).²³⁷

Furthermore, in Section 9 of the same Book 2 the explanation of celestial phenomena by means of vortices is analysed, with the result that they are incompatible with Kepler's area and $3/2$ power rules. In actual fact, the scholium to Proposition 52 clearly shows Newton's confidence in the impracticability of the hypotheses of vortices. Thus, Newton commented: "But if vortices (as is the opinion of some) move more quickly near the center, then more slowly up to a certain limit, then again more quickly near the circumference, certainly neither $3/2$ power nor any other fixed and determinate ratio can hold. It is therefore up to philosophers to see how that phenomenon of the $3/2$ power can be explained by vortices" (Newton, 1999, p. 788).

From the above passages it is hard to avoid reaching the conclusion that Newton, in effect, is asserting the existence of void spaces free of material resistance (all the more since the inertia of fluid vortices generates a resistance proportional to the density of that fluid²³⁸) and the subsequent assertion, by inference, of action at a distance.

Now, Cohen's approach to Newton's methodological procedures in the *Principia* with the special emphasis stressed upon a style which divides the mathematical and the physical domains of research, and with the explicit prominence given to the pruning out of the need to explain gravity's

²³⁷ For the second edition of the *Principia* (1713), Newton reworked entirely Section VII. According to G. E. Smith, "two factors prompted this revision. First, Newton became persuaded, largely from experiments, that his original solution to the efflux problem was erroneous. Second, some initial vertical-fall experiments in water convinced him that his pendulum decay experiments were yielding excessively high values for the resistance forces. (...) In particular, he cut three paragraphs from the General Scholium that drew conclusions from the combination of the results of the pendulum decay experiments and the propositions in the second half of Section 7, especially conclusions about the fluid medium's action on the rear of a moving sphere" (Smith, 2001, p. 299). See also, Smith, 2008.

²³⁸ For an analysis of Book II of the *Principia*, see Smith 2001, where he deals in detail with the manner in which Newton approached the study of fluid resistance consistent with Books I and III.

nature, inevitably leads to a negative answer to the riddle of action at a distance. As a matter of fact, it is hardly surprising that such a positivistic –or proto-positivist– minded Newton that Cohen conceives of, would reject outright the idea of action at a distance implied in the universal attraction. According to Cohen, on this specific subject Newton is not to be seen as stating this idea neither obliquely nor straightforwardly since the investigation undertaken in the *Principia* did not “depend on whether a planet is pushed or pulled toward the center, whether gravitation (...) is even a simple action-at-a-distance” (Cohen, 1980, p. 32).²³⁹

According to this interpretation, detractors of the *Principia* could be construed as if they focused their criticisms precisely on not taking notice of this way of reasoning and proceeding, and in consequence they inferred action at a distance from the denial of contact action typical of the current aethereal explanations of the mechanical philosophy as practiced in the Continent. Such was the case, for instance most notably, with Leibniz and Huygens.

Cohen put forward the problem of action at a distance in the following terms: “in particular, can one make one’s [i.e., Newton’s] peace with attraction, a grasping force that causes bodies to act mutually on one another ‘at a distance’ that may be as great as hundreds of millions of miles?” (p. 69). In order to deal with this issue in the *Principia*, Cohen resorts to the mathematical approach adopted by Newton in order to elaborate his point of view. Firstly, Cohen highlights the caveats that Newton put across the *Principia* where he seems to be emphatic in affirming that his approach is mathematical rather than physical²⁴⁰ (pp. 73-74). Here, once more, one of the main strengths of Newton’s method, according to Cohen, lies in the fact that it “enables him [Newton] to develop the properties of a two-and three-body gravitating system independently of the question as to whether bodies can or do attract one another. Or, it enables him to postpone this question until a later time” (p. 75). And more importantly, in accordance with the unit of analysis of the Newtonian style, by doing this Newton transformed the style of doing natural philosophy in his times “from the physics of the known (...) to the physics of the unknown”. The outstanding advantage of this approach, according to Cohen, was the fact that the introduction of “gravitational forces *that appear to have to act at a distance*” “was a tremendous intellectual leap forward that enabled Newton to transcend the limits of the terrestrial physics of his age and to forge the celestial dynamics of the future” (p. 176, emphasis added).

In the same degree that the Newtonian style freed Newton himself from the constraints of causal explanations in structuring the *Principia*, Cohen maintains, so it was the case with regard to action at a distance. By following the idea suggested by Hooke of considering a central force acting on a planet as responsible for keeping it in its orbit, Newton seized and tackled the problem strictly in mathematical terms, leaving out of the way his vacillating attitude towards the diverse versions of aethers and his apparent disbelief of distant action. As a matter of fact, and notwithstanding Newton’s beliefs, the “Newtonian style enabled him to explore the properties of this kind of force

²³⁹ Similarly, in his paper “Newton’s third law and universal gravity” (1987), Cohen comes back to the arguments expounded in his 1980’s book *The Newtonian revolution. With illustrations of the transformation of scientific ideas*. See Cohen, 1987, pp. 588-589.

²⁴⁰ See the *Principia* Book 1, definition 8; Book 1, section 11 (first paragraph) and scholium. (Newton, 1999, pp. 408, 561 and 588 respectively).

and eventually to discover (...) that universal gravity is useful and even necessary, and that it 'really exists' (...) and acts according to the laws he had set forth" (p. 254).

Passing from the framework of the *Principia* in itself to the succeeding handling of distant action in Newton's natural philosophy in the subsequent years, in the article "Newton's third law and universal gravity" (1987) Cohen dealt with the problem of action at a distance from the perspective of the post *Principia* period. This line of attack describes an embarrassed and troubled Newton, uncertain about the key concept of his *magnum opus*, namely, the universal gravity. In this study, Cohen firstly highlights the difficulties of such a notion with respect to the standard explanations of mechanical philosophy and its principle of elucidation of the behaviour of bodies along the lines of contact action.

From the time of his *Principia* until his death Newton was deeply troubled by the concept he had introduced: a universal gravity. He had been brought up in the "received" philosophy, sometimes known as the "mechanical philosophy," centering around the ideas of Descartes, which held that all explanations in natural philosophy must be couched in terms of what Robert Boyle called "those two grand and most catholick principles of bodies, matter and motion." At first sight it would seem that to these Newton had added a third principle, force. Not only was this a departure from accepted norms, it also introduced a kind of force that was astonishing in its primary characteristics or qualities. For this force had to have the power of extending itself over many hundreds of millions of miles as a kind of grasping entity which could affect huge bodies. For instance, the gravitational force could extend far beyond the visible reaches of the solar system, that is, way out beyond the planet Saturn, to turn a comet around and cause it to return to the visible regions of the neighborhood of the sun (Cohen, 1987, p. 588).

Secondly, Cohen enlists some of the multifarious ways that Newton tried to square up (unsuccessfully, by the way) the notion of universal gravity with the basics of Continental mechanical philosophy:

Newton again and again sought for some explanation of how universal gravity might act. That is, he attempted to reduce universal gravity to the action of something else, a shower of aether particles, electrical effluvia, variations in an all-pervading aether (*Ibid.*).

And finally, he states the clarification and the reason why Newton's efforts eventually rendered ineffective given the particular characteristic of gravity force: its variation inversely proportional to the square of the distance from the bodies, and its reciprocal proportion.

All of these attempted "explanations" or reductions of universal gravity to some accepted kind of mechanism failed –because none could fulfill two major requirements: that the

resultant force vary inversely as the square of the distance and that this force act mutually on every pair of bodies so as to attempt to bring them together (*Ibid.*).

Having presented the reasons and background as well as the fate of Newton's fruitless attempts to fit his natural philosophy of the *Principia* with the canons of Continental mechanism, Cohen rhetorically wonders: "how, then, could Newton have initially been able to consider the properties and actions of a force of 'attraction,' of a type in which he could not fully believe?" (*Ibid.*, pp. 588-589) And next he returns to the ideas and analysis of his *The Newtonian revolution*, and asserts: "in answering this question, I have attempted to systematize Newton's actual procedures and his statements about his procedures into an approach to mathematical natural philosophy which I have called the 'Newtonian style.' All the elements of this way of doing mathematical physics have already been presented in the analysis of Newton's steps toward universal gravity" (p. 589).

In the light of the manner that Cohen conceptualises Newton's embarrassment with the concept of universal gravity and the implicit assertion of the action at a distance, the crux of the problem of conceiving of the attraction between distant bodies did not lay in the conception of bodies attracting and being attracted by other bodies, but from the lack of an underlying mechanistic explanation in the *Principia* to account for such a phenomenon of attraction with the required fulfilment of inverse-square distance variation and the characteristic of being mutual. So, if this is correct, Cohen's judgment according to which "it is well known that by the time of the second edition of the *Principia*, in 1713, Newton publicly acknowledged the difficulty he and his fellow scientists shared in accepting the action-at-a-distance of universal gravity" (p. 588) should be put in a more nuanced and precise perspective.

As a matter of fact, what is at stake is not so much the fact of the acceptance or refusal of the action at a distance in it itself, but the very difficult problem of *discovering* a mechanical means whereby to explain the phenomenon. Additionally, such a means is mandatory to comply with the abovementioned requirements. So, gravity with the unstated assertion of distant action, as maintained by Newton himself, is to be understood as an observable *phenomenon* described in a precise manner along the lines of a mathematical way of reasoning and which, more importantly, permits that both terrestrial and celestial motions be understood, calculated and predicted.

This specific feature of action at a distance within the framework of the *Principia* has been cleverly expressed by Robert Disalle who, from a formalist point of view, avowed that "for Newton, action [at a distance] is defined by the laws of motion, which provide empirical criteria for measuring the action of one thing on another; if the planets and the sun satisfy these criteria in their direct mutual relations, then they are acting on one another" (Disalle, 2004, p. 52). In this manner, Newton was able to assert that "it is enough that gravity really exists and acts according to the laws that we have set forth and is sufficient to explain all the motions of the heavenly bodies and of our sea" (Newton, 1999, p. 943). As indicated by this interpretation, it is possible to attribute an operative connotation to action at a distance by assuming it has a meaning within the mathematical construal developed in the *Principia*, and from which future experiential claims are deduced.

Secondly, Cohen's reiteration of Newton's unsuccessful search for a mechanical model through several types of aethers to account for gravitational attraction is in agreement with his (Cohen's) deep conviction that Newton effectively rejected the idea of action at a distance. Such a conviction, abundantly shared by the most prominent Newtonian scholars, is partly based upon a conceptual reading of the *Principia*, partly supported by the Queries appended to the *Opticks*, and mainly claimed in the wake of Newton's letter to Richard Bentley (Feb. 25, 1693), in which Newton bluntly asserted that "that one body may act upon another at a distance through a vacuum without the mediation of any thing else by or through which their action or force may be conveyed from one to another is to me so great an absurdity that I believe no man who has in philosophical matters any competent faculty of thinking can ever fall into it"

As a rule, this passage has been quoted virtually by each and every single champion of Newton's denial and denunciation of action at a distance. In the next section I will analyse this statement at length within the framework of the letters related to this pronouncement. In the meanwhile, suffice it to say that I am more inclined to date Newton's abandonment of aethereal explications back to late 1670's and specifically to his letter to Robert Boyle. Ever since, when Newton returned to the aethers as a means to explain the workings of nature, it was due to his interest in contrasting those diverse aethereal mediums against the abovementioned characteristics pertaining to universal gravitation. Now, it seems to me that Cohen's determination in stressing Newton's repeated return to the diverse mechanical alternatives is in keeping with his interpretation of the rejection of action at a distance.

As a consequence, for instance, in *The Newtonian revolution*, in addition to quoting the letter to Bentley, he claimed that "the belief that attraction must be caused by a medium between (and even permeating) gross bodies persisted even after the *Principia* had been published" (Cohen, 1980, p. 117). With the purpose of strengthening this idea Cohen also refers to a letter sent to Leibniz in the same year in which Newton proclaimed that "if, meanwhile, someone explains gravity along with all its laws by the action of some subtle matter, (...), I shall be far from objecting" (p. 118). Notwithstanding this, the alleged condescending attitude of Newton towards the subtle matter is dissolved by reading what is omitted in the ellipsis of Cohen's quotation. In actual fact, Newton wrote: "But if, meanwhile, someone explains gravity along with all its laws by the action of some subtle matter, *and shows that the motion of planets and comets will not be disturbed by that matter*, I shall not object" (Newton, 1959-1977, vol. III, p. 287, emphasis added).

This demand for fluid mediums for the observance of the inverse square law and the reciprocity of action among bodies, that is to say, the characteristics of universal gravitation, are situated at the very basis of Newton's supposed willingness to accept the existence of some aethereal medium to explain the functioning of the physical world, but as is clear from Book 2 of the *Principia*, such a medium is a quite far-fetched one. Furthermore, the rejection of all subtle fluid is even more manifest in an early 1700's piece written by Newton on the theory of the moon. In this essay, he wrote:

We have attempted, by applying the theory of gravity to celestial phenomena, not only to investigate the causes of the motions, but also to compute the magnitude of these motions from their causes. And we supplied some examples of this in the motions of the Moon also. For it follows from this that the revolutions of all planets are ruled by gravity, and that not only are solid spheres to be resolved into a fluid medium, *but even this medium is to be rejected* lest it hinder or disturb the celestial motions that depend upon gravity (Newton Correspondence, Vol. 4 p. 3. Emphasis added).

So far, I have just hinted at some of the reasons why Newton's acceptance of action at distance should not be seen as awkward as Cohen's account would seem to imply, leaving for the next section a more detailed analysis of this issue.

The line of analysis that privileges the accounts for gravity force from the conceptual and methodological standpoint has recently received a new enhancement. Effectively, in "Newton and the reality of force" (2007) and in *Newton as philosopher* (2008) –especially chapter three, "Do forces exist?"–, Andrew Janiak has undertaken a new interpretation of the nature of gravity force in the *Principia*. My interest here is focused on his account for the nature of this force and the problem of action at a distance, respectively.

Two of Janiak's goals in *Newton as philosopher* are directed towards, first, a new understanding of the ontology of gravity force, according to which such an ontology is present in Newton's *Principia* when this work is subjected to an anti-metaphysical reading (Janiak, 2008, pp. 13-25); and in addition, when its fundamental concepts are understood in a special technical sense redefined by Janiak, which is basic for his new approach (*Ibid.*, pp. 50-86, *passim*). Secondly, such an interpretation, simultaneously, reinforces the interpretative line of conceptual readings of the *Principia*, according to which Newton rejected the distant action, and deemed it as implausible (*Ibid.*, 58-65). Needless to say, the idea of Newton as rejecting the *actio in distans* finds its main thrust in the celebrated letter to Bentley of 25 February 1693.

This new elucidation is focused on offering a new reading of gravity force and distant action taking as starting point a supposed dilemma Newton was confronted with, regarding these two notions. As a result, universal gravity and action at a distance, according to this scholar, mutually exclude each other from the conceptual point of view. Thus, on the one hand, along the lines of Janiak's account, given that in the *Principia* Newton does not explicate the underlying physical means responsible for the gravity force following the mainstream of the mechanical philosophy, namely the account of natural phenomena by means of contact action of fluid mediums, Newton is constrained to accept the contested *actio in distans* among bodies.

On the other hand, if Newton rejects the action at a distance, he eventually would be constrained to admit that the gravity force is a mere calculating device and, in consequence, to concede that this is not a real force.

This second horn of the dilemma tends to find support in Newton's own well-known pronouncements in the *Principia* where he asserts that his treatment of gravity force forms part of

a strict mathematical analysis of the workings of nature. For instance, explaining the terms he uses to refer to the forces by which bodies approach one another, Newton seems to imply that they are not to be considered as physical terms. Instead of the he warns the reader to consider such a language along the lines of the mathematical speech. Thus, he says in the final paragraph of Definition 8:

I call attractions and impulses accelerative and motive. Moreover, I use interchangeably and indiscriminately words signifying attraction, impulse, or any sort of propensity toward a center, considering these forces not from a physical but only from a mathematical point of view. Therefore, let the reader beware of thinking that by words of this kind I am anywhere defining a species or mode of action or a physical cause or reason, or that I am attributing forces in a true and physical sense to centers (which are mathematical points) if I happen to say that centers attract or that centers have forces (Newton 1999, p. 408).

And in Scholium to Section 11, Book 1, the same idea is repeated:

I use the word “attraction” here in a general sense for any endeavor whatever of bodies to approach one another, whether that endeavor occurs as a result of the action of the bodies either drawn toward one another or acting on one another by means of spirits emitted or whether it arises from the action of aether or of air or of any medium whatsoever whether corporeal or incorporeal in any way impelling toward one another the bodies floating therein. I use the word “impulse” in the same general sense, considering in this treatise not the species of forces and their physical qualities but their quantities and mathematical proportions, as I have explained in the definitions (Newton 1999, p. 588).

But in point of fact, this is at odds with the vigorous statement claimed in the General Scholium where Newton maintains that “it is enough that *gravity really exists* and acts according to the laws that we have set forth and is sufficient to explain all the motions of the heavenly bodies and of our sea” (Newton, 1999, p. 943, emphasis added). This being so, in “Newton and the reality of force” Janiak posits Newton’s dilemma in the following terms:

If Newton contends that gravity is a real force, he must ultimately rely on action at a distance because of his well-known failure to characterize the mechanism underlying gravity. However, if he seeks to avoid distant action, he must admit that gravity is not a real force, and that he has therefore failed to discover the cause of the phenomena his theory associates with gravity (Janiak, 2007, p. 127).

And in his book of 2008, *Newton as philosopher*, this putative quandary is affirmed slightly differently as follows:

Newton's theory treats gravity as if it involves action between extremely distant bodies, such as Jupiter and the sun. If Newton contends that gravity exists, (...) he must be claiming that material bodies act on one another across empty space. However, if he seeks to avoid distant action, he must admit that the force of gravity does not exist, and that he has therefore failed to discover the cause of the phenomena his theory associates with that force, such as the planetary orbits (Janiak, 2008, p. 53).

As is evident from these quotations, and as maintained by Janiak himself, Newton's introduction of forces into the general structure of the *Principia*, and especially the introduction of gravity force, has led him to such an overwhelming impasse in his physics regarding the reality –or ideal character– of force, on one hand, and the attendant acceptance –or rejection– of action at a distance, on the other. Along the lines of this approach, Janiak remarks that “in fact there is no consensus in the scholarly literature regarding even the most basic question concerning the mathematical treatment: does Newton think that forces exist? Does he think in particular that the force of gravity exists?” (Janiak, 2008, p. 50). As an instance of this lack of consensus among scholars, Janiak makes reference to two outstanding historians of science and interpreters of Newton, namely I. Bernard Cohen who is taken as supporting the idea that Newton did not address the question, and Richard S. Westfall who defends the idea that for Newton forces must be considered part of our fundamental ontology.

In order to surmount this dilemma, Janiak proposes to resolve it by means of “reinterpreting Newton's distinction in the *Principia* between what he calls the ‘mathematical’ and the ‘physical’ treatment of force” (Janiak, 2007, pp. 130-131; 2008, p. 57).

In contradistinction to Cohen, who maintains that the mathematical treatment of the gravity force in the *Principia* brackets the inquiry into the physical causation (obliquely adopting an instrumentalist reading of Newton's mathematics in the *Principia*, in as much as they do not intend explanations as to why the workings of nature take place as they do but, instead of that, how they are performed), Janiak's analysis is conveyed to discern the identification of this force as a real one, in as much as it implies a causal relation with some body (2007, p. 127 *passim*; 2008, p. 57 *passim*). What eventually would constitute the main improvement to the traditional reading of Newton as setting aside from the *Principia* the nature of gravity force, and also rejecting action at a distance, consists in the claim that by means of this new approach an interpretation of gravity force as a mere mathematical contrivance is avoided, and on the contrary an ontology for it is provided.

From the point of view of Janiak, as soon as the nature of gravity force is discerned, Newton's rejection of action at a distance is also comprehended. So, along the lines of his construal, “what the mathematical treatment of force leaves for future research is not the discovery of causes, (...) but rather the discovery of the complete physical characterization of the force it has identified” (*Ibid.*). At least, two questions that arise from this statement are, first, how are we to understand the nature (ontology) of gravity force, once Janiak has stated obliquely that it is implicit in the *Principia* (what is left ‘for future research is not the discovery of causes’) detached from a physical depiction? And

related to this one, how are we to understand the expression ‘physical characterization’ in a sense devoid of ontological content?

In order to build up his interpretation, and to answer these questions, Janiak firstly categorises the term force as a ‘technical’ one, “one that can be understood only through his laws of motion, which explicate force generally, and through his definitions, which define such particular items as centripetal force” (Janiak, 2008, p. 58). Then, he exhorts us to grasp its meaning as a common one, linked to the notion of causality, to the extent that “we do not require a definition or technical understanding of causation to understand the *Principia*” (*Ibid.*). It is sufficient for a clear understanding to keep in mind that force, and more specifically impressed force, is a cause of a change in a body’s state of motion.²⁴¹

The second step of Janiak’s account is based upon Newton’s distinct treatment of force between physical, on the one hand, and mathematical, on the other hand. Reinforced by the standard and the very often quoted passages of the *Principia*, where it is maintained that the investigation of natural phenomena are mainly concerned not with “the species of forces and their physical qualities but their quantities and mathematical proportions” (Newton, 1999, p. 588)²⁴², Janiak’s new exposition focuses on the *Principia* as providing a mathematical characterisation of “quantities” of force. This interpretative shift to the treatment of force as a mathematical quantity, in so far as distinct from a property of matter or as an object in itself, is the crux of Janiak’s interpretation, and this is what he considers to be the “hallmark of Newton’s approach”, all the more since the concepts of force, mass, space, time, and motion are constitutive *quantities* of the analysis disclosed in Newton’s masterwork (Janiak, 2008, p. 59).

So, with regard to the technical sense of force, it should be distinguished from two different senses used by Newton himself in the *Principia*. First, the technical senses of some concepts such as those of the Definitions like mass and momentum, for example. Second, the technical understanding of mathematical entities such as absolute space and absolute time, as distinct from vulgar, common and apparent, just as stated in the scholium to the Definitions. Having set up this, Janiak is able to cope with reality of force by declaring that such a reality lies in the fact that a physical quantity which can be measured, and more precisely gravity for the present case, exists. Thus, he announces that, in spite of

any other questions regarding the ontology of force (...) Newton’s mathematical treatment of force indicates how to measure a force by measuring mass and acceleration. This is

²⁴¹ For Janiak, “since Newton never defines ‘cause,’ or various related terms such as ‘action,’ and does not distinguish an ordinary from a more precise conception of causation, he apparently thinks that our ordinary conception is adequate for interpreting the *Principia*” (Janiak, 2008, p. 58).

²⁴² In a similar manner, the final paragraph of Definition 8 reads: “It is in this same sense that I call attractions and impulses accelerative and motive. Moreover, I use interchangeably and indiscriminately words signifying attraction, impulse, or any sort of propensity toward a center, considering these forces not from a physical but only from a mathematical point of view. Therefore, let the reader beware of thinking that by words of this kind I am anywhere defining a species or mode of action or a physical cause or reason, or that I am attributing forces in a true and physical sense to centers (which are mathematical points) if I happen to say that centers attract or that centers have forces” (Newton 1999, p. 408).

essential to Newton's approach. We can think of forces as physical quantities, precisely as the "quantity of matter" –i.e., mass– is a physical quantity. They are physical quantities because they are part of the physical world; and they are part of the physical world because they can be measured by measuring other, obviously physical, quantities. So *my suggestion will be that the mathematical treatment of force measures physical quantities* (p. 60, emphasis added).

Having dealt with the problem of gravity force in this way, that is to say, in asserting that it is a quantity whereby other physical quantities such as masses are measured with respect to distances, Janiak comes to terms with the elucidation and understanding of the term "species" as distinguished from 'quantities'. At this point, the interpretative manoeuvre consists in connoting the common features of gravity as it is discussed in Books 1 and 3 of the *Principia*, in so far as they are distinct from other impressed forces like the magnetic one or those of percussion and pressure. All along this phase, special emphasis is stressed upon the measuring of the different forces, and particularly upon the centripetal force, which is emphasised by Janiak as "essential aspects of a mathematical treatment of force" (p. 62). This is done in order to draw attention to the autonomy concerning the causal and physical investigation as developed in Book 1, and to offer a vindication of Newton's agnosticism concerning the physical causes and sites of forces (although not denying its reality), as Newton himself avers in Definition 8 (Newton, 1999, p. 407).

Thus, in Book 1, where a purely mathematical analysis of the motion of mathematical bodies is undertaken, Newton brackets "the question of whether the force is propagated through a medium, whether it occurs only through impacts between macroscopic bodies, or whether it may involve microscopic particle interactions, etc." (Janiak, 2007, p. 133; 2008, p. 62). But in Book 3, in which it is demonstrated how the phenomena of nature from the principles established in Book 1 are performed, Newton declares in the scholium to Proposition 6 that, "hitherto we have called 'centripetal' that force by which celestial bodies are kept in their orbits. It is now established that this force is gravity, and therefore we shall call it gravity from now on" (Newton, 1999, p. 806).

By calling *gravity* in Book 3 that which in Book 1 was termed *centripetal force*, Newton has taken a step further into the clarification of the term 'species', according to Janiak. As a matter of fact, in accordance with Janiak himself, in Book 3 "we are no longer dealing purely mathematically with a centripetal force, as we were in book I; we are discussing a particular "species" of centripetal force. And this is a crucial component of the physical treatment of gravity". So therefore, "the law that governs gravity *indicates its 'species,'* which indicates, in turn, how gravity differs from other members of the genus, centripetal force, such as magnetism" (2008, p. 63, emphasis added).²⁴³

At this point, from the identification of force as a 'quantity' and the discernment of its species as 'a law', it becomes clear the inference for Janiak that enables him to assert that the gravity law "allows us to measure the force of gravity between two massive bodies by measuring other

²⁴³ See also (Janiak, 2007, p. 145). For an alternative interpretation to this of Janiak, regarding the difference of mathematical and physical treatment of force in the *Principia* –especially between Books 1 and 2–, see Smith, 2002, pp. 150-152.

physical quantities, such as the distance between them”, which means that “this indicates the ‘physical species’ of gravity” (2008, pp. 63-64; 2007, p. 133). This reading of Newton’s methodological procedure in the *Principia* supposedly surpasses the limits of the interpretation of Newton’s core concept as a mere calculating device. As it happens, the very title of ‘mathematical principles’ of ‘natural philosophy’ is justified by virtue of the inclusion of “the stunning claim that the free fall of bodies on earth, the motions of the moon, and the planetary orbits, are all caused by one and the same force, governed by one and the same law” (2008, p. 64). In a concurring manner, such an approach strengthens the line of conceptual analysis developed by conceptualist scholars like Cohen.

Right after the establishment of his account of gravity as a real force, Janiak focuses his analysis on solving the second difficulty of Newton’s dilemma, which is related to his attitude towards the action at a distance, implicit in the gravitational theory of the *Principia*.

By means of the statement according to which gravity really exists, Janiak asserts that Newton is signifying two things. In one sense, the expression means that a great number of natural phenomena have as a common cause this force. This is not to say that Newton has stated the physical cause of gravity. Rather, this is done in order to give good reasons for its usage in the *Principia*, and especially in Book 3. The second meaning is directed to highlight that those multifarious phenomena, explained by way of universal gravity, are articulated simply by virtue of the variables mass and distance (2007, p. 142; 2008, p. 27, 75, 78, 81). This second meaning leads to a third and most important sense of the statement, that ‘gravity really exists’, whereby, we are told, Newton circumvents the acceptance of action at a distance. Thus, in declaring that gravity really exists, but it is not mechanical in its operation, Newton distances himself from the current mechanical philosophy.

For Janiak, this idea is cleared when attention is directed to the statement of the General Scholium where Newton makes a distinction between his approach to gravity force and that of current mechanism of the Continent. Thus, for Newton, gravity force

arises from some cause that penetrates as far as the centers of the sun and the planets without any diminution of its power to act, and that acts not in proportion to the quantity of the *surfaces* of the particles on which it acts (as mechanical causes are wont to do) but in proportion to the quantity of *solid* matter, and whose action is extended everywhere to immense distances, always decreasing as the squares of the distances (Newton, 1999, p. 943, italics in original).

For Janiak’s examination of the issue of distant action in the *Principia* and his ensuing interpretation aimed at avoiding its acceptance on the part of Newton, it is necessary to “rely on an interpretive manoeuvre” (Janiak, 2008, p. 75). According to Janiak, Newton developed a technical meaning of the word ‘mechanical’ implicating with it the rejection of two different –but closely related– senses of this word in the contemporary (Continental) natural philosophy, thus contravening the common

cannon of intelligibility as a consequence. The twofold sense of the word mechanical entails (1) the assertion that no causal modification in the state of motion of a body is possible through the distance, and (2) that such an alteration of the state of motion is admissible only in terms of contact action or impulse. The manoeuvre that Janiak carries out here is based on the supposed refutation by Newton of the second sense of 'mechanical', according to which it is required to postulate some material medium like effluvia, corpuscles, steams or aethers, for instance, in order to connect the causes and the effects of motions in nature, and thus not to go against the first sense which opens the way to the acknowledgment of action at a distance.

Now, given that gravity force is the result of a cause that 'penetrates as far as the centers of the sun and the planets' –quite different from standard mechanical comprehension–, and in contradistinction, it 'acts not in proportion to the quantity of the surfaces but in proportion to the quantity of solid matter', it must be granted "room for local action that involves the penetration of a material body by some other body, such as a material particle, or perhaps by another phenomenon, such as a ray of light" (Janiak, 2008, p. 76). In such a case, local action would not be mechanical in the common acceptance of the word (Descartes, Leibniz or Huygens, for instance). This view of local action is instantiated with the model suggested by Newton in the Query 21 of the *Opticks*.²⁴⁴ The main advantage of this interpretation, Janiak observes, lies, first, in that it "should help to illuminate how Newton can justifiably assert that gravity causes various motions while nonetheless avoiding the invocation of action at a distance" (2008, p. 77; 2007, p. 142). Secondly, viewed from this perspective, "Newton's theory is neutral with respect to the physical cause of gravity" (2008, *Ibid.*; 2007, *ibid*), thus circumventing the impugned distant action, and proving himself right with respect to the accusation of contravening the standard cannon of intelligibility of the mainstream of Continental mechanical philosophy.

As indicated by Janiak, his interpretation represents an advancement in our understanding of Newton's *Principia* in particular and in his natural philosophy in general. Hitherto we can discern two prominent features of his reading regarding the reality of force on the one hand and the conundrum of action at a distance on the other hand.

As for the first one, by relying upon a technical reading (or redefinition) of the mathematical treatment of force, Janiak aims at defending that gravity is a real force in as much as it is relative to the measure of other physical quantities. In addition, the puzzle on the subject of the species of such a force is solved by taking into account that 'the law' of universal gravity itself is what causes natural motions in bodies and is distinct from other species of force like magnetism or electricity, for instance.

As regards the second feature, by relying once again upon a technical reading (or redefinition) of the term 'mechanical', Janiak strives for the disentanglement of the problematic character of action at a distance, and to make sense, within the context of the *Principia*, of Newton's

²⁴⁴ This reference is addressed to Newton's following tentative question: "Is not this Medium much rarer within the dense Bodies of the Sun, Stars, Planets and Comets, than in the empty celestial Spaces between them? And in passing from them to great distances, doth it not grow denser and denser perpetually, and thereby cause the gravity of those great Bodies towards one another, and of their parts towards the Bodies; every Body endeavouring to go from the denser parts of the Medium towards the rarer?" (Newton, 1952, p. 350).

admonition to Bentley (in his correspondence of 1693) on the topic of considering the unmediated action among bodies as an inconceivable philosophical blunder which should not be attributable to him. This is done by reinterpreting Newton's understanding of mechanical cause as one which penetrates into the very centre of bodies acted upon, in contradistinction to the usual contemporary meaning of a mechanical cause, which was a cause acting only upon the surfaces of bodies.

Prior to presenting my comments on Janiak's interpretation, there are furthermore two upshots of his account closely related to the aforementioned which are worthy of being mentioned. The first one is addressed to reinforce Newton's disbelief of distant action, and the second related to the ontology of force.

As for the first one, Janiak observes that, "Newton can justifiably assert that gravity causes various motions while nonetheless avoiding the invocation of action at a distance" (2008, p. 77), when gravity is referred to as a physical quantity that accounts for the workings of nature in a technical mechanical sense. Subsequently, it is underlined that "Newton's theory is neutral with respect to the physical cause of gravity" and "*it is perfectly compatible with the discovery that some type of medium does in fact exist*" (*Ibid.*, emphasis added). This idea is evidenced, in Janiak's view, in a letter that sent Newton to Leibniz in 1693. In this letter, Newton wrote: "But if, meanwhile, someone explains gravity along with all its laws by the action of some subtle matter, and shows that the motion of planets and comets will not be disturbed by that matter, I shall not object" (Newton, 1959-1977, vol. III, p. 286). In contrast to Cohen, who quotes this same passage to highlight Newton's enduring search for a mechanical explanation of gravity force, even after the *Principia* (Cohen, 1980, p. 118), Janiak quotes it to maintain that "Newton thinks that any future characterization of gravity's physical cause must somehow cohere with" that developed in Book 3. But, as Janiak himself recognises, "as Newton knew, no account of gravity's physical cause in this period –including those of Huygens and Leibniz– was remotely capable of accounting for these facts" (Janiak, 2008, p. 78).²⁴⁵

In connection with the physical seat of gravity and the aetherial approach taken by Newton in Query 21 of the *Opticks*, Janiak suggests accounting for this attempt in the same way he has done with regard to the *Principia*, but this time applying the analysis to the repulsive forces of the aetherial particles which eventually could be seen as a hint of action at a distance. Thus, Janiak writes, the "ether may be the physical seat –the "cause"– of gravity, and it may involve repulsive forces among its particles that, in turn, have their own physical seat, perhaps in some other medium" (p. 79). Cognizant of the infinite regress that this claim may seem to involve, Janiak immediately remarks,

²⁴⁵ As it was mentioned in the last section where I dealt with Cohen's account of Newton's conceptual analysis of the ontology of gravity force in the *Principia* –or the lack of it– and the problem of action at a distance, some of the main properties of gravity force are (1) its far-reaching range, (2) its decrease proportional to the square of the distance from bodies, (3) its nullity inside of homogenous spherical bodies, (4) its homogenous action upon bodies which penetrates until the very center of bodies acted upon, and (5) its proportionality to the mass, in contradistinction to the surface action of mechanical means. The description of these features is portrayed by Janiak as follows: "The ether could not be mechanical in Newton's sense, but would have to flow through material bodies, interacting somehow with their masses. Similarly, it would have to exhibit differential density, or some other feature that rendered the distance between masses their salient relation. And it would have to exert only a vanishingly small –perhaps undetectable– resistance to the motions of bodies" (2008, p. 78).

“of course we cannot determine *a priori* where this investigation of forces will lead us, nor where it will stop” (*Ibid.*).

As for the second upshot, the one related to the ontology of force, Janiak seems to decipher it partially based upon his account of gravity as a physical quantity. It should be underscored, in passing, that this is done in order to present a Newton in accordance with the strict –albeit nuanced– mechanistic worldview of the Continent.²⁴⁶ Furthermore, his approach to the ontology of force forms part of Janiak’s purpose to present us a positivistic minded Newton by means of an anti-metaphysical reading of his oeuvre (pp. 13-25). So, against those like Westfall, Henry, Dobbs, and McGuire, for example, who maintain that Newton’s success in his natural endeavours lies precisely in adding to the current ontology of nature the concept of force, Janiak calls into question such a view from the conceptual schema developed in his *Newton as philosopher*.

For the argument, first, it is required to keep in mind the fact that the Newton analysed by Janiak redefines the mechanism of gravity force in so far as a distinction between local action and surface action is made; the first one (that is to say, the technical meaning suggested by Janiak) avoids the unintelligibility of universal attraction viewed from the strict mechanism (p. 81). Secondly, for Janiak, in Newton’s philosophy of nature, “forces can exist without being part of our ontology in the strict mechanist sense” (p. 80). Hence, for Newton “forces exist because they are quantities that can be measured; and indeed, they can be measured by measuring other physical quantities that are perfectly uncontroversial, such as mass and distance” (*Ibid.*). In accordance with this interpretative tactic, forces become unquestionable just because they preserve the same technical status of unquestionable notions like mass and distance which, *a propos*, are quantities as well. What is more, gravity, along these lines, is a technical term which does not represent any addition at all to the austere ontology of shape, size and motion, proper to the mainstream mechanist philosophy of the Continent. In view of this, we are in a position to see Janiak’s solution to the riddle of the ontology of force. Consequently, with regard to this problem he asserts: “hence under certain conditions, the answer to the question –what is the ontology of force? – is simple: a quantity” (p. 82, emphasis added). And more important is the conclusion according to which “Newton made the brilliant move of showing us how to measure certain fundamental quantities without understanding the ontology of those quantities in various senses of the term” (*Ibid.*, emphasis in original).

My remarks on Janiak’s interpretation will be focused, first, on the ontology of gravity force as ‘quantity’. Secondly, I will examine his solution to the problem of action at a distance from the special technical sense of ‘mechanism’. Lastly, the idea according to which Newton did not include force as a constitutive part of his ontology of nature will be discussed.

To begin with, one the first questions that Janiak’s interpretation raises is the one regarding the insight we get into the ontology of gravity force by calling it a quantity. Among other tasks, the elucidation of the ontology of gravity force is one of Janiak’s main goals in *Newton as philosopher*.

²⁴⁶ “Strict mechanism”, as Janiak explains it, rejects “the very idea of forces, arguing that all natural change occurs through impacts among material bodies characterized exclusively by size, shape, and motion (and perhaps solidity, *à la* Locke)” (Janiak, 2008, p. 52).

Accordingly, in the section where he deals with this question (pp. 81-86), we are told that, 'under certain conditions, the answer to the question –*what is the ontology of force?* – is simple: a quantity' (p. 82, emphasis added). On this reading, forces in general owe their existence to the possibility of being measured by means of other undisputed physical quantities (p. 81). Nonetheless, right after this affirmation, we also are informed that the key to understanding Newton's approach to forces lies precisely in his "showing us how to measure certain fundamental quantities without understanding the *ontology* of those quantities in various senses of the term" (p. 82, italics in original). Note, however, that in the phrases 'under certain conditions' and 'in various senses of the term' there is a particular indeterminacy with respect to the subject matter of ontology. In order to deal with such an indeterminacy of these expressions, it is necessary to turn to Newton's own pronouncements.

In the scholium to Section 11, Book 1, Newton introduces a significant methodological pronouncement, whereby he describes the line of investigation that has been undertaken in the *Principia*.

Mathematics –Newton writes– requires an investigation of those quantities of forces and their proportions that follow from any conditions that may be supposed. Then, coming down to physics, these proportions must be compared with the phenomena, so that it may be found out which conditions of forces apply to each kind of attracting bodies. And then, finally, it will be possible to argue more securely concerning the physical species, physical causes, and physical proportions of these forces (Newton, 1999, pp. 488-489).

It is reasonable to think of this scholium as articulating the mathematical setting of Book 1 with the analysis of motion in resisting media of Book 2, where Newton "adopted a different method of empirical inquiry" –to use the expression of G. E. Smith (2001, p. 249). A salient feature of this Book 2 is, in effect, the realisation that the explanation of motions as are exhibited in nature is unworkable following the model of the Cartesian vortex theory. So, having concluded that the material mediums are incompatible with the Keplerian analysis of motion, without delay Newton observes: "therefore, the hypothesis of vortices can in no way be reconciled with astronomical phenomena and serves less to clarify the celestial motions than to obscure them. But how those motions are performed in free spaces without vortices can be understood from book 1 and will now be shown more fully in book 3 on the system of the world" (Newton, 1999, p. 790).

Likewise, in the introductory remarks to Book 3, Newton articulates once again the foregoing investigation with the further application of those results to the physical reality in the system of the world. So, he claims:

In the preceding books I have presented principles of philosophy that are not, however, philosophical but strictly mathematical –that is, those on which the study of philosophy can be based. These principles are the laws and conditions of motions and of forces, which

especially relate to philosophy. (...) It still remains for us to exhibit the system of the world from these same principles (p. 793)

From the above statements, and particularly from that of the first quotation, the various other senses to which Janiak alludes could be understood as those related to the 'species', 'proportions' and 'causes' of forces in nature, when subjected to physical treatment. If this is correct, as a result the ontological portion that Janiak has discerned of forces in general is that associated to quantity. As for gravity in particular, in addition to being a quantity, Janiak has also maintained that in formulating Newton its precise law, the 'species' of this force also has been distinguished, in so far as different from, say, other forces like magnetism. Lastly, with regard to the 'proportion' of gravity, it is clear that it is directly proportional to the masses of bodies and inversely proportional to the square of the distances. As a matter of fact, in Rule 3 of the *Regula philosophandi* of Book 3, Newton expresses this idea as he highlights its observance in nature. In this sense, he writes:

it is universally established by experiments and astronomical observations that all bodies on or near the earth gravitate [lit. are heavy] toward the earth, and do so in proportion to the quantity of matter in each body, and that the moon gravitates [is heavy] toward the earth in proportion to the quantity of its matter, and that our sea in turn gravitates [is heavy] toward the moon, and that all planets gravitate [are heavy] toward one another, and that there is a similar gravity [heaviness] of comets toward the sun, it will have to be concluded by this third rule that all bodies gravitate toward one another (p. 795).

So therefore, for a complete ontological characterisation of gravity force, it is required to elucidate its quantity, proportion, species and *causes*.

In the *Principia* it is possible to account for the first three characteristics, but this is not so clear with respect to the fourth one, namely, the causes. Consequently, on the lines of the mathematical principles of natural philosophy established by Newton, the objection of the strict mechanists, who rejected the main concept of the *Principia* within the framework of the causality, remains the same. But more importantly, this situation affects Janiak's interpretation as well. His construal is lacking of the fourth and most important feature of the ontology of force, the very cornerstone of the criticism based on the causality, which is the issue at stake. Nonetheless, Janiak himself seems to be aware of this weakness in his analysis and, making virtue out of necessity, he develops the argument for measurement as becoming the outstanding characteristic of Newton's procedure in the *Principia*. But does it work?

The mathematical approach to measuring the force is the keystone of Janiak's analysis (Janiak, 2008, pp. 58-65). As a matter of fact, this idea is expressed time and again all along the course of his study.²⁴⁷ Given that prominent feature of gravity for Janiak is its category of quantity, its

²⁴⁷ To give an instance, consider the following few recurrences: "Newton's mathematical treatment of force indicates how to measure a force by measuring mass and acceleration (p. 60). They are physical quantities because they are part of the physical world; and they are part of the physical world because they can be measured by measuring other,

successful quantification, or measurement, is basic to the purpose of squaring Newton into a positivistic slant. This is not to say, by no means, that the *Principia* is not concerned with quantities and their measurements. Quite the contrary, and on pain of incurring a truism, it is opportune here to recall the overriding logical structure of the *Principia* itself.

Following the classical style of presentation of mathematical investigations of Euclid's *Elements*, for the sake of logical rigor, and in order to highlight the quantitative character of his *Principia*, the opening of the book provides definitions and axioms (or the laws of motion), followed by propositions, theorems, problems, lemmas corollaries, and scholia. The definitions are directed to the specific manner in which the technical terms are to be understood, and how they are used throughout the three books. Additionally, all the definitions are treated as quantities, being a common characteristic of all these definitions the accent marked upon how each of them are to be measured (Cohen, 1999, p. 128; Roche, 1998; Smith, 2008). Thus, the quantities of matter and motion are the subject matter of Definitions 1 and 2; Definitions 3 to 5 are about inherent, impressed, and centripetal forces in that order; and Definitions 6, 7, and 8 are related to the measurement of the absolute, accelerative, and motive quantities of these forces respectively (Newton, 1999, pp. 403-408).

The closing section of this part of the *Principia* is the famous scholium on space, time, and motion. Here Newton declares that “although time, space, place, and motion are very familiar to everyone, it must be noted that these quantities are popularly conceived solely with reference to the objects of sense perception”, and in order to correct such a preconception “it is useful to distinguish these quantities into absolute and relative, true and apparent, mathematical and common” (p. 408). In this scholium, over again, special emphasis is stressed upon the measurement of such quantities. In fact, as asserted in the final lines of this scholium, “in what follows, a fuller explanation will be given of how to determine true motions from their causes, effects, and apparent differences, and, conversely, of how to determine from motions, whether true or apparent, their causes and effects. For this was the purpose for which I composed the following treatise” (p. 415). In the words of Smith, “measurement is at the very heart of the *Principia*. It pervades the definitions and scholium on space and time precisely because the primary point of this section is to spell out (in Howard Stein’s words) ‘the empirical content of a set of theoretical notions’” (Smith, 2008, para. 44).²⁴⁸

Against this background then, there seems to be nothing surprising with respect to Janiak’s contention that Newton’s mathematical treatment of force indicates how to measure a force by measuring mass and acceleration, and that this is essential to Newton’s approach (Janiak, 2008, p. 60). But the intriguing point is the suggestion that we can think of forces as physical quantities. This

obviously physical, quantities. My suggestion will be that the mathematical treatment of force measures physical quantities (Ibid). We can measure a centripetal force by measuring the velocity or the motion that it generates in a given time in some body (p. 62). This [gravity] law allows us to measure the force of gravity between two massive bodies by measuring other physical quantities, such as the distance between them (pp. 63-64). The *Principia* begins the characterization of the cause by indicating, for instance, how to measure the cause by measuring other physical quantities, and by showing that various motions have the same cause” (p. 68).

²⁴⁸ Smith is referring to Stein, H. (1967). Newtonian space-time. In R. Palter (Ed.), *The annus mirabilis of Sir Isaac Newton* (pp. 258-284). Cambridge, MA: The MIT Press, p. 281.

idea, as I noted above, opens the way to his characterisation of the ontology of force, 'under certain conditions', as a quantity. Janiak, it should be observed, is not explicit as to how we are to understand his meaning when he talks of gravity force as a quantity but, from the overall schema of his study, it is sound to gather that his perspective is that of the mathematical discourse. A related view has been expressed by another scholar who comments on Newton's quantities of the *Principia* within a specific scheme of categories.

George Smith has pointed in the same direction as Janiak in drawing attention to the identification of the Definitions given in the opening part of the *Principia* in as much as these are quantities. But in contrast to Janiak, Smith is unambiguous in regard to the precise direction appointed by Newton. According to Smith, Newton's quantities correspond "to the ontological category of quantity in Aristotle's sense." And then he claims:

Thus force and motion are quantities that have direction as well as magnitude, and it makes no sense to talk of forces as individuated entities or substances. Newton's laws of motion and the propositions derived from them involve relations among quantities, not among objects. In place of 'no entity without identity,' we have 'no quantity without definite proportions;' and the demand on measurement is to supply values that unequivocally yield an adequate approximation to these definite proportions" (Smith, 2008, para. 41).

Smith's observation points to a guiding procedure throughout the *Principia*. According to it, no quantity should be introduced into the mathematical analysis, unless a mathematical proportion could be stipulated for it, or a criterion for its quantification. In this sense, quantities and quantification turn out to be a structural feature of the *Principia* in as much as they entail definite proportions.

But if we compare Janiak's notion of gravity as quantity in the *Principia* with the one of Smith –Janiak's say's nothing regarding the *nature* of gravity (it is not an individuated entity or a substance)– the ontological question on the nature of gravity remains problematic. In point of fact, Janiak's reading is characterised more by what it avoids than by what it accomplishes regarding this issue.

Of course, in so far as there are quantities, forces are not individual entities –to use Smith's words– or substances. To think of them in such terms would be a category mistake. According to Aristotle's theory of predication in *Categories*, there are two fundamental ontological relations, namely, being "said of" a subject, and being "present in" a subject, which corresponds to the essential and accidental predication respectively. To predicate of gravity, for the present case, in the sense of "said of" matter, is to declare a fundamental ontological relation. According to Aristotle, if gravity is said of matter, that is to say is said to be an inseparable aspect of matter (to talk of matter is to talk of something having gravity), then gravity must be essential to matter, but for Newton that would be wrong, or at the very least, misleading, as Newton himself would observe in the letter to Bentley. An alternative manner for understanding gravity along the lines of Aristotle's theory of predication would be to talk of it as "present in" matter; by this, Aristotle says in *Categories*, "I mean what is in

something, not as a part, and cannot exist separately from what it is in" (1a24). Hence, we obtain that gravity and forces in general are not substances but are *in* substances. This could indicate that gravity is ontologically dependent on matter and it is accidental and universal.²⁴⁹ But this categorisation is also problematic given the fact that gravity decreases through the distance.

Another Aristotelian perspective to account for gravity, in as much as a quantity, could be taken from his philosophy of mathematics. In the characterisation that he gives of mathematics as a science, it is markedly highlighted that the process of abstraction whereby the mathematician conducts his investigations, consists in abstracting or *removing* the physical aspects of material substances. So, in leaving out all sensible considerations of heaviness or lightness, for instance, he focuses on them *qua* quantities and *qua* continuous. Thus, in *Metaphysics* XI, he asserts that the mathematician investigates abstractions, and continues:

for in his investigation he eliminates all the sensible qualities, e.g. weight and lightness, hardness and its contrary, and also heat and cold and the other sensible contrarieties, and leaves only the quantitative and continuous, sometimes in one, sometimes in two, sometimes in three dimensions, and the attributes of things *qua* quantitative and continuous, and does not consider them in any other respect (*Metaphysics*, 1068a28-36).

At its best, this description fits with Book 1 of the *Principia* but, if taken at its word, the subject of gravity (heaviness) which 'really exists' is problematic to square within the general structure of the entire work, all the more since the rational mechanics of the *Principia* "will be the science, expressed in exact propositions and demonstrations, of the motions that result from any forces whatever and of the forces that are required for any motions whatever" (Newton, 1999, p. 382).²⁵⁰ So therefore, when taken in the Aristotelian framework of categories or from his philosophy of mathematics Janiak's characterisation of gravity as a quantity is inadequate. It follows that the question regarding the insight we get into the ontology of gravity force merely by calling it a quantity continues unanswered.

As for the problem of action at a distance, from the special technical sense of 'mechanism' attributed to Newton, Janiak's approach involves an infinite regress. Indeed, for Janiak, the fact that "gravity causes the planetary orbits does not amount to, or entail, the contention that there is no causally efficacious medium between planetary bodies that serves as the basis of their gravitational

²⁴⁹ In Aristotle's theory of predication, accidents can be universal. In *De interpretatione*, the universal is defined as "that which is by its nature predicated of a number of things" (17a38). Thus, for instance, we are told in the *Categories* that "man and animal are said of many things" (3b17).

²⁵⁰ As Newton himself states, his work is a work on physics, and as is well known is quite different from Aristotle's physics. According to this latter, while mathematics is the study of those objects that are changeless and not separate, the study of physics is on objects that are separated and not changeless (Wedin, 2009, p. 138). And in a broader sense, physics in Aristotle is a qualitative science. Besides this, all we know that the new science of sixteenth and seventeenth centuries more often than not exalted the novelty of its doctrines by contrasting the different approaches to the Aristotelian physics. Contrasts such as the quantitative over the qualitative, and the role of mathematics in the analysis of local motion over substantial forms and occult essences, are persistent claims of this time (White, 2009, p. 160).

interactions” (Janiak, 2008, p. 77). It is obvious from this contention that the acknowledgement of –or even the need for– a sort of material medium to account for the workings of earthly and heavenly bodies must be granted if the action at a distance is to be denied. But, if from Book 2 of the *Principia* it is clear that the best candidate for such a medium, the Cartesian vortex theory, is implausible, then a further means, unknown to Newton, is required. This being the state of affairs, Janiak states that since Newton’s “theory is neutral with respect to the physical cause of gravity, it is perfectly compatible with the discovery that some type of medium does in fact exist” (*Ibid.*). This claim states a potential state of affairs (when eventually some sort of an aethereal means be discovered), but it does not rule out the very problem of *actio in distans*. This being so, it is entirely reasonable to assert, as John Henry has pointed out, that following this same line of reasoning it “must be allowed to say Newton’s neutral theory is perfectly compatible with the discovery that action at a distance exists” (Henry, 2011, p. 16).

In order to prevent an objection of this type, Janiak quotes Newton himself. In a letter to Leibniz of October 16 of 1693, Newton comments on Leibniz’s invitation to explain the planetary motions based on the idea of a fluid medium (*fluidi ambientis*), slightly different from Huygens’s notion developed in the *Discourse de la cause de la pesanteur* (1690).²⁵¹ In the fragment quoted by Janiak (quoted here several times, by the way), Newton remarks:

But if, meanwhile, someone explains gravity along with all its laws by the action of some subtle matter, and shows that the motion of planets and comets will not be disturbed by that matter, I shall not object (Newton, 1959-1977, vol. III, p. 287).

From this statement Janiak concludes that eventually a special subtle matter, which does not disturb the motion of planets, different from that favoured by Leibniz or Huygens, and in any case distinct from Descartes’s vortex theory, could be discovered. This new kind of aether, Janiak writes, “would have to flow through material bodies, interacting *somehow* with their masses”, and additionally, “this characterization of gravity’s physical cause must *somehow* cohere with” Newton’s account for gravity in Book 3 of the *Principia* (Janiak, 2008, pp. 78, 77, emphasis added). From these pronouncements it is unclear how this aether specifically should act, and that is exactly the point at issue.²⁵² Henry has aptly pointed out at the heart of the conceptual problem involved here.

Consider the standard objection to the Cartesian account of gravity: if bodies are pushed towards the centre of the Earth by continual streams of downward particles, why can’t we shield a body from these streams (why does a body dropped from underneath a heavy oak

²⁵¹ See Newton, 1959-1977, vol. III, p. 260.

²⁵² At this point I find instructive to mention the recent study of John Henry on Newton and his development of the ideas on action at a distance. As Henry aptly remarks on Janiak’s approach, “it is usually the case in philosophical discourse that if we arrive at an infinite regress we assume we’ve gone wrong somewhere; it is astonishing, therefore, to see Janiak evidently unconcerned by the fact that his interpretation of Newton’s aether leads Newton into an infinite regress” (Henry, 2011, p. 16).

table, say, fall in exactly the same way as a body dropped in open air)? The standard Cartesian answer was that the particles were so fine they went through the table and affected the body just the same. To which the standard riposte was, why don't the particles also pass through the "falling" body, instead of pushing it down? Given Newton's long-standing anti-Cartesianism, it must have crossed Newton's mind that any aether which is capable of penetrating through to the innermost parts of bodies to give those parts a mechanical push, by impact, or at least by some sort of contact, would also be capable of passing through the body without making such contact. Indeed, it is hard to see how "some subtle matter" can pass through moving bodies like planets and comets so that their motions "will not be disturbed" (i.e., by friction or drag effects) and yet this same subtle matter is to be held responsible for the gravitational motions of planets by its contact actions (Henry, 2011, p. 16).

Furthermore, in order to have a complete picture of Newton's argument, it is suitable to quote the preceding argument which entails his refusal of the mentioned. In his letter to Leibniz, he observes:

For since celestial motions are more regular than if they arose from vortices and observe other laws, so much so that vortices contribute not to the regulation but to the disturbance of the motions of planets and comets; and since all phenomena of the heavens and of the sea follow precisely, so far as I am aware, from nothing but gravity acting in accordance with the laws described by me; and since nature is very simple, I have myself concluded that all other causes are to be rejected and that the heavens are to be stripped as far as may be of all matter, lest the motions of planets and comets be hindered or rendered irregular (Newton, 1959-1977, vol. III, p. 287).

Last but not least about Janiak's account of the ontology of gravity force and action at a distance, there is the accusation above mentioned, according to which Newton's scholars, especially Cohen and Westfall as representative outstanding historians of science, do not have an agreement regarding the existence of force(s), and more precisely about the question as to whether Newton thinks the force of gravity really exists? (Janiak, 2008, p. 50). On this very question I just would like to point out that ignoring the precise nature of gravity force is not the same as denying its reality.

In this sense, Janiak's instantiation of this divergence, in the precise case of Bernard Cohen, merits a slight adjustment. Firstly, in the context of Cohen (1992), he simply is reasserting the idea that Newton in the *Principia* "explored the mathematical properties of systems of forces and particles of bodies without entering into discussions of the nature of forces, the modes of operation of forces, or the existence of forces" (p. 347, the passage alluded to by Janiak). This is different from saying, as Janiak does, that "Cohen contends that Newton never even addressed the question of the 'existence of forces'" (Janiak, 2008, p. 50). Compare this assertion of Cohen with the idea expressed in his paper "Newton's concepts of force and mass, with notes on the laws of motion". In this article, dealing with the realities of force along the lines of the Newtonian style, Cohen avowed that:

“Newton came to believe in the existence of forces that could produce curved or orbital motion without contact, thereby holding a drastically revised form of the then-current mechanical philosophy. In effect he now enlarged the basis of explanation from effects produced by matter and motion, adding the further concept of force” (Cohen, 2002, p. 78).

This avowal bears a strong resemblance to that of Richard Westfall on the issue of the reality of force, assumed by Janiak as the opposite interpretation. In the seventh chapter of his *Force in Newton's physics*, “Newton and the Concept of Force”, Westfall observes, as Janiak rightly points out, that “what [Newton] proposed was an addition to the ontology of nature. Where the orthodox mechanical philosophy of seventeenth-century science insisted that physical reality consists solely of material particles in motion, characterised by size, shape, and solidity alone, Newton now added forces of attraction and repulsion, considered as properties of such particles, to the catalogue of nature's ontology (Westfall, 1970, p. 377). And immediately Westfall adds “as far as the works he published are concerned, and above all, as far as the conceptual tools he employed in scientific discussion are concerned, *he treated forces as entities that really exist*” (*Ibid.*).

Secondly, in order to be more precise regarding Cohen's standpoint on the question of the reality of force, it is suitable to mention the point as expressed in “A guide to Newton's *Principia*”. There, Cohen claims that “the Newtonian style (...) is independent of Newton's strong belief in the reality of forces –in particular, the force of universal gravity” (Cohen, 1999, pp. 63-64). Finally, it is to be recognised, notwithstanding this, that the interpretative convergence between Cohen and Janiak lies in the agnosticism adopted by Newton regarding the cause of gravity force in the *Principia* –on which there is consensus among scholars, at the best of my knowledge. In this line of analysis, Cohen writes: (1) “The Newtonian style constituted a mode of discourse which could enable him to develop the properties of such a force without the need to discuss either whether forces of that sort are part of good science or how these forces act to produce their effects (*Ibid.*, p. 64). And (2): “Happily, a main feature of the Newtonian revolution in science was the Newtonian style, which provided a sharp division between the use of concepts like centripetal force and universal gravity that one could not understand and the search for the causes of such forces or the attempts to understand them (Cohen, 1980, p. 148). These contentions in my opinion converge on Janiak's. Effectively, as he declares “What the mechanists could not foresee, and perhaps could never understand, is that Newton made the brilliant move of showing us how to measure certain fundamental quantities without understanding the ontology of those quantities in various senses of the term” (2008, p. 82).

5. Newton's ontology of gravity force in the *Principia*

The rationale behind the problematic reception of the *Principia*, as mentioned above, lies in the fact that it openly contravened the conventional credo of shape, size and motion of the mechanical philosophy. Or said in other way, the targets of criticisms to Newton's work were directed against the postulation of the gravity force, lacking the type of explanation provided by the efficient causation of contact action. Recently, Stephen Gaukroger has highlighted the underlying differences apropos the theory of matter between Newton and his detractors. Thus, on the one hand, "mechanism was a natural philosophy that premised its use of mechanics on a particular understanding of the nature of matter". But on the other hand, "Newton severs the connections between mechanics and matter theory, in the process cutting mechanics adrift from a number of natural-philosophical issues that, at least since Aristotle, had been considered to constitute the core of the discipline" (2010, p. 57).

According to Bernard Cohen's interpretation, the crux of Newton's success in the *Principia* precisely lies in his development of a mathematical physics detached from any ontological commitment to the gravity force (1980, pp. 26, 52-154). And in the same manner, Adrew Janiak's explanation of the ontology of gravity force in the *Principia* highlights the neutral character of Newton's attitude toward such a burden. Furthermore, in order to emphasise the mathematical character of this attitude, Janiak reduces the ontology of gravity force to the category of quantity (2008, pp. 82, 50-86).

One of the ideas behind these interpretations is that related to the explicit shift in the *Principia* regarding what was deemed as a valid and acceptable explanation and what was not. For both Cohen and Janiak such a shifting was towards mathematics, and mechanical explanations were set aside. Certainly, both Cohen and Janiak are quite aware of the complex meaning of the term 'mechanical' in seventeenth century.

As a matter of fact, the mechanical philosophy was a complex and varied doctrine whose sources can be traced from a heterogeneous combination of mechanics as that of Archimedes, the chemical, magical and medical traditions, the renewed interest for the philosophy of Epicurus, as well as the scholastic voluntarism and nominalism (Menn, 1988). And, as J.E. McGuire has aptly remarked:

It is obvious that the term 'mechanical' meant many different things to various thinkers of the seventeenth century: nature is governed by immutable geometrical laws; contact action

is the only mode of change; first principles are to be integrated with experimental investigations; regularities are to be explained in mathematical form; that all phenomena arise from matter in motion, or matter and motion; that compound bodies are composed of vortices (Descartes), centers of force (Leibniz), or tiny bits of matter conceived as atoms or corpuscles; that changes in phenomena result from the way in which internal particles alter their configurations; that the “new science” conceives nature dynamically in terms of motion, rather than statically in terms solely of the size and shape of internal particles; that occult qualities are to be banished from explanations which must be based on sensory experience in terms of clear and distinct ideas; or that nature is to be conceived in analogy to the operations of mechanical activities (McGuire, 1972, p. 523).

But notwithstanding this, the constructivist stance adopted by Cohen²⁵³, and the redefinition of mechanical by Janiak, disregard the relationship in Newton’s natural philosophy in general, and in the *Principia* in particular, between mechanics, geometry and mathematics, as I shall show below.

Yves Gingras has maintained a similar view in stating that “this episode [of Newton’s *Principia*] shows that the evaluation criteria for what was to count as an acceptable ‘explanation’ (of gravitation in this case) were shifting towards mathematics and away from mechanical explanations” (2001, p. 398). This separation of mathematics on the one hand and mechanics on the other hand, viewed from the conceptualist stand point, runs the risk of oversimplification.

Now, having looked at Newton’s philosophy of mathematics, and considered how that led him to accepting actions at a distance, we now turn finally to the analysis of Newton’s philosophy of mathematics with regard to the foundations of geometry upon mechanical practice, which is fundamental for the understanding of Newton’s ontology of gravity force in the *Principia*. From this analysis it will be asserted that Newton effectively does assert –albeit in a veiled manner– the nature of gravity force when his statements are grasped and viewed within the scopes and limits of his empiricist epistemology. According to this approach, we are required neither to embark on conceptual analyses that historically misrepresent Newton’s philosophy of mathematics nor to mingle his other natural philosophical inquiries in alchemy and ancient wisdom, for instance, in order to make sense of his usage and vindication of the concept of universal gravitation.

In order to develop this argument, naturally, the starting point will be the *Principia* itself, and more precisely the Preface, a piece that remained unaltered all through the successive editions of 1713 and 1726. The viewpoints expressed by Newton in this Preface are strengthened and enriched in his *Geometry* of 1693 where he develops in more detail his thoughts on the relationship between mechanics and geometry. Next, with the purpose of substantiating Newton’s ontology of mathematical entities, and specifically that of gravity force, I will take a look at his *De quadratura* (also of 1693) where a quasi-realist approach to mathematical entities is stated. Important remarks

²⁵³ See, Cohen 1980. For a critical appraisal of Cohen’s account of Newton’s mathematical models (mental constructs) see Ducheyne 2005. As a matter of fact, from the historical point of view, constructivism is a confusing term to describe Newton’s mathematical practice.

on the positions declared in the former works are also found in the unfinished treatise *De gravitatione* and also in Newton's (anonymous) account of the *Commercium epistolicum* of 1714.

To begin with, Newton's Preface to the *Principia* has received little attention when compared to other sections of this work such as the Definitions, the scholium to the Definitions, the Laws of motion, or the General Scholium (which appeared in the second edition of 1713), to name just a few. Thus, the number of studies focused on this important part of Newton's masterpiece is relatively small. At the best of my knowledge, we find Garrison (1987), Gabbey (1992, pp. 305-322), Dear (1995, pp. 210-243), Domski (2003), Guicciardini (2009, pp. 293-299), and Dunlop (2011, pp. 69-101). Surprisingly, the 370-page "Guide to Newton's *Principia*" by Cohen, included in the new translation of the *Principia* (1999), devoted no space to the Preface.²⁵⁴ Fortunately, and as a palliative, Cohen provides an important unpublished preface which shed light upon Newton's goals in this treatise on the mathematical principles of natural philosophy.

In the article "Newton and the relation of mathematics to natural philosophy" (1987), by James W. Garrison, we were warned not to assume "that the distinction between mathematics and natural philosophy, including mechanics, is, for Newton, a distinction between formal, *a priori* ideas and empirical, *a posteriori* things" (p. 609). On the contrary, in this study special attention is stressed on the fact that for Newton "geometry is founded on mechanical practice" and that it forms part of "universal mechanics" (Newton, 1999, p. 382; Garrison, 1987, p. 610). A strong point of Garrison's paper is the idea that we need to correct, –or at least not to fall into the temptation of projecting– our modern prejudices regarding Newton's philosophy of mathematics (especially in the *Principia* and as testified in the *Geometry* of 1693) that demands a close relation between mathematical entities, and empirical intuitions (Garrison, 1987, p. 613).²⁵⁵

On the other side, the weak point I find in Garrison's analysis is the distinction that he draws between 'natural geometry' as a privileged knowledge "that which we ourselves create" on the one hand, and 'natural mechanics'. According to him, this is the understanding "to which we may not aspire [since] the construction of the magnitudes we investigate geometrically is beyond our power to control, *as when God or nature is responsible for their generation*" (Garrison, 1987, p. 619, emphasis added).²⁵⁶ I take Garrison to be right in asserting that "such phenomena lie forever beyond our certain knowledge and conclusions concerning them must be inferred by induction" (*Ibid.*), but his position is extreme in view of the overall goal of the *Principia*, namely, the mathematical principles of natural philosophy.

As a matter of fact, mathematical demonstrations override the general structure of the investigation of the workings of nature. For this very reason, in the Preface Newton declares that the main goal of the *Principia* is "to discover the forces of nature from the phenomena of motions and then to *demonstrate* the other phenomena from these forces" (Newton, 1999, p. 382, emphasis added). Such a demonstration is rooted in the mathematical procedures of enquiry and exposition of Books 1 and 2, and thenceforth, in Book 3, "the motions of the planets, the comets, the moon,

²⁵⁴ See Guicciardini, 2009, p. 294.

²⁵⁵ See also Guicciardini, 1999 and Sepkoski, 2002.

²⁵⁶ For a criticism to this distinction between natural geometry and natural mechanics see Dear 1995, p. 215.

and the sea are deduced from these forces by propositions that are also mathematical” (*Ibid.*). Finally, the distinction between what Garrison calls ‘natural geometry’ and ‘natural mechanics’, in addition to not being present in the *Principia* itself, tends to downplay the fact that Newton’s emphasis is upon natural philosophy instead of manual arts or that of the ‘maker’s knowledge’ as Garrison designates them.

Another important study on Newton’s understanding of the relationship between mechanics and natural philosophy is Alan Gabbey’s “Newton’s *Mathematical principles of natural philosophy: A treatise on ‘Mechanics?’*” of 1992. In this paper Gabbey focused his analysis on the clarification of the transformation of mechanics inasmuch as it was an art on the one hand, and as a mathematically driven science on the other. For Gabbey, the main import of the *Principia* lies in the fact that this work forms an essential part of the “programme for the general *mathematization* of natural philosophy, out of which eventually developed mathematical physics as understood today” (p. 308).

Gabbey makes a good case for emphasising that Newton’s mathematical principles of natural philosophy are properly a treatise on mechanics, but on the grounds that the *Principia* should be regarded within the framework of an especial type of mechanics, that is to say, that of *rational* mechanics, as it was termed by Newton in the Preface. By tracing the complex disciplinary changes between natural philosophy and mechanics through figures such as Descartes, Galileo, Barrow, Wallis, Boyle and even Cotes, the editor of the second edition of the *Principia*, “The *Principia: a treatise on ‘mechanics?’*” has helped us to shape our understanding of Newton’s geometrical study of nature insofar as it was a rational mechanics, marshalled by mathematical demonstration and experimental evidence.

A relevant consequence of Gabbey’s analysis is the outlook we grasp when we compare the demands of the first French review of the *Principia*, that of Règis, and Newton’s own perception of his masterpiece. In point of fact, as Gabbey remarks, the contrast was not just about rational mechanics *per se* on the one hand, and Descartes’s mechanistic natural philosophy, as instantiated in the *Principia philosophiae*, on the other hand, “a wholly descriptive exercise in one version of the mechanical philosophy, the other a mathematical exploration of a different version of the mechanical philosophy” (p. 321). And more to the point, as he has reminded us, we should bear in mind Newton’s predilection for mathematical procedures over physical questions which felt out of the framework of experimental confirmation.²⁵⁷ Alan Gabbey’s study of the significance of ‘rational mechanics’, within the context of the *Principia*, illuminates the sense in which the foundation of geometry upon mechanics is established in this work.

²⁵⁷ The concluding remarks of this study put into perspective the scopes and limits of Newton’s achievement in the *Principia*, viewed either as a new model of explanatory discourse based upon the mathematical language, contrasting with the hypothetical and speculative model of explanation, that is, that of the Cartesian and the Aristotelian traditions of natural philosophy. So he writes: “Newton’s *Principia* was a transitional and truly ‘pivotal’ text. It was not a manual on the *artes mechanicae*, nor was it a *liber mechanicorum*. It was assuredly and obviously a mathematical treatise, but whether it was a revolutionary treatise in natural philosophy or a revolutionary new departure in rational mechanics depends on whether we choose to look backwards from 1687 to the achievements in natural philosophy of Descartes and the Peripatetic tradition, or whether we choose to look forward, while remembering Galileo and Huygens, to the great syntheses of Euler and Lagrange” (Gabbey, 1992, p. 322).

In his book *Discipline and experience* (1995), Peter Dear devotes the final chapter to Barrow and Newton in relation to the constructivist approach (pp. 210-243). The starting point of this book is the aim of understanding the stance adopted by the Royal Society focused on promoting the “Physico-Mathematicall-Experimentall Learning” (p. 2) inasmuch as self-consciously espoused by John Wilkins, one of the founding members of the Society. Newton can be seen as an outstanding upshot of a gradual process of evolution from the forms of natural philosophical demonstration. In effect, as Dear comments,

The uses of mathematical argument in making accredited knowledge of nature show how the foundational assumptions of a mathematical science, and the kinds of experience that underwrote them, made it possible for Newton to announce a kind of declaration of independence for physico-mathematics (p. 210).

Such a ‘declaration of independence’, and the kinds of explanations deployed in the *Principia*, to a large extent are due to Newton’s notion of geometry as a science founded upon mechanics, “evidently a different sense of the term ‘mechanical’ from that of Huygens”, for instance (p. 211).

In consonance with the mainstream argument of *Discipline and experience*, the final chapter devotes a great deal of space in showing how the discourse of geometry and constructivism are in a close relation to the rising status of physico-mathematics “as a methodologically superior ‘successor discipline’ to Aristotelian natural philosophy” (p. 223), to which could be added the Cartesian natural philosophy as well, in the light of the arguments developed by Gabbey in his study of 1992.

Dear provides a perspicacious context for the understanding of Newton’s *Principia* along the lines of the emerging mathematical physics. As an expected product of a process that could be dubbed as the passing of mathematics from subordination to hegemony in natural philosophy, the last chapter of *Discipline and experience*, in the precise instance of Newton and the *Principia*, is valuable for (1) the connections –albeit not entirely new– established between Barrow and Newton, as for the philosophy of geometry and its foundations upon mechanics. And (2) for the discernment of the idea that postulates in geometry are for Newton “assumptions of possibility rooted in experience” assumptions that belong unambiguously to the potential mechanical construction of objects (Dear, 1995, p. 226).

In the line of constructivism, another study dedicated to the Preface of the *Principia* is Mary Domski’s article “The constructible and the intelligible in Newton’s philosophy of geometry” (2003). Domski’s paper maintains that Newton’s notion of geometry is founded on mechanical practice and uses this as a springboard for her contrast between Descartes’s constructivism in his *Geometry* (1637) and that of Newton in the *Principia*. According to this scholar, “Descartes’s characterization of the ancient distinction between ‘geometrical’ and ‘mechanical’ curves may underscore what he takes to be the novelty of his approach, but he leads us astray in claiming that the ancients considered a particular class of curves not treatable in geometry” (p. 1117), namely, the mechanical ones. This last idea is the one that Newton precisely rejects in the *Principia*, as Domski shows. She

bases her study upon manuscripts dated from the pre-*Principia* period (1673-1683) and Newton's *Geometry* (1693).

The potency of Domski's paper lies in making a clear-cut distinction between types of constructivism as understood and practiced by both Descartes and Newton. In effect, one of the main strengths of "The constructible and the intelligible" is the suggestion that Newton's rejection of Descartes should be seen against the constructivism of Descartes's *Geometry* which he considered as a reinterpretation of the ancient geometry. According to Descartes, mechanical curves are not to be treated in geometry because of their lack of exactness. For him, geometrical curves are those which admit precision and accuracy in measurement.

In short, Domski's analysis has the merit of distinguishing Descartes's constructivism from that of Newton. In so doing, she highlights, on the one hand, as one of Newton's goals in the Preface a criticism of Descartes's *Geometry* and its modernity. On the other hand, by virtue of her analysis we have deepened our understanding regarding mechanical constructibility and the determination of the scope of geometrical intelligibility (p. 1121).

In the same line of Domski's analysis, Niccolò Guicciardini has devoted a section to the Preface of Newton's *Principia* in his recent book (293-299, but see also 299-305) *Isaac Newton on mathematical certainty and method* (2009). Guicciardini's analysis, additionally, enlarges Newton's targets of criticisms to Descartes's philosophy. As a matter of fact, Guicciardini interprets "the opening lines of the *Preface* as a criticism of Descartes' theories of geometry, mechanics, and certainty as laid out in the *Géométrie*", and following the long tradition of interpretation centered on contrasting the natural philosophies of Newton and Descartes, he asserts that "the *Principia* was written –from its title to the concluding General Scholium– as a criticism of Cartesian ideas, so it is not surprising to find anti-Cartesianism in its opening lines" (p. 294).

A notable feature of Guicciardini's reading of the Preface is the itemized description of these important opening lines of the *Principia*. Among these themes, I would like to underline, first, the idea that Newton sharply criticized the characterization of mechanics as lacking in the exactness proper to geometry. And secondly, the emphasis placed upon Newton's argument for rational mechanics, insofar as such a mechanics provides, by means of mathematical laws, the best understanding as regards the uniformity of the workings of nature. In point of fact, and as has been noticed above, "rather than excluding mechanics from the realm of geometrical exactness, Newton proposed to subsume geometry under mechanics" (p. 297).

The last study I would like to allude to is that of Katherine Dunlop (2011). In this analysis, Dunlop focuses her reading of the Preface of the *Principia* on Barrow's influence upon Newton's notion of geometry as founded upon mechanics, and more precisely on mechanical practice. This reading highlights Newton's "strategy for demonstrating mathematics' relevance to causality" (p. 70) in so far as postulates serve as a way to build the bridge between geometry and mechanics. For Dunlop, the first principles of geometry secure the physical *significance* of Newton's universal attraction (gravity) inasmuch as it is a theory of measurement. At his point, Dunlop's interpretation of Newton's gravity bears some resemblance to Janiak's interpretation.

Having presented in broad lines these studies on Newton's Preface to the *Principia*, now I will concentrate on the analysis of the content itself of the Preface.²⁵⁸

5.1. Geometry and Nature in the Preface to the *Principia*

In the very first sentence of the Preface, Newton establishes a connection between the Ancients and the Moderns, by means of mechanics, with regard to the importance of its study for a fitting understanding of natural phenomena. Needless to say, insofar as it is directly expressed by Newton, the main source for this statement on the ancients comes from the *Mathematical collection* by Pappus of Alexandria. Accordingly, Newton opens his Preface thus:

Since the ancients (according to Pappus) considered *mechanics* to be of the greatest importance in the investigation of nature and since the moderns rejecting substantial forms and occult qualities have undertaken to reduce the phenomena of nature to mathematical laws, it has seemed best in this treatise to concentrate on *mathematics* as it relates to natural philosophy (Newton, 1999, p. 381).²⁵⁹

First, the reference to Moderns has been considered as an approval on the part of Newton, upon considering that the rejection of substantial forms and Scholastic occult qualities (Guicciardini, 2009, p. 297) was succeeded by the programme of mathematising nature. So therefore, the undertaking 'to reduce the phenomena of nature to mathematical laws' could be thought akin to the agenda and achievements such as those of Kepler regarding his formulation of the astronomical laws or the mathematical analysis of the free fall developed by Galilei.²⁶⁰ Now, given the fact that Descartes's natural philosophy has been deemed as one of Newton's main reasons for seeking to replace the philosophy of the French philosopher with his own, it is not inappropriate to think of Descartes's non-mathematical physics as one of Newton's targets as well, though mentioned only obliquely. This is not denying the fact that Descartes's aim was directed at establishing the laws of

²⁵⁸ A similar line of analysis to the present one has been developed by Niccolò Guicciardini in his recent book *Isaac Newton on mathematical certainty and method* (2009). In the preface to this book Guicciardini declares the main goal of his study: "I focus on one aspect of Newton's mathematical work that has so far been overlooked, namely, what one could call Newton's philosophy of mathematics. The basic questions that motivate this book are What was mathematics for Newton? and What did being a mathematician mean to him?" (p. xiii). (Additionally, I would strongly suggest his *Reading the Principia* [1999]). Given this overriding concern, the main thesis of this chapter could be seen as complementary to the ideas presented in Guicciardini's book (p. 293-299, 313-315).

²⁵⁹ These words eventually would be repeated in general lines in a draft for the Query for the Latin translation (1706) of his *Opticks*. Here Newton even went so far as to imply the atheism of those philosophers who heavily relied upon speculations on the workings of nature. "Later Philosophers banish the consideration of the supreme cause out of natural Philosophy framing Hypotheses for expla[in]ing all things without it &: referring it to Metaphysicks" (Add. 3970, f. 249 bis. As quoted in Shapiro, 1993, p. 15, fn. 9).

²⁶⁰ Indeed, according to Gabbey, "Galileo (like Benedetti) was as much a natural philosopher as he was the author of *Le meccaniche* (c. 1600), and he succeeded in bridging some of the disciplinary gap between *philosophia naturalis* and *mechanica* by mathematizing one of the most intractable phenomena of the natural world, the fall of heavy bodies. Through the deployment of mathematics and *ars mechanica* to yield experimentally-derived data *de motu* he created powerful methods for exploring the operations of the *natural* world" (Gabbey, 1992, p. 311).

nature whereby to explicate, as far as possible, the whole range of natural phenomena.²⁶¹ It is in this sense that Newton, therefore, sanctions the line of research of moderns and aligns himself in the programme of the mathematical analysis of nature.

Second, regarding Pappus as the source of Newton's initial assertions, it becomes evident from the *Mathematical collection*. Here we find the Greek mathematician expressing the idea echoed in Newton's Preface: "The mechanical enquiry, Hermodorus my son, which has many and important uses for things in life, is rightly held by philosophers to be worthy of the highest esteem and is zealously studied by anybody interested in learning, *because it is almost the first to deal with the natural enquiry about the matter of the elements in the universe*".²⁶²

Newton next proceeds to heighten his reference to the Ancients, and more importantly, to characterise in historical perspective the taxonomy of mechanics. So, following with the thread of the ancient thought on mechanics, he continues stating that mechanics is divided into the rational, "which proceeds rigorously through demonstrations and the *practical*" (Newton, 1999, p. 381). As for the first sense –the rational mechanics– again through Pappus's *Mathematical collection* we learn that Hero and the school around him, maintained the same division, but under the names of discursive –or theoretical– and manual mechanics. In respect of the first one, rational or discursive mechanics, it is composed of geometry, arithmetic, astronomy and discourses about nature.²⁶³ The second sense of mechanics is that related to the manual arts. According to Pappus, for instance, we find that this is the "work in metals, architecture, carpentry and painting and of manual practice in these".²⁶⁴ This is precisely the part of mechanics that Newton is not interested in in the *Principia*. He mentions this sense of mechanics, simply to highlight that "the subject of *mechanics* as a whole has adopted its name" from practical mechanics.²⁶⁵ As a matter of fact,

²⁶¹ In his article "Metaphysics and the origins of modern science: Descartes and the importance of laws of nature" (2004), John Henry has undertaken an analysis of the concept of 'laws of nature' as having its origin precisely in the work of the French philosopher. Notwithstanding the acknowledgement of its roots in the mathematical tradition, the crux of Henry's paper lies in demonstrating the need for a well-founded metaphysics in which God has underwritten that laws in order to state the legitimation of the laws of nature in the domain of physico-mathematics.

²⁶² Pappus, *Mathematical collection*. The entire passage related to Newton's Preface is found on 1022.1-1028.3. Here I am following the translation and numbering taken from Cuomo, 2000, p. 93, emphasis added. Henceforth, Pappus's text will be quoted from Cuomo's translation from Greek. For the Latin transcription of Pappus *Mathematicae collectiones*, see Guicciardini, 2009, p. 296, footnote 9.

²⁶³ Pappus, *Mathematical collection*, as quoted in Cuomo, 2000, p. 93. Right before commenting on Hero's division, Pappus remarks: "For theoretical [mechanics] investigates the causes of rest and local motion of bodies, and their movement in space, in their generalities, and not only investigates the causes of whatever moves according to nature" (*Ibid.*)

²⁶⁴ Pappus, *Mathematical collection*, as quoted in Cuomo, 2000, p. 93.

²⁶⁵ The remaining passage of Pappus's *Mathematical collection* that I have been quoting to establish the parallel that Newton traces between Ancients and Moderns is devoted, principally, to vindicate the practical usage of mechanics. As S. Cuomo has observed, "Pappus is not a unique case. The authors of our extant texts of mechanics often come up with a definition and a history of their discipline; they seem to be particularly aware that their topic has a past and that it changes over time. Given that attitudes unfavourable to mechanics existed in antiquity (...), this heightened self-awareness can be seen as a reaction to them, and a reaffirmation of identity in the face of opposition" (Cuomo, 2000, p. 95). But in the present context, as is clear, this is not Newton's case.

Since those who practice an art do not generally work with a high degree of exactness, the whole subject of *mechanics* is distinguished from *geometry* by the attribution of exactness to *geometry* and of anything less than exactness to *mechanics*. (*Ibid.*)

Here, Newton's hint of the glory of geometry, by virtue of its exactness, is an important step towards the legitimation of the mathematical / geometrical form of investigation adopted in his study on the workings of nature, and the eventual perfection of the mathematical principles by means of experimental evidence. As it happens, and in keeping with the ancient thought of analysis and synthesis in geometry, in the *Commentary on Euclid*, this way of reasoning is praised. On the word of Proclus, in geometry, and more especially in Euclid's *Elements*, "its dearness and organic perfection are secured by the progression from the more simple to the more complex and by the foundation of the investigation upon common notions, while generality of demonstration is secured by the progression through the theorems which are primary and of the nature of principles to the things sought. As for the things which seem to be wanting, they are partly to be discovered by the same methods (...), partly alien to the character of a selection of elements as introducing hopeless and boundless complexity (...), and partly developed from things handed down (...) as causes".²⁶⁶

The next idea that Newton declares in order to develop the theme of accuracy between mechanics and geometry is the discernment of the sources of errors as rooted in the practice. Accordingly, an erroneous result does not come as a by-product *per se*, on account of pertaining to mechanics. Errors do not come "from the art but from those who practice the art" (*Ibid.*). It seems to be that here Newton considers the art in itself perfect as such, and so therefore, "anyone who works with less exactness is a more imperfect mechanic, and if anyone could work with the greatest exactness, he would be the most perfect mechanic of all" (*Ibid.*).

This statement has been commented on by Guicciardini who underlined the sharpness of Newton's criticisms to the conception of mechanics as "lacking in the exactness proper to geometry". Then he remarks that practical mechanics, by its own nature, is prone to errors. In fact, "in the application of mechanics to the construction of machines people necessarily realize imperfect constructs". And quite the opposite is what, for Guicciardini, occurs in nature, "the workings of nature are regulated by mathematical laws studied by rational mechanics". In general terms, I consider these are perspicacious statements. Notwithstanding this (and this is not what Guicciardini attempts to say as far as I read him), it is important not to be tempted to interpret this

²⁶⁶ Proclus, *Commentary on Euclid* [Friedlein edition], pp. 72 ff. As quoted in Heath, 1956, vol. 1, p. 115. This is not to say, notwithstanding this, that the underlying metaphysical assumptions regarding geometry in particular and mathematics in general share a common stance both in Newton and Proclus. As S. Cuomo has pointed out, "Proclus believed that mathematics was intrinsic to the fabric of things, and that its language enabled one to articulate the knowledge of reality: the relation between whole and parts could be expressed in terms of divisibility; the bonds between disparate parts of the same universe could be seen as proportions; the generation of beings from the divine Monad, the One which is the principle of everything, was a sort of multiplication, and so on. Mathematical objects themselves are intermediate between the intelligibles and the sensibles and consequently reflect the human condition – in fact, the soul itself is intermediate between indivisible principles and divided corporeal ones, between eternal existence and temporal activity. Mathematics is then the knowledge most appropriate to human nature. Proclus also talks of a 'general' or 'whole' mathematics, which should deal with the whole spectrum of its applications, from lower forms such as mechanics, optics and catoptrics to the knowledge of divine beings" (Cuomo, 2001, p. 237).

last remark as Newton having in mind a certain kind of Platonic conception of mathematics. In such a case the Creation would be detached from the Creator once this very act of the Creation had been executed. In nature, continues Guicciardini, there are no flaws, “and the greatest exactness reigns, since the world is under the rule of a *mechanicus omnium perfectissimus*” (Guicciardini, 2009, p. 267). Here again a nuance is in case. The expression ‘the greatest exactness reigns’ should not be taken too literally since as we know, from the 31st Query of the *Opticks*, even though the system of the world will continue for many Ages, owing to the general irregularities produced by the mutual attraction of the sun and planets, imperfections “will be apt to increase, till this System wants a Reformation” (Newton, 1952, p. 402).²⁶⁷

The significance of this statement in the Preface for Newton’s natural philosophy becomes clear when the main goal of the investigation is declared, a couple of lines below in the Preface. So far it is adequate to keep in mind the framework within which the *Principia* deploys its argumentative structure, namely, the science of motion insofar as it forms part of natural philosophy.²⁶⁸ On the other hand, mechanics as a science of motion implies agency. In order to grasp the deep gist of Newton’s meaning in talking about what could be understood as grades of perfection in the very agency of motion, we are required to focus on nature as the subject matter of this work, and additionally it is fitting to bear in mind the idea that he who works ‘with the greatest exactness, he would be the most perfect mechanic of all.’ This idea will be enhanced right after the analysis of the Preface by the examining of associated texts where Newton displays his philosophy of mathematics in more detail.

The subsequent assertion in the Preface after the one related to the exactness and the sources of inaccuracies, is what I take to be one the most prominent points expressed in the introductory remarks to the *Principia*. There, Newton affirms:

For the description of straight lines and circles, “which is the foundation of *geometry*,” appertains to *mechanics*. *Geometry* does not teach how to describe these straight lines and circles, but postulates such a description (Newton, 1999, pp. 381 – 382, quotation marks added).

Thus, mechanics provides the concrete referent to problems in geometry and geometry develops the exact mathematical solution –as a kind of scaffold– to the problem formulated. It is this same sense that the correct functioning of a machine depends on the proper mathematical design and

²⁶⁷ See Kubrin Newton and the cyclical cosmos... To put this article in “References”.

²⁶⁸ In general terms, during the sixteenth-and seventeenth-centuries the intellectual, institutional and social gaps between applied mechanics and natural philosophy became narrower to the point that even rational mechanics preserved practical component. Along this process practical mechanics enlarged its intellectual status by emphasising its utility. This was not the situation as regards natural philosophy. In point of fact, by the second half of seventeenth century natural philosophy formed part of the major academic disciplines with strong links to theology, not to mention the close relationship established with theology within the religious and social spheres, as testified by the Boyle lectures, to give an instance. See Bertoloni Meli, 2006; Westfall, 2001. The background to the mathematization of Nature 321-339. In *Isaac Newton’s Natural Philosophy*. Domenico Bertoloni Meli (2006). Mechanics. In *The Cambridge history of science* volume 3. Early modern science, pp. 632-672.

construction. As for the understanding of the work to be done, that of describing insofar as pertaining to geometry, it is clear that they are problems of mechanics. Furthermore, from the definition of “postulate”, they guarantee the existence of certain geometrical forms, that is to say, their constructability by means of ruler and compasses.²⁶⁹ According to Proclus, for example, we know that “the postulate bids us contrive and find some subject-matter to exhibit a property simple and easily grasped”.²⁷⁰ For Aristotle, in his *Posterior analytics*, we are told that “a postulate is something not in accordance with the opinion of the learner which, though demonstrable, you assume and use without proving it”.²⁷¹

Consistent with Newton’s criterion, therefore, mechanics comprises problems (‘the description of straight lines and circles’, for instance) which imply the component of geometrical construction by means of some other given components. The presentation of such problems is stated in a specific manner in such a way that “the elements which are given are expressed as numbers, the procedure is by calculation of numbers, and the element which is sought will also be expressed as a specific number”.²⁷² Thus, in accordance with Proclus “every problem and every theorem which is complete with all its parts perfect purports to contain in itself all of the following elements: enunciation, setting-out definition or specification, construction or machinery, proof, and conclusion”.²⁷³

In keeping with the notion according to which the problems of geometry are, in effect, problems of mechanics, Newton continues:

Geometry postulates that a beginner has learned to describe lines and circles exactly before he approaches the threshold of *geometry*, and then it teaches how problems are solved by these operations. To describe straight lines and to describe circles are problems, but not problems in *geometry*. *Geometry* postulates the solution of these problems from *mechanics* and teaches the use of the problems thus solved. And *geometry* can boast that with so few principles obtained from other fields, it can do so much (Newton, p. 1999, p. 382).

Having rounded off the main arguments for the relationship between geometry and mechanics, insofar as the latter precedes the former, it could be established that: (1) Mechanics has the privileged place of foundation for geometry inasmuch as geometrical figures are generated by motion, and the solution of geometrical problems is possible by means of knowing “how the figures are kinematically generated” (Guicciardini, 2009, p. 298). (2) Then comes that part of mechanics that solves problems rigorously through demonstrations. This is the rational mechanics, which shows how the figures from geometry are generated, and so generating geometrical object. Finally,

²⁶⁹ Árpád Szabó. *The beginnings of Greek mathematics*. Dordrecht: D. Reidel Publishing Company, p. 304.

²⁷⁰ Proclus, *Commentary on Euclid* [Friedlein edition], p. 181. As quoted in Heath, 1956, vol. 1, p. 123.

²⁷¹ Aristotle, *Posterior analytics* 76b 35-40. Ed. J. Barnes.

²⁷² Cuomo, 2000, p. 23.

²⁷³ Proclus, *Commentary on Euclid*, [Friedlein edition], p. 221. As quoted in Heath, 1956, p. 129.

we have geometry which, as said by Newton, ‘postulates the solution of these problems from *mechanics* and teaches the use of the problems thus solved’.²⁷⁴ This being so, Newton resumes,

Geometry is founded on mechanical practice and is nothing other than that part of *universal mechanics* which reduces the art of measuring to exact propositions and demonstrations (Newton, 1999, p. 382).

Geometry, insofar as forming part of the ‘universal mechanics’ serves to fill the gap –or to establish continuity– between speculative physics and mathematical demonstration. From this perspective, geometry will deal with forces of various types creating laws of relations to the respective motions analysed.²⁷⁵ Alan Gabbey has pointed out the common view of mechanics, as it is related to geometry, in the “sense of the scope and nature of mechanics was emerging during the 1660s, at least in England” (Gabbey, 1992, p. 313). Thus, for instance, writing about mechanics John Wallis affirmed: “we understand it to be the part of geometry that deals with [local] motion, and investigates, apodictically and using geometrical reasoning, the force with which such and such a motion takes place”.²⁷⁶ Some lines above this quotation, Wallis defined mechanics along the lines of the traditional division of practical and rational, but then he proceeded to highlight the exactness (‘apodictically’) he was keen to emphasise. In the same vein we find Newton’s special emphasis to the proper kind of mechanics he was to undertake in his *Principia*, namely, rational mechanics. Indeed, in the Preface he continues:

But since the manual arts are applied especially to making bodies move, *geometry* is commonly used in reference to magnitude, and *mechanics* in reference to motion (Newton, 1999, p. 382).

Having determined that mechanics –the science of motion– is the foundation of geometry – the science of the analysis of magnitude–, Newton is able to establish the scope of his investigation in the *Principia*.

²⁷⁴ See Guicciardini, 2009, pp. 297-298.

²⁷⁵ I find it apt to make reference to Guicciardini’s remark concerning the parallel between Newton’s usages of ‘universal mechanics’ and ‘universal arithmetic’. In the words of this scholar, he “was unable to locate other places where Newton employed the term *mechanica universalis*. This term has some resemblance to “*Arithmetica universalis*,” the title of one of Newton’s major mathematical works. The reason this mathematical discipline (now called algebra) is defined as universal is that it deals both with practical arithmetic (the science of “numbers and numerable things”) and the abstract manipulation of letters standing for constants and variables (this discipline was often called *arithmetica speciosa*). It is tempting to interpret “universal mechanics” as a discipline that comprises both rational and practical mechanics. However, the idea conveyed by the lines [in the Preface] is clear: geometrical objects are generated by motion, and that is why their description falls within the scope of mechanics” (Guicciardini, 2009, p. 298).

²⁷⁶ John Wallis, *Pars prima*, Cap. 1 (‘De motu generalis’). *Opera mathematica*, 3 vols. (Oxford, 1693-1699), vol. 1, p. 575. As quoted in Gabbey, 1992, p. 313.

In this sense *rational mechanics* will be the science, expressed in exact propositions and demonstrations, of the motions that result from any forces whatever and of the forces that are required for any motions whatever (*Ibid.*).

This precise approach is expressed in a mathematical way, consisting in definitions, laws, problems, theorems, demonstrations, etc. and it takes as fundamental starting point physical reasonings provided by mechanics. In so doing, first, Newton is reiterating the exactness of his approach to the study of nature inasmuch as it relies on rational mechanics which in turn is the foundation of geometry. Secondly, this idea is immediately connected to the main aim of Newton's rational mechanics in the *Principia*, and this is precisely an enquiry into the causal principles of motions, and such principles are not other than the forces that are 'required for any motions whatever'.²⁷⁷ As a matter of fact, in the scholium to the Definitions the idea is expressed straightforwardly in saying that "the causes which distinguish true motions from relative motions are the forces impressed upon bodies to generate motion" (Newton, 1999, p. 412). Furthermore, in the essay entitled *De gravitatione* force, as the causal principle of motion, is defined in the following terms:

Force is the causal principle of motion and rest. And it is either an external one that generates or destroys or otherwise changes impressed motion in some body; or it is an internal principle by which existing motion or rest is conserved in a body, and by which any being endeavours to continue in its state and opposes resistance (Newton, 1968, p. 148).

In order to avoid a misperception of his objective, Newton introduces an interpolation aimed at the clarity of his sense. This consists in remarking that "the ancients studied this part of *mechanics* in terms of the *five powers*²⁷⁸ that relate to the manual arts and paid hardly any attention to gravity (since it is not a manual power) except in the moving of weights by these powers" (Newton, 1999, p. 382). Then, he passes to declare the ambit of his research, specifically, the forces of nature. Thus, he continues:

But since we are concerned with natural philosophy rather than manual arts, and are writing about natural rather than manual powers, we concentrate on aspects of gravity, levity, elastic forces, resistance of fluids, and forces of this sort, whether attractive or impulsive (*Ibid.*).

Once the reader has gained clarity with respect to the philosophical basis of his approach, Newton is in a secure position to state the crux of the Preface and in turn of the three books that constitute the *Principia*: the deduction of forces from motions and motions from forces within a mathematical framework. So, he affirms:

²⁷⁷ See Guicciardini, 2009, p. 298-299.

²⁷⁸ That is to say, the wheel and axle, the lever, the wedge, the compound pulley, and the screw.

Therefore our present work sets forth mathematical principles of natural philosophy. For the basic problem of philosophy seems to be to discover the forces of nature from the phenomena of motions and then to demonstrate the other phenomena from these forces (*Ibid.*).

In the remainder of the Preface Newton presents a description of his *Principia* and how it is organised in a geometrical form of investigation. His strong confidence on this method of investigation leads him to assert that even those phenomena not analysed in his masterpiece could be explained by this form of enquiry. The last sentence of the Preface, “I hope that the principles set down here will shed some light on either this mode of philosophizing or some truer one”, far from being a methodological or a philosophical deprecation from the pen of Newton, is –as I see it– a mark of trust in his philosophy. The final part of this chapter highlights precisely this point. Given the empiricist epistemology that Newton embraced, it is not valid to expect an ultimate and culminating point in our understanding of nature.²⁷⁹ Thus, Newton ends the Preface as follows:²⁸⁰

It is to these ends that the general propositions in books 1 and 2 are directed, while in book 3 our explanation of the system of the world illustrates these propositions. For in book 3, by means of propositions demonstrated mathematically in books 1 and 2, we derive from celestial phenomena the gravitational forces by which bodies tend toward the sun and toward the individual planets. Then the motions of the planets, the comets, the moon, and the sea are deduced from these forces by propositions that are also mathematical. If only we could derive the other phenomena of nature from mechanical principles by the same kind of reasoning! For many things lead me to have a suspicion that all phenomena may depend on certain forces by which the particles of bodies, by causes not yet known, either are impelled toward one another and cohere in regular figures, or are repelled from one another and recede. Since these forces are unknown, philosophers have hitherto made trial of nature in vain. But I hope that the principles set down here will shed some light on either this mode of philosophizing or some truer one (Newton, 1999, p. 382).

Thus far, I have highlighted what I consider to be the main ideas involved in Newton’s Preface to his *Principia*. Now, it is suitable to underline two main ideas before proceeding to the next part of my interpretation.

²⁷⁹ Already in his early researches, Newton adopted certain kind of agnosticism related to our ability to comprehend completely the innermost nature of the workings of natural world by means of mathematics and experience: “we, mere men possessed only of finite intelligence, can neither designate all their terms nor so grasp them as to ascertain exactly the quantities we desire from them” (Newton, 1967-1981, vol. 2, p. 243). Nonetheless, he also avers that his method in the *Principia* “will shed some light on either this mode of philosophizing or some truer one” as testified by the last sentence of the Preface.

²⁸⁰ For the purpose of the present analysis, the last paragraph of the Preface has not been taken into consideration. It deals with the role played by Halley in the process of publication as editor.

First and foremost, it is central for the purpose in the remainder of this final chapter to highlight the relationship that Newton hierarchically structures between rational mechanics and geometry. Right from the outset, Newton asserts the empirical basis and content of his mathematical investigation of nature. In relying upon the Ancient main values and goals of geometrical thought, there is not only a token of a feeling of respect and admiration for that philosophy of mathematics but, what is more important, the demand for exact demonstrations of problems related to facts of experience.²⁸¹

Secondly, the focus on rational mechanics, instead of practical, is aimed at endowing with exactness the quality of the results obtained in the subsequent three books that comprise the *Principia*. This is also done in order to provide a foundation for the geometrical treatment of the problems that this book deals with. This point was not new in Newton's thinking by the time of his *Principia*. As a matter of fact, as early as he was Lucasian professor, in the third lecture delivered on optics he proclaimed what eventually became the chief demand for certainty in all his philosophical endeavours. These words, indeed, are thoughtfully echoed in the Preface. In this lecture on optics Newton declared the need of a mathematical treatment of the phenomenon of colours on which there is a lot of experimental evidence. In these terms:

The generation of colors includes so much geometry, and the knowledge of colors is supported by so much evidence (...). I can thus attempt to extend the bounds of mathematics somewhat, just as astronomy, geography, navigation, optics, and mechanics are considered mathematical sciences even if they deal with physical things: the heavens, earth, ships, light, and local motion. Thus, although colors may belong to physics, the science of them must nevertheless be considered mathematical, insofar as they are treated by mathematical reasoning. Indeed, since an exact science of them seems to be one of the most difficult that philosophy is in need of, I hope to show –as it were, by example– how valuable is mathematics in natural philosophy (Newton, 1984, pp. 88-89).

Next, he expresses the link between geometry and natural philosophy, and the benefits that the latter receives from the first, in a similar manner as that of the *Principia*.

I therefore urge geometers to investigate nature more rigorously, and those devoted to natural science to learn geometry first. Hence the former shall not entirely spend their time

²⁸¹ Among the several manuscripts that Newton composed after 1710, related to the controversy with Leibniz on the invention of calculus, one of them consists in a declaration on the manner of application of analysis and synthesis and their application to the *Principia*. The following fragment shows clearly the experiential basis of geometry. Thus he writes: "The geometry of the ancients had, of course, primarily to do with magnitudes, but propositions on magnitudes were from time to time demonstrated by means of local motion: as, for instance, when the equality of triangles in Proposition 4 of Book 1 of Euclid's Elements were demonstrated by transporting either one of the triangles into the other's place. Also, the genesis of magnitudes through continuous motion was received in geometry: when, for instance, a straight line were drawn into a straight line so as to generate an area, and an area were drawn into a straight line to generate a solid" (NMP, VIII, p. 455).

in speculations of no value to human life, nor shall the latter, while working assiduously with an absurd method, perpetually fail to reach their goal (*Ibid.*)

A noticeable characteristic of this assertion is the contrast established between the mere speculative way of proceeding when the study is detached from utility, and the ever-lasting abstract mathematical style when devoid of concrete ontological content, related to experience. Lastly, as a criticism to the state of affairs of the current natural philosophy, Newton claimed the *desideratum* of certainty based on mathematical exactness, in contrast with the conjectural or hypothetical methods in philosophy.²⁸²

But truly with the help of philosophical geometers and geometrical philosophers, instead of the conjectures and probabilities that are being blazoned about everywhere, we shall finally achieve a science of nature supported by the highest evidence (*Ibid.*).

This being so, there are then more things to say about the Preface in order to account for the ontological causation of gravity force in the *Principia*, besides the two points just mentioned.

5.2. The ontological basis of mechanics in the *Principia*

Now I will focus for a while on the metaphysical assumptions underlying Newton's hierarchical scheme of mechanics – rational mechanics – geometry, and more precisely, on the ontological basis of mechanics in the *Principia*.

The key passage to understand such a basis is that of the Preface itself where Newton states: “anyone who works with less exactness is a more imperfect mechanic, and if anyone could work with the greatest exactness, he would be the most perfect mechanic of all” (Newton, 1999, p. 381). One could perfectly ask what is at stake in this apparently conventional piece of rhetoric, all the more since manual arts are discarded from the analysis undertaken in this work.²⁸³ The answer to this question comes, partly, when one recognises that the mathematical principles that Newton's establishes in the *Principia* are those related to nature.

²⁸² Alan Shapiro has pointed to the fact that Newton progressively changed his mind to the point of expressing a certain kind of skepticism regarding the possibility of obtaining the definitive certainty and exactness by means of experimentalism. “Newton followed this mathematical tradition and stressed both the mathematical nature of his theories and the certitude of his deductions from experiment. Although he soon modified his excessive claims and more carefully distinguished mathematical demonstrations from less than certain experimental conclusions, he continued to prize mathematical theories and seek ‘truth’ and ‘certainty,’ words that appear frequently in his writings. Only in the last decades of his life did he accept the probabilism of his contemporaries” (Shapiro, 1993, p. 14). In actual fact, in the Rule 4 of the Rules for the study of natural philosophy, one can observe this form of ‘mitigated skepticism’ to use the expression of David Hume (*Enquiry*, XII, 3). See also Shapiro 2004.

²⁸³ “The ancients studied this part of *mechanics* in terms of the *five powers* that relate to the manual arts [i.e., the five mechanical powers] and paid hardly any attention to gravity (since it is not a manual power) except in the moving of weights by these powers. But since we are concerned with natural philosophy rather than manual arts...” (Newton, 1999, p. 382).

According to James E. McGuire, the word “principle” could mean three things in the late seventeenth century. “A principle could mean something formulated or asserted, i.e., a logical truth or a moral maxim; the primitive *arche* out of which all things could be held to originate; or the primary cause of existing phenomena as, for example, the ‘principles of matter and motion’ basic to the various mechanical philosophies” (McGuire, 1970, p. 179-180). The *Principia* itself as a whole is associated to the third sense, but in the General Scholium (appended to the second edition of 1713) God is named in the second sense, that is to say, as the Creator who by his will created “this most elegant system of the sun, planets, and comets” which “could not have arisen without the design and dominion of an intelligent and powerful being” (Newton, 1999, p. 940). Furthermore, and more significantly, there is the way that Newton declares God as a ‘principle’ in a draft preface intended for the *Opticks* of 1704. In this unpublished paper Newton stated:

One principle in Philosophy is y^e being of a God or Spirit infinite eternal omniscient omnipotent, & the best argument for such a being is the frame of nature & chiefly the contrivance of y^e bodies of living creatures. (Newton, Add. 3970.3. 479^r. As quoted in McGuire, 1970, p. 183).

This conception of God in the abovementioned senses, and its relationship with mechanics –the foundation of geometry– can be enhanced by connecting the declarations of the Preface to Newton’s allied papers on geometry, and on metaphysics of nature, in order to answer the question formulated above.

In effect, in 1693 Newton undertook the composition of an extensive treatise on the nature and method of geometry.²⁸⁴ In several important respects, this work bears strong resemblances to the Preface of the *Principia*. The first statement of the *Geometry* has to do with the applied use of geometry in land surveying. In fact, problems related to the measuring of lands “were very speedily and accurately constructed by descriptions of straight and circular lines” by means of geometry. Immediately, he observes in the same line of exposition as in the Preface that

Geometry neither teaches how to describe a plane nor postulates its description, though this is its whole foundation. To be sure, the planes of fields are not formed by the practitioner but merely measured. Geometry does not teach how to describe a straight line and a circle but postulates them; in other words, it postulates that the practitioner has learnt these operations before he attains the threshold of geometry. Once, however, these are previously understood and granted it teaches all the other operations of mensuration under the head of ‘problems’, and likewise under the head of ‘theorems’ compares quantities with one another in order from the measured and the found to derive things which have not been measured (Newton, 1968-1980, vol. 7, p. 287).

²⁸⁴ This treatise was written in Latin and bears the name of *Geometriae libri duo*.

Newton next passes to deal with the problem of exactness both in geometry and mechanics. In the following passage, he undertakes a fierce criticism of those, like Descartes, who considered that mechanical curves were lacking in exactness. According to Descartes, the ancients did not believe that the so-called constructions of the conic sections on a plane surface could be exact, and for this reason he declares that “it is true that the conic sections were never freely received into ancient geometry”, in so far as this type of complex curves demanded for their solution ‘linear’ problems, – those that required the use of more complex curves– thus deeming them untreatable in the field of geometry, whence they were called ‘mechanical’, according to Descartes narrative (Descartes, 1925, p. 43; Domski, 2003, p. 1115-1118; Guicciardini, 2009, pp. 42-47). For him, “probably the real explanation of the refusal of ancient geometers to accept curves more complex than the conic sections lies in the fact that the first curves to which their attention was attracted happened to be the spiral, the quadratrix, and similar curves, which really do belong only to mechanics, and are not among those curves that I think should be included here, since they must be conceived of as described by two separate movements whose relation does not admit of exact determination” (1925, p. 44). To Newton’s eyes, such an opinion should be completely rejected, since it is a mistake to qualify mechanics as imperfect in view of the imperfection of manual arts of practitioners of mechanics. Accordingly, he comments:

It has now, however, come to be usual to regard as geometrical everything which is exact, and as mechanical all that proves not to be of the kind, as though nothing could possibly be mechanical and at the same time exact. But this common belief is a stupid one, and has its origin in nothing else than that geometry postulates an exact mechanical practice in the description of a straight line and a circle, and moreover is exact in all its operations, while mechanics as it is commonly exercised is imperfect and without exact laws. It is from the ignorance and imperfection of mechanics that the common opinion defines mechanics. On this reasoning a thing would be the more mechanical the more imperfect it was (Newton, 1968-1980, vol. 7, p. 289).

Having established his position regarding the exactness as belonging to mechanics in opposition to the prejudice on inaccuracy, Newton then passes to specify through the agency of what means the issue of geometry takes its origin. Thus, he writes:

Both the genesis of the subject-matter of geometry (...) and the fabrication of its postulates pertain to mechanics. *Any plane figures executed by God, nature or any technician* you will be measured by geometry in the hypothesis that they are exactly constructed (p. 289, emphasis added).

From this perspective, it is clear that geometry mirrors the agency and power of God in constructing and describing the motions executed by him. By following the line of argumentation of Newton both in the Preface and in the *Geometry*, we could say that in the reading the Book of Nature the

problem –the “basic problem of philosophy”, as Newton puts it– can be enunciated in this manner: ‘to discover the forces of nature from the phenomena of motions and then to demonstrate the other phenomena from these forces’.

An important aspect of this view of God as mechanic and geometer is that in conceiving of him as geometer, it implies agency and purpose; the contrasting conception would be that of considering God as a calculator. This important feature, explicit in the *Geometry* and implicit in the Preface of the *Principia*,²⁸⁵ has been underlined by Guicciardini. “A supreme calculator” he writes “would be able to create a world that functions according to the necessity of an algorithm. A supreme geometer, instead, freely acts in nature, creating regions of impenetrable space, moving bodies, and intervening in the absolute space and time in which he abides” (2009, p. 315). This contrast serves, in turn, to illustrate the underlying metaphysical assumptions that divided Newton’s and Leibniz’s philosophies of nature with respect to their respective theologies.²⁸⁶

Coming back to the basic problem of natural philosophy in the *Principia* (the deduction of forces from motions and vice versa), it is also relevant to relate Newton’s pronouncement in the Preface according to which ‘anyone could work with the greatest exactness, he would be the most perfect mechanic of all’ to his earlier *De gravitatione*.

This treatise is important in so far as in it we find a valuable piece of exposition of Newton’s metaphysics which is articulated by his theological voluntarism. Dealing with the creation of matter, Newton states:

We may imagine that there are empty spaces scattered through the world, one of which, defined by certain limits, happens by divine power to be impervious to bodies, and *ex hypothesi* it is manifest that this would resist the motions of bodies and perhaps reflect them, and assume all the properties of a corporeal particle, except that it will be motionless (Newton, 1668, p. 139).

Needless to say, Newton here is speaking from a metaphysical standpoint, suggesting a possible genesis of matter. Nonetheless, this speculation is closely related to the experience we have of the world.²⁸⁷ This idea is further buttressed by saying that “if all this world were constituted of this kind of being, it would seem hardly any different. And hence these beings will either be bodies or like bodies” (*Ibid.*). Right after defining bodies as certain regions impervious to bodies, Newton describes how God could have created matter, and additionally what conditions it should exhibit. Thus, he writes:

²⁸⁵ Unambiguously expressed, it should be said that implicit in the first edition of 1687, in absence of the General Scholium appended to the later editions of 1713 and 1726, where God as the Creator becomes explicit.

²⁸⁶ These are known as voluntarism and intellectualism, represented by Newton and Leibniz respectively. For an excellent analysis of voluntarism and intellectualism in the rise of modern science, see Henry, 2009. For a different view on the role of voluntarism and early modern science see Harrison, 2002.

²⁸⁷ This elaboration is very much in keeping with the pronouncement of the General Scholium where phenomena have a fundamental role. “For whatever is not deduced from the phenomena must be called a hypothesis; and hypotheses, whether metaphysical or physical, or based on occult qualities, or mechanical, have no place in experimental philosophy” (Newton, 1999, p. 943).

If they are bodies, then we can define bodies as determined quantities of extension which omnipresent God *endows with certain conditions*. These conditions are (1) *that they be mobile (...)* (2) *that two of this kind cannot coincide anywhere (...)*; (3) *that they can excite various perceptions of the senses and the fancy in created minds* (p. 140, emphasis added).

Subsequently, Newton itemises five philosophical features of matter upon which its creation is founded on. The first one asserts that for the existence of matter it is not required to follow the line of reasoning of Scholasticism by proposing “some unintelligible substance”, since “extension and an act of the divine will are enough”. Secondly, such a matter (or bodies) will be as real as bodies are, and they are apt to be called proper substances, for “whatever reality we attribute to bodies arises from their phenomena and sensible qualities”. In the third place, in this conception of matter “there is almost the same analogy that the Aristotelians postulate between the *materia prima* and substantial forms”. Thus, while the matter is capable of assuming all forms, in Newton’s view “any form may be transferred through any space, and everywhere denote the same body” (*Ibid.*).

The last two philosophical features regarding the creation of matter are the most important ones, in view of the approach of the present analysis. Effectively, in the fourth feature Newton asserts that between his conceptions of extension and impressed form in matter there is more reality –i.e., ways of experiencing them– than in those of *materia prima* and substantial form of the Aristotelians –which, in the view of Newton, could be deemed as speculative. As for matter, it “can excite various perceptions of the senses and the fancy in created minds. (...) For it is certain that God can stimulate our perception by his own will, and thence apply such power to the effects of his will” (pp. 140, 139).

Here we find a recurrent idea stated time and again by Newton in diverse contexts. Thus, for example, in the abovementioned paper on analysis and synthesis in the *Principia* (1710s), discussing the nature of fluxions and fluents in so far as they are generated by motion, he observes that “quantities increasing by continuous flow we call fluents, the speeds of flowing we call fluxions and the momentary increments we call moments, and the method whereby we treat quantities of this sort we call the method of fluxions and moments” (Newton, 1976-1981, vol. 3, p. 455). And, as he stated in his *The method of fluxions and infinite series*, thus “we may have an expedient for exhibiting fluxions and fluents geometrically and mechanically, in all circumstances so as to make them the *objects of sense and ocular demonstration*” (Newton, 1736, p. 270, emphasis added). This shows the deep-seated concern on the part of Newton for making accessible to perceptual experience, to use Guicciardini’s expression, his mathematical method (Guicciardini, 2009, p. 314).

As for the creation of matter and the way that Newton has suggested its genesis –i.e., it is created out of the space but is not space in itself, and it has more reality than the Aristotelian prime matter–, there is the problem of the secondary causation of matter’s mobility, which is the very crux of the causation of force and the core of the allied problem of action at a distance. Newton indeed, admits that it could be judged as problematic, but

If there is any difficulty in this conception *it is not in the form (formae) that God imparts to space, but in the manner (modi) by which he imparts it* (Newton, 1668, p. 141, 107, emphasis added).

In this pronouncement we find an explicit reference by Newton to the distinction he makes between primary and secondary causation. Secondary causation in Newton's natural philosophy is deemed problematic (both by his critics and for historians of science) in so far as it implies, or involves, the presence of real powers or forces²⁸⁸ –as opposed to speculative hypotheses²⁸⁹– which furnishes matter with the ability of motion (p. 140).²⁹⁰ Notwithstanding this, Newton continues in *De gravitatione*,

That is not to be regarded as a difficulty, since the same question arises with regard to the way we move our bodies, and nevertheless we do believe that we can move them (p. 141).

Our nescience regarding the *mode* by which we move our bodies does not impede us from the awareness that we experience it in everyday life, as a matter of fact. This agnosticism recognises the limitations of human knowledge, while at the same time avoids foreclosing the goals of mathematics and experience. Certainly, the lesson would be, therefore, that in natural philosophy it is not possible to aspire to the certainty belonging to God (the absolute certainty), and rather, it should limit its scope and restrict them to matters within the range of experience, without incurring imaginative or speculative ways of explanation. So, there is no reason to stop the enquiry into the workings of the universe. As a matter of fact, Newton continues,

If that were known to us [the way we move our bodies], by like reasoning we should also know how God can move bodies, and expel them from a certain space bounded in a given figure, and prevent the expelled bodies or any others from penetrating into it again, that is, cause that space to be impenetrable and assume the form of body (*Ibid.*)²⁹¹

²⁸⁸ Newton, as we know, dealt with this problem by resorting to active principles and this is a central theme to deal with below.

²⁸⁹ Roger Cotes, the editor of the second edition of the *Principia* (1713), is an apt representative of Newton's rejection of hypotheses. Indeed, in his preface, he wrote: "Those who take the foundation of their speculations from hypotheses, even if they then proceed most rigorously according to mechanical laws, are merely putting together a romance, elegant perhaps and charming, but nevertheless a romance. (...) For even if these philosophers could account for the phenomena with the greatest exactness on the basis of their hypotheses, still they cannot be said to have given us a true philosophy and to have found the true causes of the celestial motions until they have demonstrated either that these causes really do exist or at least that others do not exist" (Newton, 1999, p. 393).

²⁹⁰ These powers or forces have the advantage of being liable to experimental tests, as it is abundantly shown in the *Principia*.

²⁹¹ In a draft letter sent by Newton to the editor of the *Memoirs of Literature* he used the same argumentative structure for defending gravity as a quality of bodies. Below I will comment this important letter in the light of gravity as a superadded quality.

Based upon the phenomenon of how we move our bodies, and in analogy to it, Newton has deduced the nature of matter. Such a parallel was aimed at, first, reducing the explanation of the nature of created things to the will of God; secondly, to that, in the line of this objective, we could have in “our innermost consciousness” that by the sheer will of God the world was created; and thirdly, the correlation aims to show that the “analogy between the Divine faculties and our own is greater than has formerly been perceived by Philosophers” (p. 141).

Regarding such an analogy, of course, there are some caveats to be highlighted, which have as a nucleus the difference in grade in creatures (as images of God) with respect to the Creator.²⁹² One of those caveats according to Newton is that, in the precise case of the power of creating we can only simulate creation; we do not cause it. Thus, for instance, we cannot move bodies other than ours, we can only move our own bodies, to which, Newton observes, “we are united not by our own will but by the divine constitution of things” (*Ibid.*). It is not unreasonable to infer from this reasoning the close relationship it bears with the consideration of the power of motion (force) united to bodies by the divine constitution of matter, as well. This inference, furthermore, also could be applied to the succeeding caution which underlines the fact that we cannot “move bodies in any way but only in accord with those laws which God has imposed on us” (*Ibid.*).²⁹³ In fact, matter can only move according to the laws established by God; and these laws, in turn, are empirically accessible and mathematically workable.

Having expressed these caveats, Newton deals with the eventual criticism according to which to conceive of God in this manner would be in detriment of God’s own image and power. This reproach would estimate that such a picture of created nature, and specifically of humankind, would reflect a very low idea of God as an untalented creator.²⁹⁴ But this would not be the case, Newton asserts, since

If anyone, however, prefers this our power to be called the finite and lowest level of the power which makes God the Creator, this no more detracts from the divine power than it detracts from God’s intellect that intellect in a finite degree belongs to us also. (...) Rather, if any think it possible that God may produce some intellectual creature so perfect that he could, by divine accord, in turn produce creatures of a lower order, this so far from detracting from the divine power enhances it; for that power which can bring forth creatures

²⁹² As Newton observes on this point: “his image would shine more clearly in us if only he simulated in the faculties granted to us the power of creation in the same degree as his other attributes” (Newton, 1668, p. 141).

²⁹³ A couple of lines below, Newton reasserts this position by saying: “we do not move our bodies by our own independent power but through laws imposed on us by God” (*Ibid.*)

²⁹⁴ This is precisely the type of criticism that Leibniz would have to make years later in view of the way he depicted Newton’s perception of God in the *Principia*. As a matter of fact, the first of the letters which constitute the controversy with Newton, via Clarke, points out this very critic. “Sir Isaac Newton and his followers also have a very odd opinion concerning the work of God. According to their doctrine, God Almighty needs to wind up his watch from time to time, otherwise it would cease to move. He did not, it seems, have sufficient foresight to make it a perpetual motion. No, the machine of God’s making is so imperfect, according to these gentlemen, that he is obliged to clean it now and then by an extraordinary concurrence, and even to mend it, as a clockmaker mends his work; he must consequently be so much the more unskillful a workman as he is more often obliged to mend his work and to set it right” (Leibniz & Clarke, 2000, p. 4).

not only directly but through the mediation of other creatures is exceedingly, not to say infinitely, greater (p. 142).

Given this state of affairs, for Newton, there is no need to declare or to hypothesise an intermediary being, or an immaterial substance, performing the creative action of God through his command, in order to explain natural phenomena.²⁹⁵ Accordingly, Newton affirms:

Some may perhaps prefer to suppose that God imposes on the soul of the world, created by him, the task of endowing definite spaces with the properties of bodies, rather than to believe that this function is directly discharged by God. Therefore the world should not be called the creature of that soul but of God alone, who creates it by constituting the soul of such a nature that the world necessarily emanates [from it] (*Ibid.*).

Not rejecting active principles in general, Newton does reject special intermediary agents like the soul of the world, for instance. Instead of that, and as an alternative, such a performance is proposed to be done directly by God who acting solely by his will furnishes matter with the conditions abovementioned by him.²⁹⁶ In point of fact, Newton asserts:

But I do not see why God himself does not directly inform space with bodies; so long as we distinguish between the formal reason of bodies and the act of divine will. For it is contradictory that it [body] should be the act of willing or anything other than the effect which that act produces in space (*Ibid.*).

Among the various perspectives from which it is possible to comment on about this passage, I would like to point out to its philosophical context first, which is Newton's criticism to Descartes's philosophy in *De gravitatione*; and second, to the analysis of the implications in this pronouncement done by recent scholarship.

As for the philosophical context, this reasoning of Newton is quite alien to a Cartesian, indeed. By contrasting Newton's position to that of Descartes, we can understand more clearly the foundations of both natural philosophers regarding the epistemological imperatives that lie behind their pronouncements about what amounts to a legitimate explanation in natural philosophy. On the part of Newton, we have that he sees nothing obscure in admitting the will of God at the basis

²⁹⁵ For example this is the case with Henry More. See, Henry, 2008. In point of fact, Henry More wrote on the spirit of nature in this manner: I ask (...) if there be not in nature an incorporeal substance which, while it can impress on any body all the qualities of body, or at least most of them, such as motion, figure, position of parts, etc. (...) would be further able, since it is almost certain that this substance removes and stops bodies, to add whatever is involved in such motion, that is it can unite, divide, scatter, bind, form the small parts, order the forms, set in circular motion those which are disposed for it, or move them in any way whatever, arrest their circular motion and do such similar things with them as are necessary to produce (...) light, colours and the other objects of the senses. (More, letter to Descartes, 5 March 1649, in *A Collection of Severall Philosophical Writings of Dr. Henry More* (London, 1662), pp. 79-80. As quoted in Henry, 2008.

²⁹⁶ These conditions are the mobility, the impenetrability, and the perceptibility. See Newton, 1668, p. 140.

of the creation itself. As he remarked in the General Scholium, “we certainly do not know what is the substance of any thing”. And more to the point, he continued,

We see only the shapes and colors of bodies, we hear only their sounds, we touch only their external surfaces, we smell only their odors, and we taste their flavors. But there is no direct sense and there are no indirect reflected actions by which we know innermost substances; much less do we have an idea of the substance of God (Newton, 1999, p. 942).

Here we find a clear précis of Newton’s epistemology which in a draft of what was planned to be a fifth rule of the Rules of the *Principia* was expressed in a negative and admonitory manner. This draft is interesting to the extent that it constitutes –as such I think it could be considered– almost the philosophical *credo* of Newton’s epistemology.²⁹⁷ In this short piece we find not only a restatement of his experimental philosophy based on phenomena, but also–what is even more important– an outright rejection of Descartes’s philosophy. Thus, Newton wrote:

Rule V: Whatever is not derived from things themselves, whether by the external senses or by the sensation of internal thoughts, is to be taken for a hypothesis. Thus I sense that I am thinking, which could not happen unless at the same time I were to sense that I am. But I do not sense that any idea whatever may be innate. And I do not take for a phenomenon only that which is made known to us by the five external senses, but also that which we contemplate in our minds when thinking: such as, I am, I believe, I understand, I remember, I think, I wish, I am unwilling, I am thirsty, I am hungry, I rejoice, I suffer, etc. And those things which neither can be demonstrated from the phenomenon nor follow from it by the argument of induction, I hold as hypotheses (Newton MSS 4003, n. p. As quoted in Koyré, 1965, p. 272).²⁹⁸

On the part of Descartes, in the second set of responses to the objections to his *Meditations* we can achieve a good ground to grasp Descartes’s imperatives in philosophy. In this part of the Objections, Descartes is criticised under the principle that, if one adheres to his main rule of reason, that of avoiding assenting to matters that we do not clearly and distinctly understand, then one would have to renounce believing in the principles of Christian faith, because by their own nature it is not possible to get a clear and distinct perception of them.²⁹⁹ This objection and the subsequent response by Descartes is helpful inasmuch as both Newton’s and Descartes’s pronouncements are related to the way we understand God in his actions and signs. In the case of Descartes, ignoring the

²⁹⁷ “Almost” in view of the higher value of *De gravitatione*, certainly.

²⁹⁸ Newton did not enumerate this page. See Koyré, 1965, pp. 261-272.

²⁹⁹ This objection was raised (probably) by Marin Mersenne. As he expressed it: “If the will never goes astray or errs when it follows the mind’s clear and distinct knowledge, and if the ill lays itself open to danger when it allows a conception of the understanding that is not at all clear and distinct, then take note of the consequences of this. A Turk or anyone else not only does not err in having failed to embrace the Christian religion, but actually would err if he were to embrace it, for indeed he knows the truth of it neither clearly nor distinctly” (Descartes, 2000, p. 74)

basis of judgment as in the case of motion, to give an instance, is the path to error. This stance is quite opposite to Newton's who maintained that we 'do not see why God himself does not directly inform space with bodies; so long as we distinguish between the formal reason of bodies and the act of divine will'. Thus, Descartes writes:

Surely a distinction needs to be made between the subject matter, or the thing to which we give our assent, and the formal reason (*rationem formalem*) that moves the will to give its assent. For it is only in this formal reason that we require transparency (*perspeuitatem*). [In fact,] those who make their judgment in ignorance of the basis of their judgment are the ones who are making a mistake. But a concept is said to be obscure or confused only because something *unknown* is contained in it (Descartes, 2000, p. 87, emphasis added).

Thus, along the lines of Descartes's reasoning we are required to have a clear and distinct idea of the way we move our bodies (the example mentioned by Newton); and according to Newton 'nevertheless we do believe that we can move them'. In the case of matter, we are not to suppose explanatory basis for judgments 'not derived from things themselves, whether by the external senses or by the sensation of internal thoughts'. In point of fact, the required thing that bodies 'can excite various perceptions of the senses and the fancy in created minds'.

For Newton, "the usefulness of the idea of body that I have described is brought out by the fact that it clearly involves the chief truths of metaphysics and thoroughly confirms and explains them. For we cannot postulate bodies of this kind without at the same time supposing that God exists, and has created bodies in empty space out of nothing, and that they are beings distinct from created minds, but able to combine with minds" (Newton, 1668, p. 142). From this point of view, it is not possible for the Cartesian *res extensa* to fulfil these requirements for at least two reasons. First, given Descartes's notion of extension is uncreated, there is the danger of conceiving it as independent to the extent that it is not necessary to consider God's existence. Second, the mind / body distinction is unclear and obscure, given that it is not extended, and therefore, it exists nowhere, which would mean, in the worst case, that it does not exist at all; or the conception of its union is completely incomprehensible.³⁰⁰

5.3. Gravity as a superadded quality and action at a distance

Now, I turn to the implications of Newton's assertion –according to which he does not 'see why God himself does not directly inform space with bodies'– in the recent scholarship.

Based upon this declaration of *De gravitatione*, and mainly on Newton's attitude of rejection towards the aetherial mediums after the publication of the *Principia* in 1687, some scholars have pointed to Newton's tantalising idea of attributing to God the direct responsibility and intervention in the functioning of the universe, once Newton himself has set aside, first, the possibility of *anima mundi* or spirit of nature as he does in *De gravitatione*; and secondly, once he has shown the

³⁰⁰ See Gabbey, 2004.

inadequacy of material media as a means of explanation of the workings of nature, and the utmost difficulty of their mathematical treatment (the *Principia*).³⁰¹ Thus, for example Alexandre Koyré wrote:

It is well known that Newton did not believe gravity to be an “innate, essential and inherent property or matter”; indeed, in 1675, in his *Hypothesis Explaining the Properties of Light*, and in 1679, in a letter to Boyle (28 February 1678/9), he attempted to explain gravity by mechanical means –that is, by the motions or subtle matter or an ethereal medium– but he did not pursue these hopeless attempts, at least for some time; in 1692, in a letter to Bentley, he asked Bentley not to ascribe to him that Epicurean notion; attraction as action at a distance through vacuum without mediation, he told Bentley; was an utter absurdity that nobody could believe in, stating moreover rather clearly that this mediation had to be performed by something which is not material, that is, by God (1965, p. 149).

It is interesting to note the immediate connection that Koyré establishes between Newton’s rejection of action at a distance –once Newton has also rejected the motions of a subtle matter or an ethereal medium– and God as mediator for the attraction among bodies. Interesting because it shows that secondary causation was estimated by the Russian historian only by virtue of ethers and vortices, as the mainstream explanation of the mechanical philosophy. Interesting too, given Koyré’s keen interest in highlighting the metaphysical substructures of scientific thought. As a matter of fact, the final words of the paper from which the above quotation is taken are telling: “later, the problem was very successfully hidden in the concept of field” (p. 163).³⁰²

Other scholars, nonetheless, have been more cautious and, in a more nuanced manner, have pointed to Newton’s tantalising idea of attributing to God the direct intervention in the operations of the world. In this vein, Peter Dear drew attention to this possibility for Newton in his *Revolutionizing the sciences*.

Newton’s need for something to mediate between attracting bodies might be considered the ghost of strict mechanism: *if not* matter as the mediator, then something else that plays the same role? Newton at one point played with the idea that God Himself brought about gravitational behaviours, by making bodies move according to the gravitational laws directly

³⁰¹ Recall, for example the opening words of the General Scholium. Here, Newton states: “The hypothesis of vortices is beset with many difficulties. If, by a radius drawn to the sun, each and every planet is to describe areas proportional to the time, the periodic times of the parts of the vortex must be as the squares of the distances from the sun, If the periodic times of the planets are to be as the $3/2$ powers of the distances from the sun, the periodic times of the parts of the vortex must be as the $3/2$ powers of the distances. If the smaller vortices revolving about Saturn, Jupiter, and the other planets are to be preserved and are to float without agitation in the vortex of the sun, the periodic times of the parts of the solar vortex must be the same. The axial revolutions [i.e., rotations] of the sun and planets, which would have to agree with the motions of their vortices, differ from all these proportions. The motions of comets are extremely regular, observe the same laws as the motions of planets, and cannot be explained by vortices. Comets go with very eccentric motions into all parts of the heavens, which cannot happen unless vortices are eliminated” (Newton, 1999, p. 939).

³⁰² For a study on Koyré’s historical epistemology see, Jorland, G. (1981). *La science dans la philosophie. Les recherches épistémologiques d’Alexandre Koyré*. Paris: Gallimard.

and without use of any intermediate physical cause whatsoever. That latter idea chimes nicely with Newton's famous (...) "General Scholium" (1713), concerning God (2001, p. 163)

In his study devoted to explore Newton's treatment of the ontological problem of the causation of force both in his published and unpublished papers, entitled "Force, active principles, and Newton's invisible realm", J. E. McGuire commented on Newton's various attempts to analyse the secondary causation of forces in nature which included aethers of diverse types. But as is known, the analysis undertaken in Book 2 of the *Principia* led Newton to reject this way of explanations in view of its incompatibility with Kepler's laws and the law of gravitation as well. So, McGuire wrote:

Are forces to be explained by some intermediary agent such as a world soul or a quasi-mechanical aether? Or are they a direct and continuous expression of Divine Providence? After considering the hypothesis of a world soul as a plausible but improbable source of activity in the world, Newton inclines to the view that God acts in nature without intermediaries (...) Nevertheless, a subtle aether is not dismissed as a possible means of transferring the "mutual actions" of bodies. (1995, p. 191).

Richard S. Westfall's pronouncement on God's direct intervention in the world is quite in the line of what has been said on Newton's abandonment of material mediums after the first edition of the *Principia*. His statements on this topic in his *Force in Newton's physics* are straightforward on Newton's outright rejection of a material medium.

He had filled Book II of the *Principia* with arguments meant to demonstrate, not only the impossibility of Cartesian vortices, but the non-existence of any material aether; and in this respect, Book II only repeated what his private papers affirmed with greater vehemence. If not a material aether, then an immaterial aether (...) what could an immaterial aether be? To Newton, it was the infinite omnipotent God, who by His infinity constitutes absolute space and by His omnipotence is actively present throughout it (1971, p. 396).³⁰³

The electric and elastic spirit mentioned by Newton at the end of the General Scholium (1713) could not be considered as an alternative for explaining the nature of gravity force, Westfall points out, since "from the beginning of his speculations on the electric spirit, Newton had insisted on the difference between the interparticulate forces, which it explained, and gravity, which was always proportional to the quantity of matter and obeyed the inverse-square law, and was by implication nonmechanical" (1980, p. 794).³⁰⁴

³⁰³ See also Westfall, 1980, p. 506.

³⁰⁴ Newton's return to aethers as explanatory means for forces in general, and gravity force in particular, eventually faced the same problems of his earlier considerations on them. As Westfall observes: "Newton's electric spirit diverged so radically from the fluids and effluvia of earlier mechanical philosophies that the differences outweigh the similarities. As he stressed, the electric spirit was exceedingly rare and exceedingly elastic. When he reintroduced an aether of similar qualities into his philosophy a few years later, he argued from its properties that it was composed of particles that

Betty Dobbs has also indicated God's direct intervention in the world to account for the cause of gravity force. Thus, in her "Newton's alchemy and his 'active principle' of gravitation", she noted that:

If we will move objects, we can do so only indirectly, sending messages from the brain through nerves to bodily parts, which are thereby enabled to put our wills into effect. But God is "void of organs, members or parts" and so acts directly (...). Thus, by analogy with the indirect willed activity of the human mind, the Divine Mind wills directly "to form and reform the Parts of the Universe," and that is what we call gravitation (1988, pp. 73-74).

Three years later in her book *The Janus faces of genius*, she asserted that "the first tentative solution to the problem of a cause for gravity to emerge in Newton's later years, then, was that the omnipresent supreme Deity subsumed gravity directly" (Dobbs, 1991b, p. 191).³⁰⁵

Finally, it is worth mentioning the most recent scholar who asserts that according to Newton, God acts directly upon nature, namely, Andrew Janiak. In effect, in his *Newton as philosopher* (2008) he asserted that:

If God does not act at a distance on any object, it remains unclear how material objects could engage in such action by exhibiting God's intervention in the physical world. Such a miracle, therefore, seems to be ruled out by Newton's views. (...) This point is connected, in turn, to Newton's own brief but significant speculation that an "immaterial agent" might serve as the physical basis of gravitational interactions. Since God is not distant from any object at any time, and since Newton obviously thinks that God might be the very "immaterial medium" underlying all gravitational interactions among material bodies, it

repelled each other powerfully. Thus it embodied the very concept of action at a distance that conventional mechanical aethers were summoned up to explain away. Nevertheless, the electric spirit and later the new aether involved profound problems. They were two distinct fluids in his view, the one found in the pores of bodies and concerned with attractions of particles, the other pervading the empty spaces of the cosmos. Whatever their properties, such subtle fluids had produced over the years an abundance of verbal explanations of phenomena but never an exact quantitative account. Indeed, they had invariably conflicted with exact quantitative accounts. No one had succeeded, for example, in extracting Kepler's laws of planetary motion from a vortical theory. Even in introducing the electric spirit, however, Newton indicated his primary concern with quantitative descriptions. There is no satisfactory explanation of his return to such fluids, even with their differences from conventional ones. It is hard to imagine Newton acquiescing in such a retreat at an earlier, more vigorous age. In any event, a full essay on such an electric spirit would have raised severe problems in an edition designed to defend his philosophy against conventional mechanical ones" (Westfall, 1980, p. 747).

³⁰⁵ The same idea is expressed in her others works, thus for example, in "Stoic and Epicurean doctrines in Newton's system of the world", she maintained that "How, then, did Newton propose to explain the action of gravity? The sun reaches out somehow, across millions of miles, to hold the planets in their orbits. Once Newton had cleared the heavens of the mechanical aethereal whirlpools of Descartes, there seemed to be nothing there in those vast spaces. At least there were no material substances there, but Newton hinted to Bentley that perhaps the force of gravity was mediated by something else that was not material. If there were no material aether in the heavens, then what was there? God, of course. Newton often stated his strong belief in the literal omnipresence of God, and by the 1690s he also began to make at least private statements to the effect that gravity had its foundation only in the will of God –that is, that there was no material cause for it (1991a, pp. 232-233)." See also Dobbs 1991b, pp. 116-117, 209-212.

seems clear that when Newton contemplates the idea that God might be the relevant mediating element, he is not contemplating the idea that bodies act at a distance on one another. Instead, God acts locally and directly on any object at any time (p. 39).³⁰⁶

Janiak's interpretation clearly exhibits the same pattern of misapprehension present along the lines of the standard reading in attributing to God the direct intervention in the workings of nature in order to escape from the problem of action at a distance. Moreover, the missed point in all these interpretations lies precisely in the disregarding of the secondary causation which is not to be found in aethers or vortices. As we will see, it is of paramount importance to take into account Newton's voluntarism and the alternative that Newton himself adopted concerning active principles in general, and gravity force in particular, as superadded qualities.

The idea of God's direct intervention in the functioning of the universe is a by-product, on the one hand, of the denials of aetherial mediums on the part of Newton, and on the other hand, of the enduring conviction shared by a number of scholars for whom Newton did not accept action at a distance.³⁰⁷

This tradition of interpretation is based upon documentary evidence within a specific theological framework, namely, a portion of Newton's correspondence with Richard Bentley, which has become the commonplace in each and every single interpretation of Newton's supposed rejection of distant action.³⁰⁸ Alexandre Koyré, I. Bernard Cohen, A. Rupert Hall, and Ernan McMullin form part of the standard interpretation of Newton's denial of action at a distance.³⁰⁹ In this same line, but taking as alternative the role of alchemy and Newton's theology to explicate the activity of matter, we find Betty Dobbs.³¹⁰ More recently, the denial of distant action in Newton has been supported by Andrew Janiak and Hylarie Kochiras.³¹¹ The opposite view has been assumed by John Henry.³¹²

³⁰⁶ This is not the only place in his books where Janiak asserts this. In point of fact, there are other places where he restates his approach. Thus, for example, he says: "God remains an infinite, omnipotent, and necessary being, and God's action is certainly not subject to the laws of nature, for God is obviously neither massive nor impenetrable. But God occupies and is actively present at every point in space throughout the whole history of the universe, and God acts locally, just as any other substance does" (p. 166). And a couple of pages below, "If God acts non-locally, a principal reason for characterizing God as spatiotemporally ubiquitous is removed. If divine distant action is possible, then God's omnipotence need not be construed as Newton always construes it, in terms of divine omnipresence (p. 174).

³⁰⁷ Before continuing with the analysis, a caveat is in order here. Among the abovementioned scholars Richard S. Westfall is the only scholar that does not deny Newton's acceptance of action at a distance. In point of fact, he remarked in his *Never at rest*: "whereas the invisible mechanisms of orthodox mechanical philosophy, such as Descartes's vortices, had continually diverted attention away from quantitative precision toward picturable images, Newton's new conception of action at a distance invited mathematical treatment. The first stage of Newton's work on the *Principia* was the creation of his dynamics, the instrument that the rest of the task required" (1980, p. 420). See *Ibid.*, pp. 388, 390, 469, 730, 747, 794.

³⁰⁸ For a survey of this historiographical tradition, see Henry, 1994 and 2011. This section owes much to the interpretative perspective adopted by John Henry.

³⁰⁹ See Koyré, 1965; Cohen, 1980, 1982, 1987, 1999, 2002b; McMillan, 1978; Hall, 1954, 1983.

³¹⁰ See Dobbs 1998, 1990, 1991a, 1991b, 1993.

³¹¹ See, Janiak 2008; Kochiras, 2009, 2011.

³¹² Henry 1994, 2007, 2011. See also Henry, 1986, 2008b, and 2009. More recently Steffen Ducheyne, and Eric Schliesser have adopted a line of interpretation akin to that of Henry.

According to John Henry, the main text upon which the standard reading of Newton rejecting action at a distance is based has been the product of a misleading reading and misunderstanding of Newton's pronouncements in his correspondence with Bentley. Additionally, the general consensus among historians of the customary interpretation and their analyses strongly downplays Newton's own remarks in which he openly welcomes and accepts the attraction among bodies without any material medium between them.³¹³

Notwithstanding the reliance upon this correspondence with Bentley –or on a fragment of it, to be precise– and the reading of the *Principia* on the part of scholars,³¹⁴ it is perfectly possible to make a case for the opposite view, to be exact, for asserting that Newton in fact did believe in action at a distance. In order to develop this affirmation, it is necessary to begin with Newton's correspondence with Bentley, in view of the fact that it is the starting point and main source from which we are supposed to conclude that Newton did not believe in action at a distance.³¹⁵ It is also required to call attention to those other passages where Newton directly talked about the existence of distant action, embracing it since it was a natural consequence of his natural philosophy and a pillar of his natural theology.

There is no need to remark that since its publication the *Principia* became a momentous work in natural philosophy. In fact, its importance was recognised even for those who criticised the core concept of gravity and the underlying action at a distance that such a concept implies.³¹⁶ In this work, the writer of the first review, Halley,³¹⁷ in the *Philosophical transactions* wrote that Newton “has at once shewn what are the Principles of Natural Philosophy, and so far derived from them their consequences, that he seems to have exhausted his Argument, and left little to be done by those that shall succeed him”.³¹⁸

Given the high impact of the *Principia*, an expected consequence was how it was adopted and adapted according to ideologies which used Newton's masterpiece to support their arguments. Such was the case in natural theology. As a matter of fact, the physics deployed in the *Principia* was regarded as having shown that the order of the universe demonstrates the existence of God, and in consequence it was deemed as a strong and perhaps the chief support of faith in Great Britain. Or, as Newton put it in the General Scholium (1713), “all the diversity of created things, each in its place and time, could only have arisen from the ideas and the will of a necessarily existing being” (Newton 1999, p. 942).

It is within the framework of natural theology that the correspondence between Newton and Bentley took place, and it is important to bear in mind this fact in order to appreciate the scopes and limits of Newton's pronouncements. As A. Rupert Hall has remarked, “excellent and laborious

³¹³ See Henry, 1994, 2011.

³¹⁴ Cohen, 1980, McMullin, 1978; Janiak, 2008.

³¹⁵ The Newton – Bentley correspondence consist in four letters (Newton, 1959-1977, vol. 3, letters N° 398, 399, 403, and 406) sent to Bentley by Newton.

³¹⁶ See Westfall 1980, 469-550.

³¹⁷ As Westfall observes, “although the review was unsigned, we know that Halley wrote it. With the exception of Newton himself, no one knew the contents of the work better. He insisted on its epochal significance” (Westfall, 1980, p. 469).

³¹⁸ Halley, Edmond. (1687) “Review of the Principia”, *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London*, Vol. 16, (1686-1687), pp. 291-297. As quoted in Rigaud, 1838, Apendix XXI, p. 71.

theologian as he was, he made no confusion between physics and theology” (1954, p. 272). Paradoxical, as it might seem, Hall’s denial of Newton’s belief in action at a distance is heavily based upon the interchange of letters between Newton and Bentley, not taking regard to the different levels of discourse between the *Principia* and Newton’s physico-theological ideas exhibited in this correspondence. This same comment could be applied to those who reject Newton’s acceptance of distant action, like Koyré, Cohen, and McMullin.

In 1691 the Boyle lectures were institutionalised, consisting in eight sermons to be delivered every year. They were given upon Boyle’s request for which he left annual funds. The central interest of the lectures was no other than that of defeating the threats of atheism and Epicureanism (or the neo-Epicureans) and those philosophical systems that represented a threat to Christianity.³¹⁹

According to Miller (1978), in view of the character of Richard Bentley, he “would already have been thinking that if theological propositions were now to rest their defence exclusively on demonstrations satisfactory to reason, the defender would have to know something about a book that Isaac Newton of Trinity College had published in 1687, the *Principia*” (p. 273). For Bentley, the basic strategy to deploy for reaching his goals –which eventually became the *modus procedendi* of the Boyle lectures– was to deduce religious propositions out of the argumentative structure of the *Principia*.

Bentley’s first sermon was delivered on March 1691/2, and the main theme was the purpose of religion within the society; the second one has as target the materialism; the third, fourth and fifth sermons are based upon the argument from design and illustrated with the structure of human body. The last three sermons, delivered on October, November, and December, are those related to the correspondence with Newton. They have as a central topic the argument from divine contrivance applied to the structure and disposition of the universe.³²⁰ These last three sermons were printed under the title *A confutation of atheism from the origin and frame of the world* and they make intensive use of Newton’s findings in the *Principia*.

As said by Perry Miller, Bentley had “asked a Scottish mathematician, John Craige, to tell him what books he would need to master in order to qualify himself for following the *Principia*. Craige sent back, as an essential minimum, a bibliography so tremendous that even Bentley was aghast” (1978, p. 273). In view of Craige’s shocking suggestion, Bentley opted for contacting Newton directly, and the answer from the master was quite different, regarding lectures to embark on. Newton’s recommendation was to read Euclid, John De Witt, Francis Schooten, Gassendi, and Huygens; as for his book, Newton wrote to Bentley:

At ye first perusal of my Book it’s enough if you understand ye Propositions wth some of ye Demonstrations wch are easier then the rest. For when you understand ye easier they will afterwards give you light into ye harder. When you have read ye first 60 pages, pass on to ye 3d Book & when you see the design of that you may turn back to such Propositions as you

³¹⁹ See Jacob, 1976, pp. 143-200; Guerlac and Jacob, 1969; Miller, 1978; Westfall, 498.

³²⁰ See Guerlac & Jacob, 1969, p. 311.

shall have a desire to know, or peruse the whole in order if you think fit (Newton, 1959-1977, vol. 3, p. 156)

Roughly speaking, the directions given by Newton had as focal point the first three sections of Book 1 related to the method of first and ultimate ratios (section 1); the finding of centripetal forces (section 2), and the motion of bodies in eccentric conic sections. That is to say, Propositions 1 to 17.

Now, despite the fact that Bentley's letters to Newton do not survive, we can have an idea of their content from Newton's answers. By mid-December in 1691 Bentley entered into communication with Newton again in order to get a grasp of his opinions on the matters that Bentley was developing for his sermons. By way of queries, he wanted Newton's estimation of his ideas in order to proceed with the main argumentative line for demonstrating the close relationship between natural philosophical discoveries and the role of Providence. Thus, a year and a half after the first communication, Bentley received a letter from the author of the *Principia*, replying to a series of questions posited by Bentley. The ideas discussed in this letter are about natural theology and not concerning technical aspects of the *Principia*. Newton's answer is important and deserving of attention in so far as it shows his interest in commenting and sharing his thoughts on the physico-theological assumptions underlying his mathematical principles of natural philosophy. Thus, he wrote:

When I wrote my treatise about our Systeme I had an eye upon such Principles as might work wth considering men for the beleife of a Deity & nothing can rejoyce me more then to find it usefull for that purpose. But if I have done ye publick any service this way 'tis due to nothing but industry & a patient thought (Newton, 1959-1977, vol. 3, p. 233)

A. Rupert Hall has remarked on this letter, and especially on this very first paragraph, that here Newton, however, expressed a sentiment typical of the age in a letter to Bentley.³²¹ Nevertheless, this passage could be read in a different light. If one takes into account the social context of Newton and the purpose of the Boyle lectures, it is not difficult to perceive Newton's awareness of the political and social impact that his work eventually could have. As a matter of fact, Newton played an important part in the constitution of the first Boyle lectures.³²² Additionally, from a memorandum by David Gregory we have notice of part of the contribution of Newton to the orientation of the lectures. As Gregory wrote:

³²¹ Hall, 1954, p. 272, fn. 1.

³²² See Jacob, 1979. Newton's involvement in the Boyle lectures has been observed by this scholars in these terms: "From the date and contents of Gregory's memorandum it appears likely that Newton is referring to the projected Boyle lectures. His description of the "publick speech" and the contents of "ane Act," that is, a college speech, thesis, or disputation, closely resembles the contents of lectures given in 1692 by Bentley. Newton appears to be suggesting that his discoveries in celestial physics would serve the argument from design better than that reliance on the "contrivances" in animals and plants used by John Ray in his *The Wisdom of God Manifested in the Works of the Creation*, first published in 1691" (p. 154).

In Mr Newtons opinion a good design of a publick speech (and which may serve well at ane Act) may be to shew that the most simple laws of nature are observed in the structure of a great part of the Universe, that the philosophy ought ther to begin, and that Cosmical Qualities are as much easier as they are more Universall than particular ones, and the general contrivance simpler than that of Animals plants &c: (Newton, 1959-1977, vol. 3, p. 191).

So therefore, there is more than mere conformism or unthinking religious observance in these lines. And this is something that could be accounted for by following the line of argument developed by Newton in his correspondence with Bentley.

Having shown his willingness to commence a discussion on the theological implications of his work with Bentley, Newton tackles right from the outset the inner nature of gravity force. Given the case that space was limited and if “every particle had an innate gravity towards all the rest” (p. 234) the matter eventually would form one great spherical mass at the centre. Though the subject matter of Bentley’s query is the behaviour of matter in a finite space and its lucid or opaque nature or constitution, Newton does not suppose nor affirm that gravity is innate to bodies. In this case, gravity is a matter of fact amply demonstrated in the Book 3 of the *Principia*. In the opposite case, Newton states in the second sentence, gravity of matter would give rise to the different types of heavenly bodies, some of them lucid and some of them opaque. But, Newton observes,

How the matter should divide it self into two sorts & that part of it wch is fit to compose a shining body should fall down into one mass & make a Sun & the rest wch is fit to compose an opake body should coalesce not into one great body (...) but into many little ones (...) I do not think explicable by mere natural causes but am forced to ascribe it to ye counsel & contrivance of a *voluntary Agent* (*Ibid.*, emphasis added).

An equivalent reasoning is applied by Newton in considering the disposition of celestial bodies and the sun at the centre. “Had this cause been a blind one without contrivance”, it would be indifferent in our system that there were, or not, lucid and opaque bodies. In absence of a satisfactory answer to this question on the constitution of our system from his natural philosophical standpoint, is not unwise to rely on God and to declare that it is so because of his will. Accordingly, Newton presents his point: “why there is one body in our Systeme qualified to give light & heat to all ye rest I know no reason but because the author of ye Systeme thought it convenient” (*Ibid.*). In sum, since the principles of physics both of Newton’s and Descartes’s are not able to account for the two mentioned sorts of matter, lucid and opaque, this reinforces the belief in a Deity. As for Descartes, the modifications of the first element that fills the space explains why some bodies have luminosity and others opacity and transparency. This is contrary to Newton’s system of natural philosophy. Effectively,

For the Cartesian Hypothesis of Sun’s loosing their light & then turning into Comets & Comets into Planets can have no place in my systeme & is plainly erroneous because it’s

certain that Comets as often as they appear to us descend into the system of our Planets lower then ye orb of Jupiter & sometimes lower then the orbs of Venus & Mercury, & yet never stay here but always return from the Sun with the same degrees of motion by wch they approached him (*Ibid*).

The second query of the first letter deals with the origin of motion in planets. This is the most important part of this first letter in view of the fact that Newton here, within a theological or physico-theological context, unambiguously declares immediately the nature of motion in general and of the celestial bodies in particular. So, he writes:

To your second Query I answer that ye motions wch ye Planets now have could not spring from any naturall cause alone *but were imprest* by an intelligent Agent (*Ibid*,. emphasis added).

So therefore, according to this statement of Newton, the diversity of the paths of comets as well as the homogeneity of motion in the planets (both primary and secondary) make plain that they could not arise out of a natural property. Such a property is indeed a property inherent in the nature of body (in the same way that extension is an inherent property) but not a logical concomitant of matter in the same way that extension is.

Furthermore, there is no natural property that could explain the degrees of velocity in proportion to the distances of the planets from the sun and other central bodies, nor with respect to the masses. By means of natural properties it is not possible to give an explanation for the balance of velocities, masses, and distances existing in the universe. In other words, for Newton, in short, gravity could not be thought as a natural property, since no such cause would make every body in the universe attract other bodies with a force which makes possible the synchronization of the workings of nature, and which has a direct proportion with respect to the product of the masses and that is inversely proportional to the square of the distance between them.

The final part of this argument is telling. In point of fact, here Newton connects the aforementioned reasons for denying natural causes, in so far as responsible for the workings of the universe, with the fundamental assumptions that form the basis of his approach to geometry as founded upon mechanics, and rational mechanics in the *Principia* as the best way of expressing the analysis of the natural phenomena. Thus, Newton rounds off his claim:

To make this systeme therefore wth all its motions, required a Cause wch understood & compared together the quantities of matter in ye several bodies of ye Sun & Planets & ye gravitating powers resulting from thence, the several distances of the primary Planets from ye Sun & secondary ones from Saturn Jupiter & ye earth, & ye velocities wth wch these Planets could revolve at those distances about those quantities of matter in ye central bodies. *And to compare & adjust all these things together in so great a variety of bodies argues*

that cause to be not blind & fortuitous, but very well skilled in Mechanicks & Geometry (p. 235, emphasis added).

The third query of this letter is referred to the density of planets by virtue of their distances from the sun, the fourth question is about the inclination of the axis of the earth in the light of the vortex theory, and the fifth and final has to do with the inclination of the earth.

Newton's second letter to Bentley deals with the question of "whether matter evenly spread throughout a finite space of some figure other than spherical, would not in falling down towards a central body cause that body to be of the same figure with the whole space" (p. 244). Newton copes with this problem from the perspective of mathematics and the proper way to understand the infinite.

For the present purpose, it is imperative to consider another question comprised in Bentley's second letter, inasmuch as it emphasises the need of God for establishing the actual order of the universe, not as its direct and constant responsible author, but as the agent that impresses gravity force upon the bodies of the system. Newton's treatment of that question is:

if ye earth (without ye moon) were placed any where with its center in ye Orbis magnus & stood still there without any gravitation or projection & then *at once were infused into it both a gravitating energy towards ye sun & a transverse impulse of a just quantity moving it directly in a tangent to ye Orbis magnus: ye compound of this attraction & projection would according to my notion cause a circular revolution of ye earth about ye Sun* (p. 240, emphasis added).

But, he continues, "I do not know any power in nature wch could cause this transverse motion without ye divine arm". Next, Newton is crystal clear with respect to the difference between gravity as a quality of matter *per se*, and the role of God *in infusing it into matter*. So he writes:

So then gravity may put ye planets into motion but without ye divine power it could never put them into such a Circulating motion as they have about ye Sun, & therefore for this as well as other reasons I am compelled to ascribe ye frame of this Systeme to an intelligent agent" (*Ibid.*).

It is important here to highlight that Newton does not take gravity as a natural cause of motions; on the contrary, it is *infused into matter by the Divine arm at the moment of the creation*. This precise argument precedes Newton's famous admonition 'pray do not ascribe that notion to me' to Bentley as meaning that the idea of gravity is innate (as expressed in the first letter), essential and inherent to matter must be disallowed. Surprisingly enough, no scholar seems to have paid attention to this significant passage which helps us to understand Newton's meaning of the ontology of force in the succeeding paragraph. This much quoted statement is as follows:

You sometimes speak of gravity as essential & inherent to matter: pray do not ascribe that notion to me, for ye cause of gravity is what I do not pretend to know, & therefore would take more time to consider of it (*Ibid.*).

Viewed in hindsight, the phrase 'I do not pretend to know' eventually would be reasserted in stronger terms under the motto 'I do not frame hypotheses' in the General Scholium of the second edition of the *Principia* in 1713, in the wake of the criticisms to the unexplained gravity in terms of contact action. As is well known, Newton felt obliged to expound his methodology in the *Principia* in particular, and in his natural philosophy in general, along the lines of empirical science in order to respond to attacks from the Cartesians and Leibnizians who dubbed universal attraction as an occult quality, and even worse, as a perpetual miracle. But this is not the place to take on a detailed analysis of Newton's methodological statements, since this would lead us astray from the physico-theological context of the correspondence with Bentley.

So, given the case that Newton was not as sharp as he expected to be with the notion of gravity as impressed upon matter by God, and given that Bentley's allusion to gravity as innate, in his third letter Newton returns to this specific and important point. Thus, he writes:

And thô gravity might give the Planets a motion of descent towards the Sun either directly or wth some little obliquity, yet the transverse motions by wch they revolve in their several orbs *required the divine Arm to impress them according to ye tangents of their orbs*. I would now add that the Hypothesis of matters being at first evenly spread through the heavens is, in my opinion, inconsistent wth ye Hypothesis of innate gravity *without a supernatural power* to reconcile them, & therefore it infers a Deity (p. 244, emphasis added).

What Newton emphasises here is the very need of the divine arm *to establish the law* whereby the system gets its synchronisation and congruence. Throughout his correspondence with Bentley, Newton has been talking about the argument from design in physico-theological terms in order to argue in favour of a Deity. He has also been expressing his conviction on the causation of gravity force as impressed upon, or infused into, matter by God, so as to show that "this most elegant system of the sun, planets, and comets could not have arisen without the design and dominion of an intelligent and powerful being" (Newton, 1999, p. 940).

In the last letter to Bentley, Newton deals with the issue of gravity as innate, essential and inherent to matter and the action at a distance. In conjunction with the last paragraph of the second letter – 'you sometimes speak of gravity as essential...' – , the concluding remarks of the fourth letter constitute the essential source of the interpretation of a Newton rejecting action at a distance. In addition, these also have given rise to the reading of Newton as stating obliquely the direct and sustained intervention of God in nature. For the sake of analysis, I divide this last paragraph in the three parts which contain the main ideas enunciated by Newton. So, he writes:

[1] The last clause of your second Position I like very well. Tis unconceivable that inanimate brute matter should (without ye mediation of something else wch is not material) operate upon & affect other matter without mutual contact; as it must if gravitation in the sense of Epicurus be essential & inherent in it. And this is one reason why I desired you would not ascribe innate gravity to me. [2] That gravity should be innate inherent & essential to matter so yt one body may act upon another at a distance through a vacuum without the mediation of any thing else by & through wch their action or force may be conveyed from one to another is to me so great an absurdity that I beleive no man who has in philosophical matters any competent faculty of thinking can ever fall into it. [3] Gravity must be caused by an agent acting constantly according to certain laws, but whether this agent be material or immaterial is a question I have left to ye consideration of my readers (Newton, 1959-1977, vol. 3, pp. 253-254).

All these three points in this declaration deserve a close examination in order to clear Newton's meaning. My reading of this paragraph aims at suggesting that Newton's allusion to Epicurus is not only restricted to the physico-theological ambit; in fact, there are elements that make it possible to interpret such a statement along the lines of the debate on the utility of natural philosophy within the social context of Newton's England.³²³ But more importantly it will be contended that Newton does really endorse action at a distance, which is coherent with his unambiguous declarations in his other major work, the *Opticks* and related papers. Furthermore, it will be stated that Newton is crystal clear in distinguishing between the agent that *performs* gravity and the immaterial mediator that *endows* matter with gravity. From this account for the ontological causation of gravity force it will be recognised as a superadded quality.

As for the reference to Epicurus, it is not unsuitable to recall that the main thrust of the Boyle lectures was to combat the atheism, and that during the first half of the seventeenth century Epicureanism was a subject of controversy in England. Given that it involved the idea of the inherency of motion in matter, a very likely consequence of this philosophy was that God could be removed as the necessary efficient cause. As a matter of fact, in order to be an acceptable approach to the study of natural phenomena, the atomism of Epicurus and Lucretius had to be Christianised.³²⁴ Such an undertaking was assumed by, as is known, Pierre Gassendi, Walter Charleton, Henry More, and significantly, Robert Boyle, among others. A common perspective in

³²³ Given the orientation of this investigation, to undertake a detailed analysis of this aspect would lead astray the purpose of this thesis. Notwithstanding this, by suggesting this focus of analysis I hope to point out to other possibilities of understanding Newton's pronouncements which could enrich his role in the social context of natural philosophers in the seventeenth century England.

³²⁴ On this point Margaret J. Osler's remarks on the status of Epicureanism are worth to be quoted. According to this scholar, before European intellectuals could embrace the philosophy of Epicurus, however, the views of the ancient atomist had to be purged of the accusations of atheism and materialism that had dogged them since antiquity. Epicurus was not, in fact, an atheist. He believed that the gods exist, but he thought that as blessed and immortal beings they took part in neither natural nor human affairs. Thus, he denied any providential interpretation of the world. He was a materialist, believing that everything in the world is composed of atoms moving in infinite void space. Atoms, for Epicurus, were infinite in number and had existed forever. He denied the immortality of the soul and the existence of any immaterial being except for the void" (1994, p. 38).

their efforts to make atomism a satisfactory natural philosophy was that of asserting that to consider matter without God was unreasonable –or implausible– and that the structure of nature could not have evolved by simple fate.³²⁵

But another facet of Epicureanism could be regarded in the light of Newton's pronouncements in the correspondence with Bentley. As W. R. Albury has remarked, "after the Restoration of the Stuart monarchy in 1660, and throughout the reign of Charles II, the moral doctrines of Epicurus became increasingly fashionable among the aristocrats associated with the Court" (1978, p. 32) and natural philosophy was seen, to some extent, not in accord with the aristocratic ideal of Epicureanism. Thus, for example, Sir William Temple criticised natural philosophy as purposeless and lacking of definitive demonstration:

As to that part of philosophy which is called natural, I know no end it can have but that of busying a man's brains to no purpose, or satisfying the vanity so natural to most men of distinguishing themselves, by some way or other, from those that seem their equals in birth and the common advantages of it. (...) More than this, I know no advantage mankind has gained by the progress of natural philosophy, during so many ages it has had vogue in the world, excepting always, and very justly, what we owe to the mathematics. (...) But all the different schemes of nature that have been drawn of old, or of late, by Plato, Aristotle, Epicurus, Des Cartes, Hobbs, or any other that I know of, seem to agree but in one thing, which is the want of demonstration or satisfaction to any thinking and unpossessed man.³²⁶

The criticisms of a diplomat and privy councilor to Charles II, such as Temple, eventually could have deleterious consequences on the scientific movement of the Royal Society, and surely, they went not unnoticed. As a matter of fact, in the book of William Wotton *Reflections upon ancient and modern learning* (1697), Halley contributed to the defence of the scientific activity of the Royal Society with a chapter on "Ancient and modern astronomy and optics". Here, the first editor of the *Principia* (1687) underlined the demonstrative mathematical nature of Newton's work. In so doing, he was taking part in the protection of the cause of the Royal Society.³²⁷ Thus, Halley wrote, that

That elegant Theory of the Planetary Motions (...) now lately demonstrated by that excellent Geometer Mr. Newton is the necessary Result of the Laws of Motion and Gravity, is also found rigorously to answer to all that is observed in the Motions; so that the Moderns may, with as much Reason as in any other Science whatsoever, value themselves on their having Improved, I had almost said Perfected, this of Astronomy.³²⁸

³²⁵ See Kargon, 1964.

³²⁶ William Temple, "Upon the Gardens of Epicurus; or, of Gardening" (1685), in *Five Miscellaneous Essays*, ed. Samuel H. Monk (Ann Arbor, 1963), pp. 4-5. As quoted in Albury, 1978, pp. 33-34.

³²⁷ Bentley, who assisted Roger Cotes in the second edition of the *Principia* (1713) modified some verses of Halley's Ode to Newton's work in view of the Epicurean flavour he saw in those lines. See Albury, 1978, pp. 36-43.

³²⁸ Halley, "Ancient and modern astronomy and optics", in Wotton, 1694, p. 280.

Newton's reference to Epicurus could be also interpreted, therefore, as a way of vindicating his mathematical approach to the study of nature against those criticisms that tended to restrict the advancement of the initiative of the Royal Society and put in danger the social status of natural philosophers in Newton's England. In addition, by mistakenly aligning him with the notion of gravity as inherent to matter in the sense of Epicurus, the very objective of the Boyle lectures could be undermined, since "one of the cardinal principles of Epicureanism was the absence not merely of a creator, but of any kind of divine government of, or even interest in, the workings of our world" (Milton, 1998, p. 699).

This brings me to the second and most important aspect of Newton's fourth letter to Bentley where he claims that it is 'unconceivable that inanimate brute matter should (without ye mediation of something else wch is not material) operate upon & affect other matter without mutual contact; as it must if gravitation in the sense of Epicurus be essential & inherent in it'.

Newton here is stating one of the main characteristics of his conception of nature by declaring both the passivity of matter and its activity. Activity by virtue of an immaterial mediator –that "something" else not material– that is to say God who impresses into matter the power to interact or to operate one on another. As a matter of fact, Newton insisted earlier upon this idea at least three times in the correspondence with Bentley. Thus, in the first letter he said that "ye motions wch ye Planets now have could not spring from any naturall cause alone but were *imprest* by an intelligent Agent". In the third letter: "I represented that ye diurnal rotations of the Planets could not be derived from gravity but required a divine power to *impress* them". And finally, in the same letter: "the transverse motions by wch they revolve in their several orbs required the divine Arm to *impress* them according to ye tangents of their orbs" (Newton, 1959-1977, vol. 3, pp. 234, 244).³²⁹ In this parenthetical remark on the mediator, that which is impressed into matter, or the result of the mediation, besides of functioning as the linkage between the continuity of space with the discontinuity of matter, describes the sources of change in a theistic framework.

The second sentence of this argument expands Newton's meaning while he claims the existence of the vacuum and reiterates the notion of mediation. 'That gravity should be innate inherent & essential to matter so yt one body may act upon another at a distance through a vacuum without the mediation of any thing else by & through wch their action or force may be conveyed from one to another is to me so great an absurdity that I believe no man who has in philosophical matters any competent faculty of thinking can ever fall into it'.

In the same line of reasoning of the previous letters, there is the affirmation according to which, by mere nature, it could not be possible to account for the mutual action of matter. So, the core of the argument can be enunciated thus: Gravity is not innate inherent & essential to matter since no material particle can act at a distance, *unless* a non-mechanical entity that accomplishes the task of communicating the action of gravity force among bodies is conceived. From the natural philosophical point of view, regarding nature in so far as constituted by matter and void space, to state the interaction of bodies in absence of a linkage not only is unconceivable but shows inability

³²⁹ It could be added that in the second letter to Bentley, Newton speaks of the gravity in the earth as "infused into it" by the divine arm, see Newton, 1959-1977, vol. 3, p. 239.

in philosophical matters. If this phrasing of Newton's thought is correct, then it inevitably means that he did not reject *actio in distans*; quite the opposite, he asserted that it is performed by means of what is imparted into matter, that is to say, by gravity force.

Newton, having established that (1) it is unthinkable to maintain that matter could act at a distance without supposing that such a power was impressed into matter by God –the immaterial mediator– must have taken satisfaction in the benefit to natural religion of this theory: gravity is the best expression in the natural world of divine power. And (2), that distant action is unproblematic in view of the former point, and even a natural consequence of Newton's notion of universal attraction, he passes to deal with the nature of the secondary cause of gravity. On this aspect he asserts 'gravity must be caused by an agent acting constantly according to certain laws, but whether this agent be material or immaterial is a question I have left to ye consideration of my readers'.

Clearly, this is not referred to God because to think of him along the lines of Newton's theological voluntarism acting according to certain laws would be an awkward affirmation coming from Newton's pen. What he is referring to here is that the secondary cause of gravity could be material or immaterial. There could be several reasons why Newton opted for leaving this important question to the consideration of his readers. It could be that given the theological background against which the correspondence is set, it would be sufficient to express that such a cause is not to be a mechanical one. But, as Richard S. Westfall has observed in a perspicacious comment "he [Newton] had not left it entirely to his readers, since Book II had become a sustained argument against the existence of a material agent. Newton's letter to Bentley drew on extensive revisions of Book III, which he decided in the end not to publish. He explored the meaning of his declarations to Bentley more fully in that context" (Westfall, 1980, p. 506).

Well and good, but notwithstanding this, before the *Principia* Newton considered various alternatives to the mechanical causes such as diverse sorts of active agents, or principles, tenuous aethers and immaterial agents in interaction with matter. Another reason would be that he was open to the existence of further means to explicate the cause of gravity, provided that they conform to the mathematical features of universal attraction (acting directly proportional to the masses of bodies and acting between bodies in inverse proportion to the square of their distances) and liable to experimental test.

Last but not least, the fact of characterising matter as inanimate and inert is aimed at proving that for its own activity it is ontologically dependent on the immaterial agent that transcends the very nature of matter itself.³³⁰

Newton's viewpoints on matter, motion and God in the correspondence with Bentley, eventually found echoes in the Boyle lectures. The concordance between Newton's positions and the arguments expressed in the sixth and seventh lectures by Bentley show an unflawed accord with the essential points discussed during the interchange of letters. Nevertheless, some scholars have attributed to Bentley a gross blunder in interpreting Newton's words.

³³⁰ See McGuire, 1977.

Thus, for example, Koyré maintained that “Bentley, in spite of Newton’s admonition, said in his *Confutation of Atheism* that ‘a constant Energy [is] infused into Matter by the Author of all Things’ and that ‘Gravity may be essential to Matter’” (1965, p. 149). These quotations come from the eighth and last sermon pronounced by Bentley in which he avers, first, that in orbital motion the ‘agent acting constantly according to certain laws’ is manifested in a twofold way, that is, as centripetal and as centrifugal force, and secondly that such laws were impressed by God.

This double aspect is explained in the *Principia* Book 2, Proposition 20, Corollary 8, where Newton affirms: “if the medium in which some body moves is urged either by its own gravity or by any other centripetal force, and the body is urged more strongly by the same force, then the difference between the forces is that motive force which we have considered to be the centripetal force in the preceding propositions. But if the body is urged more lightly by that force, the difference between the forces should be considered a centrifugal force” (Newton, 1999, p. 688). Bentley, therefore, is not distorting Newton’s physical consideration of force nor his theological assumptions regarding the origin and constitution of the universe. As a matter of fact, he basically is repeating Newton’s assertions in the correspondence. Indeed, he wrote:

We have shewed in our Last [sermon], that the concentric Revolutions of the Planets about the Sun proceed from a compound Motion; a Gravitation toward the Sun, which is a constant Energy infused into Matter by the Author of all things, and a projected transverse Impulse in Tangents to their several Orbs, that was impress’d at first by the Divine Arm, and will carry them around till the end of the World (Bentley, 1693b, p. 11).

With reference to the mention that gravity ‘may be essential’. Koyré takes this assertion out its context. What Bentley really declares is that given the possibility that gravity was something constitutive of the inner nature of matter, it is not enough to account for the present composition of our system without invoking God.³³¹

³³¹ Certainly, this is the complete background against which one should read Bentley’s assertion: “But now admitting that Gravity may be essential to Matter; and that a transverse Impulse might be acquired too by Natural Causes, yet to make all the Planets move about the Sun in circular Orbs; there must be given to each a determinate Impulse, these present particular degrees of Velocity which they now have, in proportion to their Distances from the Sun and to the quantity of the Solar Matter. For had the Velocities of the several Planets been greater or less than they are now, at the same distances from the Sun; or had their Distances from the Sun, or the quantity of the Sun’s Matter and consequently his Attractive Power been greater or less than they are now, with the same Velocities: they would not have revolved in concentric Circles as they do, but have moved in Hyperbola’s or Parabola’s or in Ellipses very Eccentric. The same may be said of the Velocities of the Secondary Planets with respect to their Distances from the Centers of Their Orbs, and to the Quantities of the Matter of those Central Bodies. Now that all these Distances and Motions and Quantities of Matter should be so accurately and harmoniously adjusted in this great Variety of our System, is above the fortuitous Hits of blind material Causes, and must certainly flow from that eternal Fountain of Wisdom, the Creator of Heaven and Earth, who always acts Geometrically, by just and adequate numbers and weights and measures (Bentley, 1693b, pp. 11-12). It is to be noted, in turn, that Bentley’s argument is a paraphrase of Newton’s argument developed in the second letter. In view of the close resemblance of the arguments, Newton’s words deserve to be quoted at length. “Nor is there any natural cause wch could give the Planets those just degrees of velocity in proportion to their distances from ye Sun & other central bodies about wch they move & to ye quantity of matter contained in those bodies, wch were requisite to make them move in concentrick orbs about those bodies. Had the Planets been as swift as Comets in proportion to their distances from ye Sun (as they would have been, had their motions been caused by their gravity, whereby the

For the sake of clarity, we need to recall Newton's censure to Bentley in the use of the word "innate" when referred to matter. In the absence of Bentley's letter where he states this idea, we can only reconstruct his arguments in the light of Newton's replies. Fortunately, the only surviving letter from Bentley sheds important light on this issue. In fact, he responded to Newton's warning by saying: "as to innate Gravity, you perceive yt it is wholly against my purpose and argumentation. If I used yt word, it was only for Brevity's sake" (Newton, 1959-1977, vol. 3, p. 249). From the argumentative standpoint it would be unfair to doubt of Bentley's candour in these words, all the more since to avow the essential nature of gravity in matter would destroy the entire claim according to which the universe is contingent upon God.

Additionally, we also need to see how this slip was corrected in the correspondence and how this idea was presented in the sermon. So, in this same letter, having offered apologies, Bentley wrote: "But though we could suppose Gravitation essential to matter, or rather supervene into Matter while it was diffused in a Chaos; yet it could never naturally constitute a System like ours" (p. 250). And in the seventh lecture, the second and third propositions read: "[1] That such a mutual Gravitation or spontaneous Attraction can neither be inherent and essential to Matter; nor ever supervene to it, unless impress'd and infused into it by a Divine Power. [2] That though we should allow such Attraction to be natural and essential to all Matter; yet the Atoms of a Chaos could never so convene by it, as to form the present System: or if they could form it, it could neither acquire such Motions, nor continue permanent in this state, without the Power and Providence of a Divine Being" (Bentley, 1693a, pp. 21-22).

Here is important to draw attention to the initial phrase of Newton in which he expresses his perfect accord with Bentley: 'The last clause of *your second Position* I like very well'. In the succeeding words Newton is simply paraphrasing his addressee at this point, and as such it was printed in *A confutation of atheism from the origin and frame of the world* (1693). In effect, Bentley said:

Tis utterly unconceivable, that inanimate brute Matter (without the mediation of some Immaterial Being) should operate upon and affect other Matter without mutual Contact; that distant Bodies should act upon each other through a *Vacuum* without the intervention of something else by and through which the action may be conveyed from one to the other. We will not obscure and perplex with multitude of words, what is so clear and evident by its own light, and must needs be allowed by all, that have any competent use of Thinking, and are initiated into, I do not say the Mysteries, but the plainest Principles of Philosophy (Bentley, 1693, pp. 28-29).

matter at the first formation of ye Planets might fall from ye remotest regions towards ye Sun) they would not move in concentric orbs but in such excentric ones as ye Comets move in. Were all the Planets as swift as Mercury or as slow as Saturn or his Satellites, or were their several velocities otherwise much greater or less then they are (as they might have been had they arose from any other cause then their gravity) or had their distances from the centers about wch they move been greater or less then they are wth ye same velocities; or had the quantity of matter in the Sun or in Saturn, Jupiter & the earth & by consequence their gravitating power been greater or less then it is: the primary Planets could not have revolved about ye Sun nor ye secondary ones about Saturn, Jupiter & ye earth in concentrick circles as they do, but would have moved in Hyperbolas or Parabolas or in Ellipses very excentric" (Newton, 1959-1977, vol. 3, p. 235).

Bentley, needless to say, understood perfectly Newton's conception of the causation of gravity force as a superadded quality, impressed upon matter by God. But the pronouncements expressed along the interchange of letters between the theologian and the natural philosopher two decades were repeated by Newton in an intended letter he planned to send to the Editor of *Memoirs of Literature* in 1712. This declaration is what I consider to be the most unmistakable documentary evidence of Newton's deep-seated conviction regarding the gravity force as a superadded quality. Here, Newton's approach to the problem of gravity force follows the same line of reasoning as in the correspondence with Bentley, but he is even more precise upon the foundations of his natural philosophy in the sole will of God. This letter was a response to the criticisms raised by Leibniz, in a letter addressed to Hartsoeker printed in this journal, against the core concept of the *Principia*. In the first half, Newton repeated verbatim the charges by Leibniz. Indeed, in the issue dated on May 1712 Leibniz, as Newton quotes it, wrote:

It may be said in a very good sense that every thing is a continual miracle, that is, worthy of admiration, but it seems to me that the example of a planet which goes round and preserves it[s] motion in its orbit without any other help but that of God, being compared with a planet kept in its orbit by that matter which constantly drives it toward the sun, plainly shows what difference there is between reasonable natural miracles and those that are properly so called or supernatural; or rather between a reasonable explication, and a fiction invented to support an ill-grounded opinion (Newton, 2004, p. 115).

For Leibniz, the issue at stake was to find out a natural cause for gravity on rational grounds, which in accordance with Newton's view of such an approach was simply hypothetical in the negative sense, that is to say, speculative explanations that scape the reach of observation and experience, and as such it was stated by Newton by saying that in the *Principia*

It has been proved by some that all bodies upon the surface of the earth gravitate toward the earth in proportion to the quantity of matter in each of them; that the moon tends toward the earth and all the planets toward one another by the same law; and that by this tendency all their motions are performed. These things have been proved by mathematical demonstrations grounded upon experiments and the phenomena of nature: and Mr. Leibniz himself cannot deny that they have been proved (*Ibid.*).

Since the divergence between Newton and Leibniz on the nature of gravity lies in the means whereby God acted at the moment of the creation, Newton's argument consists in following this line of reasoning, and declares that under such imperatives qualities as hardness in matter were to be considered, as well as gravity, occult qualities in its pejorative connotation. As a matter of fact, given that gravity was presented by Newton not following the principles of the rationalistic mechanism, which was deemed to be only intelligible means to account for gravity, it was "an

unreasonable and occult quality, and so very occult that it is impossible that it should ever be done though an angel or God himself should undertake to explain it” as Leibniz affirmed. So, if we are required to follow this path in strict observance, Newton asked “why may not the same be said of the *vis inertiae* and the extension, the duration and mobility of bodies, and yet no man ever attempted to explain these qualities mechanically, or took them for miracles or supernatural things or fictions or occult qualities (*Ibid.*). In consequence, for Newton, there is no reason to condemn the philosophy of the *Principia*. In fact, gravity as the other qualities mentioned

Are the natural, real, reasonable, manifest qualities of all bodies *seated in them by the will of God from the beginning of the creation and perfectly incapable of being explained mechanically*, and so may be the hardness of primitive particles of bodies. And therefore if any man should say that *bodies attract one another by a power whose cause is unknown to us, or by a power seated in the frame of nature by the will of God* (*Ibid.*, emphasis added).

The final words of Newton reinforce the convictions he expressed to Bentley and reveal in an undeniable manner the basic assumptions and guiding ideas of his entire natural philosophy. Here is suitable to insist upon the core of the divergences he had with Leibniz and the Continental critics. For Leibniz, what was required was a concordance between the judgements of men and those of God; for Newton as a supporter of the voluntarist theology, on the other hand, God is not circumscribed by what is considered physically possible, and on the contrary, if He decrees that matter is capable of attracting other matter at a distance, this is perfectly possible (Henry, 2009; 2011). This is precisely the structure of the argument concerning Newton’s theological point in this latter. As he wrote:

But he [Leibniz] goes on and tells us that *God could not create planets that should move round of themselves without any cause that should prevent their removing through the tangent. For a miracle at least must keep the planet in. But certainly God could create planets that should move round of themselves without any other cause than gravity that should prevent their removing through the tangent. For gravity without a miracle may keep the planets in. And to understand this without knowing the cause of gravity, is as good a progress in philosophy* (*Ibid.*, pp. 116-117, emphasis in original).

6. Closing Remarks

Throughout this study I have maintained a line of analysis focused on highlighting two basic and closely related themes in Newton's natural philosophy. On the one hand in chapters 1 and 2, I have argued that Newton's apparent separation between sciences like mathematics, physics and optics, characterized by experimental evidence and observation, and ruled by mathematical analysis; and extra-scientific researches like those of alchemy, chronology biblical hermeneutics, is largely a debatable category used by some historians of science in order to fit Newton, the 'hero' of the scientific revolution, to the scientific image that his work inaugurated, and which took shape through the transformations and adaptations of Newton's ideas. This transformation, as is known, has been baptised Newtonianism. Along these lines it could be said that Newton was not a Newtonian. Such an approach to his work, more often than not, fails to do historical justice to the basic assumptions, motivations as well as the traditions he adhered to which guided the whole of his endeavours in natural philosophy.

Precisely, the label 'natural philosophy' is the suitable term to bear in mind in order to understand the coherence of his philosophical enterprise. As a matter of fact, Newton's natural philosophy is constituted by those sanctioned areas (by scholars) such as the philosophy of mathematics, its methodology of analysis and synthesis, the epistemological imperatives of his experimental philosophy, and his attitude towards hypothesis. But in addition to this set of his inquiries, other areas not approved (by scholars) go hand in hand with the former. In point of fact, Newton's researches into the ancient wisdom and biblical chronology, for instance, were as important as the so-called positive studies. A number of scholars like J. E. McGuire, B. Dobbs, R. S. Westfall, and others have shed important light on our understanding of Newton's undertakings aimed at the recovery of original wisdom. This task, it should be noted, was not exclusive to Newton. Considering the issue of occult qualities, to give an instance, K. Hutchison, S. Menn and J. Henry have convincingly argued this task as a tradition practiced by a number of natural philosophers in Great Britain in Newton's time. However, the incorporation of ancient wisdom into his vision of nature also produced innovations which cannot be diminished. As expressed by Newton himself in a draft Preface to the *Principia*, what he did was not an invention but an innovation by offering new –i.e., mathematical– arguments for ancient truths about the system of the world.

On the other hand, this case of the mathematics as exhibited in the *Principia* was the central concern of the second theme explored in this study. I have analysed the ontological problem of the causation of gravity force from the point of view that integrates Newton's inquiries into the ancient wisdom and his voluntarist theology in chapters 3, 4 and 5. There, I have maintained that it is

possible to account for the nature of universal gravitation reading the *Principia* itself from the philosophical framework outlined in the previous chapters. In this sense I have avoided to fall into the false separation of Newton's rational and irrational researches. To this end we saw how Newton's philosophy of mathematical entities provides the key elements to account for the causation of gravity force by discerning the underlying assumptions of his natural philosophy and his natural theology.

The ontology of force in the *Principia* becomes clear when a close examination of the rational mechanics deployed in the *Principia*, in so far as founded upon the mechanical practice, is undertaken. In fact, Newton's approach to mechanism and geometry in the Preface clarifies the nature of gravity force. Having as its foundation mechanics, geometry does not deal with abstract entities or mental constructs but with things in nature. As he wrote in the *Account of the Commercium epistolicum*, contrasting his philosophy with that of Leibniz, his "method is also of greater use and certainty, being adapted either to the ready finding out of a proposition by such approximations as will create no error in the conclusion, or to the demonstrating it exactly; Mr. Leibnitz's is only for finding it out". So therefore, Newton develops a quasi-realist mathematics with a concrete ontological content accessible to experience.

An important consequence of Newton's theory of gravitation is the implicit and accepted action at a distance, which has been a protracted problem for Newtonian scholars. As I have shown in the last chapter, there are theological reasons which encouraged the empiricist approach to nature in Newton's thinking. In fact, for Newton our understanding of the workings of the universe derives from his conception about the limit of our understanding. When the nature cannot be fully understood by examining its parts, and how they interact, we must assume there that God responsible for its working. Newton explicitly takes this line in the first letter to Richard Bentley, December 1692, when he denies the Cartesian account of how some of the matter in the universe (in stars) gives off light and heat, while other matter (in planets) does not. Newton prefers to say that this distinction into two sorts of matter cannot be explained in terms of the principles of physics, and can only be explained by assuming a supreme creator. So, Newton's failure to work out the ontological problem of the causation of force successfully, according to his critics, was precisely what allowed him to develop his notion of Providence, and its basis in God's will, rather than in His reason, as Leibniz would have wanted to claim. Cartesian-styled mechanism, which made use of hypothetical aethers, was a recourse that Newton soon in his career abandoned and in his mature philosophy of nature rejected. This was an idea that Newton was never really happy with, and included speculations about it in additional Queries in the *Opticks* only as a gesture to Continental critics like Leibniz, who demanded a mechanism of causation in Newtonian physics. For the most part, however, he preferred not to indulge in hypotheses, or hypothetical entities. He regarded the electric spirit as something which was amply demonstrated by experiment but he found the lack of sufficient number of experiments to determine and demonstrate accurately the laws governing the actions of this spirit as an obstacle to carry out its quantification.

Newton's experimental attitude coincides with his voluntarist theology in view of the fact that since he knows that he cannot experimentally provide an account of the causation of these

forces, he must provide a metaphysical (and a methodological) account which justifies his claims about such seemingly occult forces, and his nescience about their physical causation.

The interplay and articulation of mathematics, natural philosophy, and providential theology in Newton's thought is brilliantly summarised in his anonymous account of the *Commercium epitolicum* (1715) which closed the dispute with Leibniz in particular, and with the Continental mechanical philosophers in general regarding his differences philosophical, methodological and theological. In this document Newton contrasted in a crystal-clear manner his approach to nature and that which was soon substituted for that of the *Philosophiae Naturalis Principia Mathematica*. It is appropriate to conclude, therefore, with Newton's own words:

The one [Newton] proceeds upon the Evidence arising from Experiments and Phaenomena, and stops where such Evidence is wanting; the other [Leibniz] is taken up with Hypotheses, and propounds them, not to be examined by Experiments, but to be believed without Examination. The one for want of Experiments to decide the Question doth not affirm whether the Cause of Gravity be Mechanical or not Mechanical: the other that it is a perpetual Miracle if it be not Mechanical. The one (by way of Enquiry) attributes it to the Power of the Creator that the least Particles of Matter are hard: the other attributes the Hardness of Matter to conspiring Motions, and calls it a perpetual Miracle if the Cause of this Hardness be other than Mechanical. The one doth not affirm that animal Motion in Man is purely mechanical: the other teaches that it is purely mechanical, the Soul or Mind (according to the Hypothesis of a *Harmonia Praestabilita*) never acting upon the Body so as to alter or influence its Motions. The one teaches that God (the God in whom we live and move and have our Being) is Omnipresent; but not as a Soul of the World: the other that he is not the Soul of the World, but INTELLIGENTIA SUPRAMUNDANA, an Intelligence above the Bounds of the World; whence it seems to follow that he cannot do any thing within the Bounds of the World, unless by an incredible Miracle. The one teaches that Philosophers are to argue from Phaenomena and Experiments to the Causes thereof, and thence to the Causes of those Causes, and so on till we come to the first Cause: the other that all the Actions of the first Cause are Miracles, and all the Laws imprest on Nature by the Will of God are perpetual Miracles and occult Qualities, and therefore not to be considered in Philosophy. But must the constant and universal Laws of Nature, if derived from the Power of God or the Action of a Cause not yet known to us, be called Miracles and occult Qualities, that is to say, Wonders and Absurdities? Must all the Arguments for a God taken from the Phaenomena of Nature be exploded by new hard Names? And must Experimental Philosophy be exploded as miraculous and absurd, because it asserts nothing more than can be proved by Experiments, and we cannot yet prove by Experiments that all the Phrenomena in Nature can be solved by meer Mechanical Causes? Certainly these things deserve to be better considered.

* * *

References

- Achinstein, P. (1990). "Newton's Corpuscular Query and Experimental Philosophy", in Bricker, Phillip and Hughes, R.I.G. (ed.), *Philosophical Perspective on Newtonian Science*, Cambridge Massachusetts, The MIT Press, pp. 135–175.
- Albury, W. R. (1978). Halley's Ode on the *Principia* of Newton and the Epicurean revival in England. *Journal of the History of Ideas*, 39, 24-43.
- Aldridge, A. O. (1973). "Ancients and Moderns", *The Dictionary of the History of Ideas*, New York, Charles Scribner's Sons, vol. I, pp. 76-87.
- Anstey, P. R. (2004). "The methodological origins of Newton's Queries", *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science Part A*, 35, 2, pp. 247-269.
- Ariew, R. & Gabbey, A. (1998). "The Scholastic Background", in Garber and Ayers (1988), pp. 425-453.
- Aristotle. (1960) *Posterior Analytics*, Hugh Tredennick (Trans.), London, Harvard University Press.
- Bacon, F. (1857) *The Works of Francis Bacon*, Vol. II, Spedding, James; Leslie, E. Robert; and Heath, Douglas D. (eds.), London, Longman.
- Barbour, J. B. (2001). *The discovery of dynamics*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Baron, H. (1959) "The Querelle of the Ancients and the Moderns as a problem for Renaissance scholarship", *Journal of the History of Ideas*, 20, pp. 3-22.
- Bechler, Z. (1991). *Newton's physics and the conceptual structure of the scientific revolution*. Dordrecht: Kluwer Academic Publishers.
- Bentley, R. (1693a). *A confutation of atheism from the origin and frame of the world. Part II*, Seventh lecture. London: H. Mortlock at the Phoenix in St. Paul's Church-yard.
- Bentley, R. (1693b). *A confutation of atheism from the origin and frame of the world. Part II*, Eighth lecture. London: H. Mortlock at the Phoenix in St. Paul's Church-yard.
- Bernard, A. (2003) "Sophistic aspects of Pappus's *Collection*", *Archive for History of Exact Sciences*, 57, 93-150.

- Bertoloni M. D. (2002) "Newton and the Leibniz-Clarke correspondence", in *The Cambridge Companion to Newton*, Cohen, I Bernard and Smith, George E. (eds.), Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, pp. 455-464.
- Biot, J. B. & Lefort, F. [eds.] (1856) *Commercium Epistolicum J. Collins et Aliorum de Analysi Promota*, Reimprimée sur l'édition original de 1712 avec l'indication des variantes de l'édition de 1722, complétée par une collection de pièces justificatives et documents, Paris, Mallet Bachelier.
- Boas, M. (1952) "The establishment of the mechanical philosophy", *Osiris* 10, pp. 412-541.
- Bodnár, I & Pellegrin, P. (2006) "Aristotle's Physics and Cosmology", in *A Companion to Ancient Philosophy*, Gill, Mary L. and Pellegrin, Pierre (eds.), Blackwell Publishing, pp. 270-291.
- Boyer, C. B. (1959). *The history of the calculus and its conceptual development: (The concepts of the calculus)*. New York: Dover.
- Boyle, R. (1991). The origin of forms and qualities. In M. A. Stewart (Ed.), *Selected philosophical papers of Robert Boyle*. Indianapolis: Hackett.
- Brewster, D. (1855). *Memoirs of the life, writings and discoveries of Sir Isaac Newton*. Edinburgh: Thomas Constable.
- Casini, P. (1984) "Newton: The Classical Scholia", *History of Science*, 22, pp. 1-58.
- Castillejo, D. (1981). *The expanding force in Newton's cosmos, as shown in his unpublished papers*. Madrid: Ediciones de Arte y Bibliofilia.
- Christianson, G. E. (1984). *In the presence of the Creator: Isaac Newton and his times*. New York: Free Press.
- Clarke, D. M. (2006) *Descartes. A Biography*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press.
- Clarke, J. (1730) *A Demonstration of some of the Principal Sections of Sir Isaac Newton's Principles of Natural Philosophy. In which his Peculiar Method of Treating that Useful Subject is Explained, and Applied to some of the Chief Phaenomena of the System of the World*. London, Printed for James and John Knapton.
- Cochrane, E. (1976) "Science and Humanism in the Italian Renaissance", *The American Historical Review*, 81, pp. 1039-1057.
- Cohen I. B. (1964) "'Quantum in Se Est': Newton's Concept of Inertia in Relation to Descartes and Lucretius", *Notes and Records of the Royal Society of London*, 19, 2, pp. 131-155.
- Cohen, I. B. (1966). *Franklin and Newton: An inquiry into speculative Newtonian experimental science and Franklin's work in electricity as an example thereof*. Cambridge, Mass: publ. for The American philosophical Society by Plarvard Univ. Press.
- Cohen, I. B. (1969) "Isaac Newton's *Principia*, the Scriptures, and the Divine Providence", in Morgenbesser, S., Suppes P. and White M. (ed.), *Philosophy, science, and method: essays in honor of Ernest Nagel*, New York, St Martin's Press, pp. 523-548.

- Cohen, I. B. (1971). *Introduction to Newton's "Principia"*. Cambridge, Mass.: Harvard University Press.
- Cohen, I. B. (1980). *The Newtonian revolution*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Cohen, I. B. (1982). The *Principia*, universal gravitation, and the "Newtonian style", in relation to the Newtonian revolution in science: Notes on the occasion of the 250th anniversary of Newton's death. In Z. Bechler (Ed.), *Contemporary Newtonian research* (pp. 21-108). London: Dordrecht.
- Cohen, I. B. (1987) "Newton's Third law and Universal Gravitation", *Journal of the History of Ideas*, 48, pp. 571-593.
- Cohen, I. B. (1992). The review of the first edition of Newton's *Principia* in the *Acta Eruditorum*, with notes on the other reviews. In P. M. Harman & A. Shapiro (Eds.), *The investigation of difficult things: Essays on Newton and the history of the exact sciences in honour of D. T. Whiteside* (pp. 323-353). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Cohen, I. B. (1995) "Newton's Method and Newton's Style", in I. Bernard and Richard S. Westfall, (eds.), *Newton: Texts, Backgrounds, & Commentaries*. New York: Norton Critical Edition, 1995 pp. 126-142.
- Cohen, I. B. (1999) *A guide to Newton's 'Principia'*, in Newton, 1999.
- Cohen, I. B. (2000) "Newton's Scholarship in Historical Perspective" in *The foundations of Newtonian scholarship*, Richard H. Dalitz and Michael Nauenberg (eds.), London, World Scientific Publishing, 2000, pp. 11-26.
- Cohen, I. B. (2002a). "Introduction" In I. B. Cohen & G. E. Smith (Eds.), *The Cambridge companion to Newton* (pp. 1-32). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Cohen, I. B. (2002b). Newton's concepts of force and mass, with notes on the laws of motion. In I. B. Cohen & G. E. Smith (Eds.), *The Cambridge companion to Newton* (pp. 57-84). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Cohen, I. B., & Westfall, R. S. (1995). *Newton: Texts, backgrounds, commentaries*. New York, NY: W.W. Norton.
- Conduitt, J. (1727-8c) "Conduitt's notes on Newton's character", King's College, Cambridge, Keynes Ms. 130.7.
- Copernicus, N. (1543) *De Revolutionibus Orbium Coelestium, Libri VI* (Including Edward Rosen translation into English of *De Revolutionibus Orbium Coelestium, Libri VI* (Warsaw: Polish Scientific Publications, 1978 Nuremberg), Octavo Edition, Octavo Corporation,. 1999.
- Crocker, R. (2003). *Henry More, 1614-1687: A biography of the Cambridge Platonist*. Dordrecht: Kluwer Academic Publishers.
- Cudworth, R. (1837) *The true intellectual system of the universe*, Volume 1, Thomas Birch (ed.), Gould & Newman.

- Cudworth, R. (1838) *The true intellectual system of the universe*, Volume 2, Thomas Birch (ed.), Gould & Newman.
- Cunningham, A. (1991) "How the Principia Got Its Name; or, taking Natural Philosophy Seriously", *History of Science*, 29, pp. 388-389.
- Cuomo, S. (2000). *Pappus of Alexandria and the mathematics of late Antiquity*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- De Smet, Rudolf and Verelst, Karin (2001) "Newton's Scholium Generale: The Platonic and Stoic Legacy-Philo, Justus Lipsius and the Cambridge Platonists", *History of Science*, 39, 1, pp. 1-30.
- Dear, P. (1995) *Discipline and Experience: The Mathematical Way in the Scientific Revolution*, Chicago and London, University of Chicago Press.
- Dear, P. (2001). *Revolutionizing the sciences: European knowledge and its ambitions, 1500-1700*. Princeton, N.J: Princeton University Press.
- Dear, P. (2006) *The Intelligibility of Nature. How Science Makes Sense of the World*, Chicago, The University of Chicago Press.
- Delgado-Moreira, Raquel. (2006) "Newton's Treatise on Revelation: The Use of a Mathematical Discourse", *Historical Research*, 79, pp. 224-246.
- Des Chene, D. (2002) "Cartesian Science: Regis and Rohault", in *A Companion to Early Modern Philosophy*, Nadler, Steven (ed.), Oxford, Blackwell Publishers, pp. 183-196.
- Des Chene, D. (2008) "Aristotelian Natural Philosophy: Body, Cause, Nature", in *A Companion to Descartes*, Broughton, Janet and Carriero, John (eds.) Singapore, Blackwell Publishing, pp. 17-32.
- Descartes, R. (1925). *The Geometry of René Descartes*. Translated from the French and Latin by D. E. Smith and M. L. Latham (with a facsimile of the first edition, 1637). Chicago: Open Court Publishing Company.
- Descartes, René (1967) *The Philosophical Works of Descartes*, Haldane, Elizabeth S., and Ross, G.R.T. (eds.), Cambridge, Cambridge University Press.
- Descartes, René. (1958) *Descartes. Philosophical Writings*, Kemp Smith, Norman (ed. and trans.), New York, The modern Library.
- Descartes, René. (1973-1978) *Oeuvres de Descartes*. Charles Adam and Paul Tannery (eds.). 12 Vols., Paris, Librairie Philosophique J. Vrin en co-edition avec le Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique.
- Descartes, René. (1991) *The Philosophical Writings of Descartes*, Vol. III, Cottingham, John *et al.* (ed. and trans.), Cambridge, Cambridge University Press.
- Descartes, René. (2000) *Philosophical Essays and Correspondence*, Ariew, Roger (ed.), Indianapolis, Hackett Publishing Company.

- Descartes, René. (2004) *The World and Other Writings*, Gaukroger, Stephen (ed. and trans.), Cambridge, Cambridge University Press.
- Descartes, René. (2008) *Meditations on First Philosophy. With Selections from the Objections and Replies*, Moriarty, Michael (trans.), Oxford, Oxford University Press.
- Descartes, René. *Rules for the Direction of Mind*, Elizabeth S. Haldane and G.R.T. Ross (trans.), Encyclopaedia Britannica, Chicago, The University of Chicago Press, 1952.
- Dijksterhuis, E. J. (1961) *The Mechanization of the World Picture*, Dikshoorn C. (trans.) New York, Oxford University Press.
- Disalle, Robert. (2002) "Newton's Philosophical Analysis of Space and Time", in *The Cambridge Companion to Newton*, Cohen, I Bernard and Smith, George E. (eds.), Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, pp. 33-56.
- Dobbs, B. & Jacob, M. C. (1995). *Newton and the culture of Newtonianism*. Atlantic Highlands, NJ: Humanities Press.
- Dobbs, B. (1975) *The foundations of Newton's alchemy or 'The hunting of the Green Lyon'*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press.
- Dobbs, B. (1988). Newton's alchemy and his 'active principle' of gravitation. In P. B. Scheurer & G. Debrock (Eds.), *Newton's scientific and philosophical legacy* (pp. 55-80). Dordrecht: Kluwer Academic Publishers.
- Dobbs, B. (1990) "Newton as alchemist and theologian", in *Standing on the shoulders of giants: A longer view of Newton and Halley*, Norman J.W. Thrower (ed.), Berkeley and Los Angeles, University of California Press, pp. 128-140.
- Dobbs, B. (1991a). Stoic and Epicurean doctrines in Newton's system of the world. In M. J. Osler (Ed.), *Atoms, pneuma, and tranquillity: Epicurean and Stoic themes in European thought* (pp. 221-238). Cambridge University Press: Cambridge.
- Dobbs, B. (1991b). *The Janus faces of genius. The role alchemy in Newton's thought*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press.
- Dobbs, B. (1993). "'The Unity of Truth': An Integrated View of Newton's Work" in *Action and reaction. Proceedings of a Symposium to Commemorate the Tercentenary of Newton's Principia*, Theerman, Paul and Seeff, Adele F. (eds.), Newark, University of Delaware Press, pp. 105-122.
- Domski, M. (2003). The constructible and the intelligible in Newton's philosophy of geometry. *Philosophy of Science*, 70(5), 1114-1124.
- du Châtelet, Gabrielle-Émilie Le Tonnelier de Breteuil Marquise. (1738) *Institutions de Physique*. Paris, 1740; Pierre Desmaizeaus, (ed.), *Recueil de Diverses Pieces, sur la Philosophie, le Religion*

Naturelle, l'Histoire, les Mthematiques, &c. par Messieurs Leibniz, Clarke, Newton & Authres Celebres. Lausanne.

- Ducheyne, S. (2005). Mathematical models in Newton's *Principia*: A new view of the 'Newtonian style'. *International Studies in the Philosophy of Science*, 19(1), 1-19.
- Ducheyne, Steffen. (2005 a) "Mathematical models in Newton's *Principia* : A new view of the 'Newtonian Style'", *International Studies in the Philosophy of Science*, 19, 1, pp. 1-19.
- Ducheyne, Steffen. (2005 b) "Newton's Idea and Practice of Unification", *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science (Part A)* 36, pp. 61-78.
- Ducheyne, Steffen. (2006) "The General Scholium: Some notes on Newton's Published and Unpublished Endeavours", University of Pittsburgh, PhilSci Archive, URL: <http://philsci-archive.pitt.edu/archive/00003681/>. Accessed on March 16, 2008.
- Duhamel, Jean-Marie-Constant. (1865) *Des Méthodes dans les Sciences du Raisonnement.* Paris, Gauthier-Villars.
- Dunlop, K. (2011). What geometry postulates: Newton and Barrow on the relationship of mathematics to nature. In A. Janiak & E. Schliesser (Eds.), *Interpreting Newton. Critical essays* (pp. 69-102). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Euclid (1956). *The thirteen books of Euclid's Elements.* In T. L. Heath (Ed.). New York: Dover.
- Feingold, Mordechai. (2001) "Mathematicians and Naturalists: Sir Isaac Newton and the Royal Society," in *Isaac Newton's Natural Philosophy*, Buchwald, J. Z. and Cohen I. Bernard (ed.) Cambridge Massachusetts, MIT Press, 2001, pp. 77-102.
- Figala, Karin and Petzold, Ulrich. (1993) "Alchemy in the Newtonian circle: Personal acquaintances and the problem of the late phase of Isaac Newton's alchemy", in Field, Judith Veronica and James, Frank A. J. L. (ed.) *Renaissance and Revolution: Humanists, Scholars, Craftsmen and Natural Philosophers in Early Modern Europe*, Cambridge University Press, pp. 173-191.
- Finocchiaro, Maurice A. (2008) *The Essential Galileo*, Hackett Publishing Company, Indianapolis.
- Force, James E. (1999a) "Newton's God of Dominion: the unity of Newton's theological, scientific and political thought", in Force, James E. and Popkin, Richard Henry, (ed.). *Newton and religion: Context, nature, and influence*, Dordrecht, Kluwer Academic Publishers, pp. 76-102.
- Force, James E. (1999b) "Newton, the 'Ancients' and the 'Moderns'" in Force, James E. and Popkin, Richard Henry, (ed.). *Newton and religion: Context, nature, and influence*, Dordrecht, Kluwer Academic Publishers, pp. 237-257.
- Force, James E. and Popkin, Richard Henry, (eds.) (1994) *The Books of Nature and Scripture. Recent Essays on Natural Philosophy, Thology, and Biblical Criticism in the Netherlands of Spinoza's Time and the British Isles og Newton's Time*, Dordrecht, Kluwer Academic Publishers.

- Force, James E. and Popkin, Richard Henry, (eds.) (1999). *Newton and religion: Context, nature, and influence*, Dordrecht, Kluwer Academic Publishers.
- Funkenstein, Amos. (1986) *Theology and the scientific imagination from the Middle Ages to the seventeenth century*, Princeton, Princeton University Press.
- Gabbey, A. (1990). "Henry More and the limits of mechanism". In S. Hutton & R. Crocker (Eds.), *Henry More (1614-1687) tercentenary studies* (pp. 19-35). Dordrecht, Netherlands: Kluwer Academic Publishers.
- Gabbey, A. (1992). Newton's *Mathematical principles of natural philosophy*: A treatise on 'Mechanics'? In P. M. Harman & A. E. Shapiro (Eds.), *The investigation of difficult things: Essays on Newton and the exact sciences* (pp. 305-322). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Gabbey, A. (2004). Newton, active powers, and the mechanical philosophy. In I. B. Cohen & G. Smith (Eds.), *The Cambridge Companion to Newton* (pp. 329-357). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Gandt, F. (1995). *Force and geometry in Newton's Principia*. Princeton, N.J.: Princeton University Press.
- Garber, Daniel and Ayers, Michael. [eds.] (1988) *The Cambridge History of Seventeenth-Century Philosophy*, 2 vols., Cambridge, Cambridge University Press.
- Garber, Daniel. (2000) "A different Descartes. Descartes and the programme for a mathematical physics in his correspondence", in *Descartes' Natural Philosophy* Gaukroger, Stephen; Schuster, John; and Sutton, John (eds.), London, Routledge, pp. 113-130.
- Garber, Daniel. (2008) "Physics and Foundations" in *The Cambridge History of Science, Vol. 3 Early Modern Science*, Park, Katharine and Daston, Lorraine (eds.) Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, pp. 21-69.
- Garrison, J. W. (1987). Newton and the relation of mathematics to natural philosophy. *Journal of the History of Ideas*, 48(4), 609-627.
- Gaukroger, S. (2010). *The collapse of mechanism and the rise of sensibility. Science and the shaping of Modernity, 1680–1760*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Gaukroger, Stephen. (1995) *Descartes. An Intellectual Biography*, Oxford, Clarendon Press.
- Gingras, Y. (2001). What did mathematics do to physics? *History of Science*, 39(4), 383-416.
- Goldish Matt. (1998) *Judaism in the Theology of Sir Isaac Newton*, Dordrecht: Kluwer Academic Publishers.
- Grant, Edward. (1987), "Ways to Interpret the Terms 'Aristotelian' and 'Aristotelianism' in Medieval and Renaissance Natural Philosophy", *History of Science*, 25, 4, pp. 335-358.
- Grant, Edward. (2000) "God and Natural Philosophy: The Late Middle Ages and Sir Isaac Newton" *Early Science and Medicine*, 5, 3, pp. 279-298.

- Guerlac, H., & Jacob, M. C. (1969). Bentley, Newton, and Providence. The Boyle lectures once more. *Journal of the History of Ideas*, 30(3), 307-318.
- Guicciardini, Niccolò (2004c) "Isaac Newton and the publication of his mathematical manuscripts", *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science* 35, pp. 455-70.
- Guicciardini, Niccolò. (1999) *Reading the Principia: the Debate on Newton's Mathematical Methods for Natural Philosophy from 1687 to 1736* Cambridge, Cambridge University Press.
- Guicciardini, Niccolò. (2002) "Analysis and Synthesis in Newton's Mathematical Work", in *The Cambridge Companion to Newton*, Cohen, I Bernard and Smith, George E. (eds.), Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, pp. 308-328.
- Guicciardini, Niccolò. (2003) "Conceptualism and Contextualism in the Recent Historiography of Newton's *Principia*" *Historia Mathematica*, 30, pp. 407-431.
- Guicciardini, Niccolò. (2004a) "Newton and the publication of his mathematical manuscripts", *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science*, 35, 3, pp. pp. 1-18.
- Guicciardini, Niccolò. (2004b) "Dot-Age: Newton's Mathematical Legacy in the Eighteenth Century", *Early Science and Medicine*, 9, pp. 218-256.
- Guicciardini, Niccolò. (2005) "Isaac Newton, *Philosophiae naturalis principia mathematica*, first edition (1687)" in *Landmark Writings in Western Mathematics, 1640–1940*, Grattan-Guinness, Ivor (ed.), Netherlands, Elsevier Scinec, Chapter 5, pp. 59-87.
- Hall, A. R & Hall, Boas M. (1959) "Newton's electric spirit: Four oddities", *Isis*, 50, 4, pp. 473-476.
- Hall, A. R. (1954). *The scientific revolution, 1500-1800: The formation of the modern scientific attitude*. London: Longmans, Green.
- Hall, A. Rupert. (1958) "Correcting the Principia", *Osiris*, 13, 291-326.
- Hall, A. Rupert. (1980) *Philosophers at war: The quarrel between Newton and Leibniz*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press.
- Hall, A. Rupert. (1983) *The Revolution in Science 1500-1750*, Longman, 1983.
- Hall, A. Rupert. (1992) *Isaac Newton: adventurer in thought*. Oxford, Oxford University Press.
- Hall, A. Rupert. (1995) *All was light. An introduction to Newton's Opticks*, Oxford, Clarendon Press.
- Hall, A. Rupert. (1998) "Isaac Newton and the aerial nitre", *Notes and Records of the Royal Society of London*, 52, 1, pp. 51-61.
- Harris, John. (1704) *Lexicum Technicum: Or An Universal English Dictionary of Arts and Sciences: Explaining not only the Terms of Art, but the Arts themselves*, London, vol. I.
- Harrison, P. (2002). Voluntarism and early modern science. *History of Science*, 40, 1-27.

- Harrison, Peter. (2007). *The Fall of Man and the Foundations of Science*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press.
- Hawes, J. L. (1968). Newton's revival of the aether hypothesis and the explanation of gravitational attraction. *Notes and Records of the Royal Society of London*, 23(2), 200-212.
- Haycock, David B. (2004) "'The long-lost truth': Sir Isaac Newton and the Newtonian pursuit of ancient knowledge", *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science*, 35, pp. 605-623.
- Heimann, P. M. (1973) "Newtonian Natural Philosophy and the Scientific Revolution", *History of Science*, 11, pp. 1-7.
- Henry, J. (1986) "Occult Qualities and the Experimental Philosophy: Active Principles in Pre-Newtonian. Matter Theory", *History Science*, 24, pp. 335-381.
- Henry, J. (1990) "Henry More versus Robert Boyle: The Spirit of Nature and the Nature of Providence", in *Henry More (1614-1687): Tercentenary Studies*, Hutton, Sarah (ed.), Dordrecht, Kluwer Academic Publishers, pp. 55-75.
- Henry, J. (1994). "Pray do not ascribe that notion to me": God and Newton's gravity. In J. E. Force & R. H. Popkin (Eds.), *The Books of Nature and Scripture: Recent essays on natural philosophy, theology and biblical criticism in the Netherlands of Spinoza's time and the British Isles of Newton's time* (pp. 123-147). Dordrecht: Kluwer.
- Henry, J. (2000) "Matter", in Applebaum, Wilbur [ed.] *Encyclopedia of the Scientific Revolution. From Copernicus to Newton*, New York, Garland Publishing, pp. 621-628.
- Henry, J. (2004). Metaphysics and the origins of Modern science: Descartes and the importance of laws of nature. *Early Science and Medicine*, 9(2), 73-114.
- Henry, J. (2007a). *Isaac Newton and the problem of action at a distance* (pp. 1-22). Provided by the author: Manuscript.
- Henry, J. (2007b). Isaac Newton y el problema de la acción a distancia. *Estudios de Filosofía*, 35, 189-226.
- Henry, J. (2008a) "Henry More", in *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy (Fall 2008 Edition)*, Edward N. Zalta (ed.), URL = <<http://plato.stanford.edu/archives/fall2008/entries/henry-more/>>. Accessed on December 23, 2010.
- Henry, J. (2008b) "Isaac Newton: Science and Religion in the Unity of His Thought", conference presented at the *II Seminario de Historia y Filosofía de la Ciencia*, Medellín, Universidad de Antioquia, August 2007. (Original unpublished). Spanish version "Isaac Newton: Ciencia y Religión en la Unidad de su Pensamiento", *Estudios de Filosofía*, Universidad de Antioquia, 39, 2009.
- Henry, J. (2009). Voluntarist theology at the origins of modern science: A response to Peter Harrison. *History of Science*, 47, 79-113.

- Henry, J. (2011). Gravity and *De gravitatione*: the development of Newton's ideas on action at a distance. *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science*, 42, 11-27.
- Herivel, J. W. (1965). *The background to Newton's Principia: A study of Newton's dynamical researches in the years 1664-84*. Oxford: Clarendon Press.
- Higgitt, Rebekah. (2007) *Recreating Newton: Newtonian Biography and the Making of Nineteenth-Century History of Science*, London, Pickering & Chatto.
- Hill, K. (1997a) "Neither Ancient nor Modern: Wallis and Barrow on the Composition of Continua. Part two: The Seventeenth-Century Context: The Struggle Between Ancient and Modern", *Notes and Records of the Royal Society of London*, 51, 1, 13-22.
- Hill, K. (1997b) "Neither Ancient nor Modern: Wallis and Barrow on the Composition of Continua. Part one: Mathematical styles and the composition of continua, *Notes and Records of the Royal Society of London*, 51, 2, pp. 165-178.
- Hill, K. (1998) "John Wallis and Isaac Barrow: tradition and innovation and the state of mathematics", *Endeavour* Vol. 22, 3, pp. 117-120.
- Home, R. W. (1982) Newton on electricity and the aether, in *Contemporary Newtonian Research*, Zev Bechler (ed.), D. Reidel Publishing Company, pp. 191-213.
- Home, R. W. (1985). Force, electricity, and the powers of living matter in Newton's mature philosophy of nature. In M. J. Osler & P. L. Farber (Eds.), *Religion, science, and worldview. Essays in honor of Richard S. Westfall* (pp. 95-117). London: Cambridge University Press.
- Home, R. W. (1993) Newton's subtle matter: the *Opticks* queries and the mechanical philosophy, in Field, Judith Veronica and James, Frank A. J. L. (ed.) *Renaissance and Revolution: Humanists, Scholars, Craftsmen and Natural Philosophers in Early Modern Europe*, Cambridge University Press, pp. 193-202.
- Hutchison, Keith. (1982) "What Happened to Occult Qualities in the Scientific Revolution?", *Isis*, 73, pp. 233-253.
- Iliffe, Rob. (2004) "Abstract considerations: disciplines and the incoherence of Newton's natural philosophy", *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science*, 35, pp. 427-254.
- Ingegno, Alfonso. (1998) "The new philosophy of nature", in *The Cambridge History of Renaissance Philosophy*, Schmitt, Charles B. et al. (eds.), Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, pp. 236-263.
- Jacob, M. C. (1976). *The Newtonians and the English Revolution, 1689-1720*. Ithaca: Cornell University Press.
- Jacob, M. C. (2004). Introduction. In J. E. Force & S. Hutton (Eds.), *Newton and Newtonianism. New studies* (pp. ix-xvii). Dordrecht: Kluwer Academic Publishers.
- Janiak, A. (2007). Newton and the reality of force. *Journal of the History of Philosophy*, 45(1), 127-147.

- Janiak, A. (2008). *Newton as philosopher*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Jenkins, J. E. (2000) "Arguing about Nothing: Henry More and Robert Boyle on the Theological Implications of the Void" in Osler, Margaret J. *Rethinking the Scientific Revolution*, Cambridge, University Press, 2000, pp. 153-179.
- Kargon, R. (1964). Walter Charleton, Robert Boyle, and the acceptance of Epicurean atomism in England. *Isis*, 55(2), 184-192.
- Keill, John. (1755) *Introductio ad Veram Physicam seu Lectiones Physicæ, quibus Accendunt Theorematum Hugeniorum de Vi Centrifuga & Motu Circulari Demonstrationes*, Editio Tertia, Oxoniæ, e Theatro Sheldoniano, Impensis Hen. Clements, ad Insignie Lunæ Falcatæ in Cœmeterio D. Pauli Londini.
- Keynes, John Maynard. (1947) "Newton, the Man" in *The Royal Society Newton Tercentenary Celebrations 15-19 July 1946*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, pp. 27-34.
- Kitcher, Philip. (1973) "Fluxions, Limits, and Infinite Littleness. A Study of Newton's Presentation of the Calculus", *Isis*, 64, 1, 33-49.
- Knoespel, Kenneth J. (1999) "Interpretative strategies in Newton's *Theologiae gentilis origenes philosophicæ*" in Force, James E. and Popkin, Richard Henry, (ed.). *Newton and religion: Context, nature, and influence*, Dordrecht, Kluwer Academic Publishers, pp. 179-202.
- Kochiras, H. (2009). Gravity and Newton's substance counting problem. *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science*, 40(3), 267-280.
- Kochiras, H. (2011). Gravity's cause and substance counting: contextualizing the problems. *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science*, 42(1), 167-184.
- Koyré, Alexandre and Cohen, I Bernard. (1962) "Newton and the Leibniz-Clarke correspondence". *Archives Internationales d'Histoire des Sciences*, 15, pp. 63-126.
- Koyré, Alexandre and Cohen, I. Bernard. (1960) "Newton's 'Electric and Elastic Spirit'", *Isis* 51, 3, 1960, p. 337.
- Koyré, Alexandre. (1956) "L'hypothèse et l'expérience chez Newton", *Bulletin de la Société Française de Philosophie*, 50, pp. 59-79.
- Koyré, Alexandre. (1960) "Les 'Regulae philosophandi'", *Archives internationales d'histoire des sciences* 13, pp. 3-14. Translation into English by I Bernard Cohen included in Koyré, 1965, Chapter VI "Newton's 'Regulae Philosophandi'", pp. 261-272.
- Koyré, Alexandre. (1965) *Newtonian Studies*, London, Chapman and Hall.
- Leibniz, G. W., & Clarke, S. (1717). *A collection of papers which passed between the late learned Mr. Leibnitz and Dr. Clarke in the years 1715 and 1716 relating to the principles of natural philosophy and religion: With an appendix*. London: Knapton.
- Leibniz, G. W. (1970). *Philosophical papers and letters* L. E. Loemker (Ed.). Dordrecht: D. Reidel.

- Leibniz, G. W., & Clarke, S. (2000). *G. W. Leibniz and Samuel Clarke: Correspondence*. R. Ariew (Ed.). Cambridge: Hackett Publishing Company.
- Levine, Joseph M. (1981) "Ancients and Moderns Reconsidered", *Eighteenth-Century Studies*, 15, pp. 72-89.
- Levine, Joseph M. (1991) *The battle of the Books. History and literature in the Augustan Age*, London, Cornell University Press.
- Maclaurin, Colin. (1748) *An Account of Sir Isaac Newton's philosophical Discoveries*, London, Patrick Murdoch.
- Maglo, Kofi. (2007) "Force, Mathematics and Physics in Newton's Principia: A New Approach to Enduring Issues", *Science in Context*, 20, 4, pp. 571-600.
- Mahoney, Michael S. (1968) "Another Look at Greek Geometrical Analysis", *Archive for History of Exact Sciences*, 5, 318-348.
- Mahoney, Michael S. (2005) "The Beginnings of Algebraic Thought in the Seventeenth Century", <http://www.princeton.edu/%7Emike/17thcent.html> (accessed on 2005-06-15).
- Malet, Antoni. (1997) "Isaac Barrow on the Mathematization of Nature. Theological Voluntarism and the Rise of Geometrical Optics", *Journal of the History of Ideas*, 58, 2 pp. 265-287.
- Mamiani, Maurizio. (2001) "To twist the meaning: Newton's *Regulae Philosophandi* revisited" in J.Z. Buchwald, J. Z. and Cohen I.B. (ed.), *Isaac Newton's natural philosophy*, MIT Press, Cambridge, pp. 1-14.
- Markley Robert. (1999) "Newton, Corruption, and the tradition of Universal History", in in Force, James E. and Popkin, Richard Henry, (ed.). *Newton and religion: Context, nature, and influence*, Dordrecht, Kluwer Academic Publishers, pp. 121-143.
- Markley, Robert. (1993), Review of *The Janus Faces of Genius: The Role of Alchemy in Newton's Thought*, *Configurations* 1, 2, pp. 273-276.
- McGuire, J. E. (1966) "Body and void and Newton's *De Mundi Systemate*": Some new sources", *Archives for History of the Exact Sciences*, 3 pp. 206-248. Included in McGuire, 1995 (chapter 3, pp. 103-150).
- McGuire, J. E. (1968a) "Force, active principles, and Newton's invisible realm", *Ambix*, 15, pp. 154-208. Included in McGuire, 1995 (chapter 5, pp. 190-238).
- McGuire, J. E. (1968b) "The Origin of Newton's Doctrine of Essential Qualities", *Centaurus*, 12, 4: pp. 233-260. also included in McGuire, 1995: 239-261.
- McGuire, J. E. (1970) "'Newton's Principles of Philosophy': An Intended Preface for the 1704 *Opticks* and a Related Draft Fragment", *The British Journal for the History of Science*, 5, 18, pp. 178-186.

- McGuire, J. E. (1972) "Boyle's conception of Nature", *Journal of the History of Ideas*, 33, 4, pp. 523-542.
- McGuire, J. E. (1977) "Neoplatonism and Active Principles: Newton and the *Corpus Hermeticum*", in Westman, R.S.; McGuire, J.E. (eds.), *Hermeticism and the Scientific Revolution*, University of California, Los Angeles, pp. 95-142.
- McGuire, J. E. (1978a) "Existence, Actuality and Necessity: Newton on Space and Time", *Annals of Science*, 35, pp. 463–508.
- McGuire, J. E. (1978b) "Newton on Place, Time and God: An Unpublished Source", *British Journal for the History of Science*, 11, 38, pp. 114–29.
- McGuire, J. E. (1990) "Predicates of the Pure Existence: Newton on God's Space and Time" in *Philosophical Perspectives on Newtonian Science*, Bricker, Phillip and Hughes, P.I.G. (eds.). Cambridge, Massachusetts, The MIT Press, 1990, pp. 91-108.
- McGuire, J. E. (1995) *Tradition and Innovation. Newton's Metaphysics of Nature*, Dordrecht, Kluwer Academic Publishers.
- McGuire, J. E. (2007). A dialogue with Descartes: Newton's ontology of true and immutable natures. *Journal of the History of Philosophy*, 45(1), 103-125.
- McGuire, J. E. and Rattansi, P. M. (1966) Newton and the "Pipes of Pan", *Notes and Records of the Royal Society of London*, 21, 2 pp. 108-143.
- McMullin, E. (1978) *Newton on Matter and Activity*, Indiana, University of Notre Dame Press.
- McMullin, E. (2001) "The Impact of Newton's Principia on the Philosophy of Science" *Philosophy of Science*, 68, 3, pp. 279-310.
- Meli, D. B. (1993) *Equivalence and Priority: Newton versus Leibniz: Including Leibniz's Unpublished Manuscripts on the "Principia"*, Oxford, Clarendon Press of Oxford University Press, 1993.
- Menn, S. (1988) "The intellectual setting", in Garber and Ayers (1988), pp. 33-86.
- Millen, R. (1985). The manifestation of occult qualities in the scientific revolution. In M. J. Osler & P. L. Farber (Eds.), *Religion, science, and worldview. Essays in honor of Richard S. Westfall* (pp. 233-253). London: Cambridge University Press.
- Miller, P. (1978). Bentley and Newton. In I. B. Cohen & R. E. Schofield (Eds.), *Isaac Newton's papers & letters on natural philosophy: And related documents* (2nd ed., pp. 271-278). Harvard University Press: Cambridge.
- Milton, J. R. (1998). Laws of nature. In D. Garber & M. Ayers (Eds.), *The Cambridge history of seventeenth-century philosophy* (Vol. 1, pp. 680-721). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- More, H. (1662). *A collection of several philosophical writings of*. London: Printed by James Flesher for W. Morden.

- More, H. (1925) *Philosophical Writings of Henry More*, MacKinnon, Flora I. (ed.) New York, Oxford University Press.
- Nadler, S. (1988) "Doctrines of Explanation in Late Scholasticism and in the Mechanical Philosophy", in Garber and Ayers (1988), pp. 513-552.
- Newton, I. (1664) *Quaestiones quaedam Philosophiae*, Add Ms. 3996, Cambridge, Cambridge University Library. [Newton Project]
- Newton, I. (1666) "To resolve problems by Motion", in *Unpublished Scientific Papers of Isaac Newton. A Selection from the Collection in the University Library Cambridge*, Hall, A. Rupert and Hall, M. Boas (eds.), Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 1962, pp. 15-64.
- Newton, I. (1668) "De gravitatione et aequipondio fluidorum" in *Unpublished Scientific Papers of Isaac Newton. A selection from the collection in the university library Cambridge*, A. Rupert Hall and M. Boas Hall (eds.), Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 1962, pp. 90-156.
- Newton, I. (1670-1) *De Methodis Serierum et Fluxionum*, in *The Mathematical Papers of Isaac Newton*, Derek T. Whiteside (ed. and trans.), 8 vols. Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, , Vol. III.
- Newton, I. (1670-1680c) *Untitled treatise on Revelation*, Yahuda Ms. Var. 1 Newton Ms. 1. [Newton Project]
- Newton, I. (1672) "New Theory about Light and Colors", *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London*, 80, pp. 3075-3087.
- Newton, I. (1672c) "Of Natures obvious laws & processes in vegetation", Dibner Collection MS. 1031B, Dibner Library for the History of Science and Technology, Smithsonian Institution. [Newton Project]
- Newton, I. (1675) "An Hypothesis explaining the Properties of Light", in I. Bernard Cohen and Robert E. Schofield (eds.), in *Isaac Newton's papers and letters on natural philosophy and related documents*, Cohen, I. Bernard (ed.), Schofield, Robert E. (assist.) Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, pp. 178–235.
- Newton, I. (1680c. a) "Geometria curvilinea" in *The Mathematical Papers of Isaac Newton*, Derek T. Whiteside (ed. and trans.), 8 vols. Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 1968-1980, Vol. IV, pp. 420-505.
- Newton, I. (1680c. b) "Veterum loca solida restituta" in *The Mathematical Papers of Isaac Newton*, Derek T. Whiteside (ed. and trans.), 8 vols. Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 1968-1980, Vol. IV, pp. 274-321.
- Newton, I. (1683-4) "Lectures on Algebra 1673-1693" in *The Mathematical Papers of Isaac Newton*, Derek T. Whiteside (ed. and trans.), 8 vols. Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 1968-1980, Vol. V, p. 54-517.

- Newton, I. (1690c.) *The Original of Religions*, Yahuda Ms. 41, Israel, Jewish National and University Library. [Newton Project]
- Newton, I. (1692) "Some Thoughts about the Nature of Acids" in Harris, John (1710) *Lexicum Technicum: Or An Universal English Dictionary of Arts and Sciences: Explaining not only the Terms of Art, but the Arts themselves*. London, Vol. II, Introduction, n.p.
- Newton, I. (1706) *Optice: Sive de Reflexionibus, Refractionibus, Inflexionibus et Coloribus Lucis*, London.
- Newton, I. (1710c. a) "Seven Statements on Religion", Keynes Ms. 6, Kings College Library, Cambridge, England.
- Newton, I. (1710c. b) *Three paragraphs on Religion with drafts*, Keynes Ms. 9, Cambridge, England, King's College Library [Newton Project]
- Newton, I. (1710c. c) *Irenicum, or Ecclesiastical Polyty tending to Peace*, Keynes Ms. 3, Cambridge, King's College. [Newton Project]
- Newton, I. (1711) *Analysis per Quantitatum Series, Fluxiones, ac Differentias: Cum Enumeratione Linearum Tertii Ordinis*, W. Jones (ed.), Londini.
- Newton, I. (1713) *Philosophiae Naturalis Principia Mathematica*, Editio secunda auctior et emendatior, Cantabrigae, MDCCXIII.
- Newton, I. (1714/5) "An Account of the Book entituled *Commercium Epistolicum Collinii & aliorum, De Analysi promotum*; published by order of the Royal-Society, in relation to the Dispute between Mr. Leibnitz and Dr. Keill, about the Right of Invention of the Method of Fluxions, by some call'd the Differential Method", *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London*, 342, 1714/5, pp. 173-224.
- Newton, I. (1716c[a]) ULC. Add. 3965.13, fol. 422^r, in McGuire, (1966). Also included in McGuire, (1995) *Tradition and Innovation. Newton's Metaphysics of Nature*, Dordrecht, Kluwer Academic Publishers, Chapter 3, pp. 103-150.
- Newton, I. (1716c[b]) ULC. Add. 3965.13, fol. 422^v, in McGuire, (1966). Also included in McGuire, (1995) *Tradition and Innovation. Newton's Metaphysics of Nature*, Dordrecht, Kluwer Academic Publishers, Chapter 3, pp. 103-150.
- Newton, I. (1717) *Opticks: Or, A Treatise of the Reflections, Refractions, Inflexions and Colours of Light. The Second Edition, with Additions*, London, Printed by W. Bwyer for William Innys at the Prince's Arms in St. Paul's Church-Yard.
- Newton, I. (1729) *The Mathematical Principles of Natural Philosophy*, Andrew Motte (trans.), London, Printed for Benjamin Motte.
- Newton, I. (1730) *Opticks or a Treatise of the Reflections, Refractions, Inflexions & Colours of Light*, London, Printed for William Innys at the West-End of St. Paul's.

- Newton, I. (1736). *The method of fluxions and infinite series; with its application to the geometry of curve-lines*. (Translation and notes John Colson). London: H. Woodfall.
- Newton, I. (1745) *Sir Isaac Newton's two Treatises of the Quadrature of Curves, and Analysis by Equations of an Infinite Number of Terms, Explained: Containing the Treatises Themselves, Translated into English, with a Large Commentary by John Stewart*, London.
- Newton, I. (1934) *Sir Isaac Newton's Mathematical Principles of Natural Philosophy and his System of the World*. Translated into English by Andrew Motte in 1729. The translations revised and supplied with an historical and explanatory appendix, by Florian Cajori, Two volumes, Berkeley and Los Angeles, University of California Press.
- Newton, I. (1952). *Opticks: Or, A treatise of the reflections, refractions, inflections & colours of light. Based on the 4th ed., London, 1730*. New York: Dover Publications.
- Newton, I. (1958) *Isaac Newton's papers and letters on natural philosophy and related documents*, Cohen, I. Bernard (ed.), Schofield, Robert E. (assist.) Cambridge, Cambridge University Press.
- Newton, I. (1959-1977) *The Correspondence of Isaac Newton*, H. W. Turnbull, J. F. Scott, A.R. Hall, and L. Tilling, (eds.), 7 vols. Cambridge, Cambridge University Press.
- Newton, I. (1962). *Unpublished Scientific Papers of Isaac Newton: A Selection from the Portsmouth Collection in the University Library, Cambridge*, A. R. Hall and M. B. Hall (ed.), Cambridge, Cambridge University Press.
- Newton, I. (1968-1980) *The Mathematical Papers of Isaac Newton*, Derek T. Whiteside (ed. and trans.), 8 vols. Cambridge, Cambridge University Press.
- Newton, I. (1972) *Isaac Newton's Philosophiae Naturalis Principia Mathematica*. The Third Edition (1726) with Variant Readings, Assembled and Edited by Alexandre Koyré and I. Bernard Cohen, with the Assistance of Anne Whitman, 2 volumes, Cambridge, University Press.
- Newton, I. (1976-1981). *The mathematical papers of Isaac Newton*. 8 Vols. D.T. Whiteside (Ed.), Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Newton, I. (1984). *The optical papers of Isaac Newton*. A. E. Shapiro (Ed.). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Newton, I. (1985) *Certain Philosophical Questions: Newton's Trinity Notebook*, McGuire, James E. and Tamny, Martin (eds.), Cambridge, Cambridge University Press.
- Newton, I. (1999) "An Unpublished Preface to the *Principia*", (MS Add 3968, fol. 109) in Newton, 1999.
- Newton, I. (1999) *The Principia. Mathematical Principles of Natural Philosophy*. A new translation by I. Bernard Cohen and Anne Whitman assisted by Julia Budenz, preceded by a Guide to Newton's *Principia*. Berkeley, Los Angeles, London, University of California Press.

- Newton, I. (2004) *Isaac Newton: Philosophical Writings*, Janiak, Andrew (ed.), Cambridge, Cambridge University Press.
- Osler, M. J. (1994). *Divine will and the mechanical philosophy. Gassendi and Descartes on contingency and necessity in the created world*. Cambridge University Press: Cambridge.
- Osler, M. J. (2000) "Varieties of Providentialism", in *The History of Science and Religion in the Western Tradition: An Encyclopedia*, New York, Garland Publishing, pp. 61-66.
- Osler, M. J. (2001) "How Mechanical was the Mechanical Philosophy? Non-Epicurean Themes in Gassendi's Atomism," in *Late Medieval and Early Modern Corpuscular Matter Theories*, Lüthy, Christoph; Murdoch, John; and Newman, William R. (eds.) Leiden, Brill, pp. 423-439.
- Pemberton, H. (1728) *A view of Sir Isaac Newton's Philosophy*, London: S Palmer.
- Pepper, J. (1988) "Newton's Mathematical Work", *Let Newton be!*, Fauvel, John et al. (eds.), Oxford, Oxford University Press, pp.63-79.
- Popkin, R. (2004) "Plans for Publishing Newton's Religious and Alchemical Manuscripts, 1982-1998" in *Newton and Newtonianism*, Force, James E. and Hutton, Sarah (eds.), Dordrecht, Kluwer Academic Publishers, pp. 15-22.
- Pourciau, B. (1998) "The Preliminary Mathematical Lemmas of Newton's Principia", *Archives of the History of Exact Sciences*, 52, pp. 279-295.
- Principe, L. M., & Boyle, R. (1998). *The aspiring adept: Robert Boyle and his alchemical quest*. Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press.
- Pycior, H. M. (1997) "Mathematics and Philosophy. Wallis, Hobbes, Barrow, and Berkeley", *Journal of the History of Ideas*, 48, pp. 265-286.
- Pycior, H. M. (1997) *Symbols, Impossible Numbers, and Geometric Entanglements. British Algebra through the Commentaries on Newton's Universal Arithmetick*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press.
- Raftopoulos, A. (1999) "Newton's experimental proofs as eliminative reasoning", *Erkenntnis* 50, pp. 95-125.
- Rattansi, P. M. (1972). Newton's Alchemical Studies. In A. G. Debus (Ed.), *Science medicine and society in the Renaissance* (Vol. 2, pp. 167-182). London: Heinemann.
- Rigaud, S. P. (1838) *Historical Essay on the First Publication of Sir Isaac Newton's Principia*, Oxford, Oxford University Press.
- Robinson, R. (1936) "Analysis in Greek Geometry," *Mind*, New Series, 45, 180, 464-473.
- Roche, J. (1988). Newton's *Principia*. In J. Fauvel, R. Flood, M. Shortland, & R. Wilson (Eds.), *Let Newton be!* (pp. 43-61). New York, NY: Oxford University Press.

- Rogers, G. A. J. (1982) "The system of Locke and Newton" in *Contemporary Newtonian Research*, Zev Bechler (ed.), D. Reidel Publishing Company, pp. 215-238.
- Rogers, G. A. J. (1979) "Locke, Newton, and the Cambridge Platonists on Innate Ideas" *Journal of the History of Ideas*, 40, 2, pp. 191-205.
- Rose, P. L. (1973) "Humanist Culture and Renaissance Mathematics: The Italian Libraries of the Quattrocento", *Studies in the Renaissance*, 20, 1973, pp. 46-105.
- Ross, S. (1962) "Scientist: The story of a word", *Annals of Science*, 18, 2, pp. 65–85.
- Roux, S. (2004) "Cartesian Mechanics", in *The Reception of the Galilean Science of Motion in Europe*, C.R. Palmerino and H. Thijssen (eds.), Dordrecht, Kluwer Academic Publishers, pp. 25-66.
- Rynasiewicz, R. (1995a) "By their Properties, Causes and Effects: Newton's Scholium on Time, Space, Place and Motion, I The Text", *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science*, 26, 1, pp. 133-53.
- Rynasiewicz, R. (1995b) "By their Properties, Causes and Effects: Newton's Scholium on Time, Space, Place and Motion, II The Context", *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science*, 26, 1, pp. 295–321.
- Schaffer, S. (1990) "Newtonianism", in *Companion to the History of Modern Science*, eds. Olby R.C. et al., London, Routledge, pp. 610-626.
- Schofield, R. E. (1970) *Mechanism and Materialism: British Natural Philosophy in an Age of Reason*, Princeton, Princeton University Press.
- Schüller, V. (2001) "Newton's Scholia from David Gregory's Estate on the Propositions IV through IX, Book III of His *Principia*", in W. Lefèvre, (2001). *Between Leibniz, Newton, and Kant: Philosophy and science in the eighteenth century*. Boston studies in the philosophy of science, v. 220. Dordrecht: Kluwer Academic Publishers., pp. 213-265.
- Schuster, J. A. (1990) "The Scientific Revolution," in *Companion to the History of Modern Science*, eds. Olby R.C. et al., London, Routledge, pp. 217-242.
- Sepkoski, D. C. (2002) *Numbers and Things: Nominalism and Constructivism in Seventeenth-Century Mathematical Philosophy*. PhD Dissertation, University of Minnesota.
- Sepkoski, D. C. (2005) "Nominalism and Constructivism in Seventeenth-Century Mathematical Philosophy", *Historia Mathematica*, 32, pp. 33-59, p. 52.
- sGravesande, W. J. (1738) *Mathematical Elements of Natural Philosophy Confirmed by Experiments, or an Introduction to Sir Isaac Newton's Philosophy*, London, 1720.
- Shapin, S. (1981) "Of Gods and Kings: Politics and the Leibniz–Clarke dispute," *Isis* 72 pp, 187–215.
- Shapin, S. (1996) *The Scientific Revolution*, Chicago, University of Chicago Press.
- Shapiro, A. E. (1993), *Fits, Passions and Paroxysms: Physics, method and chemistry and Newton's theories of coloured bodies and fits of easy reflection*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press.

- Shapiro, A. E. (2002) "Newton's Optics and Atomism", in *The Cambridge Companion to Newton*, I. Bernard Cohen and George E. Smith (eds.), Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, pp. 227-255.
- Shapiro, A. E. (2004) "Newton's 'Experimental Philosophy'", *Early Science and Medicine* 9, pp. 185-217.
- Smith, G. E. (2001). The Newtonian style in Book II of the *Principia*. In J. Z. Buchwald & I. B. Cohen (Eds.), *Isaac Newton's natural philosophy* (pp. 249-335). Cambridge, MA: The MIT Press.
- Smith, G. E. (2002) "The Methodology of the *Principia*", in *The Cambridge Companion to Newton*, I. Bernard Cohen and George E. Smith (eds.), Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, pp. 138-173.
- Smith, G. E. (2008). Newton's "Philosophiae naturalis principia mathematica". In E. N. Zalta (Ed.), *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (Winter 2008 ed.). Retrieved from <http://plato.stanford.edu/archives/win2008/entries/newton-principia/> (Accessed on October 27, 2011).
- Snobelen, S. (1999) "Isaac Newton, heretic: the strategies of a Nicodemite", *The British Journal for the History of Science* 32, pp. 381-419.
- Snobelen, S. (2001) "'God of Gods, and Lord of Lords': the theology of Isaac Newton's General Scholium to the Principia". *Osiris* 16, pp. 169-208.
- Snobelen, S. (2004) "'The Light of Nature': God and natural philosophy in Newton's *Opticks*" (Unpublished).
- Snobelen, S. (2005) "'The true frame of Nature': Isaac Newton, heresy and the reformation of natural philosophy". In *Heterodoxy in early modern science and religion*, John Brooke and Ian Maclean (ed.) Oxford, Oxford University Press, pp. 223-262.
- Sprat, T. (1702) *The History of the Royal Society of London for the improvement of knowledge*, Printed for Rob. Scot, Ri. Chiswell, Tho. Chapman, and Geo. Sawbridge, 1702.
- Stewart, L. (2004) "The Trouble with Newton in the Eighteenth Century" in *Newton and Newtonianism*, Force, James E. and Hutton, Sarah (eds.), Dordrecht, Kluwer Academic Publishers, pp. 221-238.
- Stillingfleet, E. (1709) *Origines sacrae: Or, a rational account of the grounds of natural and reveal'd religion* 8th ed., London, Printed for J. Heptinstall, for Henry and George Mortlock.
- Thackray, A. (1970) *Atoms and powers: An essay on Newtonian matter-theory and the development of chemistry*. Cambridge, Massachusetts, Harvard University Press.
- Thomas, I. (Trans.) (1951) *Greek Mathematical Works*, London, Harvard University Press.
- Vailati, E. (1997) *Leibniz and Clarke: A Study of their Correspondence*, Oxford, Oxford University Press, 1997.

- Van de Pitte, F. P. (1991a) "Descartes's *Mathesis Universalis*", in *René Descartes Critical Assessments*, Georges J.D. (ed.) 4 Vols., London, Routledge, Vol. I, pp. 61-79.
- Van de Pitte, F. P. (1991b) "The dating of Rule IV-B in Descartes' *Regulae ad directionem ingenii*", *Journal of the History of Philosophy*, 29, pp. 375-395.
- Voltaire, F. M. A. (1738) *Elements de la Philosophie de Newton*, Paris, 1738.
- Voltaire, F. M. A. (1740) *La Métaphysique de Neuton, ou Parallèle des Sentiments de Neuton et de Leibnitz*, Amsterdam, Chez Jacques Desbordes.
- Voltaire, F. M. A. (2007) *Philosophical Letters. Or, Letters Regarding the English Nation*, Leigh, John (ed.), Steiner, Prudence L. (trans.), Indianapolis, Hackett Publishing Company.
- Wallace, W. A. (1988) "Traditional natural philosophy", in *The Cambridge History of Renaissance Philosophy*, Skinner, Quentin; Kessler, Eckhard and Kraye, Jill (eds.), Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, pp. 201-235.
- Wedin, M. V. (2009). The science and axioms of being. In G. Anagnostopoulos (Ed.), *A companion to Aristotle* (pp. 125-143). Singapore: Wiley-Blackwell.
- Westfall, R. S. (1970). *Force in Newton's physics. The science of dynamics in the seventeenth century*. New York, NY: American Elsevier.
- Westfall, R. S. (1975), "The Role of Alchemy in Newton's Career" in R Bonelli, Righini Maria L and Shea, R. William (eds.) *Reason, Experiment, and Mysticism in the Scientific Revolution*, London Macmillan, pp. 189-232.
- Westfall, R. S. (1976) "The Changing World of the Newtonian Industry", *Journal of the History of Ideas*, 37, 1, pp. 175-184.
- Westfall, R. S. (1980) *Never at Rest. A biography of Isaac Newton*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press.
- Westfall, R. S. (1980a) "Newton's Marvelous Years of Discovery and Their Aftermath: Myth versus Manuscript", *Isis*, 71, 1, 109-121.
- Westfall, R. S. (1984). Newton and alchemy. In B. Vickers (Ed.), *Occult and scientific mentalities in the Renaissance* (pp. 315-335). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Westfall, R. S. (1993) "The Culmination of the Scientific Revolution: Isaac Newton" in *Action and reaction. Proceedings of a Symposium to Commemorate the Tercentenary of Newton's Principia*, Theerman, Paul and Seeff, Adele F. (eds.) Newark, University of Delaware Press, pp. 31-60.
- Whewell, W. (1837) *History of the Inductive Sciences*, Cambridge, J.W. Parker and J.J. Deighton.
- Whiston, W. (1716) *Sir Isaac Newton's Mathematick Philosophy More Easily Demonstrated: With Dr. Halley's Account of Comets Illustrated*, London, Printed for J. Senex and W. Taylor.

- Whiston, W. (1728) *Astronomical Lectures, Read in the Publick Schools at Cambridge. Whereunto is Added a Collection of Astronomical Tables: Being Those of Mr. Flamsteed, Corrected; Dr. Halley; Monsieur Cassini; and Mr. Street. For the Use of Young Students in the University*, London, printed for J. Senex, W. and J. Innys, J. Osborne and T. Longman.
- White, M. J. (2009). Aristotle on the infinite, space, and time. In G. Anagnostopoulos (Ed.), *A companion to Aristotle* (pp. 260-276). Singapore: Wiley-Blackwell.
- Whiteside, D T. (1982) "Newton the mathematician", in Zev Bechler (ed.), *Newtonian contemporary research*. Dordrecht, Reidel Publishing Company, 109-127.
- Whiteside, D. T. (1964) "Isaac Newton: Birth of A Mathematician", *Notes and Records of the Royal Society of London*. 19, 53-62.
- Whiteside, D. T. (1966) "Newton's Marvellous Year: 1666 and all that", *Notes and Records of the Royal Society of London*, 21, 1, 32-41.
- Wilson, C. (2008) *Epicureanism at the origins of modernity*, New York, Oxford University Press.
- Wotton, W. (1694). *Reflections upon ancient and modern learning*. London: J. Leake.